

University of the West of Scotland

Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse: exploring the relationship between mothers and health professionals during historic periods of domestic abuse to identify how these might prevent or promote disclosures of abuse.

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Date of submission: July 2024

Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to the nine women who put their trust in me to tell their stories and whose honesty and courage continue to astound and humble me.

I extend this dedication to all other victims of domestic abuse, particularly those who are yet to have their voices heard. I hope you someday have the courage to seek the support you deserve.

Acknowledgements

I offer thanks and gratitude to my supervisory team, particularly Dr Ruth Astbury, Dr Dawn Cameron, Professor Mary Lynch and Professor Jean Rankin, for their unwavering support, kindness and guidance. Their belief in me and this study has been invaluable throughout this PhD journey, and I am thankful for their knowledge, expertise and continual encouragement.

It would be remiss of me to not also acknowledge the support of my family and friends who have continued to encourage me over the duration of this programme of study, including my children who will no longer ask 'are you still doing that?'

To my husband, Scott, who has had total faith in my ability when I doubted myself and has consistently and unconditionally supported me. I am so grateful for their support, and for our many lively debates about misogyny and patriarchal attitudes, which have made our mealtimes much more interesting over recent months. Thank you all so much.

Abstract

Background

Domestic abuse between intimate partners continues to affect large proportions of people living in the UK and internationally. Domestic abuse can be physical, emotional, financial, sexual, and includes coercive and controlling behaviours, and is associated with a variety of physical and psychological health impacts for women and their children. Women rarely disclose abuse to health professionals, despite the presence of routine enquiry within current Health Visiting practice. A plethora of barriers prevent women from seeking help and also prevent professionals from asking women about abuse.

Relationship-based practice is fundamental to improving outcomes for children and their families, and this relationship is valued by both parents and professionals alike. Although it is usually intended that the same Health Visitor will support families to provide consistency, in practice it is often disrupted by staffing challenges and adapted service delivery models. This in turn affects the opportunity to establish positive relationships which provide a basis for disclosures of abuse and early intervention and support.

Methodology

This study was undertaken qualitatively, using an interpretative phenomenological approach based on Heideggerian principles and underpinned by Matricentric Feminist theory. Nine women who had experienced historical domestic abuse were identified from health visiting caseloads, and Women's Aid organisations, and were interviewed using semi-structured interviews, supported by the use of a life history calendar to aid retrospective data collection and develop a timeline of events for each participant. Data analysis was undertaken using thematic analysis of interview transcripts, hermeneutic methods, and supported by NVivo 12 software and analysis of individual timelines.

Findings

Study findings suggest that positive relationships between women and health professionals are not sufficient to promote domestic abuse disclosures, however these relationships are valued. Domestic abuse is a complex phenomenon; disclosures are often unplanned, with multiple factors impacting on women's decision-making during periods of abuse, including fear, stigma and self-blame, and a lack of awareness regarding non-violent forms of abuse. Abuse that is not witnessed by others, or that does not result in a heightened risk to children, is rarely reported to health professionals even where significant injury is sustained. Abuse always impacts on survivor's mental health, and perpetrator drug and alcohol use is closely associated with abuse. There is an association between experiences that survivors have had as children and the types of abuse experienced as adults.

Contents

List of Tables	13
List of Figures	14
List of abbreviations.....	15
1 Introduction	17
1.1 Relationship based health visiting practice	18
1.2 Motivation for the study.....	20
1.3 Structure of the thesis	21
2 Domestic abuse and the impact on the health of women and children	22
2.1 Introduction to chapter.....	22
2.2 The impact on physical health	22
2.3 The impact on psychological health.....	24
2.4 Domestic abuse during pregnancy and the perinatal period	25
2.5 The impact of domestic abuse on children.....	27
2.5.1 Policy Context	27
2.5.2 Domestic abuse and children.....	27
2.6 Conclusion.....	29
3 Key areas of focus for the study	30
4 Literature Review	32
4.1 Introduction to chapter.....	32
4.2 Development of the literature review question	32
4.3 Identifying relevant studies	33
4.4 Study selection.....	35
4.4.1 Inclusion and exclusion criteria.....	35
4.4.2 Search Strings.....	36
4.5 Charting the data	37
4.6 Collating, summarising and reporting the results.....	39
4.6.1 Theme 1 – Feasibility of Screening and Routine Enquiry.....	40
4.6.2 Theme 2 – Acceptability of screening/routine enquiry to women.....	43
4.6.3 Theme 3 – Barriers to disclosure	45
4.6.3.1 Personal factors	46
4.6.3.2 Health related factors	49
4.6.3.3 Cultural barriers	50
4.6.4 Theme 4 – Facilitators to disclosure	53
4.6.5 Theme 5 – Health professional practice and behaviours as barrier to disclosure.....	56
4.6.6 Theme 6 – Relationships.....	59

4.7	Summary of findings and identified gaps in research.....	62
4.8	Chapter summary.....	66
5	Methodology.....	67
5.1	Introduction to chapter.....	67
5.2	Research aim and objectives arising from the literature review	67
5.3	Overview of the main research paradigms.....	68
5.3.1	Positivism	68
5.3.2	Interpretivism.....	68
5.3.3	Summary of primary research paradigms.....	69
5.4	Overview of interpretative research designs.....	70
5.4.1	Interpretivist phenomenology	71
5.4.2	Descriptive Husserlian Phenomenology	71
5.4.3	Hermeneutic phenomenology	72
5.4.4	Summary of phenomenological designs	73
5.5	Ethical considerations	73
5.5.1	Research with vulnerable persons and domestic abuse research.....	74
5.5.2	Embedding ethical principles into the study.....	75
5.5.3	Ethical Permissions.....	82
5.5.4	Chapter summary.....	83
6	Theoretical Frameworks	84
6.1	Introduction to chapter.....	84
6.2	Theoretical frameworks in interpretivist research	84
6.3	Feminism as a theoretical framework	85
6.3.1	Feminist phenomenology	87
6.3.2	Matricentric Feminism (MF)	88
6.3.3	Motherhood, mothering and maternalism.....	89
6.3.4	Intensive mothering.....	90
6.4	Feminism and domestic abuse	90
6.5	Intersectionality	91
6.6	Chapter summary.....	92
7	Research design	94
7.1	Introduction to chapter.....	94
7.2	Using a Hermeneutic design	94
7.3	Sampling.....	94
7.4	Recruitment	95
7.5	Data Collection.....	96
7.5.1	Qualitative interviews	97
7.5.2	Data collection using a Heideggerian perspective	97

7.5.3	Life History Calendar	100
7.5.4	LHC modifications and interviews.....	101
7.5.5	LHC and domestic abuse	101
7.5.6	Pilot study	102
7.6	Data completeness	102
7.7	Data analysis	103
7.7.1	Heidegger’s circle method and thematic analysis	103
7.7.2	Thematic analysis.....	105
7.7.3	Rigour and trustworthiness	109
7.7.4	Reflexivity.....	110
7.7.5	Retrospective data collection	110
7.8	Chapter summary.....	111
8	Findings	112
8.1	Introduction to chapter.....	112
8.2	The participants	112
8.2.1	The researcher – participant relationship.....	113
8.2.2	Participant demographics	113
8.3	Overview of findings and emerging themes	114
8.4	Disclosing abuse.....	115
8.4.1	The presence of Routine Enquiry (RE) in practice.....	115
8.4.2	Barriers to disclosing abuse to health professionals	116
8.4.3	Conditions for disclosing abuse	118
8.5	Participant relationships with health professionals	120
8.5.1	Characteristics of positive relationships with professionals.....	121
8.5.2	Impact of relationships on domestic abuse disclosure.....	122
8.6	Physical and sexual abuse	123
8.7	Emotional abuse	124
8.7.1	Controlling and threatening behaviours	125
8.7.2	Attendance at health appointments.....	127
8.7.3	Reproduction, pregnancy and birth related abuse.....	127
8.7.4	Alienation from family and friends	128
8.8	Financial abuse.....	129
8.8.1	Financial abuse as a means of control	129
8.8.2	Financial abuse and substance misuse	131
8.9	Employment and age factors	131
8.10	Escalation of abuse	132
8.10.1	Escalation during pregnancy.....	132
8.10.2	Escalation of abuse when the relationship ends	134

8.11	Familial abuse	135
8.12	Mental Health	135
8.12.1	The impact of domestic abuse on mental health	135
8.12.2	Postnatal depression.....	137
8.12.3	Weaponising mental ill health	138
8.13	Trauma and Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs)	139
8.13.1	Survivor ACEs	139
8.13.2	Perpetrator ACEs.....	140
8.13.3	Impact of trauma on memory retrieval	140
8.14	Coronavirus Pandemic	141
8.14.1	Pressures of the pandemic.....	142
8.14.2	Lack of professional support	142
8.14.3	Escalation of abuse	142
8.14.4	Isolation.....	143
8.15	Chapter summary & summary of findings	143
9	Discussion.....	145
9.1	Introduction to chapter.....	145
9.2	Disclosing Abuse	145
9.2.1	Presence of routine enquiry in practice.....	145
9.2.2	Barriers to disclosure	149
9.2.2.1	Fear	150
9.2.2.2	Societal influences	153
9.2.2.3	The cycle of abuse.....	155
9.2.2.4	The impact of community	156
9.2.2.5	Partner’s presence and controlling behaviour.....	158
9.2.2.6	Lack of awareness of non-violent abuse.....	159
9.2.2.7	Disclosing abuse and age	160
9.2.3	Conditions for disclosing abuse	160
9.2.3.1	Escalation of abuse	162
9.2.3.2	Child abuse	162
9.2.3.3	Changes to women’s willingness to accept abuse.....	164
9.2.3.4	The presence of a supportive relationship	165
9.2.4	Relationships with health professionals	167
9.2.4.1	Kindness, compassion and empathy.....	169
9.2.4.2	Compassion and empathy in a political context	172
9.2.4.3	Barriers to relationship development.....	172
9.2.4.4	Relationships with GPs.....	175
9.2.4.5	Informal supports – Family and friends	177

9.2.4.6	Complexities of abuse disclosures and relationships	178
9.3	Emotional abuse	182
9.3.1	Emotionally abusive behaviours	182
9.3.2	Men’s attendance at health appointments	183
9.3.3	Abuse and reproductive health	184
9.3.4	Women’s awareness of emotional abuse	186
9.4	Physical abuse	187
9.5	Child abuse	189
9.5.1	Child contact arrangements	189
9.6	Sexual violence and abuse	190
9.6.1	Rape myths	194
9.7	Familial violence and abuse	196
9.8	Escalation of abuse	197
9.8.1	Escalation during pregnancy and perinatal period	198
9.8.2	Escalation in post-separation period	200
9.9	Financial abuse	203
9.9.1	Prevalence of financial abuse	206
9.9.2	Association between financial, physical and sexual abuse	208
9.10	Domestic abuse and substance misuse	208
9.10.1	Substance misuse and gender	212
9.11	Domestic abuse and mental health	214
9.11.1	The impact of domestic abuse on mental health	214
9.11.2	Sexual abuse and mental health	216
9.11.3	Mental health and help-seeking	216
9.11.4	Post-natal depression	219
9.11.5	Weaponising mental health by perpetrators	220
9.12	Mothering in domestic abuse contexts	221
9.13	Adverse childhood experiences	225
9.13.1	Impact of trauma on memory retrieval	227
9.13.2	Multiple recurring abusive relationships	227
9.14	Domestic abuse and perpetrator age	229
9.15	Coronavirus pandemic	230
9.15.1	Mothering during the pandemic	234
9.16	Chapter summary	235
10	Strengths and limitations of the study	237
10.1	Strengths	237
10.2	Limitations	237
11	Reflections and reflexivity	240

11.1	Reflections of women’s participation in domestic abuse research	240
11.2	Reflexivity and the research process	242
11.3	Theoretical frameworks	242
12	Conclusions	244
12.1	Routine Enquiry.....	244
12.2	Nature and knowledge of abuse	245
12.3	Relationships with professionals	246
12.4	Mothers.....	247
12.5	Mental Health	248
12.6	Trauma and Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs)	249
12.7	Structural and societal issues.....	249
13	Recommendations	250
13.1	Recommendations for practice.....	250
13.1.1	Routine enquiry.....	250
13.1.2	Education and training	252
13.1.3	Relationships with professionals.....	253
13.1.4	Nature and knowledge of abuse	254
13.1.5	Mental Health	254
13.1.6	ACEs.....	255
13.2	Recommendations for policy makers	256
13.3	Short term actions specific to health and social care settings	256
13.4	Medium term actions.....	256
13.5	Long term actions	257
13.6	Recommendations for future research.....	257
14	Dissemination of study findings.....	260
15	References	261
16	List of appendices	325
16.1	Appendix 1 – Search strings	326
16.2	Appendix 2 – Prisma Diagram	327
16.3	Appendix 3 - Summary of Literature Review Research Studies.....	328
16.4	Appendix 3a - Summary of Literature Review Research Studies.....	343
16.5	Appendix 3b - Patterning chart.....	349
16.6	Appendix 3c– PAGER Framework	353
16.7	Appendix 4 – Overview of interpretative research designs.....	362
16.8	Appendix 5 – Feminist theories	364
16.9	Appendix 6 - Summary of main ethical principles	366
16.10	Appendix 7 – NHS Research Ethics Committee Application	367
16.11	Appendix 8 - Participant Information Sheet (PIS).....	400

16.12	Appendix 9 - Information for Health Visitors.....	404
16.13	Appendix 10 - Information for Women’s Aid Organisations	407
16.14	Appendix 11 – Consent form	410
16.15	Appendix 12 – Life History Calendar	412
16.16	Appendix 13 - Interview schedule.....	413
16.17	Appendix 14 - Participant Safeguarding Checklist	414
16.18	Appendix 15 – Insurance.....	415
16.19	Appendix 16 – Organisation Information Document.....	416
16.20	Appendix 17 – Research protocol	437
16.21	Appendix 18 – MSc Certificate	441
16.22	Appendix 19 – University Ethical Guidelines	442
16.23	Appendix 20 – Letter of favourable opinon	448
16.24	Appendix 21 – Mind map.....	453
16.25	Appendix 22 - Women’s Aid Model of Change	454

List of Tables

	Title	Page
1	PICO framework	34
2	Literature search inclusion and exclusion criteria	35
3	Summary of themes	108
4	WHO Ethical recommendations for researchers	74
5	Age profile of participants	113
6	Participant demographic details	114
7	Participant similarities	114
8	Participant adverse childhood experiences	139
9	Age and domestic abuse in the study sample	230

List of Figures

	Title	Page
1	Pyramid of violent abuse	23
2	Short- and long-term physical health impacts of domestic abuse	23
3	Impact of domestic abuse on growing fetus	26
4	Impact of domestic abuse on children	28
5	Inclusion and exclusion criteria	75
6	NVivo nodes	106
7	Trustworthiness in qualitative research	109
8	Descriptions of positive relationships with Health Visitors and Midwives	121
9	Participant descriptions of emotionally abusive behaviours	125
10	Example of emotionally abusive behaviours experienced by participants.	125
11	Reasons for non-disclosure of abuse	149
12	Sources of fear preventing disclosures of abuse	150
13	Conditions for disclosing abuse	161
14	Reasons for positive disclosures of abuse	161
15	Disclosure of physical abuse by study participants	179
16	Domestic abuse disclosure model	181
17	Descriptions of physical abuse	188
18	Presence of children in physical assaults	189
19	Characteristics of sexual violence	193
20	Rape myths	195
21	Risk factors associated with escalation of abuse	198
22	Risk factors that predetermine harm to children	202
23	Financial abuse	204
24	Mental health of study participants	215
25	Application of help-seeking model to domestic abuse	218
26	Participants' experiences of abusive relationships, and types of abuse and ACEs	228
27	Increased risk of abuse during the Covid-19 pandemic	231
28	Implications of the Covid-19 pandemic on participants	231

List of abbreviations

A&E	Accident and Emergency
ACEs	Adverse Childhood Experiences
BAME/BME	Black and Minority Ethnic
BPD	Bi-Polar Disorder
CASP	Critical Appraisal Skills Programme
CDCP	Centres for Disease Control and Prevention
CEDAW	Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination Against Women
CEL	Chief Executive Letter
COPFS	Crown Office and Procurator Fiscal Service
DA	Domestic Abuse
DVA	Domestic Violence and Abuse
DASH	Domestic Abuse, Stalking and Honour based Violence
DASH RIC	Domestic Abuse, Stalking and Honour based Violence Risk Identification Checklist
DOVE	Domestic Violence Enhanced Intervention
ESRC	Economic and Social Research Council
EIGE	European Institute of Gender Equality
EVAW	End Violence Against Women
FGM	Female Genital Mutilation
GBV	Gender Based Violence
GIRFEC	Getting It Right For Every Child
GP	General Practitioner
HALL 4	Health For All Children
HMICFRS	Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Constabulary and Fire & Rescue Services
HV	Health Visitor
IHV	Institute of Health visiting
IPV	Intimate Partner Violence
IRAS	Integrated Research Application System
LGBT	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual and Transgender

LHC	Life History Calendar
MARAC	Multi Agency Risk Assessment Conference
MF	Matricentric Feminism
NCADV	National coalition Against Domestic Violence
NZFVC	New Zealand Family Violence Clearinghouse
NI	Northern Ireland
NICE	National Institute of Clinical Excellence
NMC	Nursing and Midwifery Council
NREC	National Research Ethics Committee
NSPCC	National Society for the Prevention of Cruelty of Children
OHN	Occupational Health Nurse
ONS	Office for National Statistics
PHN	Public Health Nurse
PSNI	Police Service of Northern Ireland
PTSD	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder
RCT	Randomised Control Trial
RE	Routine Enquiry
SCPHN	Specialist Community Public Health Nursing
SCR	Serious Case Review
SCRA	Scottish Children's Reporter Administration
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
SN	School Nurse
TA	Thematic Analysis
UHVP	Universal Health visiting Pathway
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
UNCRC	United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child
UNOCD	United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime
VAW	Violence Against Women
VAWAG	Violence Against Women and Girls
WHO	World Health Organisation

1 Introduction

Health Visitors are Specialist Community Public Health Nurses (SCPHNS) who are key health professionals, supporting parents and carers in a variety of complex circumstances and experiences, to reduce vulnerability, promote resilience and reduce inequality among children and families (Morton and Adams, 2021). In tackling these complex issues, the need for a well-developed, trusting, non-judgmental relationship becomes imperative (Cowley *et al*, 2015; Gram *et al*, 2023).

Women's Aid (2023a) suggest one in four women, and one in six men in the UK will be affected by domestic abuse in their lifetime, leading on average to two women being murdered each week in England and Wales alone. True prevalence of domestic abuse is difficult to quantify due to it being a predominantly hidden crime, often unreported, and consequently, statistics and prevalence data are frequently unreliable (Women's Aid, 2022a). It continues to be a significant international public health concern due to the profound physical and psychological impacts on its victims (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2016; Women's Aid, 2019a; WHO, 2020; Potter *et al*, 2021). Although there has been a growing awareness of domestic abuse with the criminalisation of non-physical abuse, such as coercive control in the UK, this remains a phenomenon that is not always openly confronted, and affects all genders, in heterosexual and same sex relationships, and straddles all classes, ethnicities and geographical locations (Boethius and Akerstrom, 2020).

The impacts of abuse on women and their children are vast (McFeely, 2016; Cort and Cline, 2017), and Health Visitors are key professionals, in prime positions to identify and respond to violence against women, providing safety measures, and early interventions (McFeely, 2016; Women's Aid, 2019a). However supporting and protecting women whilst also prioritising the needs and safety of children is a challenging dichotomy (Peckover and Aston, 2017), and findings from literature illustrate that domestic abuse enquiry and disclosure can be entrenched in difficulties, and as many barriers exist for women disclosing abuse, as for professionals asking about abuse (Damra *et al*, 2015; McFeely, 2016; Kirk and Bezzant, 2020; Heron, Eisma and Browne, 2022). Subsequently, women experiencing domestic abuse report

their experiences within health settings as being poor (Peckover, 2002; McFeely, 2016).

McFeely (2016) agrees, suggesting that Health Visitors, are not always effective in identifying and responding to disclosures where these do occur, despite their mandated roles in identifying risks to both children and adults. How Health Visitors screen for, and address domestic abuse are often influenced by the service provision and child health frameworks that exist within their respective UK countries (Scottish Government, 2015; Welsh Government, 2016; Public Health England, 2021; Department of Health & Social Services and Public Safety, 2010). All health visiting policies in the UK clearly state that Health Visitors have a role in reducing inequalities, promoting health, protecting children and supporting those affected by domestic abuse. Despite this, disparity exists largely due to the varying number of contacts offered to families via the respective policy driven practice across Scotland, England, Northern Ireland and Wales (Scottish Government, 2015; iHV, 2019; Public Health England, 2021; Department of Health, 2022; Welsh Government, 2023). A consequence of this, is that the development of a therapeutic relationship between Health Visitors and mothers becomes disrupted when mandated contacts are reduced or unfulfilled which, in turn, makes consistent contact with one Health Visitor difficult to achieve (iHV, 2019). This study therefore aimed to provide a deep exploration of the relationship that Health Visitors aspire to achieve with the mothers they work with, and explore whether this relationship, if developed therapeutically and meaningfully, had potential to support mothers in their disclosures of abuse.

1.1 Relationship based health visiting practice

The nurse-patient, or helper-client relationship has been well studied (Haslam, 2015; Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2017; Catlow *et al*, 2020), and it is accepted that the presence of a supportive, non-judgemental relationship positively influences health outcomes (Kelly, Lepo and Frinzi, 2011; Kwame and Petrucka, 2021; Gram *et al*, 2023). Similarly, a key tenet of Health Visitor practice is the establishment of positive, respectful relationships that are strengths-based, to support and enable families to improve health and wellbeing (Cowley *et al*, 2018), and is threaded through all UK

health visiting policy (Department of Health, 2009; Department of Health, Social Services and Public Safety, 2010; Welsh Government, 2021). Although the nature of the relationship between Health Visitor and parent differs from the traditional nurse-patient dynamic, evaluations of the Scottish Universal Health Visiting Pathway (UHVP) (Scottish Government, 2015) suggest this relationship is of similar importance to families as well as HVs (Doi *et al*, 2021). As well as being important to Health Visitors and families, the existence of a positive, trusting relationship is also considered to be crucial as a vehicle to tackle sensitive issues, such as welfare concerns, mental health, and domestic abuse (Cowley *et al*, 2018). Together with home visiting and needs assessment, relationship building is a unique and core function of the health visiting service and central to facilitating health improvement and resilience (Cowley *et al*, 2018). The Health Visitor-Parent relationship is not well researched and as a result, there continues to be difficulties in justifying the unique contribution that health visiting practice plays in improving the health of children and families (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016).

Relationship-based care is underpinned by an ethos of partnership working (iHV, 2024), reflected in much of the policy driving professional practice with children and their families in Scotland, such as GIRFEC (Scottish Government, 2015) and The Promise (Scottish Government, 2022b; The Promise Scotland, 2023). However, despite policy aspirations, the iHV (2024) argues that fewer than half of Health Visitors in England are able to provide the consistency of providing one health visitor to each family on their caseloads, although, figures are considerably more reassuring in Northern Ireland (NI), Scotland, and Wales. Furthermore, there appears to be little attention given in literature to the nature of relationship development, and methods and outcomes of partnership working within public health nursing spheres since it was suggested by Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott (2016).

Inadequate staffing, large caseloads and increased use of skill mix, are believed to encumber relationship building with families (iHV, 2022a), therefore, in recent challenging times, the role of the Health Visitor has become even more important, and their task even larger and more complex (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016). For practice to be effective, it is reliant upon Health Visitors developing effective, therapeutic relationships with the families they work alongside; without this, the

potential to create space for change, to address health inequalities and improve outcomes becomes difficult, if not impossible (Bryar *et al*, 2017; Doi *et al*, 2021).

This study set out to explore the characteristics of professional health visiting practice that relates to the identification and response to domestic abuse, and the role that a positive relationship plays in supporting disclosures of abuse. Domestic abuse was chosen as a subject topic for this thesis due to these challenges, and the desire to improve outcomes for women and children affected.

1.2 Motivation for the study

Relationship-based practice is a focus of this study due to a variety of motivations. Firstly, the over-arching policy in Scotland, arising from ambitions of The Promise, Getting it Right for Every Child (GIRFEC) and GIRFEC Refresh, as well as UK policy, emphasises the need for Health Visitors, and other health and social care professionals working with children and families, e.g. Family Nurses, Midwives, Social Workers, and Allied Health Professionals, to use strengths-based, whole family, partnership approaches when working with children and families (Scottish Government, 2015; Public Health England, 2018; Public Health England, 2020; The Promise Scotland, 2023; Scottish Government, 2022a; Scottish Government, 2022b). However, there has been evidence from practice and research that suggests some health professionals within these disciplines are not always adequately skilled in these strengths-based approaches and continue to deliver services where power imbalances exist where they present as the expert 'doing to' their clients/patients (Brook and Salmon, 2015; Tobiano *et al*, 2015).

The desire to find out what is required when working alongside families and develop an understanding of true partnership working approaches, is a strong motivator for the study, whilst also seeking to understand how such approaches exist within a health visiting context, where strict child welfare obligations exist, and child centered approaches are required (Scottish Government, 2015; Public Health England, 2018; Public Health England, 2019; Public Health England, 2020; Scottish Government, 2022a). Motivation also arises from the need to explore the lived experiences of those who have survived domestic abuse, the desire to contribute to a contemporary

evidence base driving Health Visitor practice, and to improve the experiences and outcomes for women and families who experience abuse.

1.3 **Structure of the thesis**

The thesis will begin by providing some context to this issue, and Chapter 2 will outline the significant impact of abuse on the health and wellbeing of women and their children. A review of the existing literature is detailed in Chapter 4 which provides a detailed analysis of current knowledge and highlights gaps in what is known and subsequently determines the research aim. The following study aim has been developed:

To develop an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse. Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.

With the aim of the study being clear, justification for the research methodology, approach and design is discussed in Chapter 5, 6 and 7, which considers the value of interpretative methodologies in seeking to understand lived experiences of participants. Feminist theory, in particular Matricentric Feminism, is the primary theoretical framework underpinning the study, and this will be explored in detail in Chapter 6. There are a number of ethical considerations with any study with human participants, and in particular in the context of domestic abuse research, and these are debated in Chapter 5. Study findings and critical discussion and implications for practice are found within Chapters 8 and 9. The next chapter will provide an analysis of the vast physical and psychological impact of domestic abuse on women and their children.

2 Domestic abuse and the impact on the health of women and children

2.1 Introduction to chapter

There has been much written within the domestic abuse literature regarding its impact on survivors, the associated costs, to individuals, communities and nations, and the risk factors that exist to both victims and perpetrators (WHO, 2017; Women's Aid, 2022b), however it is out with the scope of this thesis to provide a detailed background on each of these related topics. That said, the individual effects of abuse on a woman's physical and psychological wellbeing are so significant that this chapter will clearly articulate these impacts on women survivors, on their physical and psychological health (particularly during the perinatal period), and to their children's health and wellbeing. It is with these impacts in mind that the need for Health Visitors to screen and respond effectively to disclosures of abuse should be of the highest priority.

2.2 The impact on physical health

The magnitude and consequences of domestic abuse are vast (WHO, 2014), with a multitude of health, emotional, physical, financial and social impacts on a survivor, their children and family, and wider society. The impacts of physical violence on women's health can be considered within the layers of the triangle in Figure 1. Violent deaths are represented in official statistics and the most evident outcome of abusive behaviours, however their position at the top of the pyramid illustrates that this is only part of the picture (WHO, 2014). The lower layers of the pyramid demonstrate those victims of violent behaviors that seek medical attention or other care, and the bottom layer are those injuries that may never be reported but become known due to inclusion in population surveys and contribute to prevalence data (WHO, 2014). There is also a plethora of survivors who are not captured in this figure (WHO, 2014), emphasising that much of domestic abuse remains unknown and undisclosed, despite being a far-reaching phenomenon (Potter *et al*, 2021).

Figure 1 - Pyramid of violent abuse (WHO, 2014)

Although women experiencing all types of domestic abuse have poor health outcomes, Potter *et al* (2021) suggest those who suffer multiple forms of abuse experience the most significant impact to their health and are at increased risk of suicide. Similarly, McManus *et al* (2022) concur, suggesting domestic abuse is increasingly present in patients who have completed suicide. Alejo (2014) and Lutgendorf (2019) suggest those experiencing physical abuse sustain a range of physical injuries and short-term health problems to long term conditions, and even death that can be seen in Figure 2:

Figure 2 - Short and long term physical health impacts of domestic abuse (Alejo, 2014; WHO 2014; Lutgendorf, 2019).

The global health burden of domestic abuse is vast and extends beyond short term injuries arising from physical or sexual assaults (Suglia *et al*, 2018). Chandan *et al*

(2020) propose that female survivors of domestic abuse are at significantly increased risk of cardiovascular disease and type two diabetes and all-cause mortality. Additionally, women experiencing domestic abuse are also more likely to engage in higher lifestyle risk factors such as smoking, drug use, alcohol use, and poor diet, inactivity and poor sleep habits, than the general population (Suglia *et al*, 2018; Chandan *et al*, 2020).

SafeLives (2015) suggest that women experience approximately 50 incidents of abuse before getting help, and WHO (2021) states that less than half of women experiencing domestic abuse report an injury as a result of physical violence. This confirms the impact on health is likely to be prolonged and substantial and supports the view that domestic abuse is the leading contributor of injury and disease burden in women aged 15-44 years, whereby the incidence of injuries is greater for domestic abuse than the total combined for all other causes (McPhedran, 2018). With this knowledge, it is therefore important that Health Visitors consider a woman's current health and past experiences as part of whole-family assessments, and as part of their search for health needs, underpinned by positive relationships to support sensitive conversations (Cowley *et al*, 2015).

2.3 The impact on psychological health

Not all women experiencing domestic abuse sustain physical injuries, however even where abuse is non-violent, living with trauma of abuse means survivors are more likely to have poor mental health outcomes (Birchall and McCarthy, 2021; Oram *et al*, 2022). Trauma caused by exposure to domestic abuse is a key precursor to mental ill health (Women's Mental Health Task Force, 2018), and the association between domestic abuse and mental ill health have been well studied and accepted (Scott *et al*, 2015; Jonas *et al*, 2016; Oram *et al*, 2022). There is a convincing association between domestic abuse and a spectrum of mental health disorders, in particular depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) psychosis, suicide and eating disorders (Trevillion *et al*, 2012; Oram *et al*, 2013; Oram *et al*, 2017; Oram *et al*, 2022), and survivors of domestic abuse describe the mental health impacts as long lasting and destructive (Safe Lives, 2018). Parental health and ill health is of importance to the Health Visitor assessment and whole-family approaches, and

consideration is given to the child's 'wider world' and wider family networks (Scottish Government, 2015). However, the presence of a positive relationship is thought to support enquiring and responding to sensitive or stigmatising subjects (Howard *et al*, 2013).

Some mental health disorders are known to have a bi-directional causality, for example, women with depressive symptoms are more likely to experience abusive relationships, and similarly, those women experiencing domestic abuse, are more likely to suffer depression, when there is no previous history of depressive symptoms (Devries *et al*, 2013; Howard *et al*, 2013). Similarly, those with mental health conditions are more likely to experience and perpetrate domestic abuse, however perpetration rates are generally low and mostly associated with substance abuse, when this co-occurs with domestic abuse (Oram *et al*, 2022). The relationship between poor mental health and domestic abuse is complex, yet undeniable, and is a significant consideration for women at any age, however it is argued that risks to mental health increase during pregnancy (Women's Aid, 2019b), which will now be considered in the following section.

2.4 Domestic abuse during pregnancy and the perinatal period

The risk of abuse can increase during pregnancy, and Peacock *et al* (2023) state that a third of domestic abuse begins during pregnancy, and where it already occurs, it escalates during this time, with a high association between pre and postnatal abuse and violence (Yapp *et al*, 2018). Thus, the implications for the health of both woman and fetus are extensive, as outlined in Figure 3:

Figure 3 - Impact of domestic abuse on growing fetus (Donovan, Spracklen and Schwiezer, 2016)

The presence of domestic abuse in the perinatal period impacts on the ability of women to access antenatal care, reducing the ability for health professionals to identify and manage pregnancy complications, reduce maternal and neonatal mortality, through delivery of public health messages and contact with the midwifery team (Eustace et al, 2016; Atkinson *et al*, 2023). Domestic abuse has various effects on the growing fetus, potentially resulting in fetal health problems, including low birth weight, intrauterine growth restriction, preterm labour, miscarriage and longer-term cognitive difficulties for the child (Hasselle *et al*, 2019; Mojahed *et al*, 2021). A cross-sectional survey of pregnant Bangladeshi women by Islam *et al* (2017) found that women experiencing abuse were more than twice as likely to have delayed entry into pre-natal care and magnified further by cultural gender role ideations and women's lack of autonomy regarding their health.

The psychological consequences of domestic abuse on pregnant women during the perinatal period can also be significant for the women and her child, with women reporting depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorders and panic attacks, which are also associated with poor mental health outcomes for their children including a link to autism and schizophrenia (Plant *et al*, 2015; Klengel, Dias and Ressler, 2016), as well as anxiety and eating disorders (Schury *et al*, 2017). The pre- and post-natal period therefore presents a crucial time which can threaten the wellbeing of both women and her child, and health professionals from universal services who support

women during this time are well placed to identify and respond to domestic abuse in order to minimise risks to both (Middleton and Harvey, 2014; Hassell *et al*, 2019).

2.5 The impact of domestic abuse on children

2.5.1 Policy Context

The 1991 United Nations Convention of the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) (UNICEF, 2019) exists as the most widely ratified treaty of human rights, containing 54 Articles outlining a child's civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights (UNICEF, 2019). Scotland has children's rights threaded through its policies (Scottish Government, 2021b; Scottish Government, 2015), and in December 2023, the Scottish Parliament unanimously passed the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (Incorporation) (Scotland) Bill for the second time, meaning that children's rights will be protected in Scots Law (Scottish Government, 2021b).

Exposure to domestic abuse contravenes Article 19 of the UNCRC, which states children have the right to be free from violence, abuse, and neglect. Like women, children who are exposed to domestic abuse in the UK also experience poor health outcomes. Serious case reviews (SCR) undertaken where children have been killed consistently feature domestic abuse (Middleton and Harvey, 2014). Additionally, domestic abuse is the most common factor experienced by children in need of local authority children's services support in England, and features in 50% of all assessments (James, 2020). However, despite such figures, the NSPCC (2022) suggests the impact of domestic abuse on children is often overlooked, and consequently, the *Domestic Abuse (Scotland) Act (2018)* officially recognises children as victims of abuse (NSPCC, 2022).

2.5.2 Domestic abuse and children

Exposure to domestic abuse is considered to always have some detrimental effect upon a child, and it is estimated that a more than a decade ago, 750,000 children annually were exposed to such incidents (Hoare and Moon, 2010), however more recent data suggests that one in five children will be exposed to domestic abuse in the UK by the time they reach 18 years of age (HM Government, 2019). Women's Aid

(2022) data from 2020-21 recorded 42,598 children of service users in England alone in 2022, with almost 22,000 women having children, from a sample of 34,860. Thus, highlighting the volume of children affected, particularly when not all those who experience abuse receive help from specialist services such as Women’s Aid, and these figures do not stretch to all four UK countries.

Although there are a vast number of children and young people affected by domestic abuse, they may not always experience the same impact of witnessing abuse (Radford, 2011). Experience of trauma can be determined by age, stage of development, race and gender, consequently for some with protective factors in their lives, and resilience, the effects may be minimal (James, 2020). However, for some, Radford (2011) claims they can experience a short or long term behavioral, cognitive and emotional impact, presenting with neurological and physical disturbances as outlined in Figure 4:

Neurological impacts on younger children	Psychosomatic impacts on younger children	Combined Impacts on older children
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sleeping difficulties • Anxiety • Depression • Excessive screaming • Disrupted attachment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stomach/abdominal pain • Headaches • Incontinence • Behavioural difficulties • Regressive behaviours • Crying and clinginess • Withdrawn • Aggression • Low self-esteem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substance misuse • Truancy • Self-harm • Eating disorders • Other mental health difficulties • Aggression • Violent or criminal behaviours • Potential for offending • Potential for involved in abuse as an adult

Figure 4 – Impacts of domestic abuse on children (Radford, 2011; James, 2020).

Despite the presence of policy which emphasises upholding the rights of the child, this is not always realised in practice (Women’s Aid, 2019a). Birchall and Chowdry (2018) suggest that a culture of gender discrimination, disbelief, and negative perceptions of domestic abuse survivors, and a lack of awareness of the impact of abuse within court systems prevents policies from being fully implemented, resulting in probable gaps in the human rights protection for those affected (Birchall and Choudhry, 2018a; Women’s Aid, 2019a).

The psychological impact of domestic abuse on women is significant, therefore it is unsurprising that women who are mothers experiencing abuse are likely to suffer poor maternal mental health that can have an impact on how they parent their children (Middleton and Harvey, 2014). Maternal depression can result in reduced sensitivity to a child's needs, and the use of more punitive and harsh parenting styles (Davies and Ward, 2012). In addition, exposure to domestic abuse is also known to increase the risk of anxious attachments, anger, difficulties with regulating emotions and behaviour, and social isolation (Middleton and Harvey, 2014).

Brandon, Bailey, and Belderson (2010) also highlight that children can sustain physical injuries, or be fatally injured during incidents of abuse, therefore reinforcing the extensive impact of domestic abuse on children and their outcomes (Middleton and Harvey, 2014). Therefore, it is unsurprising that a close association exists between domestic abuse and emotional, physical and sexual abuse of children (Turner *et al*, 2017, Scottish Government, 2018). Of the children referred to the Scottish Children's Reporter Association (SCRA) the most common grounds for referral include a close connection with a perpetrator of domestic abuse (Scottish Government, 2018). Despite this association between domestic and child abuse being recognised in research, it is argued that professionals are often apprehensive and unsure how to respond to this in practice (Turner *et al*, 2017).

2.6 Conclusion

Domestic abuse is a complex phenomenon and has been widely researched and reported on to allow a robust understanding of the known risk factors, presentations and costs to individuals as well as societies. The physical and psychological impacts to women survivors and their children is known to be significant, and so this chapter has emphasised the wide-reaching effects of abuse. If Health Visitors are to robustly search for health needs, it is important the vast and enduring impacts of abuse on survivors, is well understood, and can facilitate effective responses to abuse disclosures.

3 Key areas of focus for the study

Domestic abuse affects over one third of women internationally and is present within large proportions of health visiting caseloads (WHO, 2021). Early scoping exercises identified that a large volume of material exists that considers domestic abuse, screening, and routine enquiry, however very little that considers the health visiting role in identifying and responding to domestic abuse. Furthermore, although health visiting research is not abundant, scoping exercises suggest that there have been few changes in how Health Visitors respond to domestic abuse over the last two decades, despite a growing awareness of the impact of domestic abuse on victims and their children.

The nature of the relationship between parents and professional helpers, for example, Health Visitors, mentors, home visitors, has been widely debated in literature, and a consensus often exists regarding the factors that should exist for a relationship to be therapeutic or supportive, for example, empathy, compassion, trust (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016; Horvath, 2000). Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott (2016) have investigated the nature of the Health Visitor-parent relationship, however, there remains little reference to how the relationship between parent and HV impacts on a woman's willingness to disclose domestic abuse.

Although Health Visitors are centrally placed to identify and respond to domestic abuse, there is a dichotomy between the policy ambitions and the reality in practice in some areas within the UK, whereby Health Visitor numbers have reduced by so much that consistent home visiting has been unachievable (IHV, 2016; IHV, 2019). The impact is that Health Visitors are often unable to develop rapport and positive relationships with parents. Without this relationship, positive change, or disclosures of abuse are unlikely to be realised. It is therefore clear from a scope of existing research and policy, that improvements in health visiting practice are required. Based on scoping exercises, and detailed analysis of background information relating to domestic abuse and health visiting practice, mind mapping was used to summarise and record ideas and create a literature review question:

'What impact does the strength of the Health Visitor-parent relationship have on a woman's willingness to disclose domestic abuse through routine enquiry?'

4 Literature Review

4.1 Introduction to chapter

A literature review is essential for appraising and synthesising existing knowledge on a particular topic, and identifying gaps, biases, and directions for future research (Rowe, 2014). This chapter will determine what is already known in the area of relationship-based health visiting practice within a context of identifying and responding to domestic abuse. These two areas of focus were reviewed in parallel and independently of each other, using a scoping review methodology as described in the seminal work of Arksey and O'Mally (2005). This framework uses prescribed steps to describe the current knowledge of a phenomenon, and highlight patterns and where there is scope for future research, practice and policy:

1. Identifying the review question
2. Identifying relevant studies
3. Study selection
4. Charting the data
5. Collating, summarising and reporting the results
6. Consultation

4.2 Development of the literature review question

Domestic abuse affects over one third of women internationally and is present within large proportions of health visiting caseloads (WHO, 2021; IHV, 2019). Early scoping focused on research evidence related to domestic abuse, screening and routine enquiry, and identified that a large volume of material exists, however very little that considers the health visiting role in identifying and responding to domestic abuse. Furthermore, although health visiting research is not abundant, scoping exercises suggest that there have been few changes in how Health Visitors have responded to domestic abuse over the last two decades, despite a growing awareness of the impact of domestic abuse on victims and their children.

Similar scoping activities highlighted that the nature of the relationship between parents and professional helpers, for example, Health Visitors, mentors, home visitors, has been widely debated. A consensus often exists regarding the factors that should be present for a relationship to be therapeutic or supportive, for example, empathy, compassion, trust (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016; Horvath, 2000). Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott (2016) have investigated the nature of the Health Visitor-parent relationship, however, there remains little reference to how the relationship between parent and the HV impacts on a woman's willingness to disclose domestic abuse.

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'What impact does the strength of the Health Visitor-parent relationship have on a woman's willingness to disclose domestic abuse through routine enquiry?'

4.3 Identifying relevant studies

The literature review question has two distinct strands within it; the impact and strength of the health visitor-parent relationship; and a woman's disclosure of abuse through routine enquiry. Each strand required its own individual search using databases that were most likely to produce findings that could effectively answer the research question. The PICO framework in Table 1, was formulated through discussion with the supervisory team, and used to identify key search terms that could be used to search for evidence that would directly relate to each part of the literature review question.

The key words identified for the intervention varied between the two strands of the review question; the various terms for domestic abuse were included, including IPV, domestic violence, and components relating to home visiting models, such as strengths based approaches, home visiting.

PICO Framework	
Population/problem	Health Visitors, public health nurses, parents, home visitors, home helpers*
Intervention	Routine enquiry, screening, domestic abuse/violence/IPV/gender-based violence, home visiting, strengths-based approaches, HV-parent relationship
Comparison	Strength of relationship, trust, empathy
Outcome	Disclosure of abuse

*Home helpers is a term referring to paid or voluntary individuals who support parenting in the home, and often where vulnerabilities exist.

Table 1: PICO framework

Although the focus of the literature review question was on Health Visitors and their relationship with women, the inclusion criteria at the outset was expanded to include other professionals or roles that reflected similarities with the health visiting model of care delivery. This decision was made to avoid losing relevant and valuable knowledge that related to home visiting, and that would also consider an international perspective where care deliver models for women differ from that of the UK.

Health Visitors are also known as Public Health Nurses globally, and therefore this term was included in the search strategy population, along with parents as the primary receivers of this model of care. It is acknowledged that these roles might vary in terms of professional qualification, however were included due to the proposition that generic characteristics might exist in the relationship between them and parents. EBSCO Host was accessed and CINAHL Ultimate supported the identification of primary databases which were then used to search for research literature. Publications were searched for within, PsycArticles, Medline, Health Source, APA PsycArticles, Psychology and Behavioural Science Collection, SocIndex. EBSCO Host was selected due to the

range of nursing and psychology literature available that was most likely to generate research findings that would answer the literature review question.

4.4 Study selection

4.4.1 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The PICO framework in Table 1 was used to determine search terms and was useful when identifying inclusion and exclusion criteria. Arksey and O'Malley (2005) suggest that inclusion and exclusion criteria are developed once familiarity with the data has been achieved (Table 2).

Inclusion	Exclusion
Papers 2009-2025	Prior to 2009
English language papers	Papers not written in English
Domestic violence/abuse affecting women as victims	Domestic violence/abuse affecting men as victims
Domestic abuse affecting women likely to receive health visiting services, or be caring for young children	Domestic abuse specifically affecting older women >45
Primary research, systematic reviews, meta-analyses	Reports, books, essays
Women's disclosure of domestic violence/abuse	Men's disclosure of domestic violence/abuse
Reference made to the relationships between parents and home visitors/Health Visitors/helpers	References made to the relationships between agencies/professionals other than home visitors/Health Visitors/helpers
Unpublished material, for example theses	Domestic abuse affecting young people under 18 years

Table 2: Literature search inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Due to the large volume of published literature which focuses on domestic abuse, and as a method of managing data, initial scoping exercises were limited to papers dated between 2009-2019, to ensure papers identified were as contemporary and relatable to current practice as possible (Machi and McEvoy, 2016). However, the searches were re-run in 2024/5 to ensure most up to date literature was identified and included where appropriate. These latter searches included two new papers that had not been originally identified (Williams, 2020; Waller et al, 2023). Searches were not limited to full text papers, or papers only published in academic journals to avoid publication

bias, and also included un-published literature, which may offer interesting or conflicting ideas (Aveyard, 2019). Excluding victims of abuse under 18 years was a deliberate decision, to make a clear distinction between child abuse and domestic abuse in adult relationships. This exclusion was a strategy to avoid ambiguity that might arise where abuse occurs in adolescent relationships and that would be responded to by differing legislative frameworks.

Advanced searches of the key databases were undertaken using Boolean operators; for example, 'domestic abuse' is known by several different terms, including domestic violence, intimate partner violence, gender-based violence and 'Health Visitor' is also known by a Public Health Nurse, or Specialist Community Public Health Nurse. Therefore, using the Boolean operator; OR was used to combine these terms (Aveyard, 2019). Additionally, asterisks were used to search for part of a word, for example, health visit*, to include both Health visiting and Health Visitor (Machi and McEvoy, 2016).

In addition to systematically searching databases, hand searching was also used as an effective strategy to identify other relevant papers; reviewing reference lists from already retrieved literature highlighted several other papers worthy of consideration (Boland, Dickson and Cherry, 2017). Also, having an awareness of authors, for example, Cowley, Bidmead, Pound, Peckover, who have published research on topics relevant to the literature review question were also searched for to identify relevant material and seminal works (Machi and McEvoy, 2016). Citation chaining, or snowballing is a strategy used to identify sources that the original source has cited, and this technique was used to find other key seminal papers (Duddy and Roberts, 2021). As well as searching published literature, grey literature such as policy documents, reports from UK and Scottish Governments, and organisations who support women who have experienced domestic abuse, were also searched for and reviewed (Aveyard, 2019).

4.4.2 Search Strings

A variety of search strings were used to search for all the publications within the databases, which are recorded in Appendix 1. A PRISMA diagram in Appendix 2 illustrates the flow of information through the systematic search methods of the

literature review, and was reviewed by the supervisory team for accuracy. As shown in the PRIMSA diagram, 812 papers were screened by title and then abstract if appropriate, followed by 93 papers being read in full to determine whether they met the inclusion criteria. All 46 papers meeting the inclusion criteria were subject to critical appraisal using the various Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) tools (CASP, 2018a, 2018b) to determine the quality of each study.

Systematic reviews or meta-analyses of randomised control trials are traditionally placed at the top of the hierarchy of evidence, suggesting these studies are superior in terms of strength of study, with interpretative research considered to be inferior to positivist alternatives (LoBiondo-Wood and Haber, 2018). However, a modern approach suggests that interpretative research provides a legitimate research design of social enquiry that is appropriate for investigating the experiences, perceptions, and behaviours of people, to understand, describe and interpret social phenomenon (Holloway and Galvin, 2023).

4.5 Charting the data

The search strategy has identified 46 relevant primary research papers and systematic reviews that help to address both elements of the review question. The papers were read and re-read and summarised in a matrix and patterning chart (Appendix 3, 3a and 3b) as a means of understanding the articles in greater depth and to visually highlight themes that were considered specific to this particular review, such as research design methodology, location of the research, the participants and which of the two elements of the review question the paper relates to - domestic abuse or relationship based practice. A PAGER framework was also developed (Appendix 3c) alongside the patterning chart to summarise the included papers, the common themes, findings and where gaps in knowledge exist. Both were reviewed by the supervisory team, and analysis of both PAGER framework and the patterning chart illustrates that of the 46 studies selected, 33 had an interpretivist approach, with only three being solely positivist in approach, and ten using mixed methods. The studies span a range of geographical countries, including 14 from the UK, and the remaining from Europe, USA, Australia, Asia and Africa, and studies take place within community, home, clinic and hospital settings. Of the 46 studies, 33 aimed to seek the views of women using

health services; 20 of these studies involved participants who were victims and survivors of domestic abuse, however only eight were UK studies.

The patterning chart and PAGER framework illustrated that domestic abuse is an area well studied, and understanding the barriers and facilitators to abuse disclosure is common area of focus for researchers, both in the UK and internationally. A further 13 studies were not related to domestic abuse, but explored the nature of relationships between women and either healthcare providers or home visitors, however with only four of these being of UK origin, this exercise highlighted that this is an area more commonly explored internationally. The majority sought service user perspectives as the source of data. Four studies were able to, in part, help to answer both elements of the literature review question, with focus on both domestic abuse and relationships between women and home visitors, counsellors and nurses (Bacchus, 2016, Roddy, 2013, Roddy 2013, Visentin et al, 2015). Only four studies were identified that involved participants who had either received or delivered health visiting services in the UK; however studies were included that used similar home visiting models, or services delivered by Public Health Nurses overseas, that had some similarity to UK roles, and that would help to answer the review question. Studies were included that involved other healthcare professionals, e.g. nurses, midwives, doctors as it was perceived that their experiences would provide useful insights, and some that would perhaps be relevant when translated into a Health Visiting context, and would offer some contrast when considering international perspectives.

Analysis of the literature identified that authors of interpretivist research studies that involved survivors of abuse commonly used individual interviews as the method of seeking their views and lived experience, as the most appropriate method to discuss sensitive topics. Research involving health professionals frequently used focus groups and surveys as the primary data collection methods. Study participants were often recruited as already accessing domestic abuse services (Waller et al, 2023, Williams et al, 2020), therefore will have had some experience of help seeking and disclosing abuse, unlike participants in other studies where screening and disclosure were the focus.

The majority of studies were published 2013-2016, and although reasons for this are not explicit within the studies themselves, it is possible that the UK research may have emerged in response to the political pressures of the time. That is, the Health Visitor Implementation Plan (Department of Health, 2011) in England was underway, and recommendations from the Francis Report (Francis, 2013) that raised concerns about the quality of care being provided in the Mid Staffordshire NHS Trust, were current. Together with the emergence of the Children and Young People's (Scotland) Act (2015) in Scotland, it is possible that these policy changes were catalysts for some of the UK studies.

4.6 Collating, summarising and reporting the results

In addition to the PAGER framework and patterning charts described previously, NVivo 12 software was also used to support the review process. The abstract and reference of each identified paper was uploaded to a document within NVivo 12, and relevant sections of the paper were highlighted and pasted to the same document, assigning a name to each theme/node, which were reviewed by the supervisory team. Once completed for all papers, the following nodes were identified, reviewed and confirmed – highlighting that of the five themes, themes 1-4 relate to domestic abuse, screening and enquiry; and only one theme related to relationships:

1. Feasibility of screening and routine enquiry
2. Acceptability of screening/routine enquiry to women
3. Barriers to disclosing abuse
4. Facilitators to disclosing abuse
5. Relationships

Scoping review methodologies are broader in nature than systematic reviews (Bradbury-Jones et al, 2021), therefore in addition to NVivo 12 software, and to further enhance rigor of the review process, the PAGER framework (Bradbury-Jones et al, 2021) was also used to apply a consistent method for reporting the analysis of the literature review. In addition, throughout the literature review process, the researcher consulted with the supervision team to enhance the credibility and robustness of the reviewing findings. The analytical process, the emergence of themes and use of tools

such as NVivo 12 were discussed and reviewed to satisfy and ensure review findings had been reached via the proposed methodology.

The PAGER framework was used to record summaries to highlight where there were large volumes of knowledge relating to certain topics, and where there were gaps in what is known. It supported a methodological review and analysis of findings (Appendix 3c) to identify Patterns, Advances, Gaps, Evidence for Practice and Research Recommendations.

The PAGER framework demonstrates the large body of research and knowledge around domestic abuse, in particular, but not limited to barriers to disclosure, the lack of evidence to support routine screening of abuse, a lack of screening within health settings, and poor responses from health professionals. Through the use of the PAGER matrix, gaps in knowledge could be identified, and recommendations for future research included the scope for further qualitative research to explore the specific needs of women, especially those from diverse ethnic backgrounds. Through the systematic use of the PAGER framework to report and NVivo 12 to support the analysis process, the following themes will be discussed below, and will help to highlight the breadth of existing knowledge, and where gaps in knowledge and understanding occur.

4.6.1 Theme 1 – Feasibility of Screening and Routine Enquiry

Although the primary aim of this literature review is not to debate the feasibility, or value of domestic abuse screening or routine enquiry within health care settings, it is worthy of discussion, as it provides a crucial vehicle for women to disclose domestic abuse and informs related support and health services. There is a variety of grey literature that directs how routine enquiry is undertaken in Scotland and the UK.

Scottish Government (2008) set out its responsibilities in relation to gender based violence via CEL 41(2008) by stipulating that routine enquiry of abuse should be implemented within priority settings, for example, Maternity Services, Mental Health, Sexual and Reproductive Health, A&E, Addictions and Primary Care, however

evidence from practice suggests that routine enquiry is not as well embedded as policy anticipated (Evans and Feder, 2014). These recommendations have been implemented into UK policy despite the evidence base to support routine enquiry being used universally in healthcare, being inconclusive (Feder *et al*, 2009, Svavarsdottir, 2010; O'Doherty *et al*, 2015).

Although it is widely recognised that routine screening of women increases the identification of those experiencing domestic abuse, it is proposed that there is a lack of evidence to support asking all women who enter healthcare settings (O'Doherty *et al*, 2015). Routine enquiry is often referred to as routine screening, and the terms will be used interchangeably to reflect terminology in the international research. Svavarsdottir (2010) has suggested that there is no clear vehicle to offer domestic abuse screening, with face to face interviews and self-reporting tools both reporting ambiguity concerning their effectiveness. Feder *et al* (2009) and O'Doherty *et al* (2015) both undertook systematic reviews which aimed to consider the evidence for routine screening, and benefits to women. Systematic reviews are tools for reviewing evidence and synthesising findings using rigorous, explicit methods (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017). Although with slightly differing aims, Feder *et al* (2009) and O'Doherty *et al* (2015) both undertook reviews that followed a robust review process, searching several databases to locate primary studies.

O'Doherty *et al*'s (2015) Cochrane review included trials totalling almost 15,000 women from diverse settings, which increases the generalisability of findings (LoBiondo-Wood and Haber, 2018) however, it was recognised that the overall quality of trials was low to moderate, with risk of bias and imprecision being identified and therefore potentially impacting upon the findings (Boland, Dickson and Cherry, 2017). Systematic search processes were undertaken, and findings indicated that screening increases the identification of women experiencing domestic abuse, as most women will not disclose unless asked (Feder *et al*, 2009), however, neither face to face interviews, nor computer-based screening were found to be better at facilitating disclosure. Referrals to specialist services following a positive disclosure remained low, and responses from services were often poorly co-ordinated (O'Doherty *et al*, 2015). Researchers' attempts to determine an effect on further outcomes, for example, health outcomes, re-exposure to violence, lack of harm arising from

screening, were proven to be inconclusive, with no evidence to support routine enquiry in healthcare settings. O'Doherty *et al* (2015) suggested that although there was no evidence of routine enquiry causing harm to women, there was equally little evidence of benefit to women experiencing domestic abuse. Therefore, it is proposed that more evidence is required to confirm an association between routine enquiry and women engaging in supportive interventions and positive impacts on health and wellbeing (O'Doherty *et al*, 2015).

The systematic review by Feder *et al* (2009) searched 14 databases however, neither Feder *et al* (2009) nor O'Doherty *et al* (2015) provided evidence of hand searching for additional material. Therefore both could have potentially excluded papers which could have had bearing on the findings (Boland, Dickson and Cherry, 2017). Feder *et al* (2009) reported using a variety of critical appraisal tools to determine the quality of selected papers and enlisted two researchers to select the studies to avoid selection bias (Gough, Oliver and Thomas, 2017).

Feder *et al* (2009) identified that despite lower estimates for prevalence, morbidity and mortality, domestic abuse is a significant public health problem, and screening tools are available with degrees of reliability and validity. There is a lack of reliable evidence to determine the cost effectiveness of routine enquiry, or the subsequent impact on morbidity and mortality; such findings conclude that there is insufficient evidence to offer routine screening universally to all women entering healthcare settings.

Feder *et al* (2009) and O'Doherty *et al* (2015) claim evidence for routine enquiry to be questionable and ambiguous and call for further research to provide more conclusive findings. A qualitative study using a constructionist approach, by Spangaro, Zwi and Poulos (2011) explored Australian women's decisions to disclose abuse, and also identified the benefits of disclosure to women were poorly defined, and found that women often returned, or were seeking to return to their abusive partners, or that abuse had continued.

4.6.2 Theme 2 – Acceptability of screening/routine enquiry to women

A common theme emerging from the literature is that screening or enquiry for domestic abuse is acceptable to women. Feder *et al* (2009) and O'Doherty *et al* (2015) both highlighted through their systematic reviews that routine enquiry is acceptable to women, and they are unlikely to offer disclosures without being asked directly. Women's views of routine enquiry often featured in research about domestic abuse (Decker *et al*, 2012; Damra *et al*, 2015; Baird, Salmon and White, 2013; Taylor *et al*, 2013; Bradbury-Jones *et al*, 2014; Bacchus *et al*, 2016; Suryavanshi, Naik, and Waghmare, 2018).

Salmon, Baird and White, (2015) explored the acceptability of routine enquiry during antenatal midwifery care, applying a mixed method approach using a survey and interviews in a UK study. They used purposive sampling to identify participants with the same characteristics or features which allowed researchers to undertake in-depth explorations of the themes or questions relevant to the phenomenon under investigation; thus, gathering rich data that is likely to answer the research question (Ritchie *et al*, 2013). The study found that high proportions of women (94.4%) reported to be comfortable being asked by the midwife about domestic abuse, although they did acknowledge that they may not disclose immediately. A similarly high response (96.6%) expected Midwives to be able to respond to a disclosure of abuse. This created a culture whereby women were aware of the impact of abuse, and support available, and knew that they could discuss abuse if and when they chose to (Salmon, Baird and White, 2015). It is important to note that this study included only those women engaging in antenatal care and attending clinic appointments. There is no evidence that women who may not consistently attend appointments have had an opportunity to be included in the study, and who could have provided alternative perspectives (Ritchie *et al*, 2013).

A two-phase qualitative study by Taylor *et al* (2013) used a critical incident technique to seek the views of health professionals working in Scottish Health Boards, and female survivors of abuse, via interviews and focus groups respectively. Efforts were made to protect female participants who had experienced abuse by using oral vignettes, rather than offering their own experiences to comment on health

professionals' responses in relation to domestic abuse. Like the findings from Salmon, Baird and White (2015), a large proportion of the women in the study stated they were comfortable being asked about domestic abuse, and over 96% believed it was appropriate for health professionals to ask about abuse.

Heron, Eisma and Browne's 2020 ethnographic study, used in-depth interviews and thematic analysis to identify that although all the study's sample of women (n=29) agreed that health professionals should ask about domestic abuse, still only 45% did disclose when asked. Health professionals in Taylor *et al's* (2013) study recounted that women usually only disclose during a period of crisis, for example, significant injury or homelessness. Taylor *et al's* (2013) research study was undertaken in Scotland, therefore, although interpretative data is not generalisable to the wider population, the findings are likely to be valuable when considered in a Scottish context (Ritchie *et al*, 2013). Taylor *et al's* study (2013) benefitted from enhanced rigour from using a reflexive journal, as well as thematic and secondary analysis. As with other domestic abuse studies the authors took several steps to ensure safety of the participants by providing support, ensuring anonymity, and considering the safety of women at all stages of the research process.

Twelve international studies were identified that considered women's views about routine enquiry for domestic abuse. Studies by Suryavanshi, Naik and Waghmare (2018), Damra *et al* (2015) and Decker *et al* (2012) used a variety of interpretivist and positivist approaches. Findings supported the view that women want to be asked about domestic abuse and would like information displayed in common areas about domestic abuse (Damra *et al* (2015). Suryavanshi, Naik and Waghmare (2018) studied Indian women's perceptions of domestic abuse screening in a cross sectional, observational study, using interviews with women (n=300) who also completed semi-structured questionnaires. Using descriptive statistics, their findings suggested that a high proportion of women were willing to be asked by healthcare providers, however they would prefer to disclose through face-to-face contact with nurses or counsellors. Suryavanshi, Naik and Waghmare's (2018) study does not make any reference to ethical considerations taken throughout the study, for example, there is no description of how women were recruited and supported during the study. These studies are all

influenced by cultural considerations due to their origins in India and Jordan. These points will be discussed later in the review.

An American nested, interpretative study by Bacchus *et al* (2016) also found that women wanted to be asked about domestic abuse to de-stigmatise the issue, talk about their experiences and access support. This study recruited women enrolled on the Domestic Violence Enhanced Intervention (DOVE) programme, who were either pregnant or three months post-partum. The researchers interviewed 26 women to gather their views of being screened for domestic abuse. Bacchus *et al* (2016) acknowledge the potential risks to study participants and detail the measures taken in the study to promote their safety. Findings from this study reflect Taylor *et al*'s (2013) findings, which suggested that a staged process to disclosure is often evident, requiring certain conditions to be in place before disclosure can take place.

Domestic abuse organisations are often used as gatekeepers to participants in research studies, and while gatekeepers allow easier access to a greater number of potential participants, they also may include or exclude subjects depending on their own values and opinions. Therefore researchers are reliant on them executing the same rigorous methods and ensuring there is no coercion or pressure to participate (Ellis, 2021). Other ethical considerations to take into account include the offer of gift vouchers to participants; Bacchus *et al* (2016) provided gift vouchers to those who participated, and it is argued that although it may be a token of appreciation, it can also be seen as coercive, however it is acknowledged that there is a lack of clear guidance on the issue of incentives (Economic and Social Research Council [ESRC], 2012).

4.6.3 Theme 3 – Barriers to disclosure

The barriers to disclosure have been widely studied and there is a great deal of knowledge and understanding relating to the factors that prevent women seeking help. Domestic abuse is a phenomenon that is multifaceted and complex, affecting women from all communities and socio-economic backgrounds, (McGarry and Ali, 2018). Heron, Eisma and Browne (2020) and Evans and Feder (2014) recognised that domestic abuse is widely under-reported, and that numerous barriers exist at three levels which prevent disclosure: individual, community and organisational levels. Due

to the multifactorial nature of barriers, this theme has been separated into subsections to include personal factors, health related factors, and other factors.

4.6.3.1 Personal factors

There are various personal factors that prevent women from disclosing abuse, including, but not limited to fear and shame. Evans and Feder (2014) suggest that disclosures are often gradual, and come after attempts to use personal strategies to cope with their experiences. An interpretivist study by Evans and Feder (2014) explored help-seeking for women experiencing domestic abuse, and used interviews that followed a guided conversation structure to understand the experiences of 31 women who were already receiving support from specialist services. Several reasons for avoiding disclosure were identified, many of which have also been identified in similar studies, such as self-blame, social isolation, and mental health issues such as depression and low self-esteem (Evans and Feder, 2014; Francis, Loxton and James, 2016; Heron, Eisma and Browne, 2020). Women often did not want to burden their family members, and experienced feelings of shame or embarrassment, and felt obliged to meet parental expectations to avoid being judged (Evans and Feder, 2014; Francis, Loxton and James, 2016). Furthermore, women in Evans and Feder's (2014) study, disclosed that violence had often featured in their lives consistently from being children and had become normalised. For these women it was difficult to imagine a life without violence and abuse, and they doubted that support would be available to them.

Francis, Loxton and James (2016) in an Australian, qualitative study used a narrative enquiry approach to identify a 'culture of pretence' constructed by women and reinforced by perpetrators and others outside the relationship, who fail to identify symptoms of abuse. Contributing factors that support women to maintain this culture of pretence includes their sense of self-blame, poor self-esteem, minimising, and normalising of the abuse. However, women in the study also expressed frustration that despite maintaining this pretence, others failed to recognise the domestic abuse.

Fear was a key factor in women's willingness to disclose abuse. Heron, Eisma and Browne (2020) and Evans and Feder (2014) also found that women were fearful of repercussions from the perpetrator in that disclosure would trigger revenge violence.

Women have described how perpetrators have manipulated professionals and prevented them from speaking to their families and friends and many were afraid to confide in their Family Doctor.

Similarities were identified in a Dutch qualitative study by Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen (2013). The authors used semi-structured interviews to seek the views of women (n=14) about help-seeking processes and identified that women's fear of their partner prevented them from seeking professional support, and abusive partners often displayed anger which prevented them from sharing their experiences with family and friends. The researchers took various steps to develop and test an interview guide to avoid any bias and enhance rigour. A financial incentive of €15 was given to each woman at the end of the interview, however it is unclear from the study whether women were aware of this at commencement of the interviews. Being unaware would increase the credibility of the findings and reduce the likelihood of coercion or pressure on women to participate in the study (Parahoo, 2014).

Findings from Hasselle *et al* (2019) suggested that women were deeply invested in their relationships with perpetrators and viewed disclosure as betrayal. Using qualitative feedback sessions, they identified that women also described controlling behaviours which curtailed their engagement with services and made them fearful of repercussions. Hasselle *et al* (2019) used a robust data analysis procedure, using consensual qualitative research methods which are often used to analyse open ended questions focussing on words, context and consideration of multiple interpretations (Hill and Knox, 2021). Co-authors and a research team were used to analyse data which increased the credibility of the findings by reducing opportunity for researcher bias (LoBiondo-Wood and Haber, 2018).

Williams *et al* (2020) in their descriptive interpretivist study, identified that women were also fearful of the impact of disclosure on their children, and of losing them, and this often led them to remain in abusive relationships. The role of children is a significant consideration for women's decision making within domestic abuse contexts, as Williams *et al* (2020) also identified that other women in the study also cited protecting their children as a reason to disclose abuse.

An English qualitative study by Rose *et al* (2010) used cross sectional interviews and purposive sampling to identify potential participants who were, or had been, receiving support from community mental health services. The recruitment strategy included advertisement of the study in various places for example, in community mental health centres, in the local voluntary mental health sector newsletter, and through care co-ordinators during routine appointments with service users. It is possible that the use of care co-ordinators as gatekeepers could add bias due to their power to include or exclude potential participants (Holloway and Galvin, 2023). Rose *et al* (2010) developed concept maps to highlight a variety of barriers, with over-arching themes relating to fear; fear of further violence, fear of disruption to their family, fear of involvement of social services, fear of not being believed, and fear of losing an immigration status. Self-blame, blaming attitudes of others, shame, embarrassment and distress were also identified as barriers to disclosure. Rose *et al* (2010) also found that personal attributes or situations also prevented disclosure, such as women not realising they were experiencing domestic abuse, or ignoring it and consequently being isolated from family and friends due to the actions of the perpetrators. Participants in this study highlighted that the relationship between health professional and service user is important to facilitate disclosures.

Self-blame was also identified as a barrier in Evans and Feder's (2014) interpretative study. Thirty one women were interviewed twice in the study which identified that those experiencing domestic abuse were often socially isolated, which affected the women's' perception of the normality of their partner's behaviours. This was an American study, however it can be proposed that experiences of American women might also be relevant within a UK context.

A lack of awareness was also highlighted in literature as a barrier to women seeking help or disclosing abuse. Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen (2013) recruited participants from a Dutch cross-sectional survey on IPV prevalence, to interview 14 participants. The study findings highlighted various barriers to disclosure similar to those identified by Evans and Feder (2014); including denial of domestic abuse, whereby problems were minimised, and women did not acknowledge that their partner's behaviours were abusive. Secondly, women demonstrated a lack of awareness of the consequences of domestic abuse and were unaware of the impact

on their children or on their own health. There was an assumption by women in the study that only women experiencing physical violence would be supported by the police and shelter organisations, and the family doctor was not the right person to help them, due to their perceived ignorance of abused women.

4.6.3.2 Health related factors

Barriers to disclosure that relate to the health care experience of victims of abuse are well covered in the literature. Many women in Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen's (2013) study have reported feeling dissatisfied with the response from their family doctor, reporting that they were not taken seriously, and the doctor made no enquiry after their children where they knew domestic abuse was occurring. Concerns were exacerbated further as women described how, when referring onto services, doctors cited mental health issues as the reason for referral rather than domestic abuse (Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen's, 2013).

Five of the studies that explored healthcare related factors as a barrier to disclosing abuse, were international, including research from Jordan, Australia, USA and the Netherlands. Like Prosman, Wong, and Lagro-Janssen (2013), Damra *et al's* (2015) Jordanian study identified that those women who had disclosed abuse to their family doctor were dissatisfied with the response they received. Women reported that doctors presented themselves as being too busy, and many recalled inadequate privacy offered in clinics. Lagro-Janssen's study (2013) felt their doctor failed to provide sufficient information about domestic abuse.

In a recent British qualitative study by Heron, Eisma and Browne (2020), 29 women were interviewed to determine barriers and facilitators of disclosing abuse. Using content analysis, authors found that abusive partners frequently used controlling behaviours to ensure they were present at health appointments. Similarly, participants described instances of perpetrators manipulating professionals, both of which limited the opportunities to ask about, and speak in confidence to health care professionals about domestic abuse.

As well as women's experiences of health care, this review also highlighted women's individual health and wellness as a barrier to disclosure. Poor mental health was a barrier to seeking help and disclosing abuse in a small scale exploratory ethnographic study by Hasselle *et al* (2019). Hasselle *et al* (2019) used purposive sampling to interview nine women in America who had experienced domestic abuse either during or immediately preceding pregnancy. It was appropriate to use individual qualitative feedback sessions to gather their accounts of their mental health, which identified that depression, anxiety, low levels of self-worth and self-esteem affected their abilities to disclose.

As well as women's mental health, physical health issues relating to pregnancy were also identified as a barrier identified in Hasselle *et al*'s (2019) study, however this factor was not identified in other studies. Weight gain, feeling uncomfortable as the pregnancy progressed, hyperemesis, were identified as contributing to lower levels of engagement with interventions, and subsequently a barrier to disclosing abuse.

4.6.3.3 Cultural barriers

Several studies highlighted cultural practises, values, social attitudes and beliefs that presented as a barrier to disclosing domestic abuse and seeking help (Decker *et al*, 2012, Damra *et al*, 2015, Suryavanshi *et al*, 2018, Hasselle *et al*, 2019, Waller *et al*, 2023). Hasselle *et al* (2019) report that social stigma which normalises domestic abuse in turn, discourages women from disclosing abuse to others. Women in this study described pervasive cultures suggesting domestic abuse was acceptable, and as a result prevented them from viewing abuse as a concern. Additionally, those who acknowledged the seriousness of their situation often demonstrated ambivalence due to the expected reactions from others.

The interpretation and understanding of domestic abuse can vary by country, influenced by attitudes, political structures and religious beliefs (Larkin and Morris, 2009). Studies have been undertaken in India (Decker *et al*, 2012; Suryavanshi, Naik and Waghmare, 2018), where it is suggested that one in three women experience domestic abuse, and there is a higher prevalence of both lifetime and physical violence

when compared with other settings (Larkin and Morris, 2009; Lee and Hadeed, 2009). These South Asian contexts bring additional barriers to women, largely grounded in cultural prohibitions against discussion of problems within a family, and the view that doing so would bring shame, stigmatisation and damage the family's reputation and honour (Lee and Hadeed, 2009; Decker *et al*, 2012). As a result, research currently suggests that women from these groups rarely share experiences of domestic abuse or seek support from formal sources (Larkin and Morris, 2009). It is also important to note that many of the international studies are set within countries that do not have health visiting services that mirror those found in the UK. However, these cultural barriers continue to be relevant to South Asian women who are living in the UK, and are likely to still influence their help-seeking practices, despite them having access to universal services offering domestic abuse enquiry and support.

A mixed methods study by Decker *et al* (2012) aimed to identify help-seeking preferences from women in India who had recently given birth. Using interviews and grounded theory methods, as well as survey data from women attending immunisation clinics with their babies under six months of age, findings suggested that women preferred to seek support from informal sources rather than professionals. Although few were asked about domestic abuse, over half reported that they would be willing to disclose when asked, despite the cultural challenges.

Unlike studies by Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen (2013) and Evans and Feder (2014), Decker *et al*'s (2012) study highlighted that, as well as fear of the perpetrator, women in this study were fearful of social repercussions and this was a primary barrier to disclosing to family and neighbours. When women did seek help, they were more likely to approach informal sources of support, for example, family, or neighbours. However, this was only likely to happen if women had sustained severe injury, or if violence had occurred in public whereby women were unable to conceal such assaults. A similar ethnographic study by Ahmad *et al* (2009) and a qualitative exploratory study by Odera *et al* (2014) both suggested that women would turn to professional health services for severe injuries only and would more commonly seek support from family, however, if women felt shame, they were likely to avoid all support.

Decker *et al* (2009) also found that women were often unaware of supportive agencies, but also were sceptical about their ability and capacity to help them. Similarly, they reported previous negative experiences with formal services, which resulted in a sense of hopelessness and resignation to their predicament. Women in India are often financially dependent on men, which accompanies the impoverished nature of the community, and the low status of women that is held (Decker *et al*, 2012). Similarly, their financial dependence on men is a significant barrier to disclosure, and support services are often reported to be disjointed, weak and victim blaming (Odero *et al*, 2014). Structural barriers exist in African countries such as Kenya, whereby most women do not hold their own identification, which is required to seek legal action, thus creating a further barrier to help-seeking and disclosure (Odero *et al*, 2014).

Damra *et al* (2015) studied 25 pregnant women in Jordan using semi-structured interviews. Similar to findings from studies by Decker *et al* (2012) and Suryavanshi, Naik, and Waghmare (2018), women in Jordan also experienced poor rates of domestic abuse disclosure. Damra *et al* (2015) suggest that a tradition of protecting abusive husbands and a culture which interprets abuse as a husband's right to correct his wife's mistakes, was a significant barrier to disclosing abuse. Nineteen women in the study received negative attitudes, where A&E staff withdrew support and apportioned blame to the women. Like previous studies, women in Jordan also claimed not to disclose to formal supports due to their lack of confidence in professionals' abilities to understand their problems. These findings are similar to those from Waller *et al*'s (2023) grounded theory study who suggest that African American women are further marginalised due to cultural factors. They suggest women are rarely referred onto shelters and experience long delays for Police responses resulting in a lack of trust in services.

Cultural gender roles, and marital obligations were also barriers for South Asian women, which delayed them from seeking support (Ahmad *et al*, 2009). Damra *et al* (2015) recruited pregnant women attending midwifery clinics with their husbands, and who had positively screened for domestic abuse. This strategy relied on women's honest disclosure of domestic abuse and excluded women who did not consistently engage with midwifery care. The study was considered increasingly credible by robust thematic content data analysis by three researchers, and the use of a validated and

tested interview guide, to promote consistency in the way questions were posed and interviews were managed (Turner, 2010).

4.6.4 Theme 4 – Facilitators to disclosure

The fourth theme will explore the facilitators to domestic abuse disclosure. Although a plethora of research exists which studies barriers to women disclosing domestic abuse, significantly less material is available which aims to identify the qualities or conditions that are required to promote disclosure to professionals. Of the material available, the majority seek the views of healthcare professionals, rather than those accessing these services.

For a woman to disclose abuse, a fundamental requirement that is highlighted from the research, is the presence of a positive relationship between women and health professional (Clancy and Svensson, 2010; Rose *et al*, 2010; Visentin, Vieira, and Trevisan, 2015; Francis, Loxton and James 2016; Shanti, 2017). Brook and Salmon (2015) report that effective communication and trust are key attributes in the relationships between Health Visitors and parents, and if this was lost, or not present, then parents were unlikely to engage with the service.

Additionally, the ability of Health Visitors to offer regular home visits was also identified as an appropriate vehicle to build positive relationships. Brook and Salmon's (2015) qualitative study based in the southwest of England used semi-structured interviews and focus groups with parents who attended local children's centres. However, it is argued that this study excluded parents who did not attend local groups, and who may be socially isolated, or may not feel comfortable in the community.

Similarly, Shanti (2017) states that a variety of strategies are commonly used to build the foundations of a working relationship, before it can develop over time into a partnership in which shared goals can be achieved. Shanti's (2017) grounded theory study found that health professionals identified essential tasks necessary in the early stages of building relationships, for example, building trust, finding common ground, communicating respectfully, displaying a genuine interest in the child and family, and establishing professional boundaries. This reflects findings from Brook and Salmon

(2015) who suggest that respecting the views of women, credibility, honesty, and having time for parents are pivotal to relationship building.

The first contact with services has also been identified as important for women experiencing domestic abuse. The Universal Health Visiting Pathway (Scottish Government, 2015) prescribes an antenatal visit between 32-34 weeks gestation, as it is considered a key contact by both Health Visitors and prospective parents, to begin relationship development (Doi et al, 2021). Despite the value of this initial contact in establishing relationships with parents, Doi *et al* (2021) identified that it is often one of the key visits to be omitted from the visiting pathway when workforce pressures occur, or when the pathway is not being fully implemented.

Lelaurain, Graziani and Lo Monaco (2017) in their systematic review, report that empathetic responses offering unconditional, non-judgemental support are likely to support abuse disclosures. Lelaurain, Graziani and Lo Monaco (2017) searched two databases, and used hand searching, to make reasonable attempts to locate all appropriate material (CASP, 2018a). Similarly, being honest, caring, friendly, knowledgeable, appearing confident, carefully listening were also identified by Bacchus *et al* (2016) as attributes necessary to develop trust.

An ethnographic observation study of Public Health Nurses (PHN) in a clinic setting in Norway identified that friendliness, openness, and directness, based within a relationship of trust and sincerity were welcomed by service users (Clancy and Svensson, 2010). This study used participant observations and interviews, which were then subject to content analysis. Due to the methods employed by the researchers, the findings are at risk of researcher bias in objectively documenting observed interactions, without applying the researcher's own views and values. This study has limitations due to the opportunity for selection bias, the small sample, and as the study is a Norwegian study, healthcare provisions and cultural expectations may differ from the UK, and therefore limits the transferability of findings even further. Like Brook and Salmon (2015), Roddy (2013) also recognises through a grounded theory and narrative pilot study that women need to develop trust before they feel comfortable disclosing domestic abuse. The consistency of health professional has also been identified as crucial to relationship development (Clancy and Svensson,

2010; Roddy, 2013; Brook and Salmon, 2015) and especially important to facilitate disclosure and discussion of domestic abuse (Roddy, 2013). Roddy (2013) explored the views of four women who were attending counselling for domestic violence; despite the small sample, women reinforced the importance of consistency in counsellor, understanding and an empathetic, non-judgemental, genuine approach. Continuity of care is a primary aim of the UHVP whereby the same HV supports a family over the course of the pathway. Continuity of care supports early relationship development, and Health Visitors acknowledge that establishing new relationships during the pathway can be challenging (Doi *et al*, 2021).

Similar findings were reported by Rossiter, Fowler and McMahon, (2012), through a qualitative, open ended questionnaire, identified the views of depressed mothers on a relationship home-based intervention. Using thematic content analysis, the study identified that home visitor characteristics such as being empathetic, warm and genuine, and also continuity of worker, supported the relationship development and helped to increase their confidence. The mothers were particularly supportive of a partnership, strengths-based, 'wondering together' approach that increased mother-baby interactions.

Such findings can be considered in relation to women experiencing domestic abuse, who often have poor mental health, and who may also benefit from relationship-based practice. Spangaro, Zwi and Poulos (2011) also discusses the importance of a trusted person being identified by women before disclosure of domestic abuse is considered. Their qualitative study used semi-structured interviews where the data gathered were subject to thematic analysis and identified that although various conditions were required for disclosure to take place, women reported only disclosing when deemed safe to do so, and when asked directly. Additionally, women assessed trustworthiness of healthcare staff by non-verbal behaviours and degree of comfort displayed by workers.

4.6.5 Theme 5 – Health professional practice and behaviours as barrier to disclosure

Health related factors that influenced women's disclosures of abuse was discussed in Theme 3, section 4.6.3.2, however this theme will consider how the practice and behaviours of health professionals influence the use of routine enquiry (RE) to illicit abuse disclosures. Although it is suggested that little is known about the role of healthcare professionals in routine enquiry, there is an abundance of research which considers how health professionals use routine enquiry and respond to disclosure (Evans and Feder, 2014). Despite literature mostly confirming that women find routine enquiry acceptable, a meta synthesis by Sinclair (2016) suggests that screening is often not undertaken and healthcare professionals are often unwilling, or feel hampered by personal and organisational barriers (Lawoko *et al*, 2011; Beynon *et al*, 2012; McFeely, 2016). A meta-synthesis by LoGuidice (2015) suggested women's healthcare professionals often wait until a relationship is established before they screen for domestic abuse.

The majority of studies highlight failings from healthcare professionals with themes suggesting that professionals often demonstrate a lack of knowledge about domestic abuse and of the impact on women and children, and also are unprepared in how to respond to disclosures (Rose *et al*, 2010, Beynon *et al*, 2012, Taylor *et al*, 2013, Visentin, Vierra and Trevison, 2015; Ahmad *et al*, 2016; McFeely, 2016).

A Swedish quantitative survey by Sundborg *et al* (2012) with primary care nurses highlighted similar findings. There was a response rate of 69.3%, authors used logistic regression analysis to test relationships between variables, which highlighted that nurses felt generally unprepared, resulting in only half of respondents routinely asking about domestic abuse. Subsequently, respondents demonstrated poor knowledge and were unsure how to ask women about abuse. A lack of mandate, organisational policy and support also contributed to the unpreparedness of nurses. This study was considered more credible due to randomisation of survey distribution, and the survey questions were based on findings from a systematic review, which was piloted and consequently amended. Findings should be interpreted with caution due to this being a Swedish study, which is governed by different political and organisational structures and priorities to those of the UK (Parahoo, 2014).

Other barriers to asking about domestic abuse were identified by Beynon *et al* (2012) in a mixed methods study. A survey design, including closed and open ended questions, was used with randomly selected nurses and physicians in Ontario, Canada. The authors employed a combination of inductive content analysis and statistical analysis which found lack of time, professionals' perceptions of women experiencing abuse, lack of training, language and cultural practices, inadequate resources, lack of space/privacy, personal discomfort, and poor management support were barriers to asking about domestic abuse. Those health professionals who were more likely to ask about domestic abuse reported to have received relevant training and to have access to professional resources, tools, or policies, to have had their own experience of domestic abuse, and to have worked in a culture of routinely asking about abuse.

A cross-sectional survey by Lawoko *et al* (2011) of healthcare workers in Sweden found similar results to those of Beynon *et al* (2012). Again, only 50% of workers reported to ask patients about domestic abuse, approximately once every three months. Statistical analysis found that female health professionals were more likely to ask than males, and the findings suggested that a lack of organisational guidelines existed, and that training was required. Those professionals that did ask routinely about abuse reported low fears of offending women, professional preparedness, and had knowledge of support networks available for victims. This was a Swedish study therefore, again, results should be applied to the UK context with caution. Additionally, due to the cross-sectional design the study can only suggest associations, rather than making causal references (Lawoko *et al*, 2011).

Although many healthcare professionals have the necessary skills and experience to enquire sensitively and effectively about domestic abuse, much of the literature investigates the barriers, and what gets in the way of this being done well (Keeling and Fisher, 2015). Findings from a UK narrative study by Keeling and Fisher (2015) and a qualitative study using descriptive methods by Lundell *et al* (2017) in Mexico, indicate that healthcare professionals are not only insensitive to disclosures, but provoke feelings of guilt, and often unintentionally reflect the perpetrator of abuse, by questioning and invalidating concerns of the women. Keeling and Fisher (2015), in

their qualitative study interviewed female survivors of abuse, and using thematic analysis identified that health professionals in some circumstances do offer support and advocacy to women who disclose abuse, and often an equitable relationship between women and the health professional was evident where there was no evidence of coercion or minimisation of injuries. The researchers took various steps to enhance rigour of the study, including the use of thematic maps, and member checking, but did acknowledge that participants were all white British, therefore limiting the diversity and generalisability of results (Keeling and Fisher, 2015).

It is suggested that women and health professionals often work with a 'dual silence', whereby professionals and women have differing views of the manifestation of abuse, and despite agreeing that women should be asked, many report resistance to do so (Bradbury-Jones *et al*, 2014). Women may hide abuse, perhaps due to a lack of recognition, or because this is easier than disclosure, or health professionals often do not recognise it, leading to a hidden issue going unaddressed. Bradbury-Jones *et al* (2014) do recognise however that decisions and actions are influenced by multiple factors, including unrecognised biases, assumptions, and prejudices.

Hultmann *et al* (2014) identified similar findings in their mixed methods study of nursing, psychology, and social work professionals working in a child psychiatric clinic. Using interviews and questionnaires, the authors identified that various barriers existed, for example professionals were reluctant to ask about domestic abuse unless there were indications to do so and were also concerned about the impact on their relationship with their patients. They were concerned about causing harm to patients, and were reluctant to make changes to their practice to undertake routine enquiry when other priorities often took precedence. These findings conflict with most other research in this area that confirms women find routine enquiry acceptable (Lawoko *et al*, 2011). This study is somewhat flawed, as the recruitment strategy was reliant on participants being recruited by managers working in the same clinical setting as the participants. Thus, the potential for coercion and pressure existed, although this is acknowledged by the researchers. Additionally, there is little reference to ethical considerations by the researchers.

4.6.6 Theme 6 – Relationships

This next theme will consider relationship-based care in the context of health visiting. The helping relationship has been widely debated in literature including psychotherapy spheres where it has been proposed that the positive helping relationship is essential for positive outcomes to be realised (Kirkpatrick et al, 2007; Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016a). Internationally, there are a variety of early intervention home visiting models that have some similarities with the UK health visiting services; however, it must be acknowledged that different political and healthcare systems suggest cautiousness is needed – when generalising the findings into a UK context (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016a; Parahoo, 2014).

That said, studies from the UK, France, Canada, and Finland, that describe relationships between parents and professionals all identify similar characteristics required to be present for these interactions to be considered meaningful to parents and professionals alike (Kirkpatrick et al, 2007; Tanninen, 2014; Shaefer, 2016; Saias *et al*, 2016; Cross and Cheyne, 2018). Although there is much written about positive relationship development within various disciplines, early scoping exercises indicate a lack of health visiting research that considers a Health Visitor's relationship with parents/carers. Furthermore, the impact of these relationships on outcomes for parents and children however remains relatively unknown (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016).

Kirkpatrick et al (2007) explored partnership working between parents and Health Visitors, through 20 in-depth interviews with mothers, and identified findings that concurred with international literature – that where positive relationships existed, the opportunity to improve outcomes for families was greatly improved, and supported mothers to seek and receive support. Similarly, Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott (2016) used video-stimulated recall as a method to explore parent-Health Visitor relationships. Considered to be a highly accurate method, this approach was used to increase memory recall with six parent-Health Visitor dyads, whereby home visits were undertaken and recorded, and followed by in-depth interviews with participants. Health Visitors identified that friendliness by the parent/carer was more likely to generate trust in the relationship, and friendliness was influenced by previous perceptions or experiences with the service (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016).

Subsequently, trust was developed by Health Visitors responding to the needs of parents, by being non-judgemental, reliable, giving sound advice, and being able to talk openly and honestly.

Health Visitors also identified parental openness was important for the development of trust and facilitating the identification of health needs. Parents also reported that time was important to allow the relationship to develop, however, it is argued that recent under investment in health visiting services in England particularly, has disrupted the ability of HVs to develop strong relationships due their limited contact with families (IHV, 2019). Health Visitors also identified that parent's interest in the service, respect for the Health Visitor, parental communication skills, information-seeking, and reciprocity were necessary for the relationship to be effective (Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016).

Shaefer (2016) found that early childhood home visitors in Canada had abilities to form empathetic relationships, a self-awareness which allowed for reflective practice, a commitment to using strengths-based principles and a belief that their clients had capacity for change. This mixed methods study used interviews, situational vignettes, and a qualitative empathy scale to increase the depth of understanding (Wasti *et al*, 2022), and noted genuineness, non-judgmental attitudes, warmth, positive regard, and genuine caring attitudes for their clients were attributes identified by home visitors to be important for developing and maintaining therapeutic relationships. This study used a purposeful sample of home visitors, identified by their managers to be health professionals who excel in their practice. This notion was not challenged by the researcher, therefore, it is acknowledged that selection bias may be present. Additionally, this was a small sample, from one small geographical area in the Midwest of Canada, and therefore not representative of the wider population (Shaefer, 2016).

A mixed methods study by Saias *et al* (2016) which reviewed case notes of home visitors, also found similar results. Using randomly selected case notes, Likert scale measures and descriptive statistical data, comparative analysis using grounded theory, results found that relationships between parents and home visitors was generally perceived to be of good quality. This was quantified by parents' interest in the home visiting process and subsequent changes in parental attitudes. For some

case records, the relationship was considered 'distant' and poor relationship quality was influenced by parental mistrust of home visitors, poor engagement displayed as frequently cancelled visits, emotionally distant behaviours, and difficulties engaging parents in conversation (Saias *et al*, 2016).

Although Saias *et al* (2016) found that parents who were more involved with the home visiting intervention benefited most, the authors acknowledge there is little evidence available that considers relationship development, and the methods used to gain trust, from families with complex vulnerabilities. Although there are many elements of relationship development between parents and home visitors in this French study that could mirror health visiting practice, the role and function of home visitors is not entirely clear. Therefore, it is unlikely findings can be applied into a UK health visiting context. However, this study does highlight the difficulties in relationship building with families who may be less willing to engage with home visiting interventions or with complex vulnerabilities.

Strengths-based approaches have been explored nationally and internationally, as a framework to support and engage families and individuals, particularly those with complex needs (Fenton *et al*, 2014). Tanninen *et al* (2014) and Cross and Cheyne (2017) both explored strengths-based approaches used with families in Finland and Scotland respectively. An empirical study by Tanninen *et al* (2014) which used semi-structured questionnaires, and was analysed using descriptive statistical methods, indicated that resource-enhancing co-operative relationships between family nurses and parents has many benefits. Parents reported that they benefited from the family nurses' social support, openness, and encouragement, advice, compassion, empathy and listening skills. Additionally, they reported that the family nurses had time for them, were reliable, and increased their confidence in their own resources and encouraged them to identify their own solutions.

As also recognised in Saias *et al*'s (2016) study, Tanninen *et al* (2014) highlights factors that facilitate effective relationship building with parents. Although family nurses differ from Health Visitors, both involve the home visiting of families with pre-school children, to promote health and development, following a prescribed pathway. While results cannot be wholly transferable into a UK context, there are some general

principles that are reflected by UK Health Visitors and the policy that underpins current practice (Scottish Government, 2015).

Cross and Cheyne (2018) highlight that in Scotland, Midwives were unfamiliar with strengths-based approaches, and training was identified as being necessary. Additionally, this approach was perceived as being more time consuming, and urban areas reported to be under more time pressure than rural Midwives. Cross and Cheyne (2018) used a combination of qualitative interviews and a realistic evaluation case study approach across three health boards and claim that health professionals' understanding of such approaches are under researched. A perception amongst managers existed which suggested they believed Midwives were implementing such strategies when working with women, despite there being little evidence of this in practice. This highlights that although the benefits of strengths-based approaches are well researched, the implementation into practice is more limited than what is expected (Fenton *et al*, 2015; Scottish Government, 2015).

4.7 Summary of findings and identified gaps in research

Section 4.2 outlined the review question:

'What impact does the strength of the Health Visitor-parent relationship have on a woman's willingness to disclose domestic abuse through routine enquiry?'

The review has separated the question into two strands, one with a focus on domestic abuse, screening and routine enquiry, and the second on Health Visitor-parent relationships. Although two elements to the question, the literature was searched in a methodical manner for each strand, in an attempt to fully answer the review question. The review identified that domestic abuse is a topic widely studied, however very few studies aim to understand how successfully Health Visitors respond to domestic abuse, and how the HV-Parent relationship affects this.

Although routine enquiry has been implemented into various healthcare settings in Scotland for several years, there remains debate internationally about its value when offered universally in healthcare settings (Feder *et al*, 2009), and doubt about how successfully this is employed in the UK. Systematic reviews exploring the benefits

and outcomes of routine enquiry suggest inconclusive findings arising from poor quality research, and evidence gaps in existing knowledge (Feder *et al*, 2009; O'Doherty *et al*, 2015). Although routine screening increases disclosure of domestic abuse, outcomes for women and their support from services remains unclear (Feder *et al*, 2009). Despite this, an exploration of grey literature, including that of UK and Scottish policy for example Getting it Right For Every Child (Scottish Government, 2020), and the Universal Health Visiting Pathway (Scottish Government, 2015), has identified that a variety of national guidance and policy exists which prioritises domestic abuse, and includes how it should be responded to by healthcare professionals.

Despite the presence of routine enquiry in UK policy, and the literature claiming that women find routine enquiry acceptable, health professionals are often unprepared or unwilling to ask, and several barriers have been identified throughout literature that prevents them from addressing the subject, and these exist at personal, social, organisational and structural levels (Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen 2013; Hasselle *et al*, 2019). Although routine enquiry is prescribed throughout the Universal Health Visiting Pathway (Scottish Government, 2015), there were no studies identified that explored how women receiving health visiting support felt about domestic abuse screening.

Women themselves face several barriers to disclosing, often associated with feelings of fear, shame, or embarrassment (Thaggard and Montayre, 2019). Additionally, cultural norms and values, gender roles, social stigma, economic dependence on men, can all contribute to a woman's decision whether or not to disclose (Damra *et al*, 2015). Literature has found that women usually will seek help firstly from informal supports, for example, friends and family (Hasselle *et al*, 2015). Studies have highlighted that formal support is often only sought when injuries are particularly severe and cannot be hidden (Suryavanshi, Naik and Waghmare, 2018), often due to a lack of confidence in services to address the issue appropriately and effectively (Hasselle *et al*, 2015). Similarly, research has indicated that when disclosing to professionals, home visits are often preferable over clinic settings, where issues of privacy and confidentiality cause concern (Damra *et al*, 2015). Although barriers have been widely debated, the research available does not explore barriers within a health visiting context, and gaps

in knowledge exist that could explain how disclosure might be impacted with a trusted professional with whom a relationship is present.

Facilitators have not been as well explored, however a general agreement exists that a positive respectful relationship between the women and health professionals is essential before disclosure can take place (Tanninen *et al*, 2014; Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott, 2016). Qualities such as empathy, genuineness, and non-judgmental approaches have been identified as conducive to building trust in relationships between Health Visitors and home visitors providing support to parents. Women experiencing domestic abuse have also confirmed that these attributes are necessary before disclosure can take place (Spangaro, Zwi, and Poulos, 2011; Lelaurain, Graziani and Lo Monaco, 2017; Shanti, 2017). With most research exploring relationships between service users and providers being international, there is very little that considers relationships between health visitors and parents; Bidmean, Cowley and Grocott's (2016) UK study is one of its kind, and provides scope for this area to be explored further.

Consistent contact with professionals has also been noted as crucial (Doi *et al*, 2021), which is an important consideration for Health Visitors, whereby staffing levels may be such that achieving consistency of HV may not be possible (IHV, 2019). Similarly, UK health visiting policy supports the use of strength-based approaches, however despite these approaches being advocated, little research exists that explores how this is used in practice (Cross and Cheyne, 2017). In particular, how these approaches are implemented in health visiting and midwifery practice, and with women who may be experiencing domestic abuse, is an area not well documented in research. Cross and Cheyne's (2017) Scottish study of Midwives suggested they had limited knowledge of such approaches, despite managerial expectation that this was being used in practice. Thus, there exists a question whether such findings would also be identified in similar disciplines.

The review of domestic abuse literature has highlighted that authors are interested in the views of both health professionals, and survivors of abuse. It is common for domestic abuse research to include the views and experiences of both health professionals and victims of abuse in one study, and less common for survivors to be

the sole focus. Throughout the review of recent studies where participants are abuse survivors, analysis using the CASP tools (2018a, 2018b), highlights that researchers mostly have a good understanding of the delicate nature of domestic abuse and have taken appropriate measures to uphold the right to beneficence, by promoting and ensuring the safety of participants, ensuring anonymity and subsequent support (ESRC, 2012). This sensitivity is evidenced through listening to women, undertaking interviews at locations suitable to them, taking appropriate steps to ensure women are safe from abusive partners during the research process and adhering to women's requests of not recording interviews.

It has been identified that the phenomenon of domestic abuse is widely researched, and the disclosure of abuse by women in various contexts is difficult, amid a plethora of barriers. Although few studies focus on disclosure to Health Visitors, there is confidence in suggesting that some barriers will exist across all contexts and for all individuals. The Health Visitor – Parent relationship has not been the subject of wide study, and a review of literature suggests this is more often the subject of international research and within a hospital or home visitor context. It is acknowledged that while some of the research findings will be applicable and transferable into a UK Health Visiting context, none of the available literature applies directly to models of Health Visiting care delivery in the UK.

Analysis using the PAGER framework has highlighted gaps in the current evidence base, and suggests further research is required that uses interpretivist research methods to explore the lived experiences of those who have experienced domestic abuse, and the impact of relationships with professionals on disclosure. The review has included papers involving other healthcare professionals, e.g. GPs, Midwives, Nurses, and whose findings suggest that the presence of trusting, supportive relationships are required before sensitive topics can be discussed. It is suggested that while some findings would be relevant for Health Visitors and their relationships with parents, the nature of this relationship and its longevity is especially unique, and differs from that of other health professionals, and therefore transferring findings of other studies into a HV context should be done with caution.

4.8 Chapter summary

Initial scoping exercises generated the question that drove the literature review:

‘What impact does the strength of the Health Visitor-parent relationship have on a woman’s willingness to disclose domestic abuse through routine enquiry?’

Two very clear strands of literature searching were undertaken to answer this question, focussing on relationships and domestic abuse. A systematic, explicit search strategy has been described and justified, appropriate for the review. The analysis of literature produced six themes, relating to routine enquiry and its acceptability to women, the plethora of barriers that prevent abuse disclosure alongside facilitators to disclosure. Additionally, the concepts of relationship-based practice in a HV context, and health professionals’ use of routine enquiry were critiqued. This chapter has led to the identification of gaps in current knowledge, and has given rise to a research aim and associated study objectives, which are presented in the following chapter.

5 Methodology

5.1 Introduction to chapter

This chapter will identify the formulated research aim and the study objectives and explore the key research paradigms and their principles to provide justification for the methods used in the study. In the context of research, a paradigm is a worldview in which research is positioned and each are compared according to their ontological and epistemological assumptions (Aveyard, Preston and Farquhar, 2022). Their primary differences arise from their conflicting epistemological philosophies about how knowledge is created and considered to be valid, and the rationale for the research (O'Donoghue, 2019). For the purposes of contrasting viewpoints, the two primary paradigms, positivism and interpretivism and their theoretical positions will be considered, before providing justification for taking an interpretative hermeneutic approach as a basis for this study.

5.2 Research aim and objectives arising from the literature review

The previous chapter was successful in synthesising existing research, and identifying existing knowledge and apparent gaps in literature that have been used to formulate a research aim for the thesis:

“Developing an insight into mother’s experiences of domestic abuse; exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse”

The following objectives have also been identified to meet the study aim:

1. To collect and chronologically record, mothers’ retrospective experiences of domestic abuse
2. To explore the factors that influence mothers’ decisions to disclose domestic abuse to health professionals

3. To develop an understanding of the influencing factors that impact on mothers' experiences of domestic abuse
4. To develop an understanding of the role health professionals take in supporting mothers who are experiencing domestic abuse
5. To identify supportive mechanisms to mothers experiencing domestic abuse

5.3 Overview of the main research paradigms

5.3.1 Positivism

Positivism is associated with realism, whereby it is assumed there is an external reality (world) that exists separate from our descriptions of it (Flick, 2019). Consequently, researchers taking a positivist perspective are focused on achieving technical control, measurement, and objectivity, rather than interpretation that is believed to form the basis for knowledge (Flick, 2019). Researchers use controlled observation, independent from the phenomena under scrutiny to formulate hypotheses or definite and universal laws, often including statistical or numerical data, which can be used to predict and control events (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020).

5.3.2 Interpretivism

In contrast to positivist approaches, researchers using an interpretivist approach are concerned with providing rich description of the phenomenon under study, to enable understanding and interpretation of it, rather than quantifying the phenomenon using prediction and control methods (Aveyard, Preston and Farquahar, 2022). Interpretivist researchers use social interactions as the basis for knowledge, and the skills as social beings to understand how others perceive their worlds to allow for knowledge to be generated through a process involving negotiation, which is specific to the situation under examination (O'Donoghue, 2019).

The fundamental principles of interpretivism in research, suggest that human actions are meaningful and need to be interpreted. Similarly, Alharahsheh and Pius, (2020) claim that researchers using interpretivist approaches believe that understanding is created from meanings in everyday settings, where by individuals and society are

believed to be inseparable units and the relationship between each is mutually interdependent.

Parahoo (2014) states that interpretivist research is an over-arching term for a variety of qualitative approaches that seek to explore and understand human experience, beliefs and behaviours through methods characterised by inductive, flexible methods of data collection and analysis. The purpose is to develop concepts and theories from the data that emerges from listening to participants, and continually interpreting and analysing this data (Aveyard, Preston and Farquhar, 2022).

Parahoo (2014) and O'Donoghue (2019) both suggest that researchers using positivist approaches seek to avoid bias by being detached from the participants, whereas, in interpretivist research, the researcher is the primary data gathering tool, working closely with participants, and considers the interaction that exists between them. Interpretivist methods support relationship development between the researcher and participants by promoting close contact during the research process. This relationship is important when gathering data, to allow researchers to explain how participants perceive their experiences and connection to the social world (Flick, 2019).

5.3.3 Summary of primary research paradigms

Positivist and interpretivist research paradigms offer differing worldviews and belief systems, about how researchers understand the nature of reality, and their different ontological and epistemological assumptions guide how knowledge is attained (Rehman and Alharthi, 2016). This study has used an interpretivist approach to the research methodology as these approaches support participants to share individual lived experiences and allows the researcher to write flexibly to understand multiple realities. This approach supports the non-judgmental understanding of individual experiences and allows participants to respond in ways that are flexible and un-prescribed; furthermore, it is more likely than a positivist alternative to generate data that can be interpreted and analysed to answer the research aims (Presser and Sandberg, 2015). The following section will review the various interpretative research designs.

5.4 Overview of interpretative research designs

Although a justification for an interpretative approach has been provided, five interpretivist designs are available to researchers, namely: narrative, grounded theory, case study, ethnography and phenomenology (Colorafia and Evans, 2016) which are summarised in Appendix 4. Each of the designs have been examined with the research focus and aim in mind, to identify a research design that is most suitable (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Although all designs have merits, not all are appropriate for this study. Selecting the most appropriate research design is influenced by several factors, including the research aims, question, esthetics, and researcher resources, time available, and researcher control that is required (Crabtree and Miller, 2023).

As this study is investigating and understanding retrospective lived experiences of participants, ethnographic and grounded theory approaches are less favourable, as the study is not driven by the desire to generate new theory or is concerned with participants with cultural similarities. It is also believed that to address the research aim, a case study design could provide a level of depth of data, which might be valuable. However this study is interested in learning the realities of participants from their perspective, rather than using a variety of strategies to obtain an in-depth understanding of individual cases. Case study research can be time consuming with often lengthy data collection processes, and therefore researcher capacity and resources are also considerations when discounting this research design (Korstjens and Moser, 2017).

This research study requires a design that is capable of producing rich in-depth data which can help researchers to understand the essence of lived experience, and particularly in a domestic abuse context (Colorafia and Evans, 2016). Phenomenology is an interpretative design approach which supports the belief that humans can be understood from within their subjective experiences which cannot be replaced by any external analysis (Gerrish and Lacey, 2010). Evidence using a phenomenological design suggests there are multiple realities to be studied, of which each is subjective; women's experiences of domestic abuse will each be different, and each will have differing interpretations and understandings of what these relationships mean to them (King *et al*, 2019). In addition, Gerrish and Lacey (2010) suggest that the context of

the lived experience can be deliberated retrospectively as the experience still has meaning for the individual, even when it exists in the past, and is therefore appropriate this study. This study is exploratory in design, as it is focusing on phenomena that has not been well studied in the past, and therefore requires exploration of new concepts and understanding of the issues that are relevant to it (Parahoo, 2014). This helps to confirm that a phenomenological research design is most appropriate for this study. The following sections will explore the differing phenomenological methodologies.

5.4.1 Interpretivist phenomenology

Phenomenology as a methodology has been used widely to understand the lived experiences of human phenomena (Sundler *et al*, 2019). The approach emerged as a discrete philosophical research design in the early 20th century, by Husserl (1859-1938), and is underpinned by the belief that only those experiencing a phenomenon can communicate this to the outside world (Gerrish and Lacey, 2010; Parahoo, 2014). Phenomenologist researchers are concerned with describing, interpreting, and reflecting on every-day human experiences that are termed 'life-world' by Husserl, or 'lived experiences' by others, rather than 'data', generating correlated, interrelated themes or stories, rather than individual pieces of information (Tatano Beck, 2021). Phenomenology can be descriptive or interpretative/hermeneutic, and these designs will now be discussed.

5.4.2 Descriptive Husserlian Phenomenology

Descriptive phenomenology is a philosophy that remains close to Husserl's beliefs and is supported as a scientific research method which believes only knowledge that arises from experiential evidence is accepted as valid (Tatano Beck, 2021). Edmund Husserl (1931) claimed that there is no requirement for meanings to be interpreted, an approach which conflicts with the interpretative/hermeneutic approach of Heidegger, Gadamer and Ricoer (Sundler *et al*, 2019).

Researchers using descriptive phenomenology suspend all prior knowledge of a phenomenon through 'bracketing' to be able to understand the lived experiences of those being studied (Lopez and Willis, 2004). Bracketing is the suspension of natural attitudes and beliefs which was a key element of Husserl's phenomenological

philosophy, to provide a visual image of applying parentheses around presuppositions and assumptions, as a means of achieving reduction. This experience was termed a transcendental experience and bracketing prevents researchers being diverted by their presuppositions (Tatano Beck, 2021). However, Husserl's founding principles have been challenged by Heidegger (1962), Merleau-Ponty (1956) and Colaizzi (1978), who argue that researchers cannot be fully certain that they have bracketed successfully, and therefore offer alternative phenomenological approaches.

5.4.3 Hermeneutic phenomenology

The concepts of epistemology and ontology are central to philosophy, with each offering a theory to support a view of how to make sense of the world (Dibley *et al*, 2020). Epistemology is the nature and theory of knowledge, or how a researcher comes to know a reality (Shisanya, 2019), and unlike Husserlian researchers, researchers following a Hermeneutic philosophy hold the epistemological premise that reality is unique to individuals, and knowledge is generated from their experiences (Dibley *et al*, 2020).

Heidegger was the first to question the validity of the basis of Western philosophy, and the accepted notions of logic and truth, and inspired the development of hermeneutic or interpretative phenomenological approaches (Mackay, 2005; Gill, 2020). Hermeneutic phenomenology differed from descriptive approaches in that it did not focus on epistemological questions; hermeneutic philosophy does not seek to understand how people came to know things in the world, but rather are interested primarily on the nature of Being, or ontology (Pham, 2022).

The ontological focus of hermeneutic phenomenology considers the relationship between human existence and the world, and their unique ability to be concerned about their own Being (Gill, 2020). Heidegger's ontology claims that our understanding of Being (the ways humans understand themselves) is informed by *temporality*, history, and experience, which are central components in understanding how we understand the world (Horrigan-Kelly *et al*, 2016). Heidegger (1962) created the term '*Dasein*' to describe the human experience of Being: to exist authentically, aware of one's own Being, and with the ability to enquire into one's own existence (Tatano Beck, 2021). With this ontological perspective of what it means '*to be*'

Hermeneutic philosophies support a belief that who we are as humans is shaped by past and present influences of the social world, emphasising the uniqueness and diversity that exists between individuals, and thereby being cautious in identifying commonalities (Dibley *et al*, 2020). Therefore, similarities may exist between research participants, however it is their unique experiences that are of primary attention (Gerrish and Lacey, 2010).

In contrast to descriptive phenomenological approaches, hermeneutic phenomenology researchers refute the requirement to bracket pre-existing knowledge, but instead make their preconceptions explicit so their strengths and limitations of the interpretations are clear to the readers (Heidegger, 1996). Benner (1994) concurs and suggests that where these biases are made explicit at the outset of a study, they are considered tentative, within a process where they can be challenged and transformed by the researcher through the participants' voices. Heidegger (1962) expands on this and suggests a hermeneutic circular process of understanding that occurs through *Being-in-the-world*, where fore-structures are made explicit through bracketing, and considered in terms of '*whole of understanding*' before being reconsidered in alternative ways (Mackey, 2005).

5.4.4 Summary of phenomenological designs

Both Husserlian and hermeneutic phenomenological research designs have been critically discussed, and it has been determined that a descriptive design is not appropriate for this study, due to the belief that a complete reduction of the researcher's presuppositions would not be possible (Colaizzi 1978) because of the researcher's background, knowledge, and experience of working with women who have experienced domestic abuse. Additionally, a Hermeneutic design is preferred for this study, as it values the researcher's personal knowledge of an issue, and considers this both useful and necessary, whereas a bracketing approach can be inconsistent and questionable (Lopez and Willis, 2004).

5.5 Ethical considerations

Ethics in research is concerned with the conduct and behaviour of the researcher, the treatment of participants during the research process and the adherence to norms and

standards that researchers are expected to follow (Parahoo, 2014).–With the research aim and objectives now defined, and the relevant theoretical frameworks also identified, it is important to understand the ethical considerations that were necessary when undertaking research of this kind. This section will explore the specific ethical considerations that were relevant for this study.

5.5.1 Research with vulnerable persons and domestic abuse research

Research with humans involves risk, and researchers have a duty to minimise this as much as possible, and provide protection to those who participate by considering the main ethical principles as identified in Appendix 6 (Gordon, 2020). Persons taking part in research who are vulnerable, or where autonomy is lacking, for example, children, the elderly, prisoners, victims of abuse, need additional protective measures, to mitigate against any risk of harm (Labbot *et al*, 2016; Gordon, 2020).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) (2016a) has created Ethical and Safety recommendations for researchers specifically investigating violence against women, that exist specifically to ensure safety is promoted and risks are mitigated. These principles have been respected in the design of this study, and are summarised below, separating recommendations into those pertaining to participants, and the research team respectively, with both prioritising safety above other considerations:

Recommendations	
Participants	Researcher/Research Team
Prioritising the safety of participants	Prioritising the safety of research team
Action to reduce potential distress caused by participating	Provision of training and support to the research team, ensuring that researchers are skilled in referring women for support
Protection of participant confidentiality	Studies should be methodologically sound
	Policy is accurately interpreted, and study is used for policy development and wider social change

Table 4 - WHO (2016a) Ethical recommendations for researchers

5.5.2 Embedding ethical principles into the study

Inclusion and exclusion criteria have been developed for this study, not only to meet the aim and objectives of the study but as a strategy to fulfil the primary ethical principles of autonomy, informed consent, veracity, beneficence, non-maleficence and justice, and ensuring any possible risk to participants is minimised (Gordon, 2020). The primary consideration for the researcher was the safety of participants; this includes safety from potential repercussions of participating in the study by perpetrators of abuse, and also protection from the psychological impact of re-living abusive experiences. Consequently, the following inclusion and exclusion criteria were developed to promote participant safety, uphold ethical principles and promote inclusion:

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Women who are mothers, and:	Women who:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •are over 18 years of age •have experienced domestic abuse in the past, while their children were pre-school (aged 0-5 years) and within the last 5 years •have no current contact with any known or suspected perpetrator of domestic abuse •feel able to discuss their domestic abuse experiences without any significant distress or adverse impacts on their general health or psychological wellbeing •are living in their own accommodation, or that provided by Women's Aid, in one of the seven identified areas in Scotland •might not speak English as their first language, or who have poor literacy skills •are employed in a gatekeeping role, employed by the NHS or Women's Aid, and meet the other required criteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •are not mothers •are under 18 years of age •report contact with past or current perpetrators of domestic abuse •are deemed by themselves likely to suffer adversely as a result of participating in the study •have formally opted out of midwifery or health visiting services •do not live in any of the seven areas within Scotland •are known to the researcher, or where a current professional relationship exists •are involved in ongoing criminal investigations or who are due to make court appearances at the time of the study taking place

Figure 5 – Inclusion and exclusion criteria

All women who met the inclusion criteria and expressed a desire to participate were given equal opportunity to do so, and all women recruited to the study were treated fairly throughout including women from different cultural and socio-economic

backgrounds, with different abuse experiences, and varying literacy and language skills were all treated fairly and equitably.

Potential participants in this study were all provided with a Participant Information Sheet (Appendix 8) which offered them this information to help them make an informed decision about whether to be involved in the study (Synder, 2016; Gordon, 2020). Support to possible participants who were not literate, or who did not have English as a first language, was also available to promote inclusion.

As this study invited participation from women who were no longer in abusive relationships, providing written information was deemed safe and acceptable to the women involved. In domestic abuse research, the safety of participants is considered equally, if not more important to the protection of researchers and institutions (McNutt *et al*, 2008). By inviting participation from only those with historical abuse experiences, and who are currently safe from harm, there was less opportunity for unpredictability and risk to either researcher or participant (Downes, Kelly and Westmarland, 2014). With these considerations in mind, it was important that the researcher in this study was able to recognise the complex and unique circumstances of the research participants and adapt procedures to be able to respond flexibly to changes in risk and safety (Downes, Kelly and Westmarland, 2014; Fraga, 2016).

As part of the recruitment process, potential participants were asked to confirm that they perceived themselves able to deal emotionally with the recollection of past abusive events or experiences. This provided reassurance to the researcher that potential participants were not likely to suffer any negative emotional repercussions because of participating and promotes inclusion to the study. Additionally, the researcher took further steps to try to ensure participants remained within their window of tolerance by identifying, at the outset of interviews, the support networks available to each participant. With this knowledge, the researcher was able to suggest participants seek support from these identified networks following their participation in the study, as it is possible that interviews will raise difficult and upsetting memories.

This study aimed to eliminate immediate risks to women by recruiting women who are not currently experiencing domestic abuse. Although they will have experienced

abuse in the past, they were perceived to be safe from harm. This perception of safety was evident from their reported lack of contact with any previously known, current or suspected perpetrator, and from the judgement of gatekeepers, such as Health Visitors, or Women's Aid support workers who knew the participants well. The researcher confirmed this with each participant during the recruitment and consent process (Appendix 11), and reserved the right to cease interviews or participation if information was disclosed that suggested participants may be at risk. Even where women were not in contact with a perpetrator of abuse, steps were still required to ensure the potential for psychological harm caused by recalling previous traumatic events is minimised (Legerski and Burnell, 2010).

The research design supported an approach that aimed to eliminate any power gradient between researcher and participant, by creating a space for participants to tell their stories, where they had control over the information they provided. In response to the large number of adults within the UK with poor literacy skills (The Literacy Trust, 2017), written information about the study was provided in a way that was easy to understand, using straightforward language, without complex or specific terminology or abbreviations (Appendix 8). With the support from gatekeepers in the study, potential participants were encouraged to express interest, and seek further information from the researcher, which provided an opportunity to ask questions and discuss what participation might mean for them as individuals. Only at the point of being interviewed was consent formally sought and women asked to sign consent forms to agree to participate (Appendix 11).

Where interviews occurred virtually, verbal consent was recorded by the researcher (Appendix 11), and consent was revisited and reviewed at various times during the interviews, including when participants were visibly upset, to confirm that they were able to continue with the interview. Participants were advised they could stop the interview at any time, for either a break, or to stop the interview completely. By regularly reviewing consent, the researcher was able to assess risks to individual participants, to offer reassurance and to satisfy them that any potential risks they might face by participating in research, had been acknowledged. It is these methods that are often key factors in decisions about taking part in research (Women's Aid, 2020).

The potential participants in this study were mothers with children in their care who were perceived to be safe from domestic abuse. However, despite this, it was possible that participants might disclose information that would suggest their children might to be at risk of significant harm or abuse (Fraga, 2016). Participant Information (Appendix 8) was provided to alert participants to the obligations of the researcher should child protection concerns arise during the research process (Fraga, 2016), however these situations did not arise. Similarly, although it was agreed that the researcher would discuss with the supervisory team, any practice issues or behaviour that suggested deviance from professional codes of practice, and determine whether any escalation was necessary, this did not arise during the study.

This research has employed an empathetic, open-minded approach to create an environment whereby participants feel as comfortable as possible to share their experiences. Efforts were made to create a warm, non-judgmental rapport with participants, to put them at ease, and reduce anxiety. The researcher was explicit in determining how participation might impact each individual and their circumstances, recognising that beneficence can be personal, and the effects of participation might differ between participants. Some participants report cathartic effects from telling their stories (Rossetto, 2014), and victims often report they want their voices to be heard (Bosworth, Hoyle, and Madden-Dempsey, 2011).

Doody and Noonan (2016) state that risk of physical harm is usually more apparent and therefore more readily diminished, however emotional or psychological impacts were more likely to affect participants in this study. These risks were likely to be less evident, and required consideration to ensure participants had access to support. The interviews in this study were described to participants as 'a space to tell their stories'; adherence to the proposed methodology was important, to ensure that participants were free to disclose what they were comfortable with. Therefore, the use of probing questions was used conservatively, to promote participant control over the interview, however, as expected this created a possibility that some experience was with-held.

For this study the researcher ensured that the participants were not inconvenienced by their involvement, by offering a range of venues, and limiting travel and any other incurred expenses (Grove, Burns and Grey, 2013). The researcher provided

participants with the choice to be interviewed in person, or by using virtual means, at locations close to them to avoid incurring time and travel costs. They were also aware that they could cease their involvement at any time, and could reconvene at their discretion (Grove, Burns and grey, 2013).

In domestic abuse research, the principle ethical concern is the potential to cause harm to participants, largely due to the risks of abuse from perpetrators as a consequence of involvement in research (WHO, 2016a). In this study, only women who were no longer in abusive relationships, were invited to participate, therefore the risk of abuse from perpetrators had been mitigated. Furthermore, steps were taken to minimise all potential harm to participants, by using a safeguarding checklist to assist in ensuring the safety of participants (Appendix 14).

There is a belief that asking individuals to recall past traumatic experiences might negatively impact on their emotional and psychological wellbeing, however, Mulla and Hlavka (2011), Fisher (2012) and Legerski and Burnell (2010) claim that direct exposure to traumatic phenomena, for example, being faced with a perpetrator, is required for research participants to become re-traumatised. Therefore, recalling events through interpretative interviews is not likely to cause significant psychological harm. In this study, the researcher mitigated against the risk of further trauma by discussing the possible impact of participation with women at the outset, and ensuring their emotional state was reviewed and responded to during interviews.

Although some participants reported negative emotions, arising from involvement in research, Johnson and Benight (2003) report that most do not report regret at their involvement in a study. The participants in this study reported that their involvement did not create any lasting distress, in fact many reported they were motivated by the desire to help others in a similar situation. The researcher undertook a continual assessment of risk during interviews to determine how the participant was responding. Responses to recalling abusive experiences differed between participants, with some acknowledging that they have dealt with the trauma of an abusive relationship, and others still finding re-living their experiences upsetting. Participants who did become upset during interviews were offered empathy, time and support. They were asked

throughout interviews about their ongoing consent to continue, and given opportunities to pause, or stop.

From the researcher's perspective, rapport was developed with all participants, however in some cases, it was evident that experiences involving sexual violence often emerged towards the end of the interview. This supports Taylor *et al's* (2013) view that a staged process of disclosure often occurs. It could be suggested that the development of a relationship with the researcher was required before participants felt able to share particularly traumatic experiences. Adherence to the proposed methodology was important, to ensure that participants were aware they only had to disclose what they were comfortable with.

Although it is possible that some women would be receiving support from Women's Aid, the researcher ensured all women participating in the study were offered information and contact details of the supportive agencies, including Women's Aid, who were available to them locally. This provided those with minimal informal support networks such as family or friends, access to agencies who could support them if required.

Despite the steps taken to minimise and manage potential distress, it was possible that during the research process women may have become so distressed that it would not have been ethical to continue, and as the WHO suggest, researchers should be sufficiently trained to recognise distress and respond appropriately, ending interviews if needed (WHO, 2016a). Measures were agreed that if such circumstances did exist, participants would be advised that interviews would be suspended, and support sought for them with their consent. Participants would then be provided with contact details of the researcher should they wish to continue interviews at a later date, and they would make the decision whether they wished to withdraw. If they chose to withdraw, all material pertaining to the participant would be destroyed and removed from the study.

The researcher in this study had experience of working with female survivors of domestic abuse, had received additional training from Women's Aid, and therefore was equipped with relevant skills to identify and respond appropriately where distress

was evident. All participants coped well with the interviews, with no reported adverse impacts on their emotional wellbeing. Additionally, it was necessary to be mindful that the brain has an inhibitory mechanism that protects itself by blocking memories of traumatic experiences, leaving victims unable to recall abuse until they consider it safe to do so (McNally, 2012). Therefore, it was imperative that during interviews, participants were encouraged to share only what they could recall and were comfortable to share, without deep and persistent probing. Although some people may have recalled their experiences due to these cognitive processes, others may have been able to remember but choose not to disclose (McNally, 2012).

Researchers are required to consider potential harm to themselves and the research team, however these are often overlooked (Doody and Noonan, 2016). Risks in this study were reduced due to the steps taken to ensure participants were not in contact with any past or current perpetrators. In addition, lone working was considered a potential risk to the researcher, for example, from aggression from participants and unfamiliar work premises or locations, and the risk of divulging excessive personal information. Consequently, the researcher complied with the employing organisation's lone working policies to promote safety when visiting participants in their own homes. Where virtual and remote means were used to engage with participants, for example using MS Teams or Zoom etc.; this risk was minimised. Where participants in the study did not have access to technology that was required to support virtual interviews, or where in-person interviews were preferred by the participants, lone working precautions, as described above were adhered to. A visiting schedule was made available and a check-in process was used to confirm the researcher's safety. As this study took place while Coronavirus was still a prevalent public health concern, the researcher was also required to adhere to the current Scottish Government and Public Health advice and recommendations.

In order to manage the emotional impact arising from listening to the stories of participants who have experienced significant trauma and abuse, the researcher participated in de-briefs, supervision and supportive conversations with the research team, which can build researcher resilience and capacity ((Aluwihare-Samaranayake, 2012; Gabriel, James and Cronin-Davis, 2017). Reflexivity was also used by the researcher, to support them to consider their own values, beliefs and previous

experience of the phenomenon, and determine how this might impact on the research process (Cope, 2017). A reflective journal was used to reduce any opportunity for bias, as it allowed a space to record and reflect on the researcher's thoughts and feelings in an effort to acknowledge any perceptions and subjectivity (Polit and Beck, 2013).

Pseudonyms have been used in this study to ensure the participants' rights to privacy, confidentiality and anonymity, by eliminating any identifiable information during transcription processes, which can be challenging in studies with smaller sample sizes (Ford and Reutter, 1990). Several other steps were taken to protect the privacy of participants, for example, the demographic details of the participants were kept securely on a password protected electronic spreadsheet that was accessed only by the researcher. This was held securely on an encrypted device and was the only place where identifiable information was located. Each participant's identity was anonymised by assignment of an identification code at the outset, which cross referenced to their interview material. This code was used throughout the study to ensure that interview data including direct quotes were not identifiable or traceable back to the participant by anyone other than the researcher (Allmark, 2009).

Additionally, all identifiable data, for example geographical location, names of children, were all retracted in transcribed texts. Data was stored electronically to reduce the use of paper records, and any paper records that exist, for instance, signed consent forms, or interview transcriptions, have been uploaded to an encrypted electronic device, and paper copies shredded. Participants were assured that their details would remain confidential, and health professionals that women may identify during interviews, would not be aware of their participation in the study and their future contact with health services would remain unaffected.

5.5.3 Ethical Permissions

As this study involved recruiting participants from NHS sites, it was necessary to seek a favourable opinion from the NHS Research Ethics Committee (NREC). The application can be found in Appendix 7, and other relevant appendices to the application in Appendices 10-17. This application was made in May 2022 in collaboration with study supervisors, and the University Lead Study Sponsor. The

process involved completion of an Integrated Research Application System (IRAS) application (Appendix 7) and attendance at the North of Scotland NREC Committee. The NREC panel acknowledged the importance of the study topic, and were satisfied with the legitimacy of the study, and the measures proposed to ensure participant safety and wellbeing during involvement in the study. Consequently, favourable opinion was granted in June 2022, with a request for only minor amendments (Appendix 20). Application to NRES removed the necessity to apply to the University ethics committee, as outlined in University Ethical Guidelines (Appendix 19). Local Research and Development protocols of the recruiting Health Boards were also adhered to prior to data collecting in these areas, which included the researcher completing Good Clinical Practice Guidance Training. The researcher also completed mandatory Equity and Diversity training and demonstrated compliance with the Equality Act (2010), and the Data Protection Act (2018), through implementation of general data protection regulations (GDPR) training.

5.5.4 Chapter summary

The literature review has generated a research aim and objectives, and this chapter has critically examined the two main research paradigms, interpretivism and positivism. These paradigms have been introduced, and discussed, with justification provided for the interpretative approach used for this study. Furthermore, five frequently applied designs of interpretative research have been summarised in Appendix 4 and further justification has been provided for the phenomenological design chosen for this study. Attention has been given to both descriptive and hermeneutic phenomenological principles, and a clear explanation has been given for selecting a hermeneutic phenomenological research design for this study. This chapter has also detailed the ethical considerations for the study, and the measures taken to uphold the primary ethical principles and to ensure compliance with the WHO recommendations as detailed in Table 4. This chapter has also described the successful application to the NHS Research Ethics Committee where favourable opinion was obtained. With congruence to these ethical principles, the following chapters will explain the theoretical frameworks and research design for the study using phenomenological principles.

6 Theoretical Frameworks

6.1 Introduction to chapter

Chapter 5 has provided the rationale for a research design using a hermeneutic phenomenological approach. This chapter will consider the use of theoretical frameworks applied in interpretivist research and introduce the theoretical frameworks guiding this study. Feminist theory has been identified as a leading framework, in part due to its long-standing association with domestic abuse research, but also due to its role in promoting equality and justice for women and highlighting oppression and inequality (George and Stith, 2014). As this study focuses on the lived experiences of women who are mothers, Matricentric Feminism (MF) offers a specific discipline of feminism by O'Reilly (2021) which considers mothers' individual needs and will be used as the primary underpinning theory to the gendered nature of domestic abuse, and the oppression and disadvantage faced by women. Intersectionality theory (Crenshaw, 1991) also offers a useful lens through which to understand the lived experience of mothers who have experienced domestic abuse (Lochart and Danis, 2010). Together they will provide the theoretical basis for the study and help to understand the experiences of the study participants.

6.2 Theoretical frameworks in interpretivist research

The theoretical basis for a research study is often defined by varying, interchangeable terminology, for example a conceptual framework, theoretical framework, theory, concept or model. Although definitions of each may vary, the approaches applied should offer a different lens through which to examine a phenomenon, and an obvious association between phenomenon and theory should be apparent (Connelly, 2014). Bradbury Jones, Taylor and Herber (2014) and Collins and Stockton (2018) recognise that theory is central to interpretivist research. Although researchers within the interpretative paradigm promote the use of theoretical frameworks and theories as a means of understanding reality or providing structure to support a study (Anfara and Mertz, 2015), the relationship between theory and methodology can be complex (Bradbury Jones, Taylor and Herber, 2014)

6.3 Feminism as a theoretical framework

The feminist perspective has been a common theoretical model associated with domestic abuse from the early 1970s (Ali and Naylor, 2013). The concept is underpinned by the principle that domestic abuse is a consequence of male oppression in a patriarchal system whereby women are the primary victims of domestic abuse, and men are the primary perpetrators (Becker, Kafonek and Manzer, 2020). It is for reasons such as these that feminism was identified as the underpinning theory to this study early in the research design process.

Gelling (2013) suggests that feminist theory arose from concerns that traditional research, grounded in positivism, were considered male dominated and oppressive to women, and did not adequately address issues that were of relevance and benefit to women, and it called for a system that promotes equal rights, justice and fairness (McPhail et al, 2007; Holloway and Wheeler, 2013). Feminist theory is a legitimate framework for this study, due to the underpinning principles that suggests violence within intimate relationships exists due to historical and continuing imbalances of power. This imbalance keeps women as subordinate, through means of abuse, intimidation, control and isolation, and where women's subordination of men is considered 'natural' and violence is an acceptable method of controlling women (Baird and Mitchell, 2014).

The feminist model challenges the ideas of male entitlement and privilege, and traditional assertions that domestic abuse is a family matter (Kurtz, 1989). Furthermore, feminist theory suggests that gender is the key determinant of social status, and problems faced by women occur at a social, political and cultural level, which require changes to over-arching policy (McPhail et al, 2007). A key motivation for using this approach is reflected in the goal of feminist theory, which is to improve the lives of women and their position in society. Therefore, as Gelling (2013) suggests, applying feminism as a theoretical framework in this study, supports the voices of women to be heard, and to empower them to give their views in their own words. This is the primary intention of this study and is not thought to be achievable using alternative research methodologies.

In this study, like other feminist research, it places women and other marginalised groups at the centre of analysis and focuses closely on their lived experiences. The study will challenge dominant sources of knowledge, while also creating opportunities for these groups to share their lived experiences and ensure knowledge and understanding is not entirely based on the interpretations of men and other dominant groups (Alldred and Gillies, 2012; Becker and Aiello, 2013). Burgess-Proctor (2015) explain that a key priority of feminist research is to reduce power differentials between researchers and participants, through strategies that are non-hierarchical, caring and compassionate, that strive for connectedness and empowerment, and this can be effectively achieved by the proposed methodology.

Emerging evidence exploring domestic abuse suggests that abuse occurs within all kinds of intimate relationships, including same-sex relationships, with women also taking a perpetrator role (Entilli and Cipolletta, 2016). Furthermore, Merry (2011) argues that although prevalence data confirms that women remain disproportionately affected by domestic abuse, it is important to acknowledge that domestic abuse is not a universal feature of male behaviour. Therefore, although feminist theory is a legitimate theoretical framework for domestic abuse research, Entilli and Cipolletta, (2016) suggests that caution should be taken to challenge ideas that abuse is always physical and a prerogative of all men.

Feminist research is notable due to its methodology rather than its methods, meaning that there is no one feminist method to conduct research, but instead requires a methodology that is sensitive to the issue of gender, and can navigate power imbalances that promote gender inequality (Letherby, 2014). The researcher considered the various different feminist approaches which can be found in Appendix 5, which all aim to give voice to female participants as collaborators in research, rather than passive subjects (Grossman et al, 1997; Letherby, 2014). The intention of using a feminist approach in this study, aimed to empower women and make them visible, however, it is recognised that the influence of feminist theory on the conduct of, or decision-making in research, is not well developed and would benefit from further study (Gelling, 2013).

By seeking to raise issues of oppression and power, a feminist approach has the capacity to influence how researchers interact with the data, by influencing the questions women are asked, and how they are framed during interviews (Jefford and Sundin, 2013). Holloway and Wheeler (2013) suggest that these methods conflict with traditional positivist approaches which they argue to be male dominated and oppressive of women. In this study, a feminist lens was deemed important to ensure that female participants were given a space to share their lived experiences of abuse through their own voices, and where their voices are not compromised by male perceptions or values (Gelling, 2013). Using a feminist theory in this way shaped the research design, by intentionally creating safe space for participants through interviews, to tell their own stories, and allow the researcher to ask questions or probe sensitively in a manner that legitimised and validated their experiences without any external or male dominance.

6.3.1 Feminist phenomenology

To identify the most appropriate feminist methodology for this study, and one which can successfully facilitate the understanding of the experiences of female victims of domestic abuse, feminist phenomenology was considered as a meaningful framework to undertake this research. This theoretical framework is capable of combining interpretative phenomenology with gender issues to strengthen the philosophical principles which support researchers to gain a deeper understanding of women's experiences of living with domestic abuse (Fisher, 2000).

Feminist phenomenology also supports women's experiences to be heard; Cohen Shabot and Landry (2018) state that women's experiences continue to be marginalised. Despite movements such as #MeToo, women's experiences of sexual assault and harassment are seen as extraordinary and not normal, and highlights that women have not spoken enough, and continue to not be heard (MeToo, 2023). This highlights one example of marginalisation that women face, although this is embedded within a range of other social, economic, political, cultural oppression that women experience in all aspects of their lives (Rich, 2021). This reinforces that women have specific needs that are different from men and need particular support to have their voices heard (Cohen Shabot and Landry, 2018). The research undertaken for this thesis concentrates on the needs and position of women who are mothers, who, it is

argued by O'Reilly (2019) have remained disempowered despite over 40 years of feminism.

Using a feminist approach that empowers participants is essential, Rich (2021), O'Reilly (2019), and Baldwin (2021) agree that motherhood has the power to divide, exclude and adversely affect women's position in society, and targets them for discrimination and inequality. Men's desire to control and own women arises from their acknowledgement of the inequality that occurs due to women's ability to bear children. The realisation that this will remain an inequality in which women are superior, creates the need to control and oppress, therefore it is perhaps unsurprising that motherhood has long since been a controversial topic (O'Reilly, 2019; Rich, 2021).

Neyer and Berndai (2011) however argue that for some, motherhood provides women with power and agency, and unites women through biology, age and culture. It can be therefore suggested that motherhood is divisive among feminists, and therein lays a complicated relationship. Therefore, it is proposed that mothers require a feminist model of their own which has a matrifocal perspective and takes seriously the role of mothering, with its associated implications for women (O'Reilly, 2019).

6.3.2 Matricentric Feminism (MF)

While a feminist approach was identified by the researcher early in the research design process, the Matricentric Feminist (MF) model was a new concept to the researcher, however, was chosen as a feminist theory to ensure the needs and position of the participants in the study were given adequate attention. Feminists have long since been advocating for women and challenging structural perceptions of 'good' and 'bad' mothering, and the negative representations of women as mothers (Zuffrey and Buchanan, 2019). Matricentric Feminism therefore offered a lens through which to understand the needs of mothers, and supported the researcher in the development of a research design that would ensure mothers' experiences were heard.

Adrienne Rich (1981) was a key scholar who initially theorised motherhood as a social institution and lived experience, with the desire to highlight the experiences and perspectives of women as mothers. Although feminists have been debating motherhood and mothering for many years, O'Reilly (2021) created the concepts of

empowered mothering, in Matricentric Feminism (MF), and this voice is apparent when critically examining the literature. It was O'Reilly's (2021) belief that motherhood has not been given adequate attention in feminist texts, and she consequently advocates for a discipline of feminism that reflects the belief that mothering is important, and the role of mother is distinct from that of woman. It is this distinction that is of interest in this study, and it therefore provides further justification of the use of MF as a legitimate underpinning theory to support understanding of participant lived experience.

Established evidence contends that modern patriarchy is harmful to mothers, where mothering is viewed as being innate, and the responsibility of biological mothers only (Aarntzen *et al*, 2019; O'Reilly, 2021). The reasoning is that, although these women are tasked with the sole mothering role, they have little power over the conditions in which they do so, and parent children within the principles and expectations of the dominant culture (Whiley, Sayer and Juanchich, 2020). Matricentric Feminism does not replace previous feminist thought, however, it provides an alternative lens through which to view the needs and position of all women who are mothers (O'Reilly, 2021).

6.3.3 Motherhood, mothering and maternalism

Matricentric Feminism (MF) is different from the concept of maternalism, which considers women who want to be mothers with natural qualities that allow them to take this role and perform it better than their male counterparts (O'Reilly, 2021). The principles of MF reinforce the value of inclusive mothering and provide a modern perspective of normative practices that suggest that maternity is the basis of female identity, mothering is the work and responsibility of one person, and natural to all women, all women know how to mother and mothering is driven by instinct rather than skill (Zefferey and Buchanan, 2019; O'Reilly, 2021).

Normative mothering assumes the nuclear family model, whereby the mother is the wife and nurturer and husband is the provider. This sets unrealistic expectations for mothers, and prioritises biological mothers as authentic mothers, whereby those mothers who might be young, transgender, non-binary or single, are defined as bad mothers (Wagner, Smith and Crocker, 2023). Similarly, normative mothering would suggest those women in non-biological mothering roles, for example adoptive or

surrogate mothers are considered inferior, although it is proposed that these attitudes no longer reflect modern motherhood or society (Schmidt *et al*, 2022).

Central to MF is the understanding that mothering as work is valuable to society, but not the sole responsibility of mothers, and it contests the patriarchal, oppressive views of motherhood by providing a practice that is empowering for mothers (Green, 2019). The need for a new mother-focused feminism is further justified by examining the impact of the second wave of feminism, which although afforded women more gender equality, argues that this equality only lasts until children are brought into the family dynamic, when gender roles and inequalities re-emerge across all social classes (Timmins, 2019). Women become mothers, primary care givers, even in the presence of professional roles, and this new modernism of neo-traditional families, continues to exist where women continue to adopt traditional roles, being responsible for most of the home labour, caregiving and child rearing alongside their own professional careers (Niemisto *et al*, 2021).

6.3.4 Intensive mothering

The emergence of intensive mothering is equally oppressive to women, as culturally it has been dictated that biological mothers are the only persons capable of fulfilling the role (Levey-Friedman, 2016). It requires mothers to put the needs of their children before their own, be selfless, and seek instruction from experts to adequately care for their children (Verniers, Bonnot and Assilamehou-Kunz, 2022). Intensive mothering requires children's' needs to be met immediately, 24 hours per day, with extensive time, money and energy (Damaske, 2013), and modern variations on intensive mothering now see mothers with the same expectations, but alongside professional careers (O'Reilly, 2019; O'Reilly, 2021, Budds, 2021).

6.4 Feminism and domestic abuse

The relationship between domestic abuse and feminism has been critically appraised within this narrative and demonstrates that feminism is a legitimate and reasonable framework under which to consider women's experiences of abuse. Radical feminism was an influential discipline of feminism in the 1960s and 1970s that helped acknowledge domestic abuse as a social problem, however there is concern about

how mothering is often addressed under this feminist perspective (Damant *et al*, 2008).

Radical feminists assert that women are oppressed due to patriarchy, and domestic abuse is one of many ways in which this occurs, which reflects power inequality within patriarchal societies (Berggren, Gottzen and Bornas, 2021). Radical feminists also suggest that while mothering has the potential to empower women in this role, mothering continues to exist within a patriarchal system that is oppressive of women (Zufferey and Buchanan, 2019). It is claimed by Damant *et al* (2008) that motherhood only adds to women's vulnerability as it is targeted in men's use of abuse against women. While this might appear as a reasonable theory to underpin this thesis, the foundations of radical feminism are based on ideas of essentialism and universalism which were later rejected by post-modern feminists (Niemisto *et al*, 2021). Of more relevance is the emerging concept of MF which offers a vehicle for understanding experiences in relation to women as mothers, and specifically their needs and positions in the world (O'Reilly, 2019).

6.5 Intersectionality

As well as MF as a theoretical framework to guide this study, it is also useful at the outset to consider intersectionality theory due to the intersecting forms of oppression facing women and mothers (Crenshaw, 1989; Sokoloff and Dupont, 2005). Intersectionality was created by Crenshaw in 1989, to describe the interaction between systems of oppression. Its origins explored the oppression of women marginalised by colour and ethnicity, however this was later reconsidered to include sex, gender, sexuality, class, ability and nationality (Crenshaw, 2017). Damant *et al* (2008) suggest that there are various intersecting forms of oppression which can be used to explain domestic abuse, and consequently it is difficult to explain domestic abuse with one theory, but instead accounts will differ in response to the intersecting forms of oppression in individual women's lives.

The integration of feminist phenomenology and intersectionality provides a theoretical framework that considers violence against women through more than only a gender-based lens (Goertz and Mazur; 2008; Lochart and Denis, 2010). As well as gender,

Lochart and Danis (2010) suggest that intersecting factors such as pregnancy, substance misuse, race, ethnicity, shape the realities of female victims of abuse, and these realities determine their help-seeking behaviours. Moreover, it is suggested that women who are marginalised are likely to be confronted by different structural barriers and complex social inequalities that influence their abuse disclosures and how their experiences are responded to (Cancoro de Matos and McFeely, 2019). Therefore, supporters of intersectionality argue that there are various social structures that intersect with gender and to overlook their intersecting nature is thought to overlook the individual experiences of different groups of marginalised women, and unknowingly default to consider only privileged white middle class, able bodied, heterosexual women (Garland-McKinney and Meinersmann, 2022).

Although the breadth of intersectionality is debated, supporters argue that the theory allows feminists to question and explore the lived experiences of women as mothers, and their intersecting relationship with societal inequalities (Zufferey and Buchanan, 2019). Thus, a theoretical framework that is supported by principles of MF and intersectionality is thought to be the most appropriate for this study, and likely to bring deeper understanding of the experiences of female survivors of domestic abuse.

6.6 Chapter summary

This chapter has introduced feminism as a key theory which is considered relevant to understand the experiences of domestic abuse survivors. The various feminist approaches have been considered, and the emerging MF theory has been identified as offering an alternative view of understanding domestic abuse from a context that is specific to mothers. This chapter has also analysed MF a lens through which to explore mothering, motherhood, maternalism and intensive mothering. Alongside MF, intersectionality has also been identified as a second theoretical framework appropriate for understanding the views and experiences of marginalised and oppressed women. These two theories will be used to underpin the research activity in this study to ensure issues of gender and power imbalances are considered, and to acknowledge how gender might influence the research process, and to give voice to women who might not otherwise have opportunity to be heard. Together, with the interpretative phenomenological principles of Heidegger, a research design has

emerged with a sound theoretical underpinning based on frameworks that are entirely relevant to the participants and subject matter (Connelly, 2014). This research design will be discussed in the next chapter.

7 Research design

7.1 Introduction to chapter

A research design is required that will support the researcher to fully respond to the research question and objectives. This chapter will illustrate the research design selected for this study, driven by Heideggerian philosophy outlined in Chapter 5, and the underpinning theory of Matricentric Feminism (MF). This chapter will consider the decision-making relating to the research process, to include, sampling, recruitment, data collection and analysis, and will also demonstrate the measures taken to ensure trustworthiness of data, and that the research aim and objectives have been met.

7.2 Using a Hermeneutic design

To fully achieve the aims of the study, a hermeneutic, interpretative research design following Heideggerian philosophical principles was required to support the fusion of ideas between participant and researcher, by adding an interpretative dimension as stories are constructed and participant voices become heard (Dibley *et al*, 2020). The aim within Heideggerian research is not to formulate generalisations but instead, to understand the nuances of individual experiences (Nigar, 2020). Therefore, an approach using semi-structured interviews was selected, to provide a credible and legitimate design that supported women to provide rich descriptions of their domestic abuse experiences, and for these to be understood and interpreted (Adolfsson, 2010).

7.3 Sampling

Gathering first-hand experiences from domestic abuse survivors is crucially important to understand the complex issues associated with the phenomenon, and meet the research question and objectives. This study employed a purposive sampling strategy to recruit participants with specific experiences, and who could provide rich, high-quality data (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009; Benoot, Hannes, and Bilsen 2016). Sample sizes in hermeneutic research can vary widely but are usually smaller than samples in positivist research. This is because, unlike positivist research hermeneutic researchers are not attempting to prove or disprove a theory, but instead aim to gain

an understanding of the meaning of an experience of those participating (Dibley *et al*, 2020).

Identifying appropriate sample sizes in phenomenological research is more ambiguous than those in studies arising from a positivist paradigm, with the main principle being that an adequate sample is one that sufficiently addresses the research aim, and where depth and breadth of information has been achieved (O'Reilly and Parker, 2013). However, Dibley *et al* (2020) also suggest that sample sizes may need flexibility to respond to the changing needs of the study. It was anticipated that this study would include between seven and ten participants, as agreed in collaboration with the supervisory team. This number was considered large enough to include a range of experiences, whilst also reflecting sample sizes in similar studies, and being achievable for the researcher to manage effectively, and allow for a micro-level analysis of participants' accounts (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009; Mason, 2010).

7.4 Recruitment

Hermeneutic researchers are not attempting to produce generalisable data or a definitive truth but are attempting to reveal the meaning of experience amongst a group of participants (Dibley *et al*, 2020). Therefore, the sampling strategy in this study is underpinned by subjective decision making rather than a scientific process (Kristensen and Ravn, 2015). Recruitment of participants in this study has been directed by the pre-defined selection criteria used to identify participants who are best able to help answer the research question based on their characteristics or experiences. With this goal in mind, participants were recruited incrementally from Health visiting Caseloads and Women's Aid organisations from seven areas across Scotland, beginning with those geographically closest to the researcher. Initially, meetings were held with Health Visitors and their managers, and with one Women's Aid organisation in one Health Board area. Details of the study were provided verbally and in written form to both disciplines (Appendices 9 & 10). Gatekeepers (Health Visitors and Women's Aid workers) were asked to identify potential participants from the pre-defined criteria illustrated in Section 5.5.2, and share information about the study. This information provided specific details about the study, including data

protection, and measures taken to protect confidentiality and anonymity, and directed women to the researcher for any further information.

Once women had received the participant information (Appendix 8) and agreed to participate in the study, arrangements were confirmed between the researcher and participant, of when the interview would take place and it was at this interview that consent was formally obtained (Appendix 11). Where women were seen in person, women were asked to initial and sign the consent form, and where interviews were conducted virtually, verbal consent was obtained and recorded.

Following contact with gatekeepers as discussed, three participants were recruited from Health visiting Caseloads and six from a Women's Aid organisation from the first Health Board area. Four Health Visitors identified five possible participants, however this reduced to three after two potential participants were unable to find time to schedule interviews. Each of the nine participants in the study met the agreed inclusion and exclusion criteria, in Chapter 5.

Online meetings then took place with Health Visitors and their Managers from a further two Health Board areas to promote the study and seek support with recruitment, however no further potential participants were identified from these areas. Similarly, initial and follow-up contact with Women's Aid organisations in the other identified regions of Scotland also proved fruitless in identifying further possible participants. Although the target sample number had been achieved from the first Health Board area, attempts to recruit further participants persisted to promote and enhance the quality and breadth of data that was being collected, however attempts were not successful,

7.5 Data Collection

The data collection strategy in this study required an approach that would support participants to tell their stories in their own ways, and that would avoid the possible restrictions of formal and prescribed questions or methods. Decision making relating to the data collection methods was influenced by the underpinning theory for the study, whereby Matricentric Feminism supports mothers to have power and control over their

study participation. Consequently, the study design ensures that participants have control over the pace and depth of what they share with researchers, and limits the direction of the researcher

7.5.1 Qualitative interviews

Qualitative interviewing is a data collection method typically associated with phenomenological research and was chosen as the preferred method in this study due to the primary aim of the study being to understand subjective experiences, rather than generalising data (Parahoo, 2014). Interviews invite individuals with specific experience to participate which generates rich data that will answer the research question or hypothesis (McGrath, Palmgren and Liljedahl, 2018). Data collection for this study has been influenced by a Heideggerian philosophy and has also been complemented using the Life History Calendar (LHC) tool (Appendix 12) and the creation of a visual timeline, both which will be discussed in the following section.

Interviews are a common and legitimate data collection method in interpretative research, as they allow researchers to explore a phenomenon through the individual experiences of the study participants and are unique in that the researcher, and the relationship with participants, is instrumental in the research process (McGrath, Palmgren and Liljedahl, 2018). Interviews are considered to be a superior data collection tool when the primary aim of research is to understand subjective experiences, rather than generalising data, as they invite individuals with specific experience to participate which generates rich data that will answer the research question or hypothesis (Parahoo, 2014). However, their success is dependent on researcher skill, and on the researcher being aware of special requirements that may be necessary, depending on the nature of the interview (King *et al*, 2018). Semi-structured interviews use probes, prompts and follow up questions to guide the interview, and consequently are the most common type of research interview technique.

7.5.2 Data collection using a Heideggerian perspective

Data collection in hermeneutic research is a complex process, requiring researchers to simultaneously listen, understand, assess, while also identifying contradictions and

recording non-verbal behaviours and observations as well as the spoken word (Dibley *et al*, 2020). Using a Heideggerian perspective, and considering *Dasein* which according to Heidegger is to understand the world, during data collection in this study, both participant and researcher were part of the world, whereby researchers aim to understand the participants' experience of *Being* (Heidegger, 1996). Interviews in hermeneutic research are often termed 'hermeneutic conversations' and are led by open ended questions that provide general direction led by the participant (Dibley *et al*, 2020).

Interviews were chosen as a data collection method in this study as they involve a process of give and take, allowing both researcher and participant to have roles in constructing the narrative (Heidegger, 1962). This iterative exchange of shared conversations reveals meaning through language which is then interpreted and co-created by researcher and participant (Dibley *et al*, 2020). These interviews supported participants to tell their stories, whereby meaning can be created, using techniques such as using incomplete sentences, looking for assent and returning the participant to the story where necessary (Vandermause and Fleming, 2011).

Semi-structured interviews often use probes, prompts and follow up questions to guide the interview. This study was supported by a semi-structured interview schedule (Appendix 13), with guiding, open-ended questions which was prepared in advance, and was used to prompt the conversation and deploy questioning that aimed to understand the centrality of the phenomenon under investigation. It is common for probes, prompts and follow up questions to be used, however in this study, the researcher was careful to allow the participant to have control and speak freely, using prompts only when needed. Individual interviews were chosen for use in this study over focus group interviews, as participants were likely to disclose sensitive or upsetting experiences, and maintaining participant confidentiality was paramount (Parahoo, 2014).

Data collection methods in the study were heavily influenced by the underpinning Matricentric Feminist theory, which existed to ensure participants were empowered and their voices could be heard in the absence of control and male dominance. Additionally, the lack of rigid questioning and employing an approach whereby

participants had control over their narratives, respected and validated their needs and experiences as mothers.

All interviews took place between August and November 2022; NHS Lone Working policies were adhered to during these interviews to promote researcher and participant safety. All interviews were audio-recorded and conducted in a naturalistic way, avoiding specialist or abstract language in favour of regular conversational language to support participants to share their experiences and make them feel more at ease (Leonard, 1994). Participants were made aware that the interviews would be recorded and were advised of the steps that would be taken to ensure their anonymity and confidentiality as detailed within Chapter 5.

Notes were taken during the interviews to record issues or ideas about the phenomenon under study that may be developing; this allowed ideas to be re-visited and considered in terms of the relationship that exists between new ideas and the researcher's own opinions and biases (Dibley *et al*, 2020). Emotions and other non-verbal emotional expressions, for example, crying, distress, silence, that arose alongside participant narratives were also recorded to allow their lived experiences to be interpreted (Heidegger, 1996; Kvale, 1996). This was difficult to balance with deep listening and maintaining full attention. Further notes were taken immediately following all interviews to capture salient points and aid timeline development, and undertake reflection and learning, and this aided analysis of the interview. Additionally, domestic abuse research is undoubtedly a sensitive and potentially distressing process that requires researchers to be fully mindful of the needs of their participants (Dragiewicz *et al*, 2023).

As suggested by Creswell and Poth (2018) efforts were made to build a trusting relationship with participants, to ensure they felt as comfortable as possible, helped by them being interviewed in their home environment, where they had privacy and could feel relaxed and safe. Therefore, using individual semi-structured interviews were thought to be more likely to provide reassurance to participants, and maintain safeguarding responsibilities rather than group interviews and would likely avoid ethical concerns about participant safety and anonymity which were discussed in Chapter 5 (Parahoo, 2014).

As discussed in Chapter 5, participants were made aware they could withdraw at any time, and only had to share what they were comfortable with, and this was reinforced continually during the interviews. The use of Matricentric Feminist theory also provided opportunity, through interviews, to build knowledge that is specific to the needs of mothers, that challenges traditional thinking that is often male dominated (Rich, 2021). Individual interviews were acceptable to each participant, as evidenced by their consent and feedback. Additionally, it was evident that a relationships were quickly established between the researcher and each participant. By using an approach that was friendly, open, transparent, and authentic, this helped to build rapport and trust; additionally, advising participants that this was an opportunity to tell their story of their experiences reinforced to them that they had control over the information they wanted to share. Using empathetic responses, and offering unconditional acceptance of their stories, helped to create a positive relationship which was central to the quality of the interview.

7.5.3 Life History Calendar

Within the interviews, the researcher used a life history calendar (LHC) as an illustrative tool which helped to identify key moments in a participant's life. Using Heidegger's principle of *Temporality*, the LHC approach was used within an interview situation to explore events from a woman's life that have disrupted the natural flow of life experiences, considering a woman's past and present in the context of domestic abuse (Heidegger, 1962). The study was designed to allow the researcher and participants to explore and record women's experiences across the life-course, including those events that are memorable and easily recalled such as the birth of children, marriage; and, less easy to recall details, in a sequence of events (Freedman *et al*, 1988; Yoshihama *et al*, 2002). Use of the LHC meets the first study objective, outlined in Section 7.5.3, and supports the accurate and reliable recall of retrospective life events (Carter-Harris, 2015) and helps researchers to understand how current behaviours and attitudes are influenced by past events (Yoshihama and Bybee, 2011; Waddell, 2018).

These events were then chronologically mapped onto a timeline, to cross check timings and identify if a relationship exists between them (Waddell, 2018). Using data

collection methods that combined life history tools, chronologies, and individual interviews, helped to build rapport between the researcher and participants, and supported participants to recall and discuss potentially sensitive and distressing events from their lives. Berends (2011) and Heath *et al* (2018) agree that using multiple methods that combine interview techniques with visual methods such as LHC enhances accuracy and completeness of information.

7.5.4 LHC modifications and interviews

Despite its origins in positivist life course research, Harris and Parisi (2007) suggest that using the LHC approach does little to explore individual decision-making during major life transitions. In response to these methodological limitations, the LHC method in this study was modified to a simple matrix (Appendix 12) and has been adapted for interpretivist research by adding open ended, in-depth interview techniques and qualitative analyses (Harris and Parisi, 2007). Additionally, using an approach which is led by the participant, with no prescribed sequence of questions is thought to obtain more in-depth narratives (Nelson, 2010). Consequently, the researcher laid out to participants the scope of the topic, the time periods and details of interest, in an attempt to improve engagement and ownership of narratives by the participant (Nelson, 2010).

7.5.5 LHC and domestic abuse

Life History Calendar techniques were first applied to domestic abuse research by Yoshihama *et al* in 2002; domestic abuse has been recognised as being a complex issue, presenting researchers with various methodological challenges (Yoshihama and Bybee, 2011). Domestic abuse often re-occurs in women's lives, and may be perpetrated by one single partner, intermittently, or by multiple partners (Gadd *et al*, 2019). Therefore, LHCs support researchers and participants to collect retrospective data where experiences occur across various partners over a lengthy period of time and supports the development of visual timelines which also captures a life story (Yoshihama and Bybee, 2011).

7.5.6 Pilot study

Pilot studies are commonly undertaken in both positivist and interpretative research with a broad aim of increasing the quality of the research and enhancing both reliability and validity, and ensuring initial aims and objectives of the study are likely to be met (Malmquist *et al*, 2019) It does this by assessing practicalities such as recruitment, data collection processes, testing research instruments and the use of resources, including time (Lees, Walters and Godbold, 2023).

A pilot study was undertaken in this study, as an intentional activity to prepare and assess the research techniques (Kim, 2010), in particular, to improve the confidence of the researcher, and familiarity with the data collection tools. It was expected that this will increase the research quality, by testing and confirming if modifications to procedures are required (Malmqvist *et al*, 2019). Repeated use of the LHC, interview schedule and prompts, and timeline development were undertaken within a mock interview situation, until the researcher was confident that these tools were adequate and could be used consistently during interviews with participants.

7.6 Data completeness

Data saturation is not a concept used in hermeneutic research; instead, the notion of completeness is used. Dibley *et al* (2020) claim that in hermeneutic research it is impossible to reach data saturation, as participants might not have experienced everything significant to the phenomenon under investigation, and they may decide not to disclose everything about their experience. That said, researchers may highlight that recurring themes have been identified which are considered sufficient to address the research aim at this time, but also acknowledge that it cannot be guaranteed that they have captured everything (Monaro, Gullick and West, 2022). In this study, completeness was achieved from the nine participants due to the commonalities that existing between them, however this was also influenced by study timescales and researcher resources. Multiple attempts were made to engage and recruit additional participants without success, and decisions were made alongside the supervisory team to complete data collection following successful recruitment of nine participants to the study.

7.7 Data analysis

Once data completeness has been achieved, and agreed with the supervisory team, the researcher was required to employ methods of analysing data using approaches that were cognisant with the principles of Heideggerian phenomenology, and also methods suitable for qualitative data. With this in mind, thematic analysis was used alongside Heidegger's circle method as means of forming interpretations of data and creating new understanding (Reiners, 2012).

In hermeneutic research, data analysis occurs alongside data collection, whereby the researcher moves backwards and forwards between their existing knowledge and experience and the new, emerging data (Dibley *et al*, 2020). Analysis also differs from Husserlian approaches, as Heidegger (1962) claims that as researchers are not bracketing their biases, they are not required to return to participants to confirm findings of research (Heotis, 2020). This is because Heidegger emphasised that the depth of the researcher's closeness and involvement would confirm credibility and argued that each participant has their own horizon of understanding which expands with each new experience (Reiners, 2012). Similarly, the researcher also has their own horizon of understanding, shaped by their own experiences and perspectives, and consideration of these pre-understandings is required to create a fusion of horizons between the interpreter and participants (Gadamer, 2013). Discussion with the supervision team ensured that the researcher's involvement with the participants, and their existing understanding of the phenomena supported data analysis and enhanced credibility of findings.

7.7.1 Heidegger's circle method and thematic analysis

Data analysis and interpretation are threaded through hermeneutic research, and it is common for data to potentially consist of several different types of experiences represented in audio-recordings, written texts and observational descriptions, none of which are analysed and understood in formal, direct ways (Dibley *et al*, 2020). In this study LHCs were used to produce a visual chronological timeline, alongside semi-structured interview transcriptions which together provided the primary basis for data analysis (Yoshihama and Bybee, 2011).

Heidegger's philosophy (1996) states that human beings use words and language to represent their world, and therefore in this study, all interviews with participants were recorded and transcribed verbatim by the researcher, which allowed the researcher to be immersed in the data and search for hidden meaning before interpretations can be made. Analysis of chronological time lines also assisted the organisation of key elements of the data in the process of 'restorying' and this sequencing makes this genre unique (Morrow, Rodriguez and King, 2015).

Heidegger's (1962) circle method of analysis has been used in this study to meticulously and continually review and question parts of, and whole parts of, texts arising from transcribed interviews with participants. This required the researcher to move back and forth between knowledge that has arisen from pre-understanding to new evidence which re-moulds thinking until the meaning at the centre is exposed (Dibley *et al*, 2020). This circle method arises from Heidegger's belief that understanding only occurs with the presence of presuppositions, and presuppositions are always understood and interpreted (Grodin, 2017), and that understanding is continually revised and co-produced by researcher and participants (Boell and Cecez-Kecmanovic, 2014). The circle comprises of the whole and its parts; the whole can only be understood by examining and understanding its parts, and similarly, parts of meaning can only be understood by their relationship with its whole (Dibley *et al*, 2020).

In this study, transcribed texts were read as a whole, to develop an understanding of the phenomenon, which supported the researcher to understand participant experiences and question individual meaning (the parts); subsequently, engaging with an individual experience relayed through interviews, helped the researcher to question and challenge their understanding of 'the whole'. By challenging our understanding of these experiences, the researcher entered into an interpretative circle, and by engaging in reflection and interpretation, acquired an improved understanding of the individual as a whole (Boell and Cecez-Kecmanovic, 2014).

Identifying and addressing presuppositions or prejudices are important, and central to Heidegger's theory and in this instance, the researcher was required to acknowledge these pre-existing fore-structures and assumptions to promote understanding

(Heidegger, 2011). This included acknowledging and considering the researcher's experience of using routine enquiry in a health visiting role, and beliefs about the value of a positive relationship between mothers and health professionals to aid a domestic abuse disclosure.

7.7.2 Thematic analysis

While considering Heidegger's circle method, the tenets of thematic analysis are also relevant to analyse data in this study. Thematic analysis (TA) is a method, rather than a methodology, that provides a common structure for identifying and interpreting patterns in qualitative data across a range of theoretical frameworks and research paradigms (Braun and Clarke, 2021). Therefore, as well as being in alignment with Heidegger's philosophical tenets, the data arising from the interviews was subject to thematic analysis using Braun and Clarke's 6 stage framework (2006):

1. Familiarisation with the data

As advocated by Heidegger, interview transcription was undertaken by the researcher themselves, thereby bringing early thoughts to the analysis process. Interviews were transcribed verbatim to ensure that transcripts were an accurate reflection of the original discourse, and to begin the search for patterns across and in the data. Immersion in the data was undertaken by repeatedly reading the interview transcripts, note taking and recording non-verbal cues and ideas as they emerged for coding, and ensuring familiarity with all aspects of the data (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Braun and Clarke, 2021).

2. Generation of initial codes

Transcription and organisation of the data provided a level of familiarity for the researcher. Coding was then undertaken to create a list of ideas and features of the data. Coding is data driven in this study and has been undertaken using a combination of manual techniques and NVivo 12 software. Using NVivo 12, cases were created for each participant, and text from the transcripts of each participant was coded and selected against the following nodes:

Figure 6 – NVivo 12 nodes

Case classification was also created to record the age and geographical location of each participant and to attribute and group data against nodes and participant. Extracts of data under each code/node were copied from transcripts into a word document and underwent further line by line scrutiny whereby words and phrases were highlighted, and ideas were recorded. These were grouped into broad categories and compared against the initial codes. From this, there were similarities and overlaps between these codes, which were recorded. Text searches using NVivo 12 were also undertaken to identify common descriptions of abuse by participants.

3. Searching for themes

Once a comprehensive list of codes had been identified, phase 2 of analysis then considered themes and sub-themes, and a mind-map was developed to illustrate all component parts, and can be found in Appendix 21. This demonstrates all the key codes and possible themes, and indicates which themes are associated and interact. It also highlights the broadness of the data set.

4. Reviewing themes

From the number of codes and possible themes highlighted in the mind map described above, a process of reviewing the data was undertaken to identify themes which are supported by sufficient data, and that appropriately capture the coded data. This involved grouping data together by collapsing and separating data into themes that replicate the meanings developing from the whole data set. Themes 1-6 emerged from the analysis and were apparent to the researcher,

however themes 7-9 emerged in an iterative manner, through a deeper analysis of parts of the texts. Theme one was created by collating data that was originally considered two separate themes. This amalgamation is thought to accurately capture data and ensures data is not too diverse. This phase was completed when final refinement was undertaken to ensure all coded data was captured. The themes identified from this process were reviewed and discussed with the supervisory team and are listed below:

1. Disclosing abuse
2. Emotional abuse
3. Physical abuse
4. Financial abuse
5. Substance misuse
6. Mental health
7. Motherhood and mothering
8. Survivor and perpetrator vulnerabilities
9. Coronavirus pandemic

5. Defining and naming themes

This stage of thematic analysis began with the themes identified in the previous stage but involves a process of questioning the purpose and content of each theme, considering what is of interest and why. This stage requires deliberation of how the individual themes relate to the research aim, and to other themes, and whether any sub-themes are required. The themes and subthemes are outlined in Table 3:

	Theme	Sub-theme
I.	Disclosing abuse	Presence of routine enquiry in practice Barriers to disclosure Conditions for disclosing abuse
II.	Participant relationships with health professionals	Characteristics of positive relationships with professionals Impact of relationships on domestic abuse disclosure
III.	Types of abuse	Physical and sexual abuse Emotional abuse Controlling and threatening behaviours Attendance at health appointments Reproduction, pregnancy and birth related abuse Financial abuse Financial abuse as a means of control Financial abuse and substance misuse Employment and age factors Escalation of abuse Familial abuse
IV.	Mental Health (MH)	The impact of domestic abuse on MH Post-natal depression Weaponising mental ill health Trauma and Adverse Childhood Experiences Survivor and perpetrator ACEs Impact of trauma on memory retrieval
V.	Coronavirus Pandemic	Pressures during the pandemic Lack of professional support Escalation of abuse Isolation from family/friends

Table 3 – Summary of themes

6. Producing a report

The final stage in the thematic analysis process is the analytical reporting of the data which confirms the validity of the analysis undertaken in previous stages (Braun and Clark, 2021). Inclusion of data extracts and a rational and sound explanation of the data across the themes identified, provide evidence that adequately addresses the research aim:

“Developing an insight into mother’s experiences of domestic abuse; exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse”

Chapter 8 will provide a detailed overview of the findings from the study, corresponding to the themes listed above.

7.7.3 Rigour and trustworthiness

Researchers preferring scientific methodologies are often keen to highlight the bias that may be present in interpretative phenomenological studies (Creswell and Poth, 2018), therefore interpretative researchers are often required to further demonstrate the quality, or rigour of their research, referred to as trustworthiness or credibility of a study and possible transferability of the findings (Dibley *et al*, 2020).

Interpretative research is concerned with understanding human experience, and hermeneutic phenomenological research goes further with a specific purpose of understanding the experiences of participants, at a moment in time, rather than suggesting this experience means the same for all who participated (Smythe *et al*, 2008). This experience cannot be measured as in positivist research; therefore, trustworthiness is the best indicator of good quality, as described by Lincoln and Guba in their seminal work (1985) as credibility, dependability, transferability, confirmability, and later authenticity, and which is widely cited. Lincoln and Guba's (1985) model is shown below:

Figure 7 – Lincoln and Guba's (1985) overview of trustworthiness in qualitative research

As a means of demonstrating the trustworthiness of the study, and the criteria discussed above, a variety of steps were taken to reduce bias and enhance rigour throughout the research process. As well as undertaking a pilot study as discussed in Section 7.5.2, research methods, including data collection and analysis have been made transparent and discussed with the supervision team, to demonstrate the credibility, dependability and confirmability of data. Direct quotes from participants

have also been incorporated to reduce the possibility of bias and to confirm data. Open ended questions during interviews have been used, driven by a curiosity of what is at the centre of the phenomenon; this allowed the meaning to be given freely by the participant, and satisfies any critics that might suggest meaning was subjectively extracted by the researcher (Tatano Beck, 2021). An audit trail of decision-making has also been kept to record decisions, to confirm the meaning and accuracy of the data. The supervision team also reviewed interview transcripts, NVivo 12 codes and data analysis process to confirm robustness and trustworthiness of the process used in the study.

7.7.4 Reflexivity

The process of reflexivity is also a method of enhancing trustworthiness and robustness of the data collection process. The earlier review of literature in Chapter 4 highlighted that reflexivity within domestic abuse research was not always consistently performed by researchers as a method of managing the emotional demands that can arise (Brackenridge, 2016). Additionally, Brackenridge (2016) also suggests that reflexivity is often concerned with how a researcher's perspective can influence data, rather than how the experience has impacted on their personal and emotional wellbeing.

Reflexivity in this research was addressed through a personal diary that was maintained during the data collection process, and reflective supervision. These measures allowed me as the researcher to consider my own personal beliefs about domestic abuse, and how these might impact on data collection and analysis. Undertaking interviews and hearing the participant's experiences was a times emotional and harrowing, therefore reflexivity as described, provided a useful tool for processing and managing these emotional impacts (Hill, 2004; Kidd and Finlayson, 2006).

7.7.5 Retrospective data collection

As discussed in Section 7.5.3, collection of retrospective data is susceptible to recall bias, which hinders the accuracy and completeness of data; however, use of the LHC approach is thought to increase the quality of retrospective data collection, and

trustworthiness of data, as it reflects autobiographical memory and offers retrieval cues for more accurate recollection of events over the life-course (Nelson, 2010).

7.8 Chapter summary

This chapter has outlined the research design used for this study, and provided justification for decisions relating to sampling, recruitment, data collection and analysis, which are necessary to understand and interpret individual domestic abuse experiences of 'being in the world', that reflect Heideggerian principles. The chapter has discussed the purposive sampling and recruitment strategies used in the study to increase the opportunity for addressing the research aim. Semi-structured interviews have been discussed alongside the use of the LHC as a tool to increase the credibility of retrospective methods used in the study, and also influenced by Matricentric Feminist theory underpinning the study. Data analysis has also been critically examined, using a combination of Heidegger's circle method, thematic analysis, and using NVivo 12 software to generate themes, as found in Section 7.7.2 and identify data completeness. The chapter has also acknowledged the measures taken within the study to enhance trustworthiness and robustness of the methods and study design. The following chapter will summarise the findings that have arisen from the data analysis stage of the study process.

8 Findings

8.1 Introduction to chapter

This chapter will provide an overview of the study findings, as they emerged from individual experiences of *Being*, as described by Heidegger (1996), and include the relationship between the researcher and participants and participant demographic data. Initial and emerging ideas arising from the data following data collection, and prior to analysis will be highlighted, and have been separated into the following themes: Disclosing abuse, participant relationships with health professionals, physical and sexual abuse, emotional abuse, financial abuse, employment and age factors, escalation of abuse, familial abuse, mental health, trauma and ACEs and the Coronavirus pandemic. Although not all themes will directly help the researcher to answer the research question, this data does help researcher understanding regarding the lives of the participants and their abuse experiences. Participants have been given pseudonyms, so they are not identifiable from their data extracts.

8.2 The participants

Despite the vulnerability associated with participants who have experienced domestic abuse, and the rigorous ethical assurances that are required for research such as this, it is important to acknowledge that throughout the data collection process, all participants clearly articulated that they wanted to tell their stories. Aside from the traumatic events the participants had experienced in their lives, the participants reported being motivated by a desire to help other women experiencing domestic abuse. Above all they demonstrated candor and strength that is only to be commended, and all were keen to be provided with feedback to the findings from the study, when complete.

The emotional impact of participation was continually observed and monitored by the researcher to gauge how participants were coping throughout the interview and implement support measures, as failure to consider women's needs during interviews can lead to data being severely compromised and thus result in limitations to the

overall study (Yoshihama and Bybee, 2011). Although some participants did become upset and occasionally tearful when recounting their experiences, I was able to provide honest and genuine support that enabled all interviews to be completed and participants all reported a positive impact of participating.

8.2.1 The researcher – participant relationship

This relationship proved to be integral to data collection, to enhance the quality of data and depth of understanding of the participants' experiences (Halcomb and Peters, 2016). The development of rapport within the interview setting was crucial to data gathering and hearing the lived experiences of participants, without judgement. I consistently used a friendly, non-judgmental and empathetic approach during all interviews, and was completely transparent regarding data storage and dissemination of findings. Demonstrating compassion, empathy, and active listening was successful in achieving rapport with participants, and the hermeneutic conversations that occurred appeared to flow naturally, and consequently increased the quality of the data arising from the interviews. I was confident I achieved positive relationships with all participants, guided by the ability of women to share their experiences with me. However, balancing the need to listen, understand and assess, alongside recording pauses, body language and emotions, was difficult to undertake simultaneously. That's said, I was able to recognise that my skill increased over the course of the data collection process.

8.2.2 Participant demographics

A total of nine participants were interviewed, and their demographic profiles are summarised below. The average age of participants was 31 years, and all residing at the time of interviews in one region of Scotland. The age profile of participants is displayed below:

Age range	20-30 years	31-40 years	40+
Number of participants within range	5	3	1

Table 5 – Age profile of study participants

The region is largely rural, and participants in the study lived in areas across the region each varying in rurality, deprivation and SIMD ranks. All participants were interviewed with only themselves and the researcher present; this is despite them being advised

they could be accompanied by someone else if required. Participants had previously confided in friends or family about their experiences, therefore the decision to be interviewed alone was perceived by the researcher to be due to the women feeling confident about sharing their experiences and the level of support they might consequently require. Table 6 illustrates their ethnicity, employment status and living arrangements. All participants were English speaking, although one participant's English was a second language.

Participant	Recruited by*	Type of interview	Residing	No. of children	Employment	Ethnicity
1	HV	In person	Home	2	Employed	White Scots
2	WA	In person	Home	9	Student/working	White British
3	HV	In person	Home	2	Unemployed	White British
4	WA	MS Teams	Home	2	Unemployed	White Irish
5	WA	In person	Home	1	Unemployed	White British
6	WA	In person	Home	2	Employed	White Scots
7	HV	MS Teams	Home	2	Unemployed	White Scots
8	WA	MS Teams	Home	1	Employed	White Scots
9	WA	In person	Refuge	1	Unemployed	Other European

Table 6 – Participant demographics

*WA – Women's Aid HV – Health Visitor

8.3 Overview of findings and emerging themes

Following the data collection stage of the study, and prior to analysis, the following similarities were identified from notes taken during and following the interviews and highlight the commonalities across the nine participants involved in the study:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Child abuse by perpetrator									
Emotional abuse									
Physical abuse									
Violent sexual assault									
Other sexual assault									
Escalation in pregnancy									
Escalation at end of relationship									
Financial abuse									
Mental health affected									
Multiple abusive relationships									
Perpetrator substance misuse									
Known perpetrator ACEs									
Impacted by Covid									
Age difference >10 yrs									

Table 7 – Participant similarities

Regardless of their individual circumstances and experiences, and varying presentations of domestic abuse, each of the nine participants had experienced emotional abuse from their partners, and all participants' mental health had been impacted as a result of the abuse they had experienced. Domestic abuse featured heavily throughout the lives of the participants, and seven of the nine participants had experienced more than one abusive relationship.

As described in Section 7.7.2, a number of emerging themes were identified across the participant interviews, and they will be discussed in the following sections, with consideration given to their meaning and relevance in answering the research aims and objectives.

8.4 Disclosing abuse

8.4.1 The presence of Routine Enquiry (RE) in practice

Routine enquiry involves asking direct questions about domestic abuse even in the absence of any signs or suspicion (Feder *et al*, 2009). The presence or absence of routine enquiry in practice is a crucially important theme which directly impacts on the willingness of women to disclose abuse. Only four participants could recall being asked about domestic abuse by either their Midwife or Health Visitor. Two could recall being asked vague, indirect questions about their relationships by GPs, Midwives and Health Visitors, however in all instances, participants denied any difficulties, and did not allude to domestic abuse in the absence of direct questioning from professionals. More commonly, six participants described being asked indirectly, '*is there anything you want to speak about*', or '*is there anything that is making you feel this way*', when attending a GP appointment for low mood/anxiety. None of the participants cited their GP as someone they would turn to for support for domestic abuse, and none recalled being asked directly about abuse when presenting for anxiety or low mood.

Often, abusive partners attended antenatal, and other health appointments with the participants, therefore limiting opportunities for health professionals to ask about domestic abuse. In such situations, examples of creative practice (whereby health professionals used differing strategies to see women alone when accompanied by partners) were uncommon, however one participant recalled a Midwife taking her

aside during an antenatal appointment when her partner was present, to ask if she was safe or was experiencing abuse. Another participant was able to recall being asked by a psychiatrist about her relationship following some of her partner's concerning behaviours:

“It came to the point where they actually asked him to wait outside, they thought this was a pattern... he started to pick up on it, a little bit, he'd say I am sensing there's something not right, and I said no its all fine” (Ruby)

None of the remaining participants described similar attempts to ask about domestic abuse when partners were present or could recall this topic being revisited at subsequent appointments. Even for those participants who were asked directly by Health Visitors, Midwives or GPs, about domestic abuse, they did not disclose the abuse they were experiencing. For those that did not recall being asked, they confirmed that although hypothetical, if they had been asked, they would not have disclosed abuse. Additionally, despite reluctance to disclose, participants stated that they expected to be asked about abuse by professionals, and agreed that by asking, it lets women know that they are someone who they can reach out to, when they are ready to disclose.

“My relationship with my Health Visitor was good, she was nice, but I wouldn't have said anything” (Tina)

“I don't remember them asking about domestic abuse, I went in a few times and had the monitor thing, and she said that could be stress, and she said is there anything, I always said no” (Zoe)

Although interpretations of routine enquiry varied between participants, interpretive analysis of the participants experiences suggest that many were not asked about abuse, and without this, women do not have choices about whether to identify a trusted person to disclose to.

8.4.2 Barriers to disclosing abuse to health professionals

As echoed across existing research, the participants recalled various explicit reasons why they did not disclose abuse to health professionals. These barriers will be

important to understand fully, and will help to determine how such barriers influence women's willingness to disclose abuse. These barriers included: Fear of their children being removed by social services, fear of making their situation worse, fear of not being believed and thinking they are to blame, and emotionally threatening behaviours from their partners.

"I was scared they would take the baby away, that was my initial fear, I thought they'll think it's my fault and they'll take the baby away" (Lynda)

"I felt like I done something wrong. He made me feel like I'd done something wrong" (Zoe)

"I think I was more scared of losing my kids. He always said if I told anyone that they'll take them away, and that was my biggest fear, that would've broken me. He'd say you'd lose the kids, I'd lose him and no one would want me" (Tina)

Participants also had a poor understanding of the support available from health professionals, for example for *Georgina* for whom English was a second language she had no awareness that Health Visitors could support her with domestic abuse, and held the misconception that Health Visitors were only concerned with the health and wellbeing of the child, and not the parent also. Additionally, a primary reason for not disclosing, which applied to eight of the participants, was the lack of awareness of emotional abuse, therefore, even if they had been asked, they were not likely to disclose, as they had not perceived this to be a type of abuse.

"No I didn't tell them because I didn't think there was anything wrong... I just thought its normal, I just thought this is what men are like with women (Lynda)

"I never actually thought I was in an abusive relationship; I just thought it was normal" (Ruby)

"I don't think lasses are aware, I think they think that's okay, if he was hitting you, yeah, but it's weird when you're going through it, I was like I know I need to get out, but in another, I didn't want to leave" (Mandy)

Emotional abuse was experienced by all participants, and for eight of the nine participants, they stated that at the time of the abuse, they did not recognise their partner's controlling and abusive behaviours as domestic abuse. This lack of awareness was a key factor in their decision not to disclose abuse and was due to a number of reasons: some participants had experienced physical abuse in their previous relationships, or witnessed it in their parent's relationship. Therefore, they held the belief that domestic abuse was always represented by physical violence and aggression. This led to their misunderstanding that emotionally abusive behaviours did not constitute domestic abuse, as described by Lynda:

"I think that's why I didn't tell anyone, because I didn't know, I just kept thinking, well he's not hitting me, so I never really knew that that was what it was" (Lynda)

Participants also reported that they had little knowledge of non-physical abuse, coercive control or unhealthy relationships. They viewed their emotionally abusive relationships as 'normal', and often had little knowledge of Women's Aid, or other supportive services at the time of abuse taking place.

Living in small communities also presented difficulties for some participants. *Lynda* described knowing her midwife through the church she attended, and therefore this influenced the information she disclosed to her. Similarly, this participant described her perception of the same midwife not pursuing some concerns about her partner's behaviour, because she knew her personally:

"The midwife took me aside and asked if I was OK, what's going on here, and I said 'oh nothing he's just messing', but he wasn't, but because she knew us, in our private life, I think it stopped her...but I knew her personally, so I didn't want to say" (Lynda)

8.4.3 Conditions for disclosing abuse

Participants were less able to articulate clearly the required conditions for disclosure of abuse. Instead, they were able to describe circumstances that acted as precursors to disclosure, and interpretive analysis highlighted that where participants did disclose to health professionals, this was often due to various factors, including an escalation

of abuse, or because of a serious violent attack or sexual assault, or increased perceived threat of it. Often disclosure was preceded by abuse being directed towards a child, or because of the involvement of others, and in other cases, disclosure was triggered by the participants themselves, as *Georgina* described:

“I said enough, I have had enough (Georgina)

Participants also described professionals ‘*being in the right place at the right time*’ in instances when abuse has escalated, or had become too overwhelming, and when asked ‘*are you ok?*’ this could be enough to trigger a disclosure of abuse. *Zoe* recalled disclosing abuse when a school-teacher, ‘a friendly face’ reached out, and she acknowledged that this could have been anyone who was kind enough to ask and pick up on visible signs of distress:

“a friendly face said are you OK, it just broke me, so if that happened at the same time as a professional asked me, it might have gone the same way as well” (Zoe)

Only one of the nine participants disclosed the abuse they were experiencing to health professionals, and this did not occur in response to routine enquiry. Although six participants sustained significant injury by their partners, this was not always sufficient to prompt disclosure and only four participants disclosed abuse following escalation of abuse, resulting in a violent attack or sexual assault which included the involvement of third parties, the Police or hospital staff. For one, abuse by her partner was escalating and she was fearful for her, and her child’s life:

“I remember he had a gun in my loft, he’d stolen it and he didn’t want the police to catch him, so it was in my loft, then when he hit him (child) I realised this can’t go on and I reported it” (Cathy)

Medical attention was rarely sought for physical injuries, for reasons similar to non-disclosure; participants were afraid of the injury being perceived as their fault, and repercussions regarding care of their children, or making their situation worse. In circumstances where participants attended for medical treatment, this often happened because of the involvement of others, including friends or family members who had

supported women to report the abuse, or who had witnessed an assault and subsequently reported it to the Police.

There were no examples of participants seeking medical help for injuries independently. In these situations, health professionals in Emergency Departments were aware of the domestic abuse and therefore disclosure was not required, however participants in these circumstances reported being open and honest about their experiences. For three participants, their friends, family and also bystanders intervened following abusive incidents, which led to incidents being reported to the Police and participants disclosing abuse and leaving the relationship.

Another key trigger for deciding to disclose abuse was the evidence of abuse directed towards their children, or the belief that their children were at increased risk of physical injury. This applied to three participants, and where this became evident, the participants prioritised the safety of their children and saw this as a reason why the abuse could not continue.

“I came home one day and (child) had an adult bite mark on his arm, and at first he denied it, there were deep bite marks, purple blood blisters, so I called the police...he admitted that he'd done it...” (Lynda)

“He started to shake her in front of me, I told you to stop I told you to stop. I thought that's enough. Something wrong is coming, even worse is coming...he lost the plot, that was it, so obviously I told him the truth...I never say anything, but I said enough, I have had enough, you are not going to hurt her anymore” (Georgina)

8.5 Participant relationships with health professionals

The research question was specifically interested in women's relationships with the Health Professionals they commonly encounter during pregnancy and when they are parenting young children – namely Health Visitors, Midwives and GPs. Although the researcher was primarily interested in their relationship with their Health Visitor, interviews with all participants inevitably included their relationships with Midwives and GPs, and participants expected the same from each, regardless of discipline.

Participants mostly described their contact and relationships with Midwives and Health Visitors, and most were overwhelmingly positive. Participants were able to identify the various characteristics that they valued in the health professionals that supported them, and could recount numerous supportive encounters. The following graphic (Figure 8) illustrates how participants described their positive relationships with their Health Visitors and Midwives:

Figure 8 – Descriptions of positive relationships with Health Visitors and Midwives

8.5.1 Characteristics of positive relationships with professionals

Understanding what women valued in their relationships with professionals was again important in being able to answer the research question. The participants in the study mostly reported a positive, supportive relationship with their Health Visitor or Midwife, as described by *Mandy*:

"I was really close with them and I felt like I could tell them anything" (Mandy)

However, this does not extend to domestic abuse disclosure. These relationships are described as being open, honest, supportive, with trust, and where relationships make participants feel at ease, however it was clear that this did not extend to encouraging the disclosures of domestic abuse within their intimate relationships.

8.5.2 Impact of relationships on domestic abuse disclosure

Despite the description of a non-judgmental, trusting relationship in all cases, the participants still maintained that this was not sufficient to disclose abuse to them, suggesting that the presence of this relationship was not the only pre-requisite required for a disclosure. Participants, however, were able to disclose other sensitive issues to GPs, Midwives and Health Visitors, for example mental health issues, depression, anxiety etc., but not domestic abuse:

*“she was very professional and made me feel at ease, she was direct and open, we could talk about things, I liked the fact she was honest and didn’t lie to me”
(Cathy)*

“I had two Midwives, I knew them both, I was really close to them and I felt I could tell them anything” (Mandy)

“we’d established a really good relationship, she was very pro breastfeeding and pro natural parenting, which is what I wanted to do, and she spent a lot of time with me...she was brilliant, and I ended up telling her in the end” (Lynda)

Interpretive analysis of data suggested that the willingness of participants to disclose abuse is not wholly determined by the quality of the relationship between them and a health professional. Even where the relationship is described as supportive and trusting by the participants, they state that there were other factors that prevented them from disclosing abuse, and often they have disclosed when they feel it is the right time for them to do so, and often in response to various contributing factors. Only one participant described a supportive relationship between her and her midwife which contributed to her being willing to tell her about the abuse she was experiencing; however, this occurred over a period of time where trust was built and common values and parenting beliefs were established, and at a time when the participant felt able to disclose, not following a routine abuse enquiry:

“I was very young and I didn’t really know what I was doing I was 19. She came with me to a housing meeting to help me find a flat. She was just brilliant, I think and I ended up telling her in the end” (Lynda)

8.6 Physical and sexual abuse

The study participants described through their interviews that they had been subject to a wide variety of types of domestic abuse. While it is acknowledged that this theme might not directly help the researcher to answer the research question and aims, it does provide a useful insight into the experiences of the participants. It also provides context to the decision making relating to abuse disclosures, and also explicitly illustrates the breadth and extremities of abuse that has been perpetrated against women.

Eight of the nine participants had experienced physical abuse in at least one of their intimate relationships; physical abuse occurred within various circumstances and contexts, and of these eight participants, two of them experienced financial abuse alongside physical abuse. Although all types of abuse were distressing to listen to, I found the physical abuse experienced by participants to be most difficult to understand, yet they articulated this clearly. They described hitting, punching, head-butting, pushing, and strangling. In a text search using Nvivo 12, 'strangled' and 'pushed' were used to describe physical abuse by two participants, and 'hitting' and 'punched' were also used by another two participants. All participants report varying descriptions of physical assaults by their partners, all of which were violent and sustained, some directed at participant's stomachs during pregnancy. Zoe and Cathy described their experiences of physical abuse in their relationships:

"He started punching me in the face, after attacking me, like I was crying, and my face was all swollen, you could clearly see a bite mark on one side my ear was bruised where he'd bit my ear" (Zoe)

"I remember he strangled me and up against the door and it was that hard, I nearly passed out, and he'd used that much force, that I had fingerprints on my neck, bruises where he'd grabbed me" (Cathy)

Physical abuse was also associated with sexual abuse; in addition to significant physical abuse, violent sexual assault and rape was experienced by three participants. In two instances this occurred in relationships with age gaps of at least ten years, with

the perpetrator being older. In this study sample, violent sexual assaults never happened in isolation from other types of abuse, but always alongside severe physical abuse. Even where injury was sustained, medical attention was rarely sought. *Mandy*, *Karen* and *Abbie* described experiencing different interpretations of sexual assault within their relationships. *Mandy* experienced a violent rape:

“It got really difficult after Christmas [gets tearful], he raped me, with the kids upstairs...my main concern was my girls upstairs, if they had heard me fighting him off” (Mandy)

In a different abusive relationship, *Mandy* also experienced sexual abuse, as did *Karen* and *Abbie*, however, did not describe these events as violent. *Georgina* described their experiences as ‘rough’ but consensual sex, although they reported feeling unable to say no to this. *Karen* described being sexually assaulted while asleep and did not initially recognise this as abuse. Both examples provided by *Karen* and *Abbie* indicated evidence of the controlling nature of their relationships. Similarly, *Mandy* reported rape within her relationship, and like *Karen*, she did not initially view this as abuse due to them being in a long-term relationship. These participants experienced sexual assault alongside emotional abuse, but not accompanied by physical abuse.

8.7 Emotional abuse

Emotional abuse is now recognised as damaging as physical abuse (Hill, 2020; Karakurt and Silver, 2013) and is apparent in all participant narratives, occurring in isolation, or alongside other forms of abuse. Participants described emotional abuse occurring in various differing forms, such as in coercive, controlling and threatening behaviours, reproductive abuse, alienation from friends and family, and is also closely associated with financial abuse. Participants rarely recognised their partner’s behaviours as emotionally abusive, and their experiences of each will now be discussed. Figure 9 and 10 illustrate the descriptions of the emotionally abusive behaviours demonstrated by partners of the participants in the study.

Figure 9 - Examples of participant descriptions of emotional abuse

In addition, the interview findings suggested that participants experienced a range of specific emotionally abusive behaviours including:

Figure 10: Examples of emotionally abusive behaviours experienced by participants.

8.7.1 Controlling and threatening behaviours

All participants in the study described experiencing emotional abuse from their partner's, whether this was accompanied by other forms of abuse or not. This included controlling, threatening and manipulative behaviours, belittling, gas-lighting, and is described by one participant as being a worse alternative to physical abuse. *Tina* recalled an incident when abuse from her partner escalated:

*“When it kicked off upstairs, and the Police came, I said to her I wish he’d kicked the **** shit out of me, and I wish he’d left bruises because no one believes what I’m saying” (Tina)*

“He’d talk to me like rubbish, he’d tell me to shut up, that I didn’t know what I was talking about and he wouldn’t let me do anything, like painting, I wasn’t allowed to do it cause I’d wreck it. I wasn’t allowed to cut the grass” (Zoe)

Manipulative, controlling, gas-lighting and threatening were examples of adjectives used by participants to describe their partner’s emotionally abusive behaviours. *Lynda* explained how emotional abuse intensified over time in her relationship:

“It started off fine, then he took more and more control and by the time I left him I had nothing” (Lynda)

All participants described how their partners controlled their lives, by denying access to their social media and emails, preventing them from working and being independent. All participants described partners who prevented them from having contact with their immediate family and friends and restricting their activities. *Tina* described being locked in the house by her partner when he went out:

“We used to go out at 9am as a family for a walk, then we came back he would go out at 10am, and he said well you don’t need to go out now, you’ve been out, then he started locking the door, which was really dangerous” (Tina)

“I got invited to a hen party but I couldn’t go because he couldn’t go” (Ruby)

Some participants describe that their lives were controlled by various means, including restricting money, being locked in the home, using coercive control to make their lives difficult, usually relating to where standards in the home, or within the relationship did not meet expectations, for example *Zoe* recalled her partner having unrealistic expectations about the home that she would spend all day cleaning to avoid an argument, and this prevented her from seeing her friends or family.

“All I did was take the kids to school, and then clean the house. If he went out to work, and came home and the house was a mess he’d have a go at me, ‘what you been doing all day, sitting on your fat arse doing nothing’...and then that would get into an argument, so every time if he was at work and I was at home, I’d make sure the house was spotless, otherwise I’d get shouted at”
(Zoe)

8.7.2 Attendance at health appointments

It was commonly reported that abusive partners would accompany participants to health appointments, for example to the GP and Midwife, and be present for health visiting contacts, and in one case, where they could not be present, a family member was present instead:

“His sister was off work and she was at my house a lot and was there for everything, appointments with Health Visitor and everything, every hospital appointment” (Tina)

Whether the family member was complicit in the abuse is unclear. Participants were of the view that this was to prevent them from disclosing abuse to professionals during these appointments. Two participants described not being allowed out without him, even to social events where partners would not normally be present.

8.7.3 Reproduction, pregnancy and birth related abuse

Four participants described emotional abuse that was related to reproduction, pregnancy and birth. Interpretative analysis of data suggests that this type of abuse described by participants, was perpetrated specifically because of their roles as women and mothers. This theme demonstrates how the data engages with the theoretical framework of Matricentric Feminism, which strives to empower women and free them from patriarchal and male dominant behaviours, which are described by the participants (Rich, 2021).

Participants recalled their partners attempting to control decisions relating to contraception, whether pregnancies should continue, labour and delivery, pain relief,

persons present at the birth, and health related decisions following the birth of the baby, for example vaccinations. *Lynda* described how her abusive husband coerced her into having multiple pregnancies, in her view to keep her at home and limit her activities due to child-rearing responsibilities, and to support his idea that a “woman’s place was at home, and they shouldn’t have careers”.

“I wanted children but I also wanted a life, and I couldn’t have that because I was always pregnant” (Lynda)

In contrast, the partner of *Mandy* was coercing her into terminating the pregnancy:

“Oh you’re going to get rid of the baby, I don’t want you to have a child, I don’t want you to do this” (Mandy)

8.7.4 Alienation from family and friends

All participants described abusive partners that stopped them from seeing their family and friends, and in some cases, created conflict in the wider family by turning the participants against some family members:

“he took me into the hall and reprimanded me ‘cause she was changing his nappy. It’s your job, why is she even here, she wants to take over” (Cathy)

In this case, the abusive partner appeared attentive and wanted to spend all their time together, however, was isolating *Tina* from her family:

“They do stuff, I thought he was being nice, looking after me, and I didn’t realise how much he was taking me away from my family” (Tina)

This also extended to restricting access to social media and personal email:

“when I moved in with him I had no friends allowed especially no family and no social media” (Mandy)

Georgina's partner prevented her contact with her family who were overseas, by controlling the vaccination status of their child. Where participants were allowed to see family or friends, their partners' behaviours continued to be emotionally abusive during these periods, resulting in family time being difficult and strained. Additionally, although participants rarely disclosed abuse to professionals, in all cases they acknowledged that they had someone in their support network who was aware of the abuse they were experiencing. Family and friends who were aware often attempted to intervene, or persuade the participants to leave, however this alone was not sufficient to end the relationship.

8.8 Financial abuse

Financial abuse is a recognised form of domestic abuse and was commonly experienced by many of the participants. The following discusses how financial abuse occurred as a means of control, and as a strategy to procure drugs within a relationship, and like other types of abuse, is perpetrated as a means of controlling and exerting power over women.

8.8.1 Financial abuse as a means of control

Financial abuse was a significant feature in the relationships of five of the nine participants, and occurred equally when partners were both in employment and when unemployed. The participants experiencing financial abuse did so mainly when they were not employed, and in all cases were looking after small children and home, with minimal income of their own other than in most cases, their child benefit payments.

Financial abuse did not present in the same way for each participant, although for each one, their partner's behaviours restricted their access to money. *Abbie* was left without money, and this meant she was unable to use public transport to maintain contact with her family who lived in a neighbouring town. She had no money of her own and her partner worked away during the week, leaving her with very little in the way of provisions.

Four participants described financial abuse by their partner as a means of controlling their activities; for two participants, they experienced severe curtailment of money to the extreme where they had no means of paying for shopping or basic essentials

needed for caring for babies or small children, for example milk and nappies. Lynda was financially abused to restrict social engagement through work:

“He used to spend money out of the account so I had no money, I had to go to work one day over the other side of the city and there was no petrol in the car, and he was like ‘oh well you can’t go to work today’, so I would be stuck...or he wouldn’t come home Friday night so I couldn’t go to work the next day, so I would have to call in sick, which would cause my employer to get upset with me” (Lynda)

Three participants describe having no access to money which resulted in them using credit cards for shopping and building up debt which remained after the relationship ended. Cathy described how their joint benefit claim would go into her partner’s account which she had no access to. Lynda also reported accruing debt, and resorting to use cloth instead of disposable nappies as she could not afford to buy the latter:

“I’m a bit of a hippy, I like gentle parenting...I cloth napped to save money, so I didn’t let on” (Lynda)

“He took more and more control and by the time I left I had nothing, I didn’t have my own money...I had no money to go shopping, I maxed out my credit card, I had to put shopping on my credit card because he was spending all the money in the account...he was walking around in brand names and me and the kids were in charity shop clothes...it was really extreme” (Lynda)

Georgina was coerced by her partner into giving him her savings, which included monetary gifts from her family. Her partner restricted her access to money by refusing to add her name to joint bank accounts and only adding her name when she became eligible for benefits:

“he made all the decisions and I had less than nothing” (Georgina)

These participant descriptions emphasise the impact of financial abuse on women and their children; like other forms of abuse, whether conscious or not by the perpetrator,

financial abuse provides a tangible barrier for women to leave abusive relationships. Lack of financial means curtails a woman's ability and opportunity to leave, and this is also likely to hinder any abuse disclosures.

8.8.2 Financial abuse and substance misuse

All except one participant in the study had abusive partners who misused drugs or alcohol. Of the five-participants experiencing financial abuse, four of them had partners who were misusing drugs or alcohol. All participants described how alcohol or drug use escalated situations and were perceived to be precursors to abuse, and similarly all participants reported drug and alcohol use was associated with stress and disharmony in the relationship. Two of the six participants experiencing financial abuse reported that their partners controlled the money in the relationship in order to fund drug use. Prioritising the purchase of drugs, often left participants without essential money for shopping, including milk and nappies for their babies, and for *Tina*, this involved stealing the participant's bank card to access their money:

"he was spending £160 a week on weed which was a struggle for us...he used to get what he needed then I had to manage with what I had, which made me get into debt...he was on so many drugs, I was so sick of fighting for a bit of the money I had left, I didn't eat, 'cause I needed to make sure I had enough for (the child)" (Tina)

Ruby also became aware that her partner was stealing from her:

"It was when my bank card went missing that I knew something was really wrong" (Ruby)

8.9 Employment and age factors

Drug use amongst participants' partners was mostly seen in those who were unemployed: *Ruby*, *Tina* and *Karen*'s partners all used cannabis and were not in work. *Georgina* and *Lynda*'s partners were in work and they did not disclose any drug use relating to them, however *Abbie*'s partner was also in work, and used cannabis. For working partners, participants reported that they restricted money as means of control,

rather than to fund a drug habit. Additionally, four of the five-participants described an age difference of ten years or more between her and her abusive partner who had subject her to financial abuse, highlighting some linkage between age, dominating behaviours and control of finances in the home.

8.10 Escalation of abuse

Escalation of abuse is often reported during the perinatal period, and when abusive relationships end (Van Parys *et al*, 2014; Mahenge *et al*, 2018; Boxall and Lawler, 2021). Study participants described instances where abuse had worsened, and had exacerbated feelings of fear, and when this had prompted disclosure of abuse and termination of the relationship. This theme emerged as a result of a deeper interpretive analysis, whereby issues of escalation emerged during interviews, and were rarely termed 'escalation' by participants.

8.10.1 Escalation during pregnancy

It was reported by all participants that domestic abuse either started or escalated during pregnancy, with some describing severe and enduring assaults. No participants described abuse ceasing during pregnancy. *Cathy* described various examples of how physical abuse escalated significantly during pregnancy:

“He was more controlling it was awful, that’s when I remember it getting worse, he pushed me with so much force, I fell on the floor onto my belly and I was terrified” (Cathy)

Cathy described the following assault during her pregnancy, which was an escalation of previous behaviours:

“he held me down on the bed...he strangled me when I was pregnant. He pushed me on the bed once and held me down and he didn’t look like a person, and he went to bite my face, he had his teeth on my nose, and it would have taken a second for me to be permanently disfigured. It made me realise it was getting worse it escalated so quickly” (Cathy)

Lynda also described being raped by her landlord which resulted in pregnancy, and subsequent severe physical abuse during her pregnancy:

“It was quite an abusive time in my life. We weren’t actually together but he raped me, and I found out I was pregnant... then I felt like I needed to stay with him so I started a relationship with him, and after that happened I was in a really bad place” (Lynda)

“He was so violent I nearly lost the baby, he repeatedly kicked me in the stomach, slapped me and broke my fingers, it was very, very, violent...he slammed my fingers in the car door and tried to drag me to the termination clinic” (Lynda)

The severity of abuse experienced by some during this period of their lives was significant. Escalation of physical abuse was noted more frequently than exacerbations of emotional abuse during pregnancy. Some participants recognised pregnancy as a time when abuse escalated in severity, however others, while they described severe physical assaults, did not recognise this as an escalation. It is presumed that this was partly due to the high level of chronic physical abuse they were experiencing outside of pregnancy. When asked if abuse had got worse when she was pregnant, Zoe replied:

“a little, there was one time he strangled me and pinned me to the bed and I was pregnant and I just tried to shake it off.....it wasn’t as bad as such, he was still very controlling and if he was in a bad mood I would know about it, he’s take it out on me” (Zoe)

For those who had experienced financial and emotional abuse prior to pregnancy, they reported that financial abuse exacerbated during pregnancy. This was often due to increasing demands on family finances due to an impending birth, and abusive partners continued to restrict finances which prevented adequate preparation for a baby’s arrival.

Additionally, once babies had arrived, the additional expense created further strain on finances, and in many instances abusive partners prioritised the financing of drug use, over providing for the family. For participants who did not experience physical abuse, they also confirmed that emotional abuse also escalated, and for one participant, abuse began during pregnancy which happened early in the relationship:

“It went down-hill quite dramatically when I got pregnant...it was a constant ‘oh you’re going to get rid of the baby, I don’t want you to have a child, I don’t want you to do this. I ended up having no friends no family, just me. A lot of it was emotional abuse” (Mandy)

8.10.2 Escalation of abuse when the relationship ends

Women are at continued risk of abuse from their partners even when the relationship ends (Women’s Aid, 2021). Six participants described abusive experiences in these circumstances, including using children to maintain contact and control, and to create arguments. However, none of the participants described the risk of potential abuse escalation an overt reason for non-disclosure. However, these experiences are worthy of further consideration in how they relate to women’s willingness to disclose abuse. *Lynda* describes how her ex-partner stalked her, and *Tina* discussed continuing to use her mental health against her in court proceedings to agree child custody arrangements. Threats to kill and threats to tell lies about the participants are also described by participants. *Zoe* described how her partner’s behaviours had escalated while they were separated resulting in him absconding with her and her children in the car and making threats to kill:

“I could stab you right now and no one would know’, I was petrified, hoping someone would come out” (Zoe)

Cathy saw an escalation in her partner’s behaviors after their relationship ended, resulting in him making false allegations to social services about her care of her child, and claiming the gun in her property belonged to her:

“I told him the police had already taken it [the gun], and he went to social services and told them he was worried about the welfare of my child and said

the police have been to the house and found a gun. He said if you're going to be like this with me, just you watch me" (Cathy)

Mandy described how escalation was associated with her ex-partner's alcohol use:

"When we broke up it really escalated, especially when he'd been drinking, he'd get really angry" (Mandy)

8.11 Familial abuse

Domestic abuse occurs within intimate relationships, but can also be perpetrated by members of the family (Women's Aid, 2019). *Ruby* and *Tina* sustained violence and abuse from members of their own, or their partner's family. *Ruby* received threats, and destruction of property at the end of the relationship from her partner's family, and *Tina* recalled sustaining physical and emotional abuse from her father throughout most of her life. This demonstrates the presence of violence against women even out with an intimate relationship. However, literature scoping by the researcher failed to identify research that focused on familial abuse as experienced by *Tina* or *Ruby* that occurred out with the context of honor based abuse.

8.12 Mental Health

Mental health was an overriding theme emerging overtly from participant narratives, who all described the adverse impacts of abuse on their mental health and wellbeing. Participants describe how abusive partners weaponised their poor mental health as a means of control in the relationship.

8.12.1 The impact of domestic abuse on mental health

Domestic abuse is inextricably linked to poor mental health, and for many participants, re-living these experiences, and reflecting on how these experiences have shaped their lives was emotional and upsetting. For five participants, their mental health remained affected, attributed in part to ongoing contact with their ex-partners due to child contact arrangements. While this was an apparent theme emerging from the data, it reflects what is already known about the impact of domestic abuse on survivors, however, the mental health of women is a key consideration when

determining whether to disclose abuse to others . *Cathy* recalled how the deterioration in her mental health was a gradual process and took time to be identified:

“I knew it wasn’t normal, but I didn’t know it was happening, it was so gradual. At the end I couldn’t have even spoken to you, I never saw myself get to that point, if I was walking down the street and I saw my friend or my mum or my sister, I would stand staring at the floor, almost involuntary I had to force myself to look up” (Cathy)

In all cases, women described a negative impact on their mental health because of the abuse they were experiencing, and four had mental health conditions, that existed prior to the abusive relationship. Isolation from social supports during abusive relationships also prevented family and friends from recognising deteriorating mental health and supporting women to seek help and support. It was also evident from the interviews that for some participants, their experiences continued to be distressing to re-live, however this was frequently reviewed, revisited and managed by the researcher to mitigate impact.

The four participants suffering from poor mental health, all demonstrated that this exacerbated during their time in an abusive relationship, and this is likely to have bearing on their willingness, or ability to disclose abuse. The remaining five participants also described disturbances to their mental health as a result of the abuse they experienced. Participants described experiencing anxiety, low mood and depression, and becoming withdrawn, and only six-participants described being able to speak to their GP for support and treatment. *Mandy* described having good support from her GP when her mood deteriorated:

“I was at the doctors all the time. The doctors were great” (Mandy)

There were no examples of GPs asking directly about domestic abuse, however participants relayed examples of indirect questioning from GPs, Health Visitors and Midwives about triggers or circumstances that might have contributed. In these circumstances, participants withheld information regarding the domestic abuse they were experiencing, however many participants accessing their GP also recounted their

partners being present at appointments which may have impacted on this. There were a few examples of GPs using alternative methods to see women on their own to ask about domestic abuse.

“He came with me to every appointment even my mental health appointments. It came to the point where they actually asked him to wait outside” (Ruby)

“We had a very close relationship [with the mental health team] but it wasn’t until after, when it finally came out, my support worker came out to see me, she was sensing something, but couldn’t ask because he was always there” (Ruby)

Only *Ruby* could recall a psychiatrist asking her partner to wait outside due to concerns about his presence at all appointments. Despite this effort by the health professional, the participant did not disclose abuse. However, many continue to live with anxiety and depression, and remain on medication, under the care of GPs and mental health teams due to the trauma they have experienced.

All participants claim their experiences have influenced the way they think about future relationships and feel better prepared to recognise abusive behaviours. Participants have advised they can recognise emotionally abusive behaviours in their friend’s relationships:

“one of my friends is going through some emotional abuse and from the outside looking in you can see it clearly and she keeps going back...her family keep telling her to leave” (Mandy)

8.12.2 Postnatal depression

Only *Lynda* reported to have experienced postnatal depression following the birth of all her children. It is difficult to determine how experiences of domestic abuse, or pre-existing mental health conditions might have contributed to this diagnosis, or whether postnatal depression might have occurred even in the absence of each of these factors. Similarly, all participants reported disturbances to their mental health during and following periods of abuse and following births of children. Although, however, routine screening for postnatal depression is part of the Universal Health Visiting

Pathway (Scottish Government, 2015), it is unclear if this was consistently undertaken during these times. Participants describe being able to identify mood deteriorations themselves, and sought support from their GP during these times, rather than the Midwives or Health Visitors that they report having good, supportive relationships with. Only one of the participants described seeking support from their GP for 'postnatal depression'; rather, in all other cases, participants attributed their poor mental health to the abuse they were experiencing.

8.12.3 Weaponising mental ill health

Participants' mental ill health, and their role as a mother was often used as a weapon against them by their partners, as a strategy for manipulation and control by threatening the removal of children. This is another theme supported by the underpinning theory that recognises the further marginalisation of women through their role as mothers. Participant descriptions highlight the lengths perpetrators will go to, to undermine and control, while using their mothering role and instincts as a weapon:

"He was telling me that... I can't be a single mum, because I have mental health problems and a history of suicide attempts, so he used to say you can't look after him, social services will take him away from you, you've got mental problems, you're not stable enough, so I stayed. I put up with what he did...he's always used my mental health against me, that's why I stayed, that's what I believed" (Tina)

"He'd drummed it into my head that if anything happens, he said they'll see us as unfit parents and you'll have the baby taken from you (Cathy)

All participants described their protectiveness of their children during period of abuse and described their efforts to keep their children safe in challenging situations. All demonstrated strength and resilience to maintain parenting in such complex and abusive situations, and *Cathy* gave an example whereby she prioritised her children's needs following an abusive incident:

“he slammed the door while I was holding him and luckily my hand was in the door, and I was in my pyjamas, and I just walked out of the house...it was the realisation that my baby was going to get hurt if I don’t go...” (Cathy)

8.13 Trauma and Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs)

Adverse childhood experiences were significant factors for several of the participants and their partners and were widespread across the sample group. Although ACEs were not the focus of the study, identifying ACEs across the participant sample was important to better understand the participants across their life course, and presents an overview of past experiences that have potential to influence adult decision making.

8.13.1 Survivor ACEs

Five participants had grown up within households where there was domestic abuse between their parents, and seven–of the nine participants had a minimum of two adverse childhood experiences (Filetti *et al*, 2008). Table 8 illustrates participant ACEs where known:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Physical abuse									
Sexual abuse									
Emotional/Psychological abuse									
Emotional neglect									
Physical neglect									
Parental mental illness									
Parental drug misuse									
Parental alcohol misuse									
Parental domestic abuse									
Parental separation/divorce									
Parental incarceration									

Table 8 – Participant Adverse Childhood Experiences

Adverse Childhood Experiences are explained as a variety of measures or events in a child’s life that, when exposed to, can lead to trauma and stress responses (Filetti *et al*, 1998). Of the women interviewed, five had lived with parental domestic abuse as a child, and four of the five reported alcohol use by their parent who perpetrated abuse, thus reaffirming the association between domestic abuse and substance misuse (Gadd *et al*, 2019). Similarly, four participants had experienced childhood emotional

or psychological abuse, and three of these four had experienced emotional neglect by a parent. Due to the study methods, it is possible that participants experienced more ACE's than reported and withheld information during the interviews relating to their early life prior to having adult relationships. This could have been intentional, or it is possible that this was unintentional, believing this was irrelevant, and therefore not discussed. Due to the methods, women were also encouraged to only share what they were comfortable with, therefore this limitation is acknowledged and justified.

8.13.2 Perpetrator ACEs

Adverse childhood experiences relating to the perpetrators of abuse was not wholly explored during the interviews, however three participants did comment on how their partners had experienced, in some cases, severe physical abuse as children. *Mandy's* partner had, witnessed domestic abuse between their own parents:

“his Dad used to batter his Mum, he was three when his Dad died and she says he’s just like his Dad” (Mandy)

Georgina's abusive partner also suffered abuse as a child:

“he was eight, and he moved from his mother to his grandmother, it was a severe case of abuse. Once I asked him did you ask your mum why she beat you and she said it was because her mother did it to her” (Georgina)

The three partners who experienced abuse as a child, perpetrated severe physical abuse against their partners. Similar to above, it is possible that other participants might not have a broad knowledge of their ex-partner's childhood experiences, or thought it irrelevant to share such details during the interviews; therefore, it is not possible to draw significant conclusions about perpetrator ACEs.

8.13.3 Impact of trauma on memory retrieval

For some participants, their memory was hindered during the interviews potentially due to the trauma they had experienced, either as children or adolescents. This is relevant for *Zoe* and *Tina*, who had experienced significant physical abuse from

partners; *Tina* also sustained abuse from family members and had multiple ACEs, and this affected her ability to recall events and the timing of these:

“I can’t remember so many things, but then I thought it was drugs, but also trauma” (Tina)

Zoe had trouble recalling details of specific incidents, due to the volume of abuse she experienced over a long period:

“I can’t remember everything he said, because there’s been so many times it’s happened that I don’t remember it all” (Zoe)

These participants required patience and more use of the prompts, to identify timings. Often, their abuse had been so prolific that they had difficulty identifying one incident from the next, and the sequences of events. Use of the life history calendar and timeline facilitated this and helped plot events and timings. Participants themselves identified that their memory retrieval was poor; *Tina* was confident this was due to trauma and possibly a long history of substance misuse which was also used as a strategy to cope with the adverse childhood experiences.

8.14 Coronavirus Pandemic

The period by which participants were parenting young children and experiencing abuse also spanned the coronavirus pandemic, and identified various challenges associated with this time, which influenced how help was sought when experiencing abuse. The unprecedented nature of the pandemic, suggests that while this brought very specific challenges for domestic abuse victims, it is unlikely that these same barriers will exist in future, outside of national emergency situations such as these. Therefore while findings under this theme may not inform the research aim, it does highlight the pressures women were under during this time, and how this impacted on their abuse experiences.

8.14.1 Pressures of the pandemic

Due to the varying ages of the participants' children, not all participants were in abusive relationships during the pandemic, however, the experiences of four participants were exacerbated during this time, largely due to the absence of professionals and services, and national lockdowns. Participants describe how lockdown periods were particularly challenging due to the additional pressures of home-schooling, caring for small children, the lack of professional support and contact with their support networks, and confinement with their abusive partners. This consequently impacted on the mental health of participants during these periods:

“Yes, it was during lockdown, it was worse, my mum was at high risk, so she couldn't come out, and his Dad has not long passed, and I had a close relationship with him, and then it went extremely downhill, it was awful, I was trying to home-school, deal with a baby and deal with all of that, it was hard, and no access to support networks” (Ruby)

8.14.2 Lack of professional support

The lack of professional support during this time also impacted on *Cathy* and her child, who were reliant on these services for supporting with child contact arrangements:

“Covid made things a whole load worse, there was nothing in place” (Cathy)

During this period, professionals who would normally visit the participants at home, for example Health Visitors and Social Workers, made contact using virtual means. Participants reported that this created a barrier for asking and responding to questions about domestic abuse. It is reasonable to suggest that this also created difficulties for professionals to seek alternative means to ask sensitive questions when restrictions were in place, and professionals were required to follow specific practice guidance.

8.14.3 Escalation of abuse

Of the four participants living with abusive partners during the pandemic, all reported an escalation of abuse, however abuse did not in all cases become more severe, although the absence of support networks, professional services, and national restrictions, added to the perception that abuse worsened during this time. Financial

abuse was heightened for some participants who had previously been working and became subject to furlough arrangements; the partner of *Karen* used the lockdown restrictions as an excuse to move in with her, rather than return to his own home, and became financially reliant on her, bringing no income and giving up his job. The fear of the virus around that time, and the perceived need to adhere to strict guidance, prevented this participant from confronting these difficulties and asserting her own needs and preferences:

“he was coming down and then lockdown happened, and he said I can’t go home, and I said what do you mean you can’t go home? He said I’m not allowed to leave, the whole country’s in lockdown, I can’t go home, and from that day on he lived with me, but I felt there wasn’t much I could say, but then I thought its lockdown, I’ll have a bit of company, so it might be good, but it was horrendous” (Karen)

8.14.4 Isolation

All participants reported that the pandemic left them feeling isolated from family, friends, as well as from professionals and during national lockdowns, their support from these people was severely restricted. As well as restrictions, often participants had family members who were shielding due to chronic illness, which further exacerbated their isolation even when some restrictions were lifted. Restrictions also meant there was no access to community services, baby groups etc., where families might normally access for support. Participants often described positive relationships with health professionals, however due to the ways services were delivered during the pandemic, their contact with these people who would traditionally be a support to them, was significantly reduced. Thus, highlighting the importance of regular health professional interaction in these situations.

8.15 Chapter summary & summary of findings

Several key commonalities have emerged and can be summarised. Routine enquiry about domestic abuse was found to be used inconsistently in practice by GPs, Midwives and Health Visitors, and there is little evidence of creative methods being employed to ask about abuse, where partners accompanied participants to health

appointments. There were multiple barriers to disclosure, and it appeared that women would only disclose abuse to professionals when they perceived the time was right for her to do so. Such situations included in response to increasing threat, or in the presence of a trusting relationship that had been established over time. Participants, however, reported that they expected professionals to ask about abuse, so they are aware that they could approach this person when they are ready to disclose.

Women in this study always confided in a friend or family member, even where women were controlled and prevented from having contact with wider social networks, all women shared their abuse with another. Relationships with health professionals were almost always reported to be positive, however, domestic abuse was rarely disclosed even in the presence of this trusting relationship; this differed from other sensitive issues, for example maternal mental health, whereby participants often sought support from their GP.

Sexual assault always appeared alongside physical abuse, however emotional abuse was present in all cases of domestic abuse. Financial abuse was also prevalent in approximately half the sample, and closely associated with perpetrator substance misuse. In five cases, abuse escalated in pregnancy, and in seven cases it escalated when the relationship ended. Abuse was considered to escalate during periods of national lockdowns during the pandemic, and this was also at a time when other supports were not available to participants.

The mental health of participants was always affected by domestic abuse and was often weaponised to undermine and incite fear and perpetrate further emotional abuse and control. Participants experienced long standing mental health conditions, and postnatal depression, and it is unclear how the role that domestic abuse played in their presentations. Seven of the nine participants had at least two adverse childhood experiences (ACEs), and there was some evidence of perpetrator ACEs; many had witnessed parental domestic abuse, and experienced abuse themselves as children. The following chapter will provide a critical discussion of the findings and the themes and subthemes that have been identified from this process, and link to the study's aim and objectives.

9 Discussion

9.1 Introduction to chapter

The study findings have described the experiences of participants, which the researcher, using Heideggerian principles, has analysed, to understand what it means for the participants, to *be in the world* (Heidegger, 1996). By summarising individual experiences and analysing participant texts, patterns and linkages have been identified, and this chapter will discuss the shared experiences and the meaning, understanding and concepts that have emerged, that will help inform the research study aim and objectives. This chapter will discuss the study findings and analysis which relates to health care professionals, however, distinctions will be made when analyses relate specifically to professionals in primary care, particularly, Health Visitors, Midwives and GPs. This chapter will be structured around the themes and subthemes previously outlined, and critically analysed with reference to how these factors influence women's willingness to disclose abuse, and their relationships with health professionals. Additional analysis and consideration to motherhood and mothering, and the theoretical frameworks that underpinned the study, as justified in Chapter 6 will be undertaken.

9.2 Disclosing Abuse

9.2.1 Presence of routine enquiry in practice

Routine enquiry offers women and health professionals a vehicle to instigate and respond to questions about domestic abuse. However findings from the study indicate that routine enquiry is not undertaken consistently amongst Health Visitors, Midwives or GPs, as less than half the sample recall being asked about domestic abuse during their contact with these professionals. When considering the research aim, the absence of consistent routine enquiry in practice provides a tangible barrier for women experiencing abuse, and is likely to affect their willingness to disclose. Critics of retrospective data collection would argue that this information is unreliable when used with interpretative research methods, due to the historical nature of the phenomenon under investigation, and the challenges associated with accurate recall (Feder *et al*, 2009). This does mean that there is scope for routine enquiry to have occurred more

frequently than participants recall, however this study does reflect comparable findings from the literature review, that suggests routine enquiry is poorly undertaken in health settings (Evans and Feder, 2014; McQuarrie & Nairn, 2015; Sinclair, 2016; Hegarty *et al*, 2020), as detailed in Section 8.4.1

All participants resided in the same Health Board area in Scotland at the time of the study, and all had experience of parenting in this region and had contact with health professionals who were responsible for delivering care driven from the same local and national standards, policies, and guidance. Additionally, three participants had experience of raising a child while living in England, however these participants also had no recollection of being asked about domestic abuse. Although all participants had experience of parenting in the same Health Board area, it is suggested that these experiences may also be reflective of women in other areas of Scotland and the UK.

Although it is not the intention of Heideggerian research to draw generalisations from interpretative data, it is important to question whether the challenges associated with routine enquiry exist across professional groups, regardless of where they are positioned in the UK. This is particularly pertinent considering that Health Visitors in Scotland are subject to the same national routine enquiry guidance as directed by the Universal Health Visiting Pathway (Scottish Government, 2015).

Shortages of Health Visitors and staffing challenges among multiple healthcare groups are apparent across the whole of the UK, and is suggestive of alternative models of service delivery being used to manage capacity issues (IHV, 2021, p3); such strategies inevitably involve reduced contact with women in the peri-natal period. This in turn is likely to have an impact on the ability of Health Visitors and Midwives to develop relationships with women, undertake successful, sensitive routine enquiry, where women are willing to disclose abuse, and respond to disclosures effectively. As well as being cognisant to the staffing challenges that differ among geographical areas, it is also important to recognise that Health Visitors in the four UK countries follow different models of care delivery.

The Scottish Universal Health Visiting Pathway (Scottish Government, 2015) offers a minimum of 11 contacts to all families beginning in pregnancy and continuing until the

child enters primary education. Although numbers of contacts might differ in relation to need, and staffing challenges, this pathway stipulates that routine enquiry is considered at each of the mandated contacts. It is suggested that the pathway offers opportunity to develop relationships, while offering a more precise and specific focus of identifying and responding to domestic abuse, and supporting disclosures of abuse, than other UK counterparts, who also stipulate that family relationships are a focus for Health Visitor assessment. However, in many cases other UK service models lack the robust visiting framework offered to families in Scotland (IHV, 2023).

When considering the relevance of the study findings to health visiting, midwifery and GP services in other UK countries, it is important to acknowledge that the use of selective and routine enquiry by health professionals is inconsistent (Evans and Feder, 2014). Although the literature around the use of routine enquiry for domestic abuse is ambiguous and inconclusive, as discussed in Section 4.6.1, this disparity means it is difficult to draw conclusions about the value, or superiority of each, when modes of service delivery also lack uniformity.

There is a reluctance of domestic abuse survivors to disclose abuse without direct questioning (Scottish Government, 2008), however over half of the participants within the study did not recall being asked directly about domestic abuse, and other participants described being asked indirectly by various professionals for example 'is there a reason for feeling like this?', or 'how is your relationship?'. These are examples within this study of selective enquiry being used by health professionals only when presented with indicators of domestic abuse. Although this approach is used in NHS England (Department of Health, 2017) and recommended by NICE (2014), routine enquiry of domestic abuse is advocated across the perinatal period in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland (Scottish Government, 2008; Western Health and Social Care Trust, 2019; NHS Wales, 2022). Selective enquiry demonstrated by the participant examples in this study used vague, in-direct and ambiguous styles of questioning which resulted in non-disclosures of abuse by all participants who were asked. Their experiences also reflect findings from similar research that suggests health professionals find direct questioning challenging and prefer selective enquiry approaches, despite their perceived ineffectiveness (Bacchus *et al*, 2016). The findings also reinforce the literature review findings, which claimed that health

professionals often lack confidence and skills in effectively asking about, and responding to, domestic abuse (Lawoko *et al*, 2011; Keeling and Fisher, 2015).

Although this study did not explore the views of health professionals, the earlier review of literature in Chapter 4, highlighted that there is a plethora of barriers that prevent domestic abuse being addressed by health professionals (Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen, 2013; Evans and Feder, 2014; Francis, Loxton and James, 2016). Hegarty *et al* (2020) suggest that addressing domestic abuse in practice is heavily influenced by a health professional's personal experience of, or commitment to the issue, or feminist or ideological perceptions of domestic abuse, and clear child-focussed approaches. Although not explored through this study, it is possible that these are reasons for a lack of enquiry in this study.

As well as the recommendations from the Department of Health (2017) and NICE (2016), findings from a systematic review by Feder *et al* (2009) also suggest that there is insufficient evidence for domestic abuse screening programmes to be used routinely within healthcare settings. However, routine enquiry has been indicated in Scotland, in CEL 41 (Scottish Government, 2008) for use in specific healthcare settings, including health visiting and midwifery and within the Universal Health Visitor Pathway (Scottish Government, 2015), but this does not include the use of prescribed screening tools to support health professionals in asking this question. The findings from this study supported conclusions highlighted in the review of literature by Feder *et al* (2009) which suggested women usually find it acceptable to be asked about domestic abuse. All participants who could recall being asked about abuse were accepting of this; of those who were not asked, all reported that they expected to be asked.

Zoe gave an example of poor practice, whereby she stated that she believed the Health Visitor suspected domestic abuse but did not ask:

“So, in that time ... I said I'm doing well, and I had to leave and was in the refuge, she said I kind of knew you were going through a domestic but I couldn't say it to you, I needed you to tell me” (Zoe)

This example conflicts with and undermines all local and national policy regarding identifying and responding to domestic abuse in health care settings. Therefore,

findings from participants in this study suggest that learning and education is required for health professionals around routine enquiry, including re-embedding into normal practice. It also suggests that although disclosures from routine enquiry were minimal in this study, if professionals bring domestic abuse into their conversations with women, it provides an invitation to discuss abuse should they wish to, as Karen suggested. Thus affording some assurance to women that health professionals are equipped to identify and respond to abuse and eliminating some of the barriers identified in research by Heron, Eisma and Browne, (2022) who stated that a perceived lack of knowledge and confidence of health professionals prevented women from disclosing abuse.

9.2.2 Barriers to disclosure

The barriers that prevent women from disclosing abuse is an area well researched (Rose *et al*, 2011; Othman *et al*, 2014; Heron, Eisma and Browne, 2022), and was debated in Section 8.4.2. However, despite the large volume of research available to help professionals understand these barriers, disclosure to health professionals remains uncommon (Kirk and Bezzant, 2020). None of the participants in this study disclosed abuse to a health professional in response to being asked directly, which reflects the plethora of barriers that exist. Only one participant recalled disclosing abuse to their Midwife, however this occurred over the course of her pregnancy and the participant did not recall disclosure as happening as a result of routine enquiry. Participants in this study described many reasons for not disclosing, however their relationship with a health professionals was not cited, as illustrated in the figure below:

<i>I was sucked in</i>	<i>I couldn't leave</i>	<i>Worried others would find out</i>	<i>Worried others would take his side</i>
<i>I didn't want to make it worse</i>	<i>Hoped it would improve</i>	<i>Knew midwife personally</i>	<i>Partner (or other person) present at appointments</i>
<i>Fear of child being removed</i>	<i>Thought it was my fault</i>	<i>Afraid of backlash</i>	<i>Fear of not being believed</i>
<i>Lack of awareness</i>	<i>Escalation of abuse</i>	<i>Increasing fear/threat</i>	<i>Wanted to be a happy family</i>

Figure 11 – Reasons for non-disclosure of abuse

9.2.2.1 Fear

Fear of retaliation, of being blamed, or their children being removed were among the reasons women were fearful of disclosing abuse. Figure 12 identifies sources of fear for study participants:

Figure 12 – Sources of fear preventing abuse disclosure

The fear of social work involvement and belief their children would be removed, or losing their children to the abusing parent was a key concern for six of the participants, and these fears were grounded in threats often made by perpetrators, that if women disclosed abuse that these fears would be realised, and children would be removed. This reinforces what was identified in the review of literature, that fear is often a primary reason for non-disclosure (Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Jenssen, 2013; Evans and Feder, 2014; Heron, Eisma and Browne, 2020). Examples of these fears, as reported by participants in this study are illustrated below:

“I think I was more scared of losing my kids. He always said if I told anyone that they’ll take them away, and that was my biggest fear, I didn’t want to lose my kids. That would’ve broken me. He’d say you’d lose the kids, I’d lose him and no one would want me. He was really nasty when he got started” (Zoe)

“he said I will go to Social Worker and tell them whatever lies I need to get them taken off you...but that was what he’d always threatened me with” (Cathy)

As identified in existing literature, three participants, all who experienced physical abuse, did not disclose abuse due to the fear of reprisal from their partners, even when significant injuries were sustained, suggesting fear outweighed concern for their own physical health (Evans and Feder, 2014). Artz (2011) agreed that fear is a primary reason for not reporting domestic abuse, due in part to the uniqueness of the nature of abuse, whereby violence and threatening behaviours often escalate in response to help-seeking, and perpetrators often retaliate against the victim when they seek help or report abuse.

Fear was a primary concern for *Cathy* whose partner had a gun hidden in her property, and she described how the perpetrator fulfilled his threat:

“He phoned me and begged me to get the gun, but I told him the Police had already taken it, and he went to social services and told them he was worried about the welfare of my child and said the Police have been to the house and found a gun. He said if you’re going to be like this with me, just you watch and me. He said it wasn’t in my house, it was in your house” (Cathy)

This fear is validated by the potential consequences, and the suggestion by Clare *et al* (2021) that having a firearm in the home increases domestic homicide threefold. Therefore, it is unsurprising that survivors are fearful of reporting abuse due to risks to themselves increasing at this time, and the capacity this has to impact further on their psychological health and wellbeing. Fear also increases the vulnerability of domestic abuse survivors, as they become more susceptible to further abuse or violence, as well as other social, personal, and economic consequences (Artz, 2011). *Tina* described how her partner made threats to harm himself if she left:

“so I tried to leave him twice, but he said if you go I have nothing, and I’ll throw myself in the river” (Tina)

Zoe described how fear prevented her from telling her GP or Health Visitor about the abuse she was experiencing:

“I didn’t want to say, I was too scared” (Zoe)

Tina and *Zoe* described feelings of responsibility and emotional guilt in their interview narratives; this reflects work of Thaggard and Montayre (2019) who claim that feelings of shame, often invite the judgement of others, and therefore encourages women to keep details private and prevents disclosures and help-seeking. Women in this study, like *Tina* and *Zoe* were reluctant to disclose abuse due to the fear that it would be seen as their fault. Anticipated stigma is related to a fear of rejection and disapproval, and often is compounded by cultural ideologies that work to undermine the legitimacy of domestic abuse, and create a narrative that victims provoke abuse (Thaggard and Montayre, 2019). Fear of not being believed and that their situation would be perceived to be their own fault was also a comment from five participants; this was particularly relevant for those experiencing non-physical emotional or financial abuse:

“I don’t know, I was scared and nervous, I thought maybe it is my fault, you know, I don’t know, it was made out to be my fault... I felt like I done something wrong. He made me feel like I’d done something wrong” (Zoe)

These views are consistent with findings from research by Evans and Feder (2014) and Keeling and Fisher (2015) who also highlighted within the review of literature, that when women did disclose to health professionals they were often met with dismissal, and minimising of their experiences, through deflection or an absence of probing, which together reinforced to women survivors that domestic abuse was their fault. Although participants in the study had fears of not being believed, they did not disclose actual experiences of this. It is possible, however to suggest that if women across society are exposed, either directly or indirectly to these attitudes and responses, it will influence their willingness to disclose abuse to a professional, and be less inclined to share their experiences (Epstein and Goodman, 2019). The experiences of participants in this study support the view of feminists (O’Reilly, 2019; Rich, 2021) and intersectionality theorists (Crenshaw, 1991), who would argue that domestic abuse works to maintain subordination and domination of women, and whereby patriarchal

attitudes have resulted in abuse being seen as an acceptable method of controlling women (Baird and Mitchell, 2014).

There is a role for Health Visitors, Midwives, GPs and other health professionals in addressing these fears. By validating their experiences and concerns, by providing compassionate responses, and reassurance and information regarding systems and processes that are available to support them, it is possible some of this fear could be alleviated. It would support positive relationships and women's willingness to make disclosures to the health professionals they come into contact with, but more so to Health Visitors, Midwives and GPs who women are more likely to have consistent contact with.

9.2.2.2 Societal influences

As noted in the previous section, it is unsurprising that women are fearful of not being believed when disclosing abuse, particularly in light of the #MeToo movement, which has highlighted multiple stories of abuse against women being discounted and not believed, resulting in a lack of protection from the legal system which is designed to support them (Epstein and Goodman, 2019). The #MeToo movement highlights and reflects what is seen among participants in this study, for example, how gender, sex and other factors such as ethnicity and pregnancy intersect to shape women's realities. For many participants in this study, their realities are those where they are dismissed and disbelieved, due to their marginalised position in society (Crenshaw, 1991).

Despite efforts in recent decades to increase public awareness on the subject of domestic abuse, as well as years of activism and scholarly activity, Epstein and Goodman (2019) argue that women are still not believed due to a lack of understanding of domestic abuse, its presentations and the impact of trauma. Additionally, the reasons why women decide to report abuse and seek help are entrenched in negative assumptions, underpinned by misogyny and patriarchal attitudes as described by feminist theorists such as O'Reilly (2019) and Rich (2021). It is suggested that inherent dismissal of survivors' experiences are so well embedded in society, it has created an almost tangible barrier preventing women from seeking

help, and simultaneously intensifies the harm they experience (Thaggard and Montayre, 2019; Szekeres, Shuman and Saguy, 2020).

Women's fear of not being believed is echoed in the social narrative that is maintained by the media, who are believed by Easteal, Holland and Judd (2015) to strengthen the outdated and patriarchal stereotypes that negate a feminist view, creates a dominant reality of gendered harms, and impedes progressive social change. Easteal, Holland and Judd (2015) argue that the media is one institution, alongside other industrial, religious, legal and political establishments that maintain gendered inequality, via their patriarchal principles and ambivalence to feminist ideologies.

Suggestions that violence against women are mostly isolated incidents, are often represented rather than being recognised as symptoms of a wider problem arising from male dominance and gender imbalances (Bullock, 2007). Similarly, language which describes perpetrators as 'provoked', 'psychotic', 'poor' or 'uneducated', and victims as 'real', 'powerless' or 'deserving' is harmful. Equally harmful is the victimisation of women who experience abuse and who do not conform to these stereotypes, and as a result are perceived to lack credibility and believability (Easteal, Holland and Judd, 2015). Such portrayals of violence against women are argued by Bullock (2007) to be inflammatory and outdated, as are suggestions by the media that those who perpetrate or experience domestic abuse are unlike the rest of society. This again, ignores the view that domestic abuse involves gender inequalities, and it is therefore important to recognise that wider societal attitudes are likely to be influenced by messages portrayed in the media (Bullock, 2007). These arguments support the use of a Matricentric Feminist theory to underpin this study, in an attempt to represent women and their views in a manner that is not coloured by the media and external male dominated influences.

Furthermore, damaging patriarchal attitudes towards victims and perpetrators are likely to have a bearing on the willingness of women to disclose abuse, and in their confidence in being believed and supported. It is equally important that such damaging language used to describe perpetrators and victims is avoided in patient records and professional accounts, thus making attempts to create and sustain a culture which supports victims of abuse and supports them to make disclosures.

Although participants in this study did not directly report societal attitudes as barriers to disclosing abuse, they commonly spoke of feelings of self-blame and fear of not being believed, which indirectly arises from societal and cultural attitudes, values and expectations of women, men, and their roles in relationships. The attitudes of health professionals directly influence the care they provide to women experiencing abuse, and Doran *et al* (2019) states it is therefore crucial that professional practice is not affected by personal beliefs that reflect gendered stereotypes or misogynistic attitudes as this will determine the level of comfort women feel when debating whether to disclose abuse.

9.2.2.3 The cycle of abuse

Participants in this study experienced abuse which was also accompanied by complex feelings about their relationship and the desire to create a happy, stable family for themselves and their children. This desire and optimism that their situation would improve was a key reason for not disclosing abuse, and supports findings from the review of literature, that suggested women are often heavily invested in their relationships, which prevents disclosures (Hasselle *et al*, 2019). *Tina* had not had a stable, loving upbringing of her own, and had difficult relationships with her own parents and wider family. Therefore, she was attracted to the family life that this relationship brought her, despite the abuse she experienced. Her desire to feel she belonged within a loving family was a primary reason she stayed in the relationship and affected her decision-making relating to help-seeking.

If women like *Tina*, with a number of ACEs are able to overlook abuse from their partners, in order to seek out a stable family life, then assessment of ACEs by healthcare professionals might support earlier interventions and education to avoid future harm to women and their children. Additionally, Hughes *et al*'s (2017) systematic review of the health impacts of ACEs suggested that future violence was one of the most significant outcomes for adults who have experienced multiple ACEs in childhood, and this is reflected in *Tina*'s descriptions. It is also important for health professionals, specifically Health Visitors and Midwives and GPs to understand the cycle of abuse, so they can fully understand women's decision-making relating to abuse, and provide compassionate responses, which again supports positive relationship development and could promote earlier disclosures.

Zoe described being consumed by her relationship and acknowledged that she was ignorant to the concept of domestic abuse. She described feelings of shame and embarrassment and that she had little awareness of her situation and the abuse she was experiencing. *Mandy* and *Zoe* described being 'sucked in', and described the relationship as 'magnetic' where they knew they should leave, but couldn't, or even didn't want to; this cycle of abuse was typified by abuse that was often followed by apologies and promises (Rakovec-Felser, 2014).

Mandy described the predictable and repetitive nature of abuse, with periods between incidents characterised by loving and apologetic gestures, and promises for the future. These behaviours added to the difficulties participants in this study had in making positive changes to their situations, as they believed their partner's abusive behaviours would cease (Rakovec-Felser, 2014). An interpretative study by Both, Favaretto and Machade-Freitas (2019) identified similar findings, suggesting that women living with abuse find it difficult to break the cycle. This is because living with abusive, impulsive and unpredictable behaviours, create feelings of intense stress, alongside feelings of shame and isolation, meaning they are often unable to make significant changes to their lives (Both, Favaretto and Machade-Freitas, 2019). This is reflected in 2023 Scottish MARAC data, where the percentage of repeat cases for discussion vary between 13 - 42%, confirming the cyclic and repetitive nature of abuse is a reality for victims (*SafeLives, 2024*). The cyclical nature of abuse also supports the use of continuous routine enquiry which is more likely to target women during this cycle, and therefore illicit positive disclosures.

9.2.2.4 The impact of community

The communities in which participants in this study lived, were found to affect their ability and willingness to seek help for the abuse they were experiencing. *Lynda* had more than one abusive relationship; her first abusive partner was Muslim, therefore she also converted to this faith. She recalled living in a Muslim community and described a culture of acceptance regarding domestic abuse, alongside the belief that she would not be supported or believed by others in the community if she disclosed:

“in the Muslim community everybody knew that everybody hit their wives, it was just a cultural..... so people knew, I think they knew what was going on but no one said anything” (Lynda)

This reflects findings from similar studies discussed in the literature review, in Chapter 4, by Hasselle *et al* (2019), Decker *et al* (2012) and Odero *et al* (2014) who identified that religious or cultural factors frequently influence women’s help-seeking behaviours, and provide structural barriers to them disclosing abuse. In this study, *Lynda* also described living in a small community with another abusive partner, where everyone was known to each other. In this case her Midwife was known to her personally as they attended the same church. This was a barrier to her disclosing abuse, as she feared that she would not be believed, or supported, and did not have trust that her disclosure would remain confidential.

Health Visitors and Midwives should be aware of such structural considerations affecting women. In small, rural communities, or where cultural factors like this are relevant, consideration is needed by professionals, to ensure conditions are created that eliminate barriers like *Lynda* describes, to allow relationships to be fostered, and to support disclosures of abuse to health professionals. Professionals are required to provide reassurance that confidentiality will be upheld where personal relationships exist; similarly, a knowledge of cultures is needed so they can question and respond sensitively.

Study findings echo Odero *et al*'s (2014) study that highlighted the cultural and familial connections in a community which often prevent women from seeking help for domestic abuse, and often advocate matters being resolved within the family. Study participants lived within a small rural region, where individuals, including those working for specialist domestic abuse services, are often well known in their communities, resulting in a lack of anonymity. It is possible this was a factor which contributed to women’s decision-making regarding disclosure, and might contrast with disclosures in larger urban areas. Efforts to recruit from larger Health Board areas was unsuccessful but may have provided this contrast from which new knowledge could be drawn.

9.2.2.5 Partner's presence and controlling behaviour

One of the key barriers preventing conversations about domestic abuse, and initiating help-seeking, is the presence of abusive partners at health appointments, including home visits by professionals. DeBoer *et al* (2013) and NICE (2016a) stated that it should be routine practice for every health professional to create opportunities to see women individually and offer confidential space to ask about and disclose domestic abuse. However, despite these suggestions, interview narratives in this study suggest that there is little evidence of this in practice.

Five participants described their partners always being present at health appointments, which created a barrier to professionals asking about abuse, and women being able to positively respond. This was a prevalent barrier evident in the review of literature in Chapter 4, and is a common feature across domestic abuse situations, whereby women are controlled so they have limited opportunities to be seen alone, and this creates additional barriers for those health professionals who are well positioned to ask about abuse (Kirk and Bezzant, 2020). This study concurred with existing literature that health professionals rarely seek out opportunities for routine enquiry, and often cite the presence of partners as a reason for not enquiring about abuse (Heron, Eisma and Browne, 2020). Of the nine participants, only *Tina* and *Ruby* could recall situations whereby health professionals were creative in separating them from their partners to enquire about their safety and whether they were experiencing any domestic abuse. Despite these examples of good practice, both participants still responded negatively, and did not disclose the abuse they were experiencing. This was due to reasons of fear and stigma as discussed in Section 9.2.2.1. Although this issue relates primarily to Health Visitors and Midwives, health professionals in other settings, such as A&E, sexual health and mental health should also consider creating safe spaces for routine enquiry and conversations about domestic abuse, especially when partners or others are present with women at appointments.

Interestingly, and considering the prevalence of financial abuse across the sample, none of the participants cited financial barriers as a reason for not disclosing abuse, or not being able to leave. Although the abuse experienced was prior to the cost-of-living crisis in the UK, many participants were dependent on benefits, or subject to severe financial limitations due to their partner's controlling behaviours which

prevented them from working outside of the home. This dependence on benefits, may also account for the lack of reference to finances during the pandemic. None of the participants described being subject to furlough arrangements and subsequent curtailment of income, therefore the dependence on benefit payments suggested their income remained static during this time, and therefore was not an apparent source of further stress in the family during this period.

9.2.2.6 Lack of awareness of non-violent abuse

All nine participants experienced emotional abuse within their relationships, however six were unaware that their partners' controlling and manipulative behaviours were illustrative of domestic abuse. They cited various reasons for this, but the primary reason was a lack of education and knowledge about non-violent abuse, stating they were not educated about this at school, or in later life. These findings support what is known from the current review of literature, that a lack of awareness presents a significant barrier to many women experiencing abuse. Similarly, participants stated that they only attributed domestic abuse with physical violence, and beatings. Their perceptions were that there was little attention to non-violent abuse in the media, or the press, or within society, until recently. Others were influenced by their beliefs and expectations about relationships, and what they should be like. As suggested within feminist theory (Rich, 2021), participants had an understanding and acceptance that men were dominant within relationships, where their needs were inferior to their partner's.

Five participants had been exposed as children to domestic abuse in their parents' relationships, and they indicated that they knew domestic abuse to be only physically violent, which led them to not recognise other non-physical forms of abuse. Therefore, these women described in the interviews that they would have said 'no' to a routine enquiry question about abuse, because they did not believe they were experiencing domestic abuse. Several participants stated they can now identify similar abuse in their friend's relationships and have supported other women to identify patterns of behaviour indicating emotional abuse. Erdman (2020) states that emotionally abusive behaviours often go unidentified and unreported, as reflected in this study, whereby a lack of awareness of this type of abuse was a key contributory factor to not seeking support. Without addressing this lack of education and awareness, any attempts to

use routine enquiry by professionals is likely to be unsuccessful and prevent early identification and support to women experiencing abuse.

None of the participants in this study cited the quality of their relationship with their GP, Health Visitor or Midwife as a sole reason for not disclosing abuse, suggesting that the presence of a positive relationship is not a sufficient pre-cursor to a disclosure of abuse. Furthermore, the range of reasons presented by the participants indicate that there were a variety of complex, interrelating issues at play for women experiencing abuse, which contributed to the decision-making surrounding whether to disclose their experience of abuse or not.

9.2.2.7 Disclosing abuse and age

Participants in the study were aged between 18 and 40, with two being aged 18-20, and the remaining seven being 25-40. It is unclear whether the age of participants was a barrier to disclosure and help-seeking, and there is little research investigating age as a factor in disclosing abuse. However, early studies by Barrett and St Pierre (2011), indicate that younger women are more likely to disclose abuse than older women, and Flicker *et al* (2011) reported that older women are less likely to confide in family, but equally likely to disclose to friends than younger women. These studies conflict with earlier research by Yoshioka *et al* (2003) who suggested that older ethnic minority women are more likely to disclose abuse to friends and family. The age of these studies, and more recent understandings of domestic abuse research suggests the findings could change over time, and should be interpreted with caution. The study design has included only women who are mothers with young children, and therefore experiences of older women have not been explored; therefore it is not possible within this study to make any inferences into the role of age in abuse disclosures.

9.2.3 Conditions for disclosing abuse

In the earlier review of literature, in Chapter 4, it was suggested that for women to disclose domestic abuse to a health professional, there was a requirement for a trusting, non-judgmental relationship to exist (Clancy and Svensson, 2010; Rose, 2010; Visentin, Viera and Trevison, 2015; Francis, Loxton and James, 2016; Shanti, 2017). It is also acknowledged that facilitators, or conditions for disclosures is an area that has received much less attention in literature, when compared to barriers.

However, interviews with participants in this study contested that although the presence of a positive relationship is important to women, and the presence of a positive relationship mostly exists, it is not sufficient, in isolation to prompt a disclosure. The reasons why participants in the study chose to disclose the abuse that they were experiencing fell into three broad themes, which often overlapped (Figures 13 & 14):

Figure 13 – Conditions for disclosing abuse

Escalation of abuse	Child abuse	Changes in women's willingness to accept abuse
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing violence • Increasing control • Increased threat • Significant violent/sexual attack • Intervention from others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Child injured or at increased risk of being hurt • Threat of child protection proceedings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timing • Threshold of tolerance • 'Just had enough'

Figure 14 – Reasons for a positive disclosure

These three themes were identified through a process of 'dwelling on data', common to hermeneutic data analysis whereby the researcher builds meaning and understanding (Dibley *et al*, 2020, p125). Each individual's lived experience described during the interviews was different, and subject to different contextual and individual factors, and complexities; however, these three commonalities were present across the data set and will now be discussed.

9.2.3.1 Escalation of abuse

Escalation of abuse was not identified as a prominent trigger for disclosing abuse in the earlier review of literature in Chapter 4, however this was a key motivator for many participants in this study. For five of the women in the study, it was the Police who were the agency involved in the disclosure, rather than any health professional, due to the criminal nature and perceived threat to life. Five participants described an escalation of abuse which led to their decision to disclose. This escalation varied from participant to participant, but included a rape, a physical assault in public witnessed by others, and the recognition by one participant that her partner's behaviours were becoming more extreme and erratic.

Cathy and *Tina* both saw their partner's controlling behaviours escalating, leading to them reporting them to the Police. It arose from the interviews that even where women sustained injuries from a physical assault, this rarely led to reporting the offence, and a disclosure of abuse. However, *Mandy*, with the support of a friend, reported a rape to the Police, and considered this to have met an unacknowledged threshold of what abuse was acceptable or tolerable to her. An assault on *Ruby* was witnessed by others who called the Police, leading to her disclosing her partner's abusive behaviours. *Lynda* experienced a violent attack in the street by her partner when pregnant, and was taken to hospital by a passer-by, who also called the Police. It is unclear if these crimes would have been reported without the involvement of others in these events, and supports the earlier review of literature which suggests women are unlikely to seek support for abuse even when injuries are sustained (Odero *et al*, 2014). All women in these examples reported to have been honest with professionals when asked about abuse when questioned following these assaults, and having presented with physical injuries. If Health Visitors, Midwives and GPs who have established relationships with women were able to identify patterns of abuse, and in particular escalating behaviours, it is possible they could facilitate earlier conversations, support and disclosures prior to significant injury occurring.

9.2.3.2 Child abuse

The heightened risk to their children proved to be a key reason for participants in the study to leave their abusive relationships. This supports findings identified in the review of literature which also highlighted that mothers often prioritised the needs of

their children in abusive situations, and were often a precursor to seeking support (*Williams et al, 2020*). Two participants witnessed abuse of their children by their partners and made the decision to report their behaviour and make disclosures regarding the abuse they were experiencing. Two other participants in the study identified increasing threats to themselves and their child, and their partner's lack of acknowledgement of the risk to the child. In these circumstances, participants appeared to prioritise the needs of their children, and these events proved to be a trigger to make changes to her situation. *Lynda* had been advised of the possible child protection procedures that would apply should she return to her partner, and this was likely a strong influencing factor in her decision-making to leave. In both examples, women reported the abuse to the Police, however *Georgina* also disclosed to a Health Visitor in a Children's Centre. These instances resulted in the women leaving their partners.

The negative impacts of domestic abuse on children's social, emotional and cognitive development are largely uncontested; however, the effect of domestic abuse on mothering is less certain, and in many cases, ambiguous (*Buchanan, Power and Verity, 2014*). Although children's exposure to domestic abuse is unequivocally harmful, research by *Mullender et al (2002)* has described mothers to be hyper vigilant, on-guard, as a means of protecting their children, whereas *Dayton et al (2010)* suggests no impact on mothering.

Similarly, a longitudinal study by *Levendosky et al (2006)* suggested that women experiencing abuse provided adequate protection for their children, providing their mental health was not significantly impacted. *Levendosky et al (2006)* claim that although current domestic abuse adversely impacts on both maternal mental health and parenting, it is only maternal mental health that is negatively impacted by past experiences of abuse. *Levendosky's (2006)* study suggests that parenting behaviours are less affected by past events, and suggest that the impact of abuse on mothering can vary. *O'Reilly's (2019)* Matricentric Feminist (MF) theory proposes that women are marginalised further by mothering roles, and this is noted by *Buchanan, Power and Verity (2014)* who claim that patriarchal cultures mean that the responsibility lies with women to keep their children safe in a domestically abusive environment, with no similar expectation from a father who is perpetrating abuse. This was seen in an

account by Zoe who described being held accountable for her children's safety by agencies. The threat of child protection processes was used by agencies to persuade her to disclose abuse, implying it was her role to protect her children from her partner's abusive behaviours. The implementation of the Safe and Together model (Mandel, 2013) aims to address such expectations, however requires large-scale systematic changes to practice which will take time to fully embed (Scottish Government, 2018).

Participants in this study demonstrated maternal protective behaviours to shield their babies and children from abuse, remaining vigilant, and pre-empting potential threats to keep them safe; thereafter being prompted into disclosing abuse and leaving the relationship, due to the threat to their children. This reflects the views of Neyer and Berndai (2011), who suggest in Section 6.3.2 that motherhood can provide some women agency and power, and empower them to regain control over their lives. This is also reflective of existing literature as described in Chapter 4.

9.2.3.3 Changes to women's willingness to accept abuse

Zoe disclosed abuse to a school teacher following an argument with her partner, when she was asked how she was. This differed from other participants and she was noted to have suffered a variety of significant physical abuse within her relationship, in which she had never reported or sought medical attention for injuries. These assaults occurred in her home, and the incident preceding the disclosure was a verbal altercation, however when asked if she was OK by a teacher, Zoe made the decision to disclose the abuse she had been experiencing. When asked what had made a difference that day, she described:

"we had fell out and he'd been nasty to me, because that just happened, and a friendly face said are you OK, it just broke me, so if that happened at the same time as a professional asked me, it might have gone the same way as well"
(Zoe)

Here, this disclosure was influenced by timing of the event, and the personal decision to end this pattern of abuse, rather than being dependent entirely on the relationship that already existed between her and the teacher. Unplanned disclosures like this are termed 'turning points' by Boethius and Akerstrom (2020), whereby a display of

empathetic curiosity by someone in a trusted relationship almost forced a disclosure but was also facilitated by creating an environment that was acceptable to Zoe. Again, this supports an approach of professional curiosity built on positive relationships, and use of routine enquiry where Health Visitors and Midwives may be unaware of turning points and personal thresholds which may lead to abuse disclosures.

The earlier review of literature suggested that abuse disclosures are often gradual, and occur when personal strategies have been exhausted (Evans and Feder, 2014), however this was not overtly mirrored in participant's experiences. While disclosures were often unplanned, participants did not describe gradual disclosures like Evans and Feder (2014) suggest is often the case.

9.2.3.4 The presence of a supportive relationship

An interpretative study by Boethius and Akerstrom (2020), found that women disclosed abuse in both planned and unplanned manners, however the findings in this study demonstrate that for most participants, disclosures were unplanned, and almost always to the Police. These 'turning points' as described by Boethius and Akerstrom (2020) arose in response to various circumstances, for example, in response to an emergency or crisis, in spontaneous revelations, or due to others' initiatives. *Cathy and Tina* disclosed abuse in response to increased threat and danger. Although they had previously hidden or denied their abuse, and their disclosures were not planned, their quickly escalating situations led to disclosures of abuse to the Police. *Mandy and Lynda* also disclosed to the Police and health professionals in an unplanned manner, but as a result of the involvement of others. In these situations, there were almost coerced into disclosing by others, and therefore there was no requirement for a relationship to exist in these circumstances.

Georgina's decision to disclose abuse was planned in response to increasing threat to her child, and she identified the GP as the professional of choice to disclose to, however this was influenced by the norms and traditions of her country and culture, and not by the presence of an existing relationship. *Zoe's* disclosure was unplanned, and spontaneous; despite the unplanned nature of the disclosure, Zoe had a familiarity with the professional within the school setting to whom enquired after her. Although

Zoe did not have a close relationship with this person, Zoe's interview suggested that she viewed this person as someone in a trusted role to whom she could disclose abuse to. She did however state that any professional could have asked after her at that particular day, and she was likely to have disclosed.

None of the women in the study described disclosing abuse in a planned way, where she identified who she would tell, and how, beforehand, as described by Boethius and Akerstrom (2020). The participants in the study disclosed abuse in a variety of different scenarios, and in response to differing triggers. The earlier review of literature suggested that the presence of a positive relationship was crucial to support a disclosure of abuse (Visentin, Vieira, and Trevisan, 2015; Francis, Loxton and James 2016; Shanti, 2017), however findings from this study indicate that women's decision making regarding disclosing abuse is influenced by various factors, and not solely dependent on the presence of an established positive relationship. The complexity of decision making regarding abuse disclosures was not found to be well reflected in existing literature.

Although this study highlighted few examples of participants disclosing abuse to a professional with whom they had an established trusting relationship, health professionals working with women over long periods, such as GPs, Midwives and Health Visitors, have a key role in creating conditions for such relationships to develop, to provide women opportunities to disclose abuse in a planned way, rather than in emergency or crisis situations. If conditions that supported the use of routine enquiry and empathetic curiosity were created, and offered consistently to women throughout the duration of their professional relationship, women might be more likely to disclose in ways that could be both planned and unplanned, but earlier in their abusive relationships.

As well as a supportive relationship, a disclosure would also be influenced by the ongoing and cyclical nature of domestic abuse, and position of the women in the cycle and her willingness to seek support (Rakovec-Felser, 2014). However, findings from this study suggest that the presence of a supportive, trusting non-judgmental relationship with a health professional is, alone, not sufficient to prompt help-seeking. In each of the cases, participants in this study made the decisions to disclose

themselves, often triggered by others, or by events, and emphasising the multi-factorial nature of abuse disclosure. In each case, the women had reached their own threshold for what they were willing or able to accept or tolerate. It is suggestive that had this point not been reached by these individual women, then disclosure would not have taken place, regardless of the presence of others, the established relationship with a professional, or the increasing threat to themselves or their children. Consequently, it is important to consider how the provision of early public health messages about domestic abuse and healthy relationships, might support women to reach their threshold earlier in their abusive relationships.

9.2.4 Relationships with health professionals

Participants in this study spoke positively about their Health Visitor and Midwives, and this reflects much of the international literature whereby families receive home visiting models of care, albeit it often from 'home helpers', or 'home visitors' rather than qualified Health Visitors, and who all report positive relationships mostly exist (Tandon et al, 2005). Health Visitor research from across the UK suggests that the development of trusting relationships is essential to affect positive change with the families they support and is necessary to address inequalities and complex issues including maternal and infant mental health and domestic abuse (Cowley *et al*, 2015; Scottish Government, 2015). Similarly, Doi *et al*'s (2021) recent Evaluation of the Universal Health Visiting Pathway, also reinforces the idea that trusting relationships are required between families and their Health Visitor to achieve the desired outcomes and ensure families are better placed to seek help when needed. Although these statements are in most, not in dispute, and they are confirmed to be an essential requirement in nursing, midwifery, healthcare and therapeutic spheres, findings from this study indicate that this suggestion does not play out into a domestic abuse context. Each of the nine participants in the study stated, consistent with Doi *et al*'s study (2021) that they had a good relationship with their Health Visitor, however none disclosed abuse to them following routine enquiry and only one confided in their midwife. Interview narratives implied they could '*tell them anything*', however this did not extend to domestic abuse disclosures. Cathy spoke positively about her Health Visitor:

"I'd spoken to the health visitor, and we always got on, and although I hadn't told her, at the start, I knew I could speak to her if I needed to.... The thing I

really liked was that she was really honest...I respected that; she would never go behind my back. She would say this is what I'm doing, but I am telling you what I'm doing. I respected her and she respected me" (Cathy)

This example, plus the adjectives used by participants in Figure 7, reflect similar terms noted by Bidmead, Cowley and Grocott (2016) and Tanninen *et al* (2014), regarding relationships with professionals in helping roles, for example Health Visitors. However, despite the description of a non-judgmental, trusting relationship in many cases, the participants in the study mostly, still maintained that this was not sufficient to disclose abuse to them, suggesting that the presence of this relationship was not the only pre-requisite required to support a disclosure.

In one of her abusive relationships, *Lynda* disclosed abuse to a midwife during pregnancy, and she stated this was due to them having a well-established relationship, and she described the various actions this midwife had undertaken to support the participant as a young parent, for example attending meetings with her. This relationship also existed in the context of *Lynda* having frequent, consistent support from her Midwife, and them both having similar values and beliefs about infant feeding and parenting, which may have been a factor in developing a meaningful relationship. This does suggest that if consistent, regular contact can be achieved, with the context of a supportive relationship, there is potential for disclosures to happen over time.

Although a trusting and supportive relationship had developed in this instance due to consistent and frequent contact, and led to a disclosure of domestic abuse for *Lynda*, the remaining participants in the study did not have similar experiences. Their interview narratives did not describe building relationships over a prolonged period, or receiving frequent contact, so it is unclear how these factors might influence a willingness to disclose abuse. This suggests that the phenomenon of domestic abuse has far more complexities than other public health issues that appear to be more easily and readily discussed with Health Visitors and Midwives. For example, all women in the study confirmed the negative impact of domestic abuse on their mental health, and reported being able to speak to their GP, Health Visitor or Midwife about this, even where a positive relationship might not have fully existed. They reported being able to identify disturbances to their mental health and a willingness to seek support

accordingly, without fear of repercussions or judgement, and similarly, they reported being able to freely contact their Health Visitor if they had any other concerns about their child's health or development. This willingness to seek support for mental health, but not domestic abuse appears to be a new phenomenon that has not been identified by the author in similar domestic abuse research, or within the earlier review of literature. This demonstrates a clear difference between how women seek help for issues that are both often stigmatising and having profound impacts on their lives.

Although it is accepted that achieving consistency in health professional is more likely to support relationship building, other international research suggests this is less significant (Maguigan, Katzer and Pratt, 2003). Although participants mostly maintained that they had good relationships with their Midwives and Health Visitors, as described in Section 9.2.3.4, a dichotomy exists, which suggests that while relationships were positive, they existed within a context that prevented women disclosing abuse. It was common within the participant interviews for Midwives or Health Visitors to be informed of the abuse by someone other than the participant, and following this, all participants reported them to be supportive, and they were able to be open and honest about the abuse they had experienced. This suggests that the issue of disclosure is the challenge for women experiencing abuse. Once disclosure had taken place, these positive relationship characteristics became valuable again, and became the foundation on which mothers sought support for themselves and their children (Doi *et al*, 2021), and 'gave permission' for women to tell all about their experiences. Again, this nuance is not overtly evident in the researcher's scope of the existing literature.

9.2.4.1 Kindness, compassion and empathy

Kindness, compassion or empathy were not words used by participants in their interviews to describe health professionals, however, it can be judged that the adjectives and phrases that were used, for example '*honest*', '*good*', '*went above and beyond*' could translate into a context that describes kind and compassionate behaviours. It is the subjective view of the researcher, that had participants been asked directly if their Health Visitors, Midwives or GPs showed kindness, compassion or empathy, they would have responded positively.

Kindness, compassion and empathy are considered vital to all caring relationships and are associated with improved outcomes for patients and service users as well as being central to regulatory codes of conduct (Haslam, 2015; NMC, 2018). At the heart of any relationship-based practice, is compassion; a combination of empathy, kindness, sensitivity, warmth (Haslam, 2015; Sinclair, 2020). Reid (2012) and Sinclair et al (2016) claim that compassion is central to caring when patients are in times of need and vulnerability, pain or distress, and is core business for all nursing professionals, or those in a helping role. This is therefore reflected within the pillars of practice of the NMC Code (2022).

Carl Rogers (1957) stated that empathy was a core element in producing change in those seeking help; and Kelly, Lepo and Frinzi (2011) suggest that when someone is consistently shown empathy, unconditional positive regard and genuineness, positive changes can occur. For example, within healthcare, empathy can result in improved clinical outcomes for patients, and improved wellbeing and job satisfaction for health professionals (Guidi and Traversa, 2021).

The capacity to practice with kindness, compassion and empathy can be influenced by various factors, including perceptions and attitudes of the victimisation and perpetration of abuse, and compassion fatigue (Post *et al*, 2014). Although enabling compassion is a mandatory requirement, it is argued to be difficult to evidence (McVicar *et al*, 2020). Health professionals who have experienced high self-criticism, insecurities, and who lack close personal relationships may be uncomfortable addressing the distress of others and will therefore be challenged when building relationships with women experiencing abuse (McVicar *et al*, 2020). Therefore, the ability to build relationships is heavily dependent on the health professional to create conditions where trusting, supportive relationships can flourish. This can be difficult when families are highly vulnerable, as Azzi-Lessing (2013) states that challenges often exist when trying to engage and build relationships due to the presence of poverty and stress in families, or past experiences with services.

Sinclair *et al*'s (2016) review of literature from the last 25 years suggests that terms such as compassion remain poorly understood and defined. Although a desire to deliver compassionate and empathetic care has always been central to nursing practice, being able to demonstrate such characteristics is an intrinsic communication

skill, essential to building positive relationships between Health Visitors, Midwives and the families they serve (Cowley *et al*, 2018; Doi *et al*, 2021).

Incidents of substandard care have led to concern about the presence of compassion in modern healthcare settings (Keogh, 2013; Francis, 2013). Compassion and kindness in nursing are expected attributes and fundamental skills expected of nursing graduates (Catlow *et al*, 2020). However, failings within healthcare have highlighted that poor organisational systems often prevent health professionals from demonstrating compassion. Nursing is difficult, challenging work, and health professionals need multi-factorial support to be able to deliver compassionate care rather than task orientated approaches (Goodrich, 2012; Haslam, 2015; Sawbridge, 2015). It can be suggested that in areas where Midwifery or Health Visitor staffing levels are low, with high caseloads, the ability and capacity to offer compassionate care might be compromised, and reduce the likelihood of women being asked about domestic abuse, and Health Visitors or Midwives being able to sensitively respond.

Balancing the delivery of relational care, which is empathetic and compassionate, with safeguarding and organisational obligations, presents challenges for health professionals, and has potential to threaten the relationship development (Koloroutis and Trout, 2013). Relationship development can be difficult for survivors of abuse as they often experience vulnerability and a lack of autonomy which can affect their engagement with services (Sturley, Shotton and Hanlan, 2023). The development of trust and reciprocal relationships becomes even more problematic when professionals are obligated to meet professional and safeguarding responsibilities, to enquire about, or respond to concerns about domestic abuse (Koloroutis and Trout, 2013).

Similarly, it is in circumstances such as this, where power is often perceived to lie with professionals, rather than clients or parents, thus hindering the development of trust and existence of therapeutic relationships (Stephen and Nettleton, 2023). Therefore, to shift power to the service user, or abuse survivor, professionals must strive to deliver professional practice that is salutogenic, solution focussed and demonstrates positive regard for the families they work with (Stephen and Nettleton, 2023). Twedde (2007) and Van der Elst, Dierckx de Casterlé and Gasmans, (2011) also state that

professionals need to build rapport with patients, create space to listen and provide opportunities to discuss feelings if compassionate care is to be delivered.

9.2.4.2 Compassion and empathy in a political context

Compassion in Practice (Department of Health, 2012) brought the 6Cs to be central elements necessary for person centred care, set within a backdrop of supportive organisational cultures, directed by similar compassionate leadership. This is also reflected in reports from the Chief Medical Office in Scotland advocating for Realistic Medicine since 2016, as an approach to promote shared decision-making and person-centred approaches to care (Scottish Government, 2023). Both UK and Scottish governments have set out renewed mandates to deliver high quality compassionate care, suggesting a renewed commitment to ensuring the values of the NHS are reflected in UK wide policy and practice (Department of Health, 2015; Scottish Government, 2023). However, despite this, there remains workforce and financial challenges that have led to services being delivered inconsistently and which have negative impacts on both health professionals and families alike. Similarly, it can be anticipated that these challenges also compromise the delivery of empathetic and compassionate care (IHV, 2019).

9.2.4.3 Barriers to relationship development

Health Visitor practice is underpinned by the requirement for a positive relationship that features reciprocity; the ability to initiate, regulate and terminate interactions appropriately, which in turn supports trust between the parties (Sturley, Shotton and Hanlan, 2023). It supports Health Visitors to effectively assess identify and respond to risks and strengths, and build partnerships that Cowley *et al*, (2018) suggest facilitates strengths-based practice; whereby families feel seen and heard and where their abilities are recognised. While this approach underpins modern health visiting practice and training and reflects how Health Visitors can enquire collaboratively to respect and connect with clients, it is an approach that has evolved from traditional practice grounded in surveillance, where power sat firmly with professionals (Peckover and Aston, 2017).

Socially constructed negative perceptions regarding surveillance have, in the past been associated with health visiting practice and child protection services. Health

Visitors are tasked with balancing relational care and safeguarding duties and this dichotomy, coupled with lack of training and education regarding values and strengths-based approaches, has led to difficulties in achieving true partnership working that is advocated in modern healthcare (Peckover and Appleton, 2019). Similarly, the discussion of sensitive or challenging issues, for example substance misuse or child protection concerns, also has the potential to disrupt the development and maintenance of a positive relationship between professional and parent (Peckover, 2002), and reinforces the negative policing roles that have been traditionally attributed to health visiting (Kirkpatrick *et al*, 2007).

Pound (2014) states that when professionals are under pressure to get the job done, focusing on tasks, or faced with heavy workloads, this also interferes with the ability to connect with clients and provide empathetic responses. Sturley, Shotton and Hanlan (2023) suggest that health professionals should pay attention to their own feelings, values and communication, and acknowledge their role in relationship development, so they are able to respond in a kind and compassionate manner, particularly when addressing domestic abuse concerns or other sensitive issues that disrupt relational aspects of care (Kolorutis and Trout, 2013, p194). Furthermore, Pound (2014) suggests that a degree of health professional skill to 'enquire collaboratively' is required, while suspending their own judgements, as without such efforts, power is likely to stay with the professional and be a barrier to positive disclosures. As this study did not include the views of professionals, the distribution of power within these relationships remains unknown.

Four participants, *Cathy*, *Ruby*, *Lynda* and *Tina* had received multiagency support due to the risks relating to their abusive relationships. The interview narratives relating to this support lacked the positive descriptions that were used to depict relationships with Midwives and Health Visitors where risks or concerns by agencies were not present. Participants described their contact with health and social care professionals during these periods more negatively. *Cathy* discussed being defensive when speaking to health and social work professionals during pregnancy and following a domestic abuse incident. She talked about her lack of trust in her Midwife who she felt was not honest with her:

“she never told me that she knew about that, she asked me about any criminal convictions, and I told them he was going through court, but it’s nothing to worry about, I was so defensive, and she said she had to make a thing to social services, and it’s up to them if they want to get involved, but she told me that after I told her.... I was so defensive, and even if she had (asked about abuse), I probably wouldn’t have said anything at that point in time” (Cathy)

She described that her fears about her baby being removed, and possible social work involvement prevented her from being honest about what she had experienced. She confirmed that when asked about other abusive incidents, she reported ‘*everything was fine*’. Although this is only from *Cathy’s* perspective, she recalls that during this scenario, there were no examples of efforts made by Health or Social Work professionals to develop a relationship with her during this time, or to investigate and allay her anxieties. Although *Cathy* described her engagement with services as reluctant, it is possible that her barriers prevented her from recognising this. However, any efforts to ask about abuse in compliance with the Universal Health Visiting Pathway, or by Midwives or GPs, were unlikely to have resulted in a positive disclosure whilst she held the fears and assumptions that she did. It is therefore suggested that health professionals have a role in asking about and addressing fears and worries, to allow supportive conversations about abuse to happen.

Ruby also described poor relationships with multi-agency partners during periods of involvement. Although this does not pertain specifically to health professionals, it gives some insight into how relationships with professionals might differ when in a safeguarding or protection context, and how they are perceived by those who have involvement with them:

“Social Work weren’t supportive, they were constantly watching, in my case I constantly got reported by his family, they had the police reports, and they got harassed by him and his family. My kids got put on the Child Protection register, it wasn’t until a year later, that it hit me. I had to flee my house, I had my windows smashed by him, I always got an ultimatum from Social Work, to go back to the house, or lose my kids” (Ruby)

Ruby's example also demonstrates how she was held responsible for keeping her children safe, rather than her abusive partner, and reflects women's marginalised position in society, where they are held accountable for male behaviours, as discussed in Chapter 6. Although there was little reference in the study to participant relationships with health professionals in a safeguarding context, the participants spoke more negatively, and did not highlight positive relationships with the same clarity during these periods of multiagency involvement. Participant narratives describe professionals' behaviours such as a lack of openness and honesty, which created a lack of trust within the relationships, which would not promote any kind of disclosure or sensitive conversation. The nature of parent-professional relationships during periods of multi-agency involvement is not widely covered within existing literature, therefore this study highlights that relationship building, repair and development within safeguarding or welfare contexts requires strategies and approaches different from those that exist within universal services alone.

9.2.4.4 Relationships with GPs

As all participants in the study were mothers with young children, they spoke mostly of their relationships with Midwives or Health Visitors. GPs were rarely discussed by participants and were referred to mostly as someone participants would speak to about their deteriorating mental health. Participants described being able to seek a GP appointment themselves and appeared comfortable to do so. Parker *et al* (2020) confirms this in their interpretative study, and states patients often present with a medical issue initially before disclosing emotional difficulties to their GP, however this was not discussed by participants in the study.

None of the participants identified their GP as a professional they would choose to discuss domestic abuse with, or who asked directly about domestic abuse when presenting for treatment. This echoes existing research as identified in the review of literature, which states that women are often dissatisfied with the response from their family doctor, and who are not a professional they would disclose to (Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen's, 2013). For those participants who saw their GP for support with their mental health, some described being asked indirectly about triggers or circumstances that might be contributing to low mood, depression or anxiety, including their relationship, however, none could recall being asked directly about abuse. It is

interesting that participants in this study sought support from their GP for deteriorating mental health, and if considering Parker *et al*'s (2020) study findings, it might be suggested that this is a 'run up' to disclosing domestic abuse. The differences between how women seek help from GPs for mental health and domestic abuse are not found to be explored in depth during scoping exercises by the researcher, and therefore such nuances offer scope for further study and exploration.

Similarly, Parker *et al* (2020) also found the relationship between patient and GP to be pivotal to discussing emotional difficulties, whereby GPs played roles of investigators and validators. This could suggest that it was the absence of a trusting relationship that prevented further disclosure of abuse. Additionally, it could also be proposed that disclosure or help-seeking for domestic abuse would be unlikely in the absence of adequate investigating (routine or selective enquiry) for abuse, or validation by the GP, or other health professional.

Participants in this study were, in general dismissive of GPs as a professional group that would support them with domestic abuse, reflecting similar studies. Findings in this study suggest that the relationship between women and their GP differed greatly from that relationship that parents might have had with a Health Visitor or Midwife, however research by Cocker *et al* (2013) suggests that the doctor-patient relationship exists synonymously with the former. Trusting relationships are those where patients feel taken seriously, where communication skills exist alongside shared decision-making, consistency of doctor and person-centered approaches to care.

Patients' desires for longer consultation times is one key factor that differentiates the relationships between these professional groups (Croker *et al*, 2013). Although a debate of GP practice in the UK is out-with the scope of the thesis, there are undoubtedly other factors that influence the GP-patient relationship, in part determined by the consistency of GP and the time they have available within consultations. This might be difficult to achieve in the culture of national shortages, as is similar within Health Visitor and Midwifery practice in some parts of the UK and Scotland (The Health Foundation, 2022).

MacKenzie *et al* (2019) suggest that how GPs communicate their views on women's domestic abuse situations shape their help-seeking behaviours. Where women feel their experiences are not legitimised by GPs, they are unlikely to return to discuss similar difficulties in future. There are key differences in roles between GP, Midwife and Health Visitors, notably, but not exclusively, relating to the clinical setting, time constraints, and the model of care. Further exploration is likely required to explain the negative associations between domestic abuse disclosure, the GP, and their relationship with patients, as well as a review of domestic abuse education and awareness of specialist support within this professional group.

9.2.4.5 Informal supports – Family and friends

Women often rely on informal supports from family, friends and work colleagues during periods of abuse, either exclusively, or alongside specialist or professional support, and it is believed to buffer against the myriad of physical and psychological impacts of living with domestic abuse (Gregory *et al*, 2017). However, there is very little written in literature about the informal support women who are experiencing domestic abuse receive, despite family, friends and work colleagues often having a good insight into the situation, and often playing a significant role in influencing the outcomes for women (Gregory and Williamson, 2021).

Participants in this study rarely disclosed abuse to professionals, however, most had confided in either a friend or family member at some point, particularly when physical or financial abuse was perpetrated. Often, friends or family members supported participants to recognise that their partner's behaviours were abusive and unacceptable. *Karen* described how she had confided in her friend and sister who had alerted to her partner's abusive behaviours. *Mandy* also described disclosing to her mum, who helped her to understand the abusive nature of her partner's behaviours.

Participant accounts demonstrate that women are more likely to confide in their friends and family before disclosing abuse to professionals, and this is reflective of similar domestic abuse research as identified in the earlier literature review. It also suggests that health professionals have a role in facilitating support for women, whether that is directly to specialist support services, or to the same services but via their social

networks (Shucan-Bird *et al*, 2022). Despite such aspirations, there is little research evidence of these interventions in practice. Furthermore, it is argued by Finneran (2021) that both informal and formal supports available to women are often ineffective due to gaps in understanding about the complexity of domestic abuse, resulting in misconceptions about who is affected, and how it presents. If awareness was raised about domestic abuse, Health Visitors and Midwives could have a powerful role in encouraging women to share their circumstances with friends and family members, being confident that they will disclose, receive support and reach specialist services in a timely manner.

The characteristics describing the positive relationship between the participants and health professionals have been illustrated in Section 8.5.1, however, it is evident that these qualities mirror those that women value in their friendships. Although professional relationships differ from friendships in their role and function, it is notable that women appear to expect and value the same support from both formal and informal supports. Professional support will potentially differ in frequency, and operate within professional and regulatory boundaries, however both have the opportunity to buffer against the impacts of living in abusive situations (Finneran, 2021).

Although participants did not often disclose abuse to health professionals, they could talk openly to their Health Visitor or Midwife about other matters, therefore, it is possible that the professional relationship could have been as protective to the women as a friendship is thought to be. Additionally, if we are confident that informal supports bring benefits to women experiencing abuse, there are opportunities to be had in promoting disclosure in this way. That is, health professionals such as Health Visitors and Midwives are well placed to promote the potential value to women from seeking support from friends and family members.

9.2.4.6 Complexities of abuse disclosures and relationships

Interview narratives highlighted that there are a variety of complexities relating to reasons why women choose to disclose or not to disclose abuse. Women in this study disclosed abuse in response to certain factors aligning at a point in time: women were influenced by personal thresholds and triggers, such as child abuse, increasing severity or escalation. Additionally, the presence of others during an incident and the

presence of a trusted person were often precursors to reporting abuse as has been illustrated in Figure 15:

Figure 15 – Disclosure of abuse by study participants

The interplay between these factors is not always clearly articulated within existing research. Women’s Aid (2023) Change that lasts model (Appendix 22), goes some way to identifying factors required to provide an effective response to women experiencing abuse, illustrating the importance of trusted professionals and specialist services in providing support to women. The model also emphasises the value of community based responses including safe enquiry, increased awareness and a culture that supports women to be believed, and where abuse is unacceptable. The model in Figure 16 has been developed in response to the study findings, and provides an explanation and insight which informs the study aim. The model highlights the interplay of factors that can promote disclosure of abuse and provide early intervention and support to women and their families.

When considering the research aim and study objectives, the findings suggest that the presence of supportive relationships with health professionals, using effective enquiry or screening by using creative and purposeful opportunities to ask women about abuse, can be successful in promoting a disclosure of abuse. However this needs to occur in a context that works to raise awareness of non-physical forms of abuse, for example coercive control and financial abuse. An increased awareness of emotional abuse and other forms of non-violent abuse by health professionals and women alike,

alongside routine or sensitive enquiry, is likely to have a positive impact on early help-seeking and disclosures, but only when trusting relationships exist. Study findings suggest, that where trust is not present, disclosure is unlikely to take place, even where routine and sensitive enquiry, and awareness of emotional abuse are evident. Where trusting relationships between women and health professionals do exist, and where both have a good understanding of all types of abuse, it remains unlikely that women will disclose abuse without being asked about it directly. There are plentiful examples in the study whereby women had good relationships with their Health Visitors or Midwives, but still failed to tell them about any kind of abuse, even where this was violent and injurious. Therefore, it can be determined that where all 3 components are present, as shown in Figure 16, there is increased opportunity for women to disclose abuse, without fear of stigma or women-blaming attitudes, which is likely to result in fewer crisis situations being the trigger for help-seeking. However for these impacts to be maximised and sustained across all sectors of society, structural and cultural changes are required to move societal attitudes to those that do not accept domestic abuse and are reflective of gender stereotypes and patriarchal attitudes that influence community and society responses. This study offers a comprehensive understanding of women's abuse disclosures that is not well documented in existing research.

Figure 16 - Domestic abuse disclosure model

9.3 Emotional abuse

Emotional abuse is considered as harmful as physical abuse, and is often demonstrated by mind or mental manipulating strategies, aimed to control and threaten, and can include psychological and financial abuse, intimidation, gas-lighting, stalking, alienation from friends and family, destruction of property, all which results in women becoming socially isolated women, and their mental health being negatively impacted (Stark, 2007; Burman and Brooks-Hay, 2019; Sweet, 2019). As identified in existing research, findings from this study strongly indicate that emotional abuse was always present across all participants in this study, either in isolation, or alongside other types of domestic abuse. In response to Stark's work (2007), there is an argument that coercive control is being reflected as a modern conceptualisation of domestic abuse, which was previously overlooked, particularly in the justice system (Burman and Brooks-Hay, 2019), and has been influential in policy developments in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2018).

9.3.1 Emotionally abusive behaviours

Participants in the study described various examples of abuse. Figures 9 and 10, in Chapter 8, highlight the descriptions of the extensive emotionally abusive behaviours demonstrated by partners of the participants in the study. Gas-lighting is a newly termed phenomenon, and therefore present in more recent domestic abuse studies, and a central feature of domestic abuse, described by participants a strategy used by abusers to manipulate the realities of their partners (The National Domestic Violence Hotline, 2020). It is mostly described as a strategy used by men against female partners due to the idea that women lack the cultural, economic and political capital to use this strategy in the same way against men (Sweet, 2019). Sweet (2019) suggests that gas lighting is a feature of emotional abuse that is embedded in social inequalities and gendered stereotypes, and is used to systematically unbalance the realities of women by building a narrative where they believe they are crazy and unstable. Feminists would agree that such gendered labels sustain the view that women are over-emotional and unreasonable, as this view has been supported by the gendered systems of medicine and law institutions for many generations, as a strategy to maintain the superior position of men (Douglas, 2012). Gas-lighting and similar forms

of emotional abuse were described by all participants, including controlling, threatening behaviours often using their role as mother to manipulate and de-stabilise their realities.

9.3.2 Men's attendance at health appointments

Men's involvement in the antenatal, childbirth and postnatal period is strongly recommended (WHO, 2015; Scottish Government, 2017), due to the belief that men's inclusion in maternal and peri-natal health is associated with improved outcomes for both maternal and child health (Asefa, Geleto and Dessie, 2014). Including men in decision-making relating to maternal health is thought to be a valuable strategy to educate men regarding the importance of health care during pregnancy and the postnatal period, as well as addressing their own sexual and reproductive health (Forbes *et al*, 2018). Family centred care, and involvement of partners is also advocated as part of Best Start plan for maternity care in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2017).

In this study, many of the participants' partners frequently attended health appointments with them during or after pregnancy, and although this is recommended for promotion of maternal and child health, it does restrict the opportunity to ask about domestic abuse or speak freely and openly about aspects of their relationship:

"I couldn't say because he was always in the room, if I had meetings or appointments he would always be there so I couldn't say anything" (Ruby)

Where participants were accompanied to appointments, there were only two examples of health professionals making efforts to use creative methods to ask about domestic abuse in private away from their partner. *Tina* describes the actions of one of her Midwives:

"I went for a scan and a nurse came out and said I want to take your height and weight, and he stood up and she said no, it's only round here, I'll take her, I won't be a minute, and she said I need to ask you if your family, your home is safe, are you safe, is the baby going to be safe, and do you need any help" (Tina)

It is not uncommon for partners to be present at maternity appointments, or to be present at home visits in the initial weeks following the birth of a new baby, and there should be caution in assuming that abuse is present for all women in the perinatal period. However, this does present difficulties for health professionals when enquiring about domestic abuse and requires routine enquiry to be revisited over time to ensure opportunities are created where women can disclose if desired. The attendance of male partners at health appointments with participants was identified in Section 9.2.2.5 as a barrier to disclosing abuse, and is apparent as a controlling strategy in existing research, as identified in Chapter 4. Matricentric feminist theories of O'Reilly (2019) would suggest that being pregnant offers further opportunity to abusive male partners to control aspects of maternity care, to ensure male dominated views are heard, and to reduce opportunity for women to exercise their own agency and autonomy over their bodies.

9.3.3 Abuse and reproductive health

Reproductive abuse is a deliberate attempt to control a woman's reproductive choices, most often by a male perpetrator, and may or may not accompany other forms of domestic abuse (Tarzia and Hegarty, 2021). However, it is a woman's human right to have control over decisions about her reproductive health, including to become pregnant, or to continue or end a pregnancy (WHO, 2015). Reproductive abuse can include but is not limited to sabotage of birth control methods, for example, removing condoms; pregnancy coercion, for example pressuring or promoting pregnancy that is not desired by the woman; and controlling the outcome of pregnancy, for example, not allowing access to terminations (Srinivasan *et al*, 2020). Health Visitors and Midwives are connected to women during pregnancy, and therefore have opportunity to explore issues pertaining to conception, and women's feelings about their pregnancies.

Reproductive abuse is an area of domestic abuse that has not been well explored and is poorly understood; current research into this area mostly exists within US or low-income country contexts (Nicolajski *et al*, 2015; Cleeve, 2017). The involvement of abusive partners in decision-making relating to pregnancy and the perinatal period provides an opportunity for manipulation and control. Bagwell-Grey, Messing and Baldwin-White (2015) suggest reproductive coercion and control over reproductive decision-making are associated with various negative health outcomes, and often

occurs concurrently with domestic abuse. This study provides further evidence of controlling behaviours relating to reproductive health, and were reported by four participants. *Lynda* describes different types of reproductive coercion experienced in two separate abusive relationships:

“he wanted me to have a termination and I didn’t want to, so that’s when it got really, really, violent and I ended up having to go to hospital because he slammed my fingers in the car door and tried to drag me into the car to go to the termination clinic” (Lynda)

“I had (child) a year later, and I was getting pregnant again and again, I wanted children but I also wanted a life, and I couldn’t have that because I was always pregnant....he believed a women’s place was at home, and women shouldn’t have careers” (Lynda)

Lynda’s view was that this was a deliberate attempt to express male dominance in the home, and supported the structural gender roles of men which remove power from women (Mandel and Paul, 2020). *Lynda’s* view reflects the underpinning Matricentric Feminist theory for this study, which supports addressing the patriarchal attitudes of *Lynda’s* partner, who believed that women were responsible for producing children, child rearing, and domestic duties, restricting women’s freedom to control their own sexuality and reproductive function (Mandel and Paul, 2020). This patriarchal view highlights the role expectations of women reflected in various cultures, where she does what is expected of her, which is also assuming and fulfilling her position as a subordinate within the relationship and in the hierarchy of power (Mshweshwe, 2020). This also supports the Matricentric Feminist theories of O’Reilly (2019) and intersectionality theory (Crenshaw, 1991), who propose that women become marginalised further in their roles as mothers. *Lynda’s* experiences illustrate how women’s gender intersects with their roles as mothers and childbearing capacity, and creates opportunity for them to become further marginalised even before they become mothers, when they are carrying unborn children.

Reproductive control and coercion are linked to restriction of personal autonomy and sexual and reproductive freedom (Grace and Anderson, 2016), and were relevant to

two other participants who both described instances whereby their partners attempted to pressurise them into terminating or continuing with pregnancies. Findings from this study demonstrate that pregnancy and childbirth create opportunity for perpetrators of abuse to inflict control and harm over their partners, which in turn has the opposite effect from the policy ambitions of the World Health Organisation and the Scottish Government (2017) via Best Start, to promote maternal and child health and choice (Rowlands and Walker, 2019). It also means that health professionals working with women in the perinatal period are required to be vigilant and demonstrate professional curiosity to their circumstances, being cognisant of the increased risks during this period.

9.3.4 Women's awareness of emotional abuse

As discussed in Section 9.2.2.6 it was notable that most of the participants in the study had little awareness that the behaviours of their partners were emotionally abusive. This reflects what is currently understood about domestic abuse and is apparent across existing research (Prosman, Wong and Lagro-Janssen, 2013; Evans and Feder, 2014). This was an overwhelming feeling across participants, that because of their own experiences in relationships, or in their own family, that they did not recognise abusive behaviours in an intimate relationship. This conflicts with findings from a recent Scottish study by the Young Women's Movement and Women's Aid (2022) which states that young women have a good understanding of health and unhealthy relationships, although this learning did not take place at school.

As discussed earlier in this chapter, the lack of recognition of emotionally abusive behaviours prevented participants from disclosing abuse when asked by health professionals. For participants who were not asked about domestic abuse by health professionals, they stated that should they have been asked, they would have been unlikely to disclose due to their beliefs that their partner's behaviours were normal, and perceptions that they were not experiencing domestic abuse. This view is unsurprising, when considering work by Sims (2008) who alleged that emotional abuse is often overlooked and excluded from discussions about domestic abuse, which typically favour physically violent behaviours. However, this view is perhaps outdated, considering the progress made to understand that emotional abuse is a construct of abuse separate to one that involves physical violence (Karakurt and Silver, 2013).

Additionally, Karakurt and Silver (2013) claim that some of the typical traits of emotional abuse can be subtle, which could also account for why they might often go unrecognised, however it is accepted that health professionals should be adept at identifying all types of abuse including emotional abuse.

O'Leary (2008) claimed the idea of emotional abuse as a separate abusive entity was emerging over two decades ago, therefore, a dichotomy exists between an early notion that emotional abuse is a well-established phenomenon, and the lived experiences of participants in this study who divulged that they had little awareness of the emotional abuse they were experiencing. Likewise, Women's Aid (2023) confirms that there are current misconceptions about some types of abuse, and a belief still exists that domestic abuse is only ever violent and physical, despite the impacts of emotional abuse being as harmful.

This reflects the narratives from participants in the study and brings doubts to evidence that suggests emotional abuse is a well-known form of abuse that is easily recognisable. Considering what is already known about the damaging impacts of emotional abuse, and the lack of awareness that still appears to be prevalent among the study participants, health professionals such as Midwives, Health Visitors and GPs have a significant potential role to play in informing women of the types of domestic abuse and recognising the signs and symptoms of abuse to support women to seek early help and prevent abuse where possible. The Young Women's Movement and Women's Aid (2022) suggest young women are not informed about domestic abuse at school, therefore further exploration is required to identify whether healthy relationships and domestic abuse are present within curricula, and to determine the quality of information provided to young people, and awareness raising potential.

9.4 Physical abuse

Eight out of nine study participants in the study had experienced physical abuse in at least one of their intimate relationships; the figure below describes the physical abuse sustained by participants:

Rape	Bitten to face & ear	Strangled	Left finger marks on my neck
Sexual assault	Punched in face	Thrown downstairs	Black eyes
Kicked in stomach while pregnant	Pushed down and strangled	Hit and kicked	Pushed and fell onto toys
Thrown outside in the night	head-butted	Pushed onto pregnant belly	Slammed fingers in car door

Figure 17 - Descriptions of physical abuse sustained by study participants.

In all these cases, emotional abuse was experienced alongside physical abuse. All eight participants experiencing physical abuse reported ongoing abuse which was always part of a pattern. This conflicts with the narrative often represented in media accounts that portray domestic abuse as isolated incidents (Easteal, Holland and Judd, 2015).

Physical abuse experienced by participants was often severe and sustained, and in all cases, where assaults occurred without the presence of others, it was never reported or disclosed to a health professional, regardless of severity or the injuries sustained. This reflects similar research, and supports findings from the earlier review of literature. Of those participants who had experienced physical assault by their partner, four were assaulted in the presence of their children, as illustrated in Figure 18, suggesting the presence of children is not a deterrent by perpetrators, nor does it initiate a disclosure to professionals. This is not a phenomenon that is widely studied within existing literature.

Participant 1	Child in bed at time of assault; Assaulted during pregnancy
Participant 2	Assaulted while pregnant, witnessed by others
Participant 3	Assaulted various times, both in the presence and absence of children
Participant 4	Assaulted in presence of child and others
Participant 5	Assaulted in presence of child
Participant 6	Child not present during assault
Participant 7	Assaulted in presence of child
Participant 8	Child not present

Figure 18 – Presence of children in physical assaults

Three participants in this study experienced physical abuse during pregnancy; this is discussed in Section 9.8.1

9.5 Child abuse

As discussed earlier in the chapter, two participants in the study disclosed abuse due to their concerns about their partner’s behaviour towards their children, and two participants had children who were subjected to physical abuse by their fathers. *Cathy’s* child was present during a physical assault, and was at risk of being harmed during this incident. Other participants had children who were present during abusive episodes, and it is therefore suggested that they were subject to emotionally abusive circumstances as a result of their parent’s behaviours (James, 2020). The impacts of domestic abuse on children are documented by James (2020) and Flood and Wilkinson (2022) and have been discussed in Chapter 2, and these impacts have led to children being recognised as victims of abuse in their own right in domestic abuse legislation. Findings from this study echo similar research findings, indicating that children are a key motivator for women seeking help when experiencing domestic abuse.

9.5.1 Child contact arrangements

Child contact in a post-separation context is out with the scope of this thesis to be addressed in detail, however it is acknowledged by Katz, Nikupeteri and Laitinen (2020) that domestic abuse rarely ceases when a relationship ends and it is common for abuse to continue or escalate during this period, often using child contact arrangements as a vehicle to perpetrate further abuse and continuing to exert power over women (Katz, Nikupeteri and Laitinen, 2020). Almost all the participants in the

study (eight out of nine) had continued to experience abuse in the post-separation period, and during child contact arrangements. *Ruby* describes efforts of her abusive partner in the post-separation period to continue the abuse:

“He wanted to see him, and he contacted my other child’s Dad, he’s not had contact in nearly 8 years and told him you need to take him off me, so they started panicking, and phoning Social Work” (Ruby)

This example by *Ruby* demonstrates her partner’s efforts to emotionally abuse and manipulate her after the relationship had ended, resulting in him trying to seek custody and requesting social work involvement, knowing this would cause her distress. Again this is an example of men using women’s roles as mothers as a strategy to undermine and abuse, as described by O’Reilly (2019) in her Matricentric Feminist theory.

Participant experiences varied from abuse via social media, verbal abuse, to stalking and harassment, and threats to kill, and other extreme measures used to control where the family lived and where contact took place. *Georgina* continued to be controlled by her ex-partner, who was able to manipulate where child contact took place, resulting in her having to leave her support network to comply with the arrangements. *Georgina* and *Tina* continued to experience abuse by their ex-partners via the court system, as they were required to engage with legal proceedings to agree child contact arrangements. Both women described this as a strategy used by their abusers to maintain power and control over them and their children, and this has often shown to be successful due to a lack of institutional understanding of domestic abuse (Gilantai, Ligeti and Wirth, 2019). Health Visitors and Midwives are commonly involved in multi-agency planning for children and young people, alongside social work colleagues. Therefore, they should have the knowledge and skills to recognise the potential for escalation in the post separation period and the potential impact on children and young people during period of contact.

9.6 Sexual violence and abuse

It is no longer accepted that domestic abuse and sexual violence are committed by a small number of deviant perpetrators, but instead are common occurrences affecting

large proportions of the population in the UK and globally (Hamby, 2014). Intimate partner sexual abuse and violence frequently co-occurs with domestic abuse (Bagwell-Gray, Messing and Baldwin-White, 2015), and participant narratives in this study highlight that this association exists. Of the eight participants who sustained significant physical injury from their partners, three had also sustained violent sexual assault including rape, and in no instances did violent sexual assault occur without physical abuse. It was common among the participants to speak about sexual violence and abuse towards the end of the interviews. I assumed this was due to the developing relationship between them and I, whereby trust had developed and they felt safe to disclose experiences that were especially sensitive. This example evidenced how my presence and role in Heideggerian interviews supported collection of rich data, that otherwise might not have been retrieved by using alternative methodologies.

It is estimated that 798,000 women are raped or sexually assaulted each year equating to one in 30 (Rape Crisis, 2023). The feature of violence alongside sexual assault is important to recognise, as two other participants in the study reported non-violent sexual assault, for example consensual and non-consensual, coercive sexual activity, and these instances existed in a context of other non-physical examples of abuse, for example emotional and financial abuse.

In two of the three participants' narratives, violent sexual assault occurred with partners who were significantly older than the participant. Where sexual assault was reported as non-violent, there was a notable age gap in one of the two reported cases. Similarly, there was no significant age difference between women and perpetrators of physical abuse that occurred without sexual assault. This suggests that there is meaning in age and power dynamics of a relationship where violent sexual assault takes place, however there is little available research to confirm or help explain any possible significance, and further exploration would be valuable.

Karen described non-consensual sexual activity during her relationship:

“During the pregnancy I was sore, and tired, and I would wake up, and he was trying me basically, and I messaged my friend saying he’s just done this, and I woke up to him doing this..and I confronted him...I’m carrying your child, I’m

sore, totally understandable you should be respectful to my feelings, and it sort of continued, like several times” (Karen)

Mandy also described being raped by her partner:

“I’d seen a scene in Emmerdale, it was a husband and wife and he forced her to have sex. I watched that and I spoke to mum and said that’s what happened to me last weekend. I wanted to and we did, but halfway through I was like no, but he didn’t stop, and I thought well, he’s my boyfriend its fine, but then when that came on I thought that’s not normal” (Mandy)

Neither *Karen* nor *Mandy* described these incidents as violent, despite their non-consensual nature. The experiences of both *Karen* and *Mandy* are similar in that the women involved did not initially believe these acts were abusive, and stated they did not have a good understanding of what was normal, acceptable behaviour within an intimate relationship until intervention from external influences. This reflects findings from literature, that suggest women are more likely to report rape where there are situational characteristics that suggest she has been a victim of crime, for example rape being committed by a stranger through force and causing injury (McGregor *et al*, 2000; Menard, 2005). It appears therefore that there are roles for several health and social care professionals, as well as other professionals, e.g. Police, to sufficiently advising and informing women of the nature of abuse, and in particular the behaviours expected within healthy relationships, to successfully promote abuse disclosures.

Rape is not often defined as rape by victims due to it occurring within an intimate relationship, despite professionals being able to identify it as such (Bagwell-Grey, Messing and Baldwin-White, 2015). Similarly, it is also suggested by Bagwell-Grey, Messing and Baldwin-White, (2015) that definitions of sexual abuse are inconsistently applied, challenged further by misinformation and myths regarding rape, particularly when this occurs between partners who have previously been engaged in consensual sexual activity. Inconsistencies like this account for *Mandy’s* experiences in the study, who did not initially define her experience as rape due to it occurring within an existing relationship.

Fisher *et al* (2003) reported that 43% of rape victims did not report their experiences to the Police as they were not sure if a crime had been committed. More recent figures from Rape Crisis (2023) suggest that one in two rapes against women are committed by a partner or ex-partner, and five in six rapes are not reported. Reasons for not reporting do not cite women's understanding about whether this constituted a crime, but instead cited embarrassment and humiliation, and not thinking the Police could help. This continues to highlight why reporting figures have remained poor over the last two decades.

Katz, Moore and May (2008) argue that physical and sexual abuse that co-occur in intimate relationships offer a distinct form of victimisation which is traditionally difficult to define and measure, due to differences in language for example rape, forced sex, sexual coercion. Bagwell-Grey, Messing and Baldwin-White (2015) claim that these ambiguities remain prevalent, however cite the Centre for Disease Control and Preventions (CDCP) (2021) who provide 4 characteristics of sexual violence outlined in Figure 19:

Figure 19 - Characteristics of sexual violence (CDCP, 2021)

Karen described sexual assault while asleep, and not using force, however this was an invasive, unwanted sexual act without consent and is suggested by Jejeebhoy and Bott (2003) this is experienced commonly by women and girls, largely due to gender-based double standards. Sexual coercion as a non-physical form of sexual violence was described by *Abbie*, who was forced non-physically, and participated in acts that although were consenting, she described as 'rough' and felt unable to stop. It is

argued that these behaviours are emotionally abusive, even without force and invasiveness, as she described her partner using control and dominating behaviours to keep her in a subservient position, and which will likely have long term psychological impacts (Black et al, 2011; Bagwell-Grey, Messing and Baldwin-White, 2015). These behaviours commonly occur where gender roles are enforced, and where there are associations of masculinity and dominance; these roles increase vulnerability for women and girls and require challenge at an individual as well as societal level (Jejeebhoy and Bott, 2003). Non violent, coercive sexual abuse is an area of domestic abuse that has received less attention in literature, and subsequently is likely to contribute to women's lack of knowledge and understanding, resulting in this rarely being discussed by female victims. It is therefore unsurprising that it is difficult for women to determine between sexual assault and sexual coercion when committed by an intimate partner (CDCP, 2022). Equally, while women are encouraged to define their own experiences, a challenging dichotomy exists when these conflict with defined terms regarding sexual violence and abuse, which is perhaps unsurprising when volumes of misinformation still exist, and the law criminalising rape within marriage was only introduced in recent decades (Bagwell-Grey, Messing and Baldwin-White, 2015).

9.6.1 Rape myths

The widespread nature of inaccurate perceptions or myths, regarding rape and sexual assault, alongside stereotyped beliefs and gender roles has concerning implications (Jenkins, 2017). The following rape myths (Figure 20) provide some explanation behind the participant narratives in this study, and account for the absence of disclosure to health professionals:

Figure 20 – Rape myths (Jenkins, 2017)

Rape Crisis (2023) proposes that these myths have created a rape culture in the UK which accounts for the widespread nature of sexual violence and abuse against women and girls. This culture is grounded in an inadequate criminal justice system whereby perpetrators are rarely punished, within a society that makes excuses for perpetrators, victims are rarely believed, and specialist support is difficult to obtain (Leverick, 2020). *Karen* held the belief that ‘*men have needs*’, which provides a modern example of how myths are still widely evident, and how patriarchy is pervasive and continues to control women, by ensuring they are subordinate to men (Rich, 2019). While these myths exist, it becomes challenging for women to disclose abuse, and also difficult for health professionals to facilitate conversations that aims to dispel such myths, when so widespread and ingrained into modern culture.

Kelly (1988) proposes that women are the only marginalised group expected to reside within intimate relationships, with partners who have power over them. Additionally, as discussed in Chapter 6, feminist theory suggests women are expected to respect and love their partners in their role as subordinates (Rich, 1981; Kelly, 1988). Male social roles add to this problem, as men are attributed to various roles, for example, husband, boss, which have associations with authority and power, and this is further exacerbated when gender roles are added to influence power dynamics behind domestic and sexual abuse, which gives men power to initiate and expect sexual contact (Kelly, 1988).

9.7 Familial violence and abuse

As well as experiencing abuse from their partners, three participants also experienced violence and abuse from members of their family, or their partner's family. Abuse from an abusive partner's family is not an area that has received much attention in literature, however *Ruby* described verbal aggression and threats, and damage to property by her partner's family in the post-separation period, who were also complicit in stealing money and belongings:

"He didn't take it great, and neither did his family. They ended up smashing all my belongings, my glasses that I'd left, I had to go get new glasses, all my clothes were ripped" (*Ruby*)

Engel (2002, p13) states that property damage represents emotional abuse that is "symbolic violence" that impacts on psychological, social and economic wellbeing. *Tina* had multiple adverse childhood experiences, including experiencing abuse and neglect herself as a child. She described sustaining ongoing physical assaults and emotional abuse from her father into adulthood:

"when I was 19, I got pregnant, my Dad found out and kicked the shit out of me and said get rid of it or we're done, so I had an abortion, mine and my Dads relationship is really volatile" (*Tina*)

In more recent years, *Tina's* Father resorted to emotional abuse to control *Tina*:

"I told my Dad I was moving in with (partner) he said he was OK with it, then my sister phoned me to say he'd taken an overdose, and drank 3 bottles of vodka and taken loads of pills, then when we went to see him, and he laughed, he said you're all here now, I need you here, so he'd done it for attention. He did that twice, 'cause he didn't want me to go. He did it again not long after" (*Tina*)

These examples from *Tina* confirms the association between abuse as a child and domestic abuse, and that multiple forms of trauma can have cumulative effects

(Shields, 2020). *Karen and Ruby* both recalled experiencing verbal abuse from her partner's parents at the end of their relationship. The partner of *Mandy* also threatened violence against her family as a means of retaliation once the relationship had ended. The familial nature of abuse within the participant sample and cumulative effects can only be presumed to impact on the willingness of women to disclose abuse, particularly when abuse has been entrenched in their lives from an early age. Exploring ACEs with mothers would be one strategy to understand lived experiences, to enable Health Visitors, Midwives and GP, and other health professionals supporting women, to facilitate supportive conversations and provide appropriate responses.

9.8 Escalation of abuse

The National Domestic Violence Hotline (2020) states that abuse almost always escalates, in either a gradual or sudden manner, as an emboldened means of controlling and trapping a survivor. Critical timeframes where escalation of abuse is apparent are following the end of the relationship, and during pregnancy, or in the perinatal period. Additionally, and since the Coronavirus pandemic, abuse is also thought to escalate during or following large scale disasters or crises (New Zealand Family Violence Clearinghouse [NZFVC], 2020). Although not immediately apparent to participants in the study, patterns of escalation during pregnancy, the pandemic, and after relationships ended, did begin to be acknowledged during the interviews.

Escalation can be defined as a pattern of abuse that becomes more frequent and/or severe over time, however can be considered as an outcome, and not always accompanied by increasing severity or frequency, for example intimate partner homicide, or choking/throttling (Boxall and Lawler, 2021). Boxall and Lawler (2021) propose that the nature of abuse escalation, its definitions and prevalence remains ambiguous, and they suggest that escalation of abuse does not apply to all abusive relationships, but instead is a characteristic of serious or prolific perpetrators.

This lack of certainty around the presence of escalation is important when risk assessment is undertaken by professionals from health, social work or Police. Although the presence of escalation is part of the DASH Risk Checklist (*SafeLives*, 2014), Robinson, Pinchevesky and Guthrie (2018) suggest that escalating behaviours

can often be overlooked in favour of other factors that are prioritised when assessing risk, potentially compromising any safety plans. Health Visitors and Midwives, as well as other health and social care professionals therefore have roles in ensuring escalation is given adequate consideration in safety planning. Participants in this study did not discuss the use of domestic abuse risk assessments, or being referred to multi-agency risk assessment forums; although this does not necessarily mean this did not happen, it reinforces safety planning in relation to escalation may be lacking and worthy of further scrutiny and improvement. Despite the lack of clarity around the escalation of abuse in intimate relationships, escalation remains a dimension of abuse that is central to decision-making processes, and a consensus has been reached in determining key risk factors associated with specific times, events or places (Bushway and Tahamont, 2016; Boxall and Lawler, 2021), which are seen below:

Figure 21 – Risk factors associated with the escalation of domestic abuse (Roberts *et al*, 2011; Parkinson and Zara, 2013; Morgan and Boxhall, 2020).

9.8.1 Escalation during pregnancy and perinatal period

As well as the post-separation period, pregnancy and perinatal period are also examples of specific events within a relationship that might result in an escalation of abuse, or commencement of abuse (Peacock *et al*, 2023). Within the study Zoe and Lynda who were pregnant at the time of experiencing abuse, described being physically assaulted, with partners often targeting their unborn baby and their abdomen. Zoe described the physical abuse continuing during pregnancy, with no specific change in pattern:

“there was one time he strangled me and pinned me to the bed, and I was pregnant, I just cried, and then tried to shake it off” (Zoe)

“He was so violent I nearly lost the baby he just used to kick me in the stomach” (Lynda)

Other partners who were not physically abusive, escalated their emotionally controlling behaviours during this period:

“he was more controlling it was awful, that’s when I remember it getting worse, he pushed me with so much force, I fell on the floor onto my belly and I was terrified” (Cathy)

There was no evidence of partners reducing their physical abuse in the presence of a new or unborn baby, which supports the idea that routine enquiry should be offered consistently during perinatal periods. Participants perceived incidents of physical abuse during pregnancy to be deliberate attacks on their bodies and their unborn babies. However, without the insights of perpetrator behaviours, it is unclear whether experiences of physical abuse during this time were attacks directly to harm the unborn baby, or to create fear and hurt to the woman. Finnbogadóttir *et al* (2014) suggests that women experiencing physical abuse during pregnancy are more likely to remain in the relationship to protect the unborn baby. Participants did not report this explicitly, however also did not suggest anything to the contrary and this was not identified as a precursor to leaving.

Participants’ experiences reflect what is currently known in existing research regarding the escalation or starting of abuse during pregnancy and the perinatal period, and highlights women’s vulnerability during this time (Mazza *et al*, 2021). Findings from this, and existing studies suggests that pregnancy is not a protective characteristic for women experiencing domestic abuse, with WHO estimating approximately 4-12% of women being subject to physical violence during pregnancy (Garcia Moreno, 2005). However, a more recent study suggests only 2.5% of women reported physical abuse compared to 14.9% who reported psychological abuse (Van Parys, *et al*, 2014). This echoes findings from this study whereby participants were not forthcoming about the abuse they were experiencing during pregnancy; in fact, *Cathy* describes crying

following a violent attack, with feelings of guilt, as she was too scared to seek medical or maternity advice following the incident:

“I was terrified, and I lay in bed all day crying ‘cause I was worried, but I was more worried to go to the hospital to get checked ‘cause I felt what would they say to me – he’s drummed it into my head that if anything happens, he said they’ll see us as unfit parents and you’ll have the baby taken from you” (Cathy)

It is therefore possible that although prevalence of abuse during pregnancy and the perinatal period might be elevated, fewer women disclose during this time, when compared with at other times in their lives, and therefore requires more proactive and attuned responses and screening from maternity, health visiting and GP services (Tavoli *et al*, 2016).

Domestic abuse has a significant adverse impact on both maternal and fetal health (Finnbogadóttir *et al*, 2014), as discussed in Section 2.4, and it is suggested by Garcia Moreno (2005) that most abuse towards unborn babies is perpetrated by the biological father. Similar findings are reflected in this study, whereby biological fathers are the primary perpetrators. It is suggested by Finnbogadóttir *et al* (2014) that the father’s aggression is partly due to jealousy and disrespect towards the growing baby, and like in this study, Finnbogadóttir *et al* (2014) found physical and sexual violence were synonymous with pregnancy. All three participants in this study who experienced violence during pregnancy were primiparous; and two were under 25 years old. The younger participants (under 25 years) were pregnant to partners who were considerably older than themselves. Health professionals in contact with women during these periods therefore are ideally placed to be exploring relationships with women, and identifying changes in behaviours that might indicate domestic abuse escalating.

9.8.2 Escalation in post-separation period

The lived experiences of participants in this study described escalation of abuse that reflect the factors in Figure 21, particularly those relationship related factors. As well as abuse continuing in the post-separation period, participants described an escalation also at this time. *Ruby* described receiving threats to kill her over social media, and

Cathy's partner's behaviour also escalated significantly during this time, which was a trigger for her disclosing the abuse. *Georgina* also described her partner's behaviour escalating once she had ended their relationship. Although this did not result in an escalation of physical abuse, it heightened his efforts to control her movements and prevent her finding employment by removing her immigration documents, including visa to work. *Mandy* experienced an escalation of physical abuse including rape when the abusive relationship ended. *Zoe* also experienced an escalation of her partner's behaviours following separation, for example reckless driving. He had offered to take her and the children home following contact, and used this opportunity to scare and control her following separation. Reckless driving is considered to be emotional abuse, like throwing or kicking objects, shaking a fist, as it represents physical violence and causes psychological harm to victims (Karakurt and Silver, 2013; Marshall, 1996).

Although the post-separation period is a time when the risk of further abuse or escalation is heightened, it offers an opportunity for women to make disclosures about the abuse they have experienced and seek help and support for themselves and their children (Jaffe *et al*, 2015). However, this period presents particular risks to women and their children, often triggered by conflict and disputes relating to custody and contact, and can result, in the extreme, in domestic homicide and retaliating filicide and familicide, whereby a child or family member respectively, are deliberately killed to cause suffering of the other parent (Ewing, 1997; Jaffe, Wolf and Campbell, 2012). Jaffe *et al* (2015) name a variety of risk factors that predetermine harm to children in the post-separation period, including but not limited to:

Figure 22 – Risk factors that predetermine harm to children in the post-separation period (Jaffe, 2015)

This study did not fully explore perpetrator characteristics, however Jaffe's (2015) model does broadly reflect experiences of participants in this study, and suggests that where previous abuse, alcohol use and access to firearms existed, this presented a greater risk to a child in the family. Increasing the knowledge and skills of Midwives, Health Visitors and GPs, would increase their confidence to be professionally curious, and identify where women might be living with these circumstances, and support them to create conditions for supportive conversations about abuse to take place.

Ornstein and Rickne (2013) also suggest that stalking and harassment are frequently experienced by women in the post-separation period, and these behaviours can be partially predicted based on various confounding variables, such as emotionally manipulative and controlling behaviours, for example, preventing access to work, family and friends, damage to property and belongings, threats to harm children, threats to harm himself, verbal aggression, jealousy, disparaging comments and put-downs. This same study also found that the presence of children in a relationship increases the risk of stalking and physical assault. Similarly, there is an association between substance misuse and stalking in the post-separation period (Ornstein and Rickne, 2013). Although none of the study participants described their partner's behaviours as 'stalking', *Lynda* and *Zoe* did describe instances whereby partners

would turn up unexpectedly at work and school in the post-separation period in an attempt to either communicate with them, see them or the children. *Lynda* describes patterns of behaviours from her ex-partner and the impact it had on her:

“he’s making my life hell, he’s turning up at school, outside my home, outside work... I’m exhausted trying to keep us away from this man”

All women in this study experienced emotional abuse that was categorised by various manipulative and controlling behaviours as described by Ornstein and Rickne (2013). As they all had children within an abusive relationship, it is also proposed that experiencing continuing or escalating abuse following the end of the relationship could in part have been predicted. Therefore by working closely with women, building relationships, and understanding their lives and the trajectory of their relationships, could support health professionals to recognise periods where escalation might occur, instigate open dialogue, and provide earlier help.

9.9 Financial abuse

Financial or economic abuse, more often associated with elder abuse, is typified by the disruption of women’s access to their finances and other assets (Sharp-Jeffs, 2021). Five of the participants experienced widespread financial abuse, examples consisting of:

Figure 23: Examples of financial abuse experienced by study participants.

Figure 23 illustrates the variety of ways in which financial abuse was experienced by the study participants, demonstrating that financial abuse is widespread, and reflecting current research in this area research (Antai *et al*, 2014; Postmus *et al* 2018). Financial abuse is the deliberate control of finances, where the ability to acquire and use financial resources are obstructed by an intimate partner, and where they have no decision-making powers (Postmus *et al*, 2012; Postmus *et al*, 2018). Financial abuse is often difficult to recognise, and often only identified retrospectively, and this was the case for several of the participants. Smallwood (2015) suggests this kind of abuse is subtle and embedded within gender roles and social expectations around money, as discussed by feminist theories in Chapter 6, Section 6.3.

It is reported that prevalence of financial abuse is similar to that of other forms of abuse, and due to women’s marginalised position in society, being more prone to poverty than men, this type of abuse is particularly harmful to them (Cannie, 2022). The participants in this study were mostly new mothers at the time of experiencing abuse, dependent on child benefits and not in employment by nature of the age of

their children. Male perpetration of abuse targets women's vulnerabilities in this post-natal period to ensure they remain marginalised and lacking in power and agency (O'Reilly, 2019).

In many instances in this study there appeared to be little recognition of the harmful impact of financial abuse on the children in the family, and this appears to also be the case in wider research (Antai *et al*, 2014; Postmus *et al* 2018), where the impact of financial abuse on families is rarely recognised by perpetrators of abuse. Several participants described having no access to money to buy essentials such as baby formula, nappies and clothing for their children. *Lynda* described using cloth, reusable nappies because of this. This study was unable to confirm the intent of perpetrators of abuse, however their behaviours undermined and dis-empowered women in their role as mothers, as they were unable to provide necessary items for their babies which had a detrimental effect on their mental health and wellbeing. Feminists such as O'Reilly (2019) and Rich (2021), would emphasise that financial abuse is another example of how motherhood further marginalises women in society, by keeping them subordinate through the imbalance of power that abuse exploits, and keeps them financially dependent on men.

Postmus *et al* (2018) suggests that financial abuse is less well understood than other forms of abuse and has received less attention in domestic abuse literature. For women experiencing financial abuse in an intimate relationship, this often includes not having control over money and activities, including work related activities and including decisions regarding how money is spent in the home, resulting in women's financial dependence. All these experiences of financial abuse as entrapment make leaving abusive relationships even more difficult (Antai *et al*, 2014), and it is likely that this concern would be a factor preventing women from disclosing abuse to professionals.

The presence and impact of domestic abuse is still often measured by the degree of physical abuse and injury, when in fact the impact of non-physical abuse such as financial abuse often impacts women in ways that are equally significant to physical forms of abuse (Stylinou, 2018). This perception is often confounded by the absence of research into non-physical abuse such as emotional and financial abuse (Postmus *et al*, 2018). Although the presence of coercive control is a more widely recognised

phenomenon (Stark, 2007), it is used by perpetrators to control and force economic dependency which acts as an additional barrier for women leaving abusive relationships, whereby the impact is rarely recognised. This is amplified further by the strategies used by perpetrators which often mirror the expectations facing women in their roles as parents, homemakers and intimate partners (Stark, 2007; Postmus *et al*, 2018).

Findings from this study illustrate key issues: the wide prevalence of financial abuse amongst the study participants, as illustrated in Table 7; the connection between financial abuse, physical abuse and substance misuse, and the presence of a large (over ten years) age gap between the women and the perpetrator in some cases where financial abuse is present. These will be discussed in the following sections.

9.9.1 Prevalence of financial abuse

Refuge (2020) estimates that 8.7 million people in the UK are experiencing financial abuse, with 1.6 million reporting that this began as a consequence of the Covid-19 pandemic. Approximately 39% of all adults have experienced financial abuse in either their current or former relationships, although it is estimated that only 16% recognise their experiences as abusive. Refuge (2020) also suggests that financial abuse begins early in an intimate relationship, and is often triggered by events such as co-habiting, marriage, or other events when couples join their finances.

Financial abuse was experienced by five of the nine participants in this study (Table 7) and although the initial onset of financial abuse was not clearly identified during participant interviews, the birth of new babies often triggered joint benefit claims, changes to benefit claims and employment status, which in many cases, provided a trigger for abuse to commence. Despite this evidence, early research by Postmus *et al* (2012) and Citizen's Advice (2015) suggest that this type of abuse is not always associated with domestic abuse, and this is confounded by the lack of knowledge and awareness that often fails to recognise financial abuse as a form of domestic abuse. Postmus *et al*'s (2012) framework suggests that financial abuse often uses three strategies: financial control, financial exploitation and financial sabotage, whereby one or more strategies are used, often simultaneously. Sharp (2008) and Littwin (2012) claim these strategies are often used alongside refusals to share details of their, or

household income. Postmus *et al's* framework (2012) can be used to understand the experiences of the participants in this study, where a variety of strategies were used by abusive partners to control, exploit and sabotage the lives of their partners. Financial abuse was described by participants as withholding, not having their own money, and was also closely aligned to emotional abuse, for example, restricting money for clothes and personal items, while perpetrators spent lavishly on personal items, and victims of abuse and their children were left without.

Similarly, partners controlled their activities and disrupted their access to employment, thus controlling their income and independence, and causing harm (Cannie, 2022). *Lynda, Tina* and *Georgina* described having no access to money, or were given small allowances, insufficient to buy essentials such as food, nappies, baby milk, which for two participants resulted in debt being accrued as they used credit cards to fund these items. The experiences of *Ruby, Tina, Karen* and *Georgina* illustrate examples of financial exploitation, whereby women's names were used for joint benefit claims held in accounts they had no access to, or strategies were used to gain access to money or savings. Although financial exploitation occurs more commonly to older adults, it can happen at any age, often where someone is deemed to be vulnerable (WHO, 2015). It could be argued that perpetrators of financial abuse therefore view their partners in vulnerable positions, and in inferior, non-equal positions in their relationships, which would be supported by feminist theories (Rich, 2021).

In the study, financial abuse was also associated with reproductive abuse, and again reflected beliefs about gender roles, and women being home-makers and child-rearers, rather than having access to employment and their own income. *Georgina* experienced her partner removing her immigration documents, which then restricted her ability to find employment and confirm her identity, which in turn affected her resident status in the UK. This reflects findings from a study by Howard and Skipp (2015) who also found that women's immigration status was often exploited to execute financial abuse, by facilitating easier benefit claims. *Georgina* claimed her partner only added her name to a joint bank account so he could make a joint benefit claim and have access to this money. Her partner also coerced her to hand over savings for a new car that she then was not allowed to use.

Tina, *Abbie* and *Georgina* were receiving child benefit payments, and reported that this was often their only means of income, but even this was often taken by their partners. It is important to note, that for many participants in the study, the debt accrued during these abusive relationships continued to be a financial burden and the women were still left to deal with the financial implications for several years, even after the relationship had ended. Financial inclusion has become integrated into Health Visiting assessments, and provides opportunity to explore family finances, and broader financial matters. This requires skills by Health Visitors to initiate sensitive conversations, identify concerns and provide supports and signposting to financial maximisation services.

9.9.2 Association between financial, physical and sexual abuse

Unlike earlier views of financial abuse, a study by Stylianou, Postmus and McMahon (2013) demonstrated a co-occurrence of financial abuse alongside physical and sexual abuse, which suggests that financial abuse commonly occurs alongside other abusive behaviours. Therefore, considering that this study recruited participants who had experience of domestic abuse, it is unsurprising that a large proportion were also victims of financial abuse.

Stylianou, Postmus and McMahon (2013) propose that financial abuse, as a form of emotional abuse, can occur even when not spatially connected to the victim, unlike physical and sexual abuse, which requires a certain proximity. This can account for the difficulties in ending financial abuse, as difficulties can persist even when other forms of abuse have ceased. This is reflected in the narratives of *Tina* and *Georgina* who described the ongoing emotional abuse post-separation, including ongoing financial control relating to child contact and court proceedings and decision-making relating to where contact would take place, with the knowledge that this would significantly impact on the financial situation of the female victim.

9.10 Domestic abuse and substance misuse

Gadd *et al* (2019) confirms that the connections between drugs, alcohol and domestic abuse are complicated, but well established, however it is often studied in the context

of the behaviours of substance misusing victims rather than perpetrators of abuse. The participant narratives in this study highlight a significant association between the perpetration of domestic abuse and substance misuse, and there is overwhelming evidence of drug and/or alcohol use by partners in eight out of nine participants in the study sample. This supports previous reports that substance misuse features in approximately half of all domestic abuse cases, and in half of UK domestic homicides (Gadd *et al*, 2019), and similar findings by Cliffe (2018) who's international systematic review also suggests that perpetrator drug use is a significant risk factor to domestic homicide of pregnant women. Although drug and alcohol use was not discussed in depth in the interviews, cannabis was the drug commonly used by partners of *Ruby, Tina, Abbie, Karen* and *Cathy*. Alcohol was misused by *Mandy, Zoe* and *Cathy's* partners; other variations in drug use are not known.

Alcohol and drug use have been persistently identified in UK and international research as precursors to perpetration of domestic abuse, mainly arising from the pharmacological effects of substances on behaviours, including presentations of anger, irritability, hostility, depression and paranoia that are associated with withdrawal as well as intoxication (Sacks *et al*, 2009; Cliffe, 2018; Gilchrist *et al*, 2019). This reflects participant experiences in this study, who describe incidents of abuse which were often followed their partner's use of alcohol.

International research indicates that men perpetrate more severe physical assaults following consumption of alcohol (Graham *et al*, 2011), and there is an additional suggestion that those with low levels of empathy and self-regulation, coupled with high levels of sensitivity and threats are more inclined to be violent following alcohol consumption up to four hours prior to the perceived threat or provocation (Leonard and Quigley, 2017). Findings from this thesis study indicates that physical or sexual abuse was almost always perpetrated following consumption of drugs and/or alcohol. However for some, their partner's substance misuse was so prolific that it was difficult for participants to ascertain whether they were under the influence when perpetrating abuse, or not, and is perhaps an indicator that abuse was present throughout long periods of their relationship and not isolated to defined periods of intoxication or inebriation. Participants themselves did not always openly associate substance misuse with the abuse they experienced; their accounts described the abuse they

suffered, and their partner's drug or alcohol use, as almost separate issues. However, physical abuse appeared to escalate following a partner's use of drugs or alcohol, while other forms of abuse, for example financial or emotional appeared to be present in their relationships even when substance misuse was not present. Professional curiosity and in-depth assessments by Health Visitors and Midwives offers a strategy to understand drug and alcohol use in the home, and consequently risk assess for domestic abuse that might co-occur.

By the nature of the recruitment strategy for the study, all participants in the study had experienced domestic abuse, however eight of the participants' partners all used cannabis. Abuse perpetrated by cannabis-using perpetrators was more commonly non-violent, and included perpetration of non-violent sexual abuse and financial abuse, however *Ruby* and *Tina* experienced physical assaults. In contrast, participants' partners who used alcohol instead of, or as well as, drugs demonstrated higher perpetration of violent physical and sexual abuse, which also reflects what is currently understood about the intersection of violent abuse and alcohol (Langenderfer, 2013).

Participants described their partners' substance use differently, depending on whether drugs or alcohol were involved. Drug/cannabis use was described by participants as a chronic pattern of use, whereby drugs were used consistently, with no defined periods of usage, for example, weekends, evenings. This contrasts with those partners who used alcohol, which was often associated with acute incidents, and specific periods of time, for example, at weekends, evenings, and occurring often as part of social events and free time outside of work. All four participants whose partners drank alcohol described abuse escalating following their partner's consumption of alcohol. This reflects similar findings from research that suggests alcohol is closely associated with violence (Langenderfer, 2013; McKinney *et al*, 2010).

Although not all substance users have experience of domestic abuse, as victim or perpetrator, many have, and this study confirms the strong association between substance use, perpetrators, and victims as described by Cafferky *et al* (2016), and studies have shown that interventions targeting substance misuse have reduced domestic abuse prevalence, including victimisation and perpetration (O'Farrell *et al*,

2003; Stuart *et al*, 2003). Similarly, it is possible Midwives and Health Visitors, could be attuned to such triggers, e.g. football matches, bank holidays, and occasions typified by excessive alcohol use and provide additional support to women following these events to proactively identify domestic abuse which could have escalated at these times.

Cafferky *et al* (2016) claims that most research in this area rarely differentiates between drug types, and has been unable to conclusively confirm associations between domestic abuse and cannabis use, suggesting a weak and inconsistent relationship, often suggesting that cannabis reduces domestic abuse perpetration and victimisation due to its lower addiction potential and perception that it is a less dangerous drug (Ostrowsky, 2011). However, studies by Boles and Miotto (2003) have also suggested that cannabis withdrawal symptoms are strongly associated with irritability, anger and aggression which could contribute to higher levels of domestic abuse, and would support findings from this study, which confirm a high presence of cannabis within the abusive relationships of almost all participants in this study.

Because of the lack of research into how different drug types impact on domestic abuse, there remains uncertainty about which drugs have the strongest association with domestic abuse, and how gender, cultural and psychological factors also influence outcomes (Cafferky *et al*, 2016). Cafferky *et al's* (2016) meta-analysis confirmed that there is a stronger association between drug use and domestic abuse, than alcohol use and domestic abuse. Many complexities exist to account for this, however, Cafferky *et al* (2016) suggest that the illegal nature of drug use, drug sourcing, and associations with illicit activities, that often support violent behaviours and habitual substance use, may be strong influencing factors.

The findings in this study highlight that both drug and alcohol use are associated with abuse perpetration across the spectrum of physical and non-physical behaviours. These findings are supported by a narrative analysis by Radcliffe, Gadd and Gilchrist (2019), who suggest that women often report enduring domestic abuse that is related to their partner's behaviours when under the influence of drugs or alcohol, or as a result of cravings, withdrawal or obtaining such substances. Similarly, women in relationships with a partner who misuses drugs or alcohol, when they themselves do

not, commonly report emotional and financial abuse as a result of substance misuse and relapse.

Substance misuse was not the focus of this study, therefore details around the nature of drug or alcohol use was not discussed in detail with the participants. However, where drug use by perpetrators was highlighted, their narratives suggested that the nature of obtaining drugs, the financial impact, and the patterns of craving, withdrawal and behaviour changes associated with drug use, had a direct impact on the women who lived with them and who were experiencing domestic abuse. Health Visitors, Midwives and GPs who work with women in the peri natal period therefore need to be aware of the complex circumstances women often live in, and understand the intersecting nature of drug and alcohol use, and domestic abuse. By considering this knowledge when undertaking assessments and engaging women in sensitive questioning, it is possible this would enhance relationship building and promote earlier disclosures of abuse, aid risk assessment and safety planning.

9.10.1 Substance misuse and gender

As suggested by Gadd *et al* (2019), substance misuse is more commonly discussed in relation to its use by abuse victims, rather than perpetrators. This could be in part due to the relationship between substance misuse and experiences of trauma, although it is suggested by Morton, Curran and O’Gorman (2022) that little is known about this relationship when in a context coupled with domestic abuse. Feminists would also likely argue that existing research is entrenched in male dominant and misogynistic attitudes, laying the responsibility of abuse on women’s substance misusing habits. Existing research supports a narrative of women-blaming, rather than acknowledge that male behaviours are also influenced by drug and alcohol use, and are often the fuel behind the perpetration of abusive acts (Gadd *et al*, 2019; Rich, 2021).

It can be argued that due to the focus on victim rather than perpetrator behaviours, it is unsurprising that men often minimise violence when under the influence of substances and ascribe drugs or alcohol as being responsible for domestic abuse (Gilchrist *et al*, 2015). Notably, substance misusing, domestic abusers are rarely referred to perpetrator rehabilitation programmes and when they are attrition is high

and attendance is low; and Gilchrist *et al* (2015) suggest that intervention programmes should be incorporated into mainstream, or core substance misusing treatment services.

Only one study participant disclosed personal drug or alcohol misuse, and there were no incidents disclosed by study participants whereby they were the perpetrators of abuse. A cohort study by Seid *et al* (2021) supports a plethora of empirical research that demonstrates a strong correlation between male substance misuse and female victimisation and heightened victimisation where there is female substance use. *Tina* indicated that she misused substances and described her relationship with her substance misusing partner where she experienced high levels of violent physical and sexual assault. In this relationship drug and alcohol use was significant and contributed to the mental health difficulties and vulnerabilities.

Gadd *et al* (2019) reflect feminist perspectives on domestic abuse and suggest that perpetrators of abuse retain power over women by using their alcohol or drug intoxication as an explanation for their behaviour, or for a lack of recall following such events. These perspectives are favoured over any argument which pharmacological changes from substance misuse might invoke (Gadd *et al*, 2019).

Although the relationship between substance misuse and domestic abuse is not the primary focus of this study, it does appear that associations between the use of drugs and alcohol, and physical assault as identified elsewhere in literature, (Javaid, 2015; Gilchrist *et al*, 2019; Radcliffe, Gadd and Gilchrist, 2019), are upheld in this study. There appears to be less available evidence that supports the association between emotional abuse, coercive and controlling behaviours and perpetrator use of substances which are reflected in the findings from this study.

All participants in this research described partners who exhibited controlling behaviours during their relationships, and exacerbation of abuse due to drugs or alcohol was always included when there was an escalation in physical assaults, rather than necessarily an increase in controlling, non-violent behaviours. This highlights a need for further exploration in how drug and alcohol use impacts on domestic abuse

that is non-violent and controlling, and supports existing practice that enquires about alcohol and drug use within Midwifery and Health Visiting assessments.

9.11 Domestic abuse and mental health

9.11.1 The impact of domestic abuse on mental health

Structural inequalities experienced by those with mental ill health intersect with gender inequalities, and result in women with severe mental health difficulties being more at risk of domestic abuse than women in the general population (Oram, Khalifeh and Howard, 2017). Survivors of abuse with mental health issues report feeling stigmatised and ignored, and these experiences influence their willingness to report abuse, perceiving that their mental ill health status will affect their ability to be believed. Despite this well-established understanding between abuse and poor mental health outcomes, ambiguity remains when understanding the relationship between domestic abuse and other mental health conditions (Anderson *et al*, 2016). This includes the impact of childhood sexual abuse which is also closely associated with experiencing domestic abuse and poor mental health as adults (Anderson *et al*, 2016; Oram, Khalifeh and Howard, 2017). The differences between the impact of physical, sexual and emotional abuse, including coercive control remain unclear, and are made more complex when more than one type of abuse is experienced simultaneously (Oram, Kahlifeh and Howard, 2017).

Existing literature confirms the impact of abuse on mental health as described in Chapter 2 (Oram *et al*, 2022), and the participants in the thesis study sample all experienced deteriorating mental health during periods of abuse, irrespective of whether they had pre-existing mental health conditions, including low mood, depression, and anxiety. Although these mental health conditions presented commonly throughout the sample, only *Tina*, who had multiple adverse childhood experiences, described having suicidal thoughts in the past while experiencing domestic abuse, despite established associations between domestic abuse and suicide in women (Keynejad *et al*, 2021). Low mood, depression and anxiety were commonly described in the sample, including lack of confidence, low self-esteem, and self-worth, and were present regardless of the type of abuse women sustained. As cited in existing literature, those with pre-existing disorders and conditions, for

example, depression, bi-polar, borderline personality disorder (BPD), found their symptoms to be exacerbated during periods of abuse when they would otherwise be well managed (Oram et al, 2022).

Figure 24 illustrates the mental health of the study participants, including their pre-existing conditions, experience of trauma, and impact of abuse that they had experienced:

Figure 24 – Mental health of study participants

Those participants who had experienced abuse as a child reported the most significant mental health conditions, which reflects the findings of McKay *et al* (2020), who confirm an association between childhood trauma and adult mental health disorders. Even those participants who had not disclosed adverse childhood experiences reported significant impact on their mental health as a result of experiencing domestic abuse, which continued to persist after the relationship had ended, confirming the long and enduring impact on women and their health (WHO, 2021). While the impact of abuse on women's mental health is largely uncontested, the suggestion of stigma by

Anderson *et al* (2016) was not supported by participants in the study who did not cite the existence of mental health conditions and mental ill health as a reason for not disclosing abuse, however, this would benefit from further study to explore in detail.

9.11.2 Sexual abuse and mental health

Research suggests that women with severe mental disorders are six times more likely to be a victim of sexual violence (Kamperman *et al*, 2014); three of the study participants experienced violent sexual assaults, and two had pre-existing mental health conditions, for example PTSD and bi-polar disorder. Most research does not distinguish between partner and stranger sexual assaults; therefore it is relatively unknown how the mental health impact differs when sexual abuse is experienced within an intimate relationship and whether differences exist when attacks occur as isolated incidents or as a pattern of abuse (Oram, Kahlifeh and Howard, 2017).

The multitude of health implications that arise as a result of sexual abuse, for example unwanted pregnancy, infections, as well as social stigma associated with sexual violence, also exacerbate women's mental ill health (Jina and Thomas, 2013). Again, the mental health of all participants in the study was affected because of domestic abuse; the spectrum of mental ill health varied across participants, however there were no notable differences between the mental health of those who had experienced sexual and physical abuse, when compared to others who had experienced non-physical abuse.

9.11.3 Mental health and help-seeking

Despite the ongoing stigmatisation of suffering mental ill health (Mental Health Foundation, 2021), the study findings suggest that participants readily identified their own deteriorating mental health and were forthcoming in seeking help from their GP or discussing with their Health Visitor or Midwife. This contrasts directly with a willingness to discuss domestic abuse, and it is unclear why women feel more able to seek support for their mental health, however it would seem there are fewer perceived barriers when compared to domestic abuse. There appears to be little available existing research that explores this phenomenon. This suggests opportunity exists for GPs to explore the occurrence of domestic abuse when consulting with women presenting with deteriorating mental health in the perinatal period. This is an

interesting proposition considering participants in the study were dismissive of their GP being a trusted professional who they would disclose to; therefore efforts would be required if this was to be a successful strategy to support women disclosing abuse.

Although Pescosolido *et al* (2021) suggest that stigma related to depression has decreased, as more people are able to recognise problems such as mental illness, they suggest that it has remained static for other mental health conditions. Although depression is referred to in a general sense, and not specific to post-natal depression, it is possible that the stigma reduction associated with depression has led to women confidently seeking support without fear of reprisal or threat to themselves or their children, which has shown in the study to be a primary fear of disclosing domestic abuse. This suggestion conflicts with findings from other studies, which suggest internal and external stigma surrounding mental ill health exist, which prevent women from seeking help (Moore, Ayres and Drey, 2016; Lucas *et al*, 2019).

Lucas *et al*'s (2019) study found young women more likely to conceal mental ill health after pregnancy, for fear of further scrutiny from professionals, and being judged as 'not a good mother'. Similarly, Moore, Ayres and Drey (2016) suggest that women feel stigma that is two-fold; stigma of having a mental illness, and that of being mothers with mental ill health, alongside the associated negative assumptions around social services intervention, loss of custody and hospitalisation. The experiences of the participants in this study contradicted with these findings, as the participants did seek support for their deteriorating mental health, regardless of age or apparent stigma. The age of the participants ranged from between 20 – 42, and they each sought support for their mental health at various times in their life.

Laing *et al* (2005) suggest that help-seeking for domestic abuse has three stages: recognising the problem, making a decision to seek help, and choosing the help provider; and this decision-making is influenced by personal and socio-cultural factors. Participants in this study were more able to move through the three stages as described by Laing *et al* (2005) when considering their own mental health, yet more difficulties arose when applying Laing's model to seeking help for domestic abuse. Figure 21 identifies the presence of barriers at each of the three stages which prevent women from seeking support.

This model highlights that domestic abuse remains a phenomenon with more complexities than mental ill, that influence a woman's help seeking. Women in the study were able to recognise their own mental health distress and it can be proposed, that they were knowledgeable about the impact that deteriorating mental health has on their lives, their mothering ability and potentially on their children. The lack of knowledge and awareness that surrounds domestic abuse, its presentation, its impact on women and whole families is perhaps less well known, and therefore, might attribute the differences in help-seeking when compared to seeking help for mental health difficulties.

Figure 25 – Applying Laing's (2005) model of help-seeking to domestic abuse.

9.11.4 Post-natal depression

Domestic abuse during pregnancy is associated with post-natal depression (PND) (Mahenge *et al* 2018), and Howard *et al* (2013) suggest that domestic abuse could be attributed to over 10% of presentations of post-natal depression. All participants in the study were mothers who noted deterioration in their mental health during periods of abuse, and many recalled undertaking a post-natal depression score with their Health Visitor. Women experiencing physical or sexual violence during pregnancy are at highest risk of post-natal depression (Mahenge *et al*, 2018), and this was reflected in the study sample, whereby the one participant who disclosed suffering from post-natal depression after each of her children, had experienced severe physical and sexual abuse during pregnancy. This participant also had a bi-polar disorder diagnosis, which also placed her at heightened risk of post-natal depression (Jones and Shakespeare, 2014).

This suggests there is scope for Health Visitors to enquire further about domestic abuse in the post-natal period, particularly as the Edinburgh Post Natal Score tool is recommended as a tool to support discussion throughout the first year of post-natal contacts with the Health Visitor in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2015). Kothari *et al* (2016) agree that domestic abuse is an indicator for post-natal depression, and depression is more likely to follow domestic abuse rather than precede it. Furthermore, they claim a clear association with poverty, with women living in poverty more predisposed to post-natal depression and other depressive episodes, as well as the condition being severe and chronic. The current cost of living crisis therefore suggests that more women than in previous years might be at risk of domestic abuse and mental health disorders, especially when it is understood that poverty is both a cause and effect of domestic abuse (Kothari *et al*, 2016).

Five participants reported mental health disturbances in the post-natal period, however this was not explored in depth during the interviews; it is entirely probable that the deterioration in the participants' mental health during this post-natal period was due to domestic abuse, rather than primarily due to post-natal depression, however it is impossible to be certain, and this is not a phenomenon that appears to be well reflected in current research. Although all participants recognised their mental health had been affected by their experiences, only one participant referred to this as post-natal

depression; the large majority did not disclose that they suffered post-natal depression following the births of their children, suggesting there is scope for Health Visitors to explore mental health changes with the support of existing tools, to support women in the post-natal period.

9.11.5 Weaponising mental health by perpetrators

Evidence from this study found that the mental health of all participants was adversely affected by the abuse they experienced, and those with existing mental health conditions experienced exacerbation of these conditions. These findings also support evidence which suggests that women with pre-existing mental health conditions are more at risk of domestic abuse and sexual violence, due to being targeted by perpetrators as a result of their additional vulnerabilities (Howard *et al.*, 2010; Khalifeh *et al.*, 2015; Pettitt *et al.*, 2013; Women's Mental Health Taskforce, 2018).

All participants experienced emotional abuse, whether in isolation or alongside other forms of abuse. Where women had a history of mental ill health, abusive partners used this personal knowledge to target emotional vulnerabilities, as a strategy to control, degrade and ridicule, isolate and create dependency (Karakurt and Silver, 2013). A participant with a history of suicide attempts had this personal information used against her by her partner to incite shame and imply her history would be used against her by professionals, resulting in the removal of the child. This reflects the work of Pettit *et al.* (2013), who states perpetrators of abuse seek to harm women when unwell, and become attuned to periods of mental ill health, while reinforcing a perception that those suffering mental ill health will be less credible and disbelieved if they disclosed abuse (Pettit *et al.*, 2013).

There is a plethora of research to emphasise the severe impacts of emotional abuse on those who experience it; using a women's personal situation as a means of control over time is a tactic considered just as harmful as physical abuse; like men who use financial control, the use of a woman's mental health, or exploiting her role as a mother, is another example of a strategy used to control and manipulate (Howard *et al.*, 2010; Karakurt and Silver, 2013; Khalifeh *et al.*, 2015).

9.12 Mothering in domestic abuse contexts

The theme of mothering, emerged from a deep interpretive analysis of the participant interview data, in a manner less apparent than other themes that have been discussed. Feminist mothering challenges traditional patriarchal mothering, by promoting balance and eliminating guilt to achieve empowerment, and values the importance of mothers meeting their own needs (O'Reilly, 2019). Such feminist approaches advocate mothers to involve others in raising children and acknowledge that being a mother does not fulfil all a women's needs, while challenging the perception that mothers should be solely responsible for their child's growth and development, and all they should feel for their child is love (Horwitz, 2004; O'Reilly, 2021).

O'Reilly (2021) argues however, that empowered mothering can only be achieved when women have 'agency, authority, authenticity and autonomy' (O'Reilly, 2021, p173). Women who live with domestic abuse, like the participants in this study, have their identity and self-hood's compromised and challenged, and their ability to live with the agency and autonomy that motherhood can bring, as discussed in Section 6.3.3, is limited. As they are restricted and controlled, it is unsurprising that the act of mothering is likely to be compromised, as abusive partners strive to maintain a patriarchal state (Rich, 2021, Baldwin, 2021).

Empowered mothering, and the philosophies of Matricentric Feminism imply that women have lives outside of motherhood, however achieving this act of mothering becomes increasingly difficult when taking place within an abusive context, where perpetrators control and restrict women's lives outside of motherhood and the home, reducing opportunities for disclosure, and upholding a context whereby they will not be believed. Consequently, it is suggested that challenging patriarchal stereotypes and male privilege and power are likely to be risky to both mother and child (O'Reilly, 2019, 2021). Participants in this study did not use terms such as 'patriarchy' or 'power' to describe patriarchal structures, gender roles and inequalities, however they did speak frequently of being controlled, having access to money and employment controlled and denied, and being physically and emotionally abused and manipulated.

This describes the numerous instances across all participants whereby patriarchal beliefs, as discussed in Section 6.3, generated power imbalances in intimate relationships that led to further violence and abuse (Tonsing and Tonsing, 2019). It is understandable therefore, that when women are living within such circumstances, it can become increasingly difficult to develop relationships and disclose abusive experiences to professionals, if entrenched and surrounded by patriarchal cultures and attitudes, that confirm their views are secondary, they are less important and unlikely to be taken seriously (Rich, 1981).

Due to the widespread prevalence of domestic abuse, mothering frequently occurs within a context of abuse, shaping the experiences of both women and child (Broughton, Ford-Gilboe and Varcoe, 2022). Women are subject to dominant mothering ideals in the western world which promote that to be a 'good mother' is to invest all their time in caring for their child, and to be constantly available to them and their nurture (Smyth and Craig, 2017). Such norms, ideals and understandings of motherhood create guilt for women even where domestic abuse is not present, but more-so where it is, with accompanied harmful effects (Broughton, Ford-Gilboe and Varcoe, 2022). It is argued that perpetrators reinforce these mothering ideals, placing women at the forefront of parental responsibility to meet all a child's needs, while dismissing any role they may have in the development or protection of their children (Broughton, Ford-Gilboe and Varcoe, 2022)

There has been much written about mothering in the context of domestic abuse that highlights the structural and gendered inequalities and patriarchal attitudes and cultures that exist, whereby women are held responsible for the abuse they experience within their intimate relationships (Wendt, Buchanan and Moulding, 2015; Thiara and Humphreys, 2017). It has long since been acknowledged that women are frequently scrutinised for their parenting abilities and their capacity to protect their children from abuse and held accountable for contributing to domestic abuse (Wendt, Buchanan and Moulding, 2015; Maher *et al*, 2020). Only some of the study participants had multi-agency involvement during the periods of abuse, and therefore this was not discussed in depth. However, one of the primary contributing factors that prevented mothers from disclosing abuse was fear from social services, fear of judgement and their own belief that they were responsible for their situations and the abuse they were

experiencing. It is essential that these assumptions and fears are addressed for women to feel safe to disclose abuse to professionals.

Much research to date has focused on the impact of abuse on children and associated mothering practices; judgements are often made about the protectiveness of mothers, and their attachments with their children (Buchanan, Power and Verity, 2014), with mothers and their parenting frequently being judged through the court system (Miller and Manzer, 2018). The reasons why women, and indeed mothers stay in abusive relationships is not an area well studied, however, many participants in the study cited the reason they did not disclose abuse was to keep their family together, and thus to protect their children from the loss of family. This reflects findings from Meyer (2011) however, it is suggested that mothers frequently reassess the risk to their children, and protect their children in challenging circumstances (Lapierre, 2010; Ateah *et al*, 2019), and participants in this study were, in many cases able to identify increasing threat of danger, which prompted them to leave the relationship and report abuse. Once women have left abusive relationships, feminist theorists would also support suggestions that male behaviours are often overlooked in the court system, whereas women are considered to be disobedient or recalcitrant by challenging abuse or decisions (Miller and Manzer, 2018).

Mothering is often considered in relation to its practices of rearing children to ensure appropriate child development, but often fails to consider mothering as an experience that is affected by the presence of abuse in the home and the stressors that inevitably occur as a result (Morgan, 2021). By considering mothering within a narrow context of domestic abuse, it fails to understand women's agency alongside the various intersecting structural barriers that influence the impact of mothering on mothers (Buchanan and Humphreys, 2021). Several participants in the study were subject to financial abuse, which was a large cause of ongoing stress to those affected. Mothering within financial hardship caused by domestic abuse helps to understand that mothering is more than a practice and helps to offer a more complex understanding of mothering and the impacts on multiple aspects of the lives of mothers (Gilroy, 2020). Health Professionals such as Health Visitors and Midwives must work through these complexities to try to understand role and positions of mothers, challenge stereotypes and assumptions so to be able to offer support that is acceptable to them.

Study participants spoke during interviews of being responsible, in their own opinion, for keeping their children safe, and McFeely (2016) suggests that this child-centred approach fails to consider the impact on women themselves. Participants did not speak of having their parenting judged, or felt they were held accountable for their partners actions by professionals, however, the mothers judged themselves against normative parenting expectations of 'good mothering' and blamed themselves for putting their children at risk (Maher *et al*, 2020). It was unclear whether the multi-agency systems supported this view, however it is an important consideration when creating conditions for abuse disclosures.

Whiley, Sayer and Juanchich (2020) claim that the impact of domestic abuse on women's health and wellbeing is largely overlooked, and more commonly viewed in relation to the impact on their children. That is, women, unlike men, are viewed as vehicles to promote children's development and health, which means interventions to improve women's health are often neglected. This is an important factor for health professionals, particularly Health Visitors and Midwives to consider and to be aware of. Additionally, there is an expectation that mothers should continue to meet the needs of their children, even in the context of domestic abuse, despite the challenges that this brings, which reflects normative parenting models and rarely featuring the responsibilities of fathers (Brooks and McFarlane, 2018).

Kelly (1994) described domestic abuse as being 'double intentioned' that targets both women and children and attempts to undermine their relationships. When considering domestic abuse, women and children are often connected, as abuse frequently begins during pregnancy, and women's decision-making regarding contraception and childbearing can often be restricted and controlled by abusive partners, as discussed in Section 8.7.3. Even at the outset of a child's birth, the nature of the mother-child relationship is often controlled by an abusive partner (Morrison and Houghton, 2022). Despite children often witnessing and sometimes being coerced into abuse, and parenting being impaired by abuse, a mother and her children's relationships are often strengthened as a result; consequently fortifying these relationships are often an aim of interventions designed to protect children living with domestic abuse (Katz, 2016).

Participants in this study cited their children as catalysts for disclosing abuse, seeking help, and prioritising their child's safety. Feminists will often focus on the mother-child relationship to counter domestic abuse and provide a contrast to the 'mother blaming' response which has been familiar when addressing child welfare concerns (Jackson and Mannix, 2004; Lapierre, 2008; Lapierre, 2021). While motherhood in this study has been shown to be a target of abuse by perpetrators of abuse, by means of threatening and undermining the mothering role, Rich (1981) and O'Reilly (2021) demonstrate how motherhood can also be empowering, even when hindered by patriarchy.

Approaches such as Signs of Safety (Turnell and Edwards, 2019), and Safe and Together (Safe and Together Institute, 2019) aim to work in partnership with families by building on their strengths, resources and networks and reducing risk to children, to improve wellbeing and outcomes. Both require cultural change and are used throughout many areas in the UK (Department of Education, 2017). The focus on family strengths, honest and respectful working relationships, reflect the theoretical underpinnings of health visiting practice, policy guidance, and the over-arching approach of GIRFEC (Scottish Government, 2015, 2020). Ambitions such as this are promising in readjusting approaches to addressing domestic abuse in families and removing responsibility from mothers who have traditionally been held accountable for any harm to their children and parenting choices (Whiley, Sayer and Juanchick, 2020). These models are in their infancy in Scotland, therefore potential impacts on children and survivors of abuse will not be seen for a number of years, however it is suggested that widespread culture change, which tackles patriarchal views of mothering, is also required before any strategy will be successful (Kuskoff and Parcell, 2020).

9.13 Adverse childhood experiences

Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) are traumatic events that can affect brain function, impair wellbeing, have negative impacts on mental and physical health, and can influence life expectancy, and economic stability (Boulliere and Blair, 2018). ACE's in this study were measured by Filetti *et al* (2008)'s descriptors, and study findings highlighted that seven of the nine participants had experienced at least two ACEs, and three experienced four or more ACEs, suggesting they are more

susceptible to health problems and to participate in risky behaviours. Two participants had experienced more than six ACEs, which was associated with a reduction in life expectancy of 20 years compared to those with no ACEs in Filetti *et al's* study (2008). It is suggested that those adults who have experienced ACEs are more likely to engage in activities that will incur ACEs for their own children (Bellis *et al*, 2015), hence an association is acknowledged between ACEs and adult experience of domestic abuse within an intimate relationship (Morton and Curran, 2019).

Participants in the study with the highest number of ACEs had experienced violence and abuse throughout their childhood and adult relationships and had chronic mental health difficulties that had been present throughout their lives. Despite these similarities, each of these participants had experienced different types of domestic abuse, suggesting that although there might not be a distinct correlation between ACEs and type of abuse experienced as adults, it does emphasise that women with multiple ACEs might be more likely to experience chronic and enduring abusive relationships throughout their lives, rather than this being isolated to one relationship. This evidence was seen in the study, for example, the participant with eight ACEs also disclosed the most significant mental ill health, resulting in suicidal ideations at times during her life. Although there is an established association between suicidal ideation and domestic abuse (Oram *et al*, 2022), *Tina's* interview narrative suggests that whilst domestic abuse may have been a contributing factor to her poor mental health it was not the sole factor among multiple other vulnerabilities and trauma.

Over half the participants in this study had witnessed domestic abuse in their parents' relationships, all of which had been physical abuse, and had accounted in part to their lack of awareness of non-physical forms of abuse. Of these five participants, four experienced physical abuse within at least one of their intimate relationships. This study also highlighted that parental domestic abuse was closely associated with separation and divorce, alcohol use, and has weaker connections with emotional abuse and parental mental illness. Where Health Visitors and Midwives, by nature of longevity of relationship, are able to explore these historical experiences, women may be more likely to disclose abuse and historical traumatic events, that may in turn facilitate abuse disclosures.

9.13.1 Impact of trauma on memory retrieval

Trauma has a negative impact on memory function, and those who have experienced trauma often have difficulty retrieving memories as a means of coping with their lived experiences (Hulbert and Anderson, 2018). *Tina*, who had multiple ACEs, had experienced several abusive relationships throughout her life, and had also been a prolific drug user in the years before she became a mother. During her interview, she often had trouble remembering events and timescales, and attributed her poor memory to her drug use during certain periods of her life, when in fact it was possible this was due to the trauma she had experienced (Hulbert and Anderson, 2018). Other participants in the study, some with fewer ACEs, but who still experienced traumatic events that endured over long periods, had similar difficulties recalling events; often exacerbated by recurrent assaults and abusive incidents, where recalling single events, and providing accurate timings proved challenging.

Studies have suggested that recalling adverse childhood experiences can be fraught with challenges regarding validity and reliability of historical events, and this can be increasingly complicated by the mood and mental health, in particular depression, of the person revisiting past events (Gotlib and Joormann, 2010; Whalley, Rugg and Brewin, 2012; Colman *et al*, 2015). All participants disclosed that their mental health had been impacted due to the abuse they had experienced. Although they were no longer in abusive relationships some participants were clearly still greatly affected by their experiences and continuing to have medication prescribed to manage their mental health. Therefore it was unclear the extent to which their mental health might have impacted on their memory retrieval. Use of the life history calendar and timeline were beneficial in these circumstances, and helped participants identify timings of events in their lives.

9.13.2 Multiple recurring abusive relationships

Interview narratives highlighted that six of the nine participants had experienced more than one abusive intimate relationship during their lives; however interviews did not afford time to discuss all in depth. Additionally, participants were informed they were in control of what they disclosed, so it is possible that the full extent of their abusive relationship history might not have been discussed. This is acknowledged in the study design that valuable data could be lost from participant narratives. Several participants

disclosed a specific number of abusive partners, and other participants were more general and reflected various abusive relationships that had featured throughout their lives. *Tina* had experienced physical and sexual abuse throughout her life from several perpetrators, and therefore spoke briefly about some of them. Despite this ambiguity arising from varied participant experiences the interview narratives about the extent of abuse experienced over the life-course, it is worthy of note that *Tina* and *Karen* who had eight and four ACEs respectively, had both been in four abusive relationships. *Zoe* and *Cathy* both disclosed two ACEs, and a smaller number of abusive relationships. *Abbie* had a high number of ACEs, but only disclosed one abusive relationship. She was however, the youngest participant at 20 years, several years younger than the oldest participant, which might account for the smaller numbers of partners. *Tina* and *Karen* who have had more abusive relationships, also describe a higher number of differing types of abuse. Figure 26 illustrates the participants' abusive relationships, the types of abuse and ACEs:

Figure 26 – Participants' experiences of abusive relationships, and types of abuse and ACEs

Research findings suggest that domestic abuse perpetrators are often repeat offenders; and repeat offending is, in turn, more prevalent than being a repeat victim of domestic abuse (Bland and Ariel, 2015), and consequently legislation such as 'Claire's Law' has been established to allow potential victims to explore whether partners have a history of violent offending. While serial domestic abuse offending

has been widely studied (Robinson, Clancy and Samuel, 2014; Bland and Ariel, 2015; Robinson and Clancy, 2021) considerably less is known about serial victims of domestic abuse. As evident in this study, there is a wide variety of victimisation with some participants having had one abusive relationship, and others where they have been subjected to living with abuse for a greater proportion of their lives.

9.14 Domestic abuse and perpetrator age

Research regarding an association between age and domestic abuse is often ambiguous and conflicting (Karakurt and Silver, 2013). Within this study five out of nine participants had been in abusive relationships with men ten years or more their senior, and various experiences were noted from the interviews:

Participant	Financial abuse	Physical abuse	Emotional abuse	Perpetrator substance misuse	Escalation at end of relationship	Child abuse by perpetrator
<i>Lynda</i>						
<i>Tina</i>						
<i>Karen</i>						
<i>Abbie</i>						
<i>Georgina</i>						

Table 9 – Age and domestic abuse in the study sample

Observations from the participants' interviews highlight that *Lynda, Tina, Karen, Abbie and Georgina*, who had significantly older partners had also experienced financial abuse, and most of their partners had been misusing drugs or alcohol. The experiences of participants in this study support findings from research by Fageeh (2017) of women in Saudi Arabia, who identified that spouses of abused women were significantly older than those of non-abused women. Alhabib, Nur and Jones (2010) also claim abuse increases when this age gap is over 15 years. However, findings are contrasted with other research by Caetano, Vaeth, and Ramisetty-Mikler (2008) and Adebowale, (2018) who suggest abuse reduces with increased age gaps in relationships. With this ambiguity in mind, it is possible that the age differences noted in this study adds to a power differential in a relationship that often precludes domestic

abuse, however there is little literature available to confirm how financial abuse intersects with gender and other characteristics such as age (Sharp-Jeffs, 2015).

9.15 Coronavirus pandemic

The completion of this thesis spanned the global coronavirus pandemic which began in the UK in March 2020. The pandemic has magnified the issue of domestic abuse in various ways; incidence has increased globally, with the World Health Organisation (WHO) claiming between 50-60% increases to domestic abuse helplines during the pandemic. Similar increases were seen by the UK's National Domestic Abuse Hotline, who saw a 65% increase in calls between April and June 2020, compared to the first three months of that year (UK Research and Innovation, 2022), and the Police have reported increases in domestic abuse related calls, and demand for victim services following lockdown measures (ONS, 2020). It can be presumed that as families adhered to the stay-at-home messages during the pandemic, and had limited access to supportive networks, these additional barriers will mean that even fewer incidents of abuse will have been disclosed and reported during this period (Scottish Government, 2020).

The measures used to control the virus and preserve life, such as national lockdowns, catapulted domestic abuse into the public and professional foreground, as the unintended impact of the measures became evident, and were highlighted to be particularly harmful to those in homes where abuse was already present (Bradbury Jones and Isham, 2020; Riddell and Haighton, 2022). Termed the shadow pandemic (Keynejad, 2023), the extent and nature of domestic abuse during this period has been widely documented, with mothers and their children being identified as particularly vulnerable during the time of school closures, economic fragility and job losses (End Violence Against Children, 2020; Ali, Rogers and Heward-Belle, 2021; Heward-Belle, 2021).

The true impact on those experiencing domestic abuse during the pandemic is not fully known due to the limited and developing evidence base (Riddell and Haighton, 2022), however Keynejad (2023) proposes that there were several aspects to the pandemic that increased the risks during this period, including inequalities evident between partners caused by the pandemic, such as unemployment, child-caring and

home schooling duties, and increased opportunities to control partners, through restricting movement and use of PPE. These can be seen in Figure 27. The increase in both levels and intensity of abuse during the pandemic was concerning, particularly as these reflected findings from previous similar global emergencies, which also demonstrated the changing and increasing nature of abuse against women (Morrison and Houghton, 2022).

Figure 27 – Increased risk of abuse during the pandemic (Keynejad, 2023)

Data collection in the study began in the summer of 2022, once many of the restrictions had lifted; four of the participants were living with abusive partners during the height of the pandemic and their experiences during this time are illustrated in Figure 28, and also reflect the views of Keynejad (2023):

Figure 28 - Implications of the Coronavirus pandemic on participants

Participants who were in abusive relationships during the pandemic spoke negatively about the experience, and their experiences reflected those highlighted by survivors in Women's Aid research, who stated their abuse had worsened since Covid-19, when their partners had more control over their lives (Women's Aid, 2020a). As Figure 28 illustrates, the pandemic brought many challenges to participants; isolation from others was central to the public health response to the virus, however this prolonged contact with abusive partners, and lack of contact with friends and family, resulted in reduced opportunities to seek help, meaning the pandemic contributed to keeping abuse hidden within the home (Usher *et al*, 2020). As well as limited contact with family and friends, participants spoke of missing community services such as baby groups, which would have usually provided respite and balance to the lives of these women.

As health professionals responded to the national guidance regarding home visiting, women reported that they rarely saw professionals which limited opportunities to enquire about domestic abuse. Additionally, changes and restrictions to community service delivery patterns created disruptions to the relationship building that would normally have occurred between women and health professionals in the perinatal period and which facilitates routine enquiry about domestic abuse.

The weaponising of national restrictions as described by Keynejad (2023) was evident in participant accounts, whereby abusive partners used the anxiety regarding the virus, and the 'stay at home' messages as a strategy to control movements and perpetrate abuse. This was heightened for those experiencing financial abuse and whose partners used drugs; abusive partners who already misused drugs or alcohol continued to do so, or their use escalated during this time, and therefore the impact on family finances became more strained, as echoed in research by Riddell and Haughton (2022).

Davidge (2020) claims that during the pandemic children witnessing more abuse in the home, and it was more difficult for women to escape abuse; similarly, abusers actively used lockdown restrictions to stop them from leaving, and when women had tried to leave, many had been unable to access housing or refuge space (Davidge, 2020). This reflects many of the participant narratives; *Georgina* described that

lockdown created stress within the family unit, resulting in physical abuse to the child in the home; this participant also lacked contact with specialist services during this time, who had provided considerable support prior to the pandemic. The timing of the pandemic also prevented this participant from leaving the relationship, as she had been preparing to do, due to restrictions on foreign travel.

Although the evidence base regarding the impact of the pandemic on abuse survivors is perhaps currently lacking, it can only be surmised that the health impact of prolonged stress during the pandemic will be significant (Riddell and Haughton, 2022). It has been recognised that the presence of natural or human emergencies, including pandemics or earthquakes, disproportionately affects women and children, particularly due to the increase in domestic abuse (Ali, Rogers and Heward-Belle, 2021). Although the Coronavirus pandemic was unprecedented in the UK, it is unlikely to be the last global emergency, and therefore learning is essential to better prepare for vulnerable groups in the future, and structural inequalities also need to be addressed for this to be successful (Rao, 2020). The longer-term impacts of the pandemic, are not yet fully known, and the impact on mental health is only just becoming evident (Wallbridge Boumistrova *et al*, 2022). Domestic abuse has a significant impact on the mental health of survivors, and this is reflected in the interview narratives of the study participants; therefore, coupled with additional pressures of the pandemic and its control measures, the long-term consequences are likely to be seen for some time to come (Rao, 2020; Ali, Rogers and Heward-Belle, 2021).

The experiences of women during the pandemic are unique and unrivalled; parenting and surviving abuse during this time is unprecedented, in modern times. This rich data was important to help me, as the researcher understand how women lived during these months when their liberties were restricted due national measures as well as abusive partners. It is acknowledged however, that despite these specific, individual accounts, this data within this theme is unlikely to support researchers better understand the wider decision making relating to abuse disclosures and help to provide insight relating to the research aim . However, to not acknowledge their experiences during the pandemic would be an oversight and dismissive of a time that impacted so greatly on their lives and the lives of their children.

9.15.1 Mothering during the pandemic

Study participants recalled the challenges they faced during the pandemic relating to home schooling and caring for their children, while in close proximity to their partners and without support networks. As reported by Lutz, Lee and Bokayev (2021), participants reported taking on multiple roles during this time, as they balanced the needs of young babies, with school aged children and maintaining household duties, often leading to role strain. None of the participants were employed during this time, however reported that juggling the needs of the household was difficult:

‘...it was awful, I was trying to home-school, deal with a baby and deal with all of that, it was hard, and no access to support networks’ (Ruby)

The institution of school provided mothers with respite from their children, however during the pandemic, mothers were also given the role of providing education for their children (Lutz, Lee and Bokayev, 2021). Even before the pandemic mothers took a disproportionate role in childcare, but it seems this was exacerbated during this time (Calarco *et al*, 2020), as all participants reported that caring and home-schooling children fell to them, rather than their partners. The pandemic highlighted a gendered division of labour that was not present to this extent in pre-pandemic times and the impact of intersecting systems of sex, race and disability on women were exacerbated due to the additional, more intensive demands of home schooling that were not felt by male partners (Lutz, Lees and Bokayev, 2021; Richards, 2022; Haney and Barber, 2022),.

Feminist theories, as discussed in Section 6.3, explain the long-standing marginalisation of women, and more-so in their roles as mothers (O’Reilly, 2019; Rich, 2021). During the pandemic, women were reported to have been disproportionately affected by stress, and attribute this mostly to school closures and associated caring and educating responsibilities, exacerbated further by the absence of support and community networks, leading to anxiety and depression in mothers with small children (Haney and Barber, 2022). Intensive mothering, discussed in section in 6.3.4 identified women are the primary caretakers of children, whereby they prioritise the needs of their children at all costs (Hays, 1996). However, Garland-McKinney and Meinersman (2022) claim that during the pandemic, achieving this became

unachievable due to a shift in roles, and lent itself to the judgement that to fail at normative mothering was to be a bad mother. In turn, this led to shame, and similar impacts on mothers' emotional health and wellbeing.

Although mothers were disproportionately affected by the pandemic, this period exacerbated the existing inequalities they experience as women (Whiley, Sayer and Juanchich, 2020), and is compounded further when they experience domestic abuse (Maher *et al*, 2020). The study participants were mostly unaffected by furlough and changes to employment status during the pandemic; however, they remained impacted by the gendered role expectations placed up on them as women and mothers (Lutz, Lees and Bokayev, 2021).

9.16 Chapter summary

This study has highlighted several important messages that are relevant for contemporary health care practice in Scotland and the UK. This chapter has critically examined the findings from the study and discussed these in relation to existing research and policy, and Health Visitor, Midwifery and GP practice, as these are health professionals who have most contact with women in the perinatal period, and mothers with young children. The study findings suggest routine enquiry for domestic abuse is not consistent in practice, however this provides a vehicle to open conversations and provide opportunities for disclosures. A variety of barriers were identified, similar to findings elsewhere, and health professionals have a role, through their relationships with women, in dispelling myths, allaying fears and anxieties, and helping to create conditions that can facilitate disclosures. Much of this will require health professionals to have high level knowledge and understanding of the nature of domestic abuse.

The relationship between mothers and health professionals was reported by participants in the study to be good; it was also found to be important, and necessary, however was not sufficient to promote disclosures, without consideration of other factors, such as wider political and structural attitudes to domestic abuse and ideas about women's roles. This study has provided a more detailed explanation of the conditions needed for disclosures than is evident in current research. Matricentric Feminism was the primary theoretical framework that was used throughout the study

to understand and bring meaning to participant's voices and experiences using Heideggerian principles that guided the study.

Participants in the study were subject to a variety of types of abuse, and these have been explored, to consider the impact on mothers, and their willingness to disclose abuse which are specific to the type of abuse experienced. This includes the strategies used by abusive partners to control women during the perinatal period, and acknowledging the trigger points for escalations, e.g. pregnancy, perinatal and post separation period. The study also highlighted how men use women's role as mothers, to undermine, control and abuse. A lack of awareness of emotional abuse was a key factor for women and behind many reasons why women choose not to disclose abuse. Health Professionals have roles when working with women during these periods to raise awareness, identify these high risk periods and give adequate consideration in safety planning, especially when within a multi-agency setting.

The study has highlighted complicating factors such as mental ill health, substance misuse and adverse childhood experiences, which often occur alongside domestic abuse, and present further complexities for women when choosing to disclose abuse, and for health professionals to navigate when working with survivors of abuse. The study highlighted that disclosures were mostly unplanned, but often due to the presence of positive relationships with others and women reaching personal thresholds of what is acceptable and tolerable. The study also discussed the impact of the Coronavirus pandemic on participants, their mothering, and the abuse they experienced.

The following chapter will discuss the strengths and limitations of the study.

10 Strengths and limitations of the study

10.1 Strengths

This study has provided a valuable insight into the lived experiences of mothers who have been victims of domestic abuse and has highlighted some important implications for practice and policy makers. Findings from the study have challenged some elements of existing practice, and emphasised changes that might be required if we are to improve the experiences for abused women when in contact with health professionals, in particular Health Visitors, Midwives and GPs. The study has contributed to the evidence base of contemporary health visiting, which has the potential to influence practice across the UK.

The study has sought to give voices to the women affected by domestic abuse, and in doing so, has been accepting of their truths. The researcher's skills and ability to put participants at ease is evident throughout the study, in the variety of experiences and rich data that arose to give the reader a meaningful insight into the lives of abused women, which is not widely available elsewhere. Feedback from the participants has confirmed that they found their involvement in the study cathartic, motivated entirely by the desire to help other women who are also experiencing abuse. They acknowledged that the researcher's role in hearing their stories, without any motivation to advise or assess, as in a professional capacity, helped them to share their lived experiences without feeling any pressure or judgement.

10.2 Limitations

There are also a number of noteworthy limitations associated with the study. Firstly, the interpretative phenomenological methodology chosen for the study provides opportunity for scrutiny by Heideggerian critics who may question the notion of truth, as it is possible for study participants to withhold information relating to their lived experiences during interviews. This is mitigated by the underpinning foundations of hermeneutic research which does not strive to establish truth, but instead is attempting to create understanding which might otherwise be hidden (Dibley *et al*, 2020). Concerns that accounts may not be wholly reflective of participant experiences through concealment are justified by Dibley *et al* (2020) who state that the whole story can never be told, due to various meanings that can be understood and accepted by

others (Gadamer, 2003). Hermeneutic researchers 'borrow the experiences of others' to understand a phenomenon (Van Manen and Levering, 1990), and regardless of whether participants withhold information, the interview narrative tells the researcher of their experiences in that period of time and directs us to an understanding about what it meant for them, at that time; and acknowledges that individual experiences are different for each participant (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

Additional limitations relate to the sample used in the study; although the size of sample is often scrutinised by positivist researchers, it is determined by study design and research aim (Boddy, 2016). The limitation here is not the size of the sample, but the breadth of geographical area that participants were recruited from. Despite the initial intention to recruit participants from multiple Health Board areas in Scotland, all participants resided in one Health Board area, contributed in part due to a lack of established professional networks to facilitate recruitment (Gall, Gall and Borg, 2003). The size of sample supported the generation of detailed, rich data, often unobtainable in large samples, and was able to offer experiential data from which meaning about the phenomenon in question could be uncovered (Bartholomew *et al*, 2021).

Although hermeneutic research is not concerned with representativeness, or demonstrating 'sameness, as evidence of truth' (Dibley *et al*, 2020, p60), it values each participant's experience as valuable and unique, and sample size is important for highlighting both similarities, shared experiences and differences in data. The sample size in the study allowed for shared experiences and differences to be identified, however it is acknowledged that depth and richness of data could have been enhanced by recruiting participants from a wider range of rural and urban regions across Scotland, offering further potential to understand the individual worlds of abuse survivors (Bartholomew *et al*, 2021).

Similar to the breadth of sample, the study might have been enhanced by a spread of participants that spanned differing sexualities, genders, and variations of motherhood, for example women who are not biological mothers, and women in same sex relationships. All participants in the study were women in heterosexual relationships with men, who sustained abuse by men; alternative experiences of motherhood would have added greater depth to data and meaning arising from interviews and would have demonstrated a wider view of intersectional theory. Seeking to understand the views

of health professionals such as Health Visitors, Midwives or GPs, might have also brought an additional perspective to the study, however this was avoided due to the researcher's desire to understand mothers' experiences of domestic abuse, and also due to the plethora of research that already exists that seeks to understand the experiences of health professionals. To include a second phase of research to understand health professional perspectives had potential to dilute the meaning derived from the study, and fail to adequately meet the gap in literature that had previously been identified.

Interpretative research is commonly influenced by the researcher's pre-existing understanding and experience and is often the focus of judgement and scrutiny; however, Heidegger (1962, 1996) advocated against bracketing, the suspension of existing attitudes and beliefs, instead suggesting that researchers make these known and explicit, thus being less likely to adversely influence and provide bias to the study process. Efforts were made to be familiar with the domestic abuse phenomenon, supported by an in-depth literature review coupled with practice experience, and a strategy to accept participant experiences as the truth, without scrutiny or question. Dibley *et al* (2020) suggest this closeness to phenomena enhances the ability to uncover meaning and supports participants to share their experiences without judgement or fear. Additionally, the novice researcher provided a further weakness to the study, however this was mitigated for, by undertaking study of hermeneutic research methods, participating in supervision, keeping a reflexive journal and by undertaking a pilot study to enhance confidence in the use of interview technique and data collection tools (Darwasheh, 2014; Doody and Doody, 2015).

Unfortunately, the study was also hindered by technology failure, as one interview failed to record, and therefore transcription was not possible, and the researcher was reliant on notes made during and following the interview for analysis. Although the researcher was able to record the key events and experiences, the inability to read and re-read transcripts, and dwell with the data to establish links and build meaning limited the interpretation and richness of meaning that could have arisen from this participant's experiences and contribution to knowledge (Dibley *et al*, 2020, p125).

The following chapter will discuss reflexivity and the author's reflections relating to the study.

11 Reflections and reflexivity

11.1 Reflections of women's participation in domestic abuse research

As with any study involving human participants, and particularly with vulnerable groups, this study was subject to rigorous ethical scrutiny from the Research Ethics Committee, as described in Chapter 5, section 5.5.3. It has been suggested that the ethical scrutiny is heightened by the presumption that all sensitive research causes harm, and that risk adverse cultures drive this interrogative approach (Downes, Kelly and Westmarland, 2014). Although ethical approvals are largely supported, it is suggested by Westmarland and Bows (2019) that heightened ethical scrutiny can adversely affect the volume of research carried out in this area and affect outcomes for survivors.

It has traditionally been perceived that to be referred to as 'vulnerable' in research, means to lack ability to understand and assess risks and potential consequences of participating (Downes *et al*, 2014). However, considering the prevalence of domestic abuse within our societies, it can be determined that many participants will be survivors, and women in this study have proved to be active and skilful agents, rather than passive victims as suggested by Westmarland and Bows (2019).

The participants in this study were all survivors of abuse; like much other research, follow up conversations with some of the participants confirmed that they found their involvement to be a positive experience (Dragiewicz *et al*, 2023). Although some were upset during interviews, none of the participants described, or were observed to experience trauma as a result of reliving their abuse. Like findings in Dragiewicz *et al*'s (2023) study, all participants were driven by a desire to help others and viewed that their involvement could lead to greater benefits to themselves and others, which were more substantial than any perceived risks or threats to their wellbeing.

All participants told me that they had worked through their experiences and trauma and were now able to support their friends, who were also experiencing abuse. Many participants said they were able to identify emotional abuse in their friend's relationships and help to seek specialist support. Even for the small number of

participants who were still upset by their experiences, they all freely gave their time and honesty in the hope that other women would not suffer the same abuse.

It is also worth noting that all participants had received specialist support from Women's Aid during their abuse journeys, and therefore, had already told their stories to others before me. None were reliving their experiences for the first time and therefore had some insight into how recalling their experiences would impact on them. Several participants also reported that their involvement in this research was positive in that they were being heard, which reflects the views of Synder (2016) ; they recalled that as I was there to listen, not offer any advice, or with any professional duty or agenda, this allowed them to speak freely with candour. Although they had spoken about their experiences prior to this participation, they did divulge that there were details in their accounts that they were speaking about for the first time. It is hoped that this reflects the level of comfort and confidence participants had in both me and the research process. All participants were interested to read a summarised version of the study outcomes when they become available.

The researcher in hermeneutic research is a vital part of the research process, and a reflective diary was kept to record thoughts, feelings and to help examine my role throughout the research journey. Although I had experience of supporting women who had been abused within their intimate relationships, I was still moved by hearing their accounts first-hand. Considering we had not previously met, I was surprised by their trust and willingness to tell their stories.

There was a notable level of detail often progressed as the interviews went on, with some participants revealing more sensitive and detailed accounts nearer the end of the interviews. This suggested to me that women began to feel more comfortable as the interviews progressed and felt a level of comfort and confidence that there would be no judgement because of their experiences. Rapport was easy to develop with all women in the study, and a natural demonstration of empathy and compassion facilitated and supported them to share their lived experiences. This was not a tactical display of empathy or compassion for the purposes of research activity, but a human interaction that conveyed to the women that there was an understanding of the abuse they had survived, and a genuine gratitude to them for sharing their stories. I am sceptical that this level of empathy and rapport development could have been

achieved without prior experience of supporting women with domestic abuse experiences.

Many women in the study had participated in programmes to help them recover from their experiences and support them to have healthier relationships in the future. This was evident, that many appeared to have great insight into their pasts and were confident their future relationships would not repeat those of their past. Some women had emerged from their abusive relationships having had specialist support, with an ability to empower and support other women with similar experiences.

11.2 Reflexivity and the research process

Reflexivity is an essential aspect of hermeneutic research (Cope, 2017), therefore it was important to continually, and critically examine my own role in the research process to enhance the integrity of the study. Examining my own values and understanding of the phenomenon helped to manage any personal biases, and make these explicit. Collaboration with the supervisory team throughout the research process was also supportive to ensure that various perceptions were considered and subjective interpretations avoided.

I was also aware that my role in data collection was a key factor in the quality of data obtained through interviews. It was important I held an in-depth knowledge of the phenomenon, and the context in which it existed for the study participants. Challenges did arise while trying to simultaneously listen, understand, ask follow up questions, take notes and descriptions, whilst also ensuring personal beliefs and values were managed so as to not influence the data collected. My ability to connect with the participants however, was a crucial factor in the success of the data collection process, whereby vulnerable women disclosed their sensitive and distressing experiences.

11.3 Theoretical frameworks

Intersectionality and feminist theory have been closely aligned for some time, therefore these two theories appeared to be legitimate and relevant theories to support the

study. Intersectionality had been identified to support the study at the outset due to Crenshaw's work (1989) and its origins from black feminism, and it was anticipated that this theory would help me as the researcher recognise and understand how differing forms of oppression and marginalisation intersect, to support women's voices to be heard.

Feminist theory has several variations, and although these were explored as potential theories to underpin the study, none of the existing feminist theories were felt to truly support understanding of views and experiences of women who were mothers. On initial review, Matricentric Feminism, it was agreed with the supervisory team, provided a theoretical framework that supported the views of mothers to be heard and understood, in a way that other feminist theory did not.

I also felt that Matricentric Feminism could be more practically applied in practice, and less complex than intersectionality as it focused on similarities and shared experiences between women rather than highlighting differences. Matricentric feminism also allowed me to focus on specific marginalisation, and the evolving role of mothers, whereas intersectionality only served to offer a broader explanation of women's oppression, without the nuances of motherhood, which was felt to be less useful in this study context (O'Reilly, 2019; Garland-McKinney and Meinersmann, 2022).

Therefore although intersectionality offered a framework to understand the various overlapping points of oppression, it was considered to be less useful than Matricentric Feminism in this study. Matricentric Feminism provided a lens through which to understand the needs of mothers, that were distinct from those of women, and therefore this theory became iteratively more prominent throughout the study, and consequently was more useful for understanding and learning the experiences of participants.

The following chapters will consider the conclusions in more details, and the recommendations arising from the research evidence.

12 Conclusions

Study Aim

Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse: exploring the relationship between mothers and health professionals during historic periods of domestic abuse to identify how these might prevent or promote disclosures of abuse.

At the outset of this study, the following **study objectives** were identified:

1. To collect and chronologically record, mothers' retrospective experiences of domestic abuse
2. To explore the factors that influence mothers' decisions to disclose domestic abuse to health professionals
3. To develop an understanding of the influencing factors that impact on mothers' experiences of domestic abuse
4. To develop an understanding of the role health professionals take in supporting mothers who are experiencing domestic abuse
5. To identify supportive mechanisms to mothers experiencing domestic abuse

The study, through its design and methodology, has addressed each of the objectives above. Chapter 7 has detailed how mothers' experiences have been collected and recorded and Chapter 8 has presented the findings emerging from the individual interview narratives, and Chapter 9 responds with critical analysis to the remaining four objectives. The study has presented evidence that has arisen directly from the voices of the participants, and, along with research evidence, has enabled a variety of conclusions to be drawn which are relevant for policy and practice. Conclusions are often applicable to a range of healthcare professionals and settings, however others have potential to contribute to the evidence base driving health visiting and midwifery practice in Scotland and the UK. This chapter will summarise the various conclusions which will then lead to generate recommendations for policy and practice.

12.1 Routine Enquiry

As discussed in Chapter 9, Section 9.2, routine enquiry for domestic abuse was poorly undertaken by health professionals, particularly in health visiting, midwifery and GP practice, indicating that more can be done to create conditions where women feel able

to discuss abuse. There was a lack of direct questioning and this appears to have been partly due to health professionals preferring selective enquiry approaches, or broad, and vague questioning, which the study found to be ineffective in eliciting disclosures. These difficulties support what has been identified in earlier reviews of literature. Abusive partners often accompanied women to health appointments in the perinatal period, however health professionals rarely used creative methods to see women by themselves to create conditions for disclosures. Like other literature (Feder et al, 2009), women found routine enquiry acceptable, and expected health professionals to ask about abuse, even though they might not disclose at that point. The study also highlighted that not all health professional practice is in line with policy and procedure. To support women to make disclosures and seek early help, health professionals need knowledge and skills, to increase their confidence at instigating conversations about abuse and implementing and responding to routine enquiry consistently and effectively.

Women had a poor understanding of what constitutes abuse, especially abuse that is emotional and non-physical, including controlling, coercive behaviours, and financial abuse. Study findings highlighted in Section 8.4.2 demonstrated that disclosure of abuse to any kind of health professional was uncommon, and a plethora of barriers existed, including personal, health and cultural considerations; however women were more likely to disclose to family or friends. These findings support what is cited in literature, and Health Visitors and Midwives have a role to play here in addressing myths and raising awareness of non violent types of abuse, to remove barriers and increase their willingness to seek support.

12.2 Nature and knowledge of abuse

Domestic abuse was found to be cyclical and repetitive, with women having a lack of awareness of non-violent abuse, including emotional abuse, coercive and controlling behaviours and financially motivated abuse. Emotional abuse was discussed in Section 9.3, and found to be present for all the women in the study, either in isolation or alongside other forms of abuse. As reflected in similar research, physical abuse was rarely reported, even when severe injuries; however, when abuse was disclosed it was usually unplanned, to friends, family members, or to the Police following a physical assault witnessed by others, or following significant escalation. Abuse rarely

ceased after relationships ended, and child contact arrangements were frequently used as a vehicle for abuse to be perpetrated. This is also reflective of existing domestic abuse literature. Understanding the nature of abuse is important for health professionals, especially Health Visitors and Midwives, to fully understand women's decision making, and to identify triggers where escalation is likely.

Like similar studies, violent physical abuse was associated with perpetrator alcohol use, and violent sexual abuse always accompanied physical abuse. The findings, in Section 8.6 indicated that violent sexual abuse was more prevalent in relationships when there was a ten year age gap between partners. The impact of age and age gaps is not an area that is very evident in current research, however due to the small sample, and research approach for the study, correlations cannot be confirmed. Non-violent sexual abuse is not an area well studied and was rarely recognised by participants as abuse; a variety of rape myths existed which were likely to account for this.

Women were subject to abuse within their intimate relationships and also within wider family relationships, as discussed in Chapter 9, Section 9.7, confirming that violence against women and girls has complex and varied presentations (WHO, 2021). The data suggested that financial abuse was very prevalent, however there was a low awareness of this type of abuse amongst the participants. Although this was not cited as a reason for not disclosing abuse or leaving the relationship, critical analysis has identified that lack of access to money, and financial dependence on the perpetrator is likely to be a contributing factor. Health professionals who are able to refer to specialist services can enable them to seek financial help and advice that might support leaving a relationship that otherwise felt unachievable. The data indicated that connections existed between financial abuse and perpetrator substance misuse and it was also observed in these cases that there was large age difference between women and their partners.

12.3 Relationships with professionals

Section 8.12 and Section 9.11.3 described how study participants sought support from their GP for disturbances to their mental health, however were unlikely to disclose domestic abuse to them, and did not identify them as professionals who they would

seek help from in such circumstances. This confirms what research already states about the limited role of GPs in supporting women with domestic abuse, however it is unclear from existing literature why women seek support more readily from their GP for mental health issues. This study has highlighted that the complexity of domestic abuse differs from women's mental health difficulties, and the desire to seek support is driven by differing factors that are yet to be seen in contemporary research.

Similar to research identified in the literature review, participant relationships with Health Visitors and Midwives were mostly positive, and these relationships proved to be important to women. Despite this, unlike the suggestions from earlier research, a positive relationship alone was not sufficient to promote a disclosure of abuse. A combination of factors contributed to help-seeking and disclosure, including abuse escalation, threats to safety of children, abuse being witnessed by others, and due to personal thresholds. Relationships with professionals needed to be well-established, trusting and non-judgemental, and findings suggest these relationships were enhanced once abuse had been disclosed. Women described positive relationships following disclosure, and reported that they could speak openly to Midwives, Health Visitors and GPs once they were aware of the abuse they had experienced.

12.4 Mothers

It was evident from the study findings that participants were frequently mothering in challenging circumstances, and always prioritised the safety of their children during periods of abuse. Increased threat to their children was a key motivator for women disclosing abuse and ending abusive relationships, as demonstrated in Section 9.2.3, and this also supports earlier research which confirms the role of children within abusive relationships. Abusers frequently targeted women's reproductive capacity and role of mothers as a vehicle to perpetrate abuse, as described in Section 9.3.3. The presence of children was not a deterrent to perpetrators. These findings are not well studied elsewhere, with reproductive abuse being a relatively new phenomenon, however this study highlights that this is a very real emerging threat to women and their children.

Financial abuse was reported by several of the study participants, as illustrated in Section 9.9, reflecting the widespread nature of this type of abuse. Mothers were often

impacted by financial abuse, either as a means of control, or due to their partner's decision to prioritise drug use; either would be likely to limit opportunities for leaving a relationship, and seeking support from others. Financial abuse reduced the participants' ability to care for their children, by restricting resources available for nappies, milk and other necessities. Mothers also incurred debt during abusive relationships due to the financial control by their partners, which lasted for many years after separation.

Abusers often targeted women during pregnancy, or targeted the unborn baby. Similar to existing research, findings confirmed that in all cases, abuse continued or escalated during pregnancy, as indicated in Section 9.8.1. Despite this, women were less likely to disclose abuse during this period, even with routine enquiry from Midwives and Health Visitors. Abusive partners also used women's role as mothers and the relationship with their child as a weapon to perpetrate further abuse, even after the intimate relationship had ended.

12.5 Mental Health

Findings highlighted in Section 8.12.2, demonstrated that screening for mental ill health and postnatal depression in the perinatal period was widespread by health professionals. Participants in the study were commonly diagnosed with post-natal depression (PND) when presenting in the perinatal period with mental health disturbances. There was a lack of evidence from participants in the study that GPs had undertaken comprehensive assessments to confirm that mental ill health was PND, and not attributable to domestic abuse, and this is not an area well studied in other domestic abuse research.

As existing literature confirms, mental health was always impacted by domestic abuse, and there was a close association between mental ill health and domestic abuse. Existing mental health conditions were exacerbated in the presence of domestic abuse, and perpetrators often weaponised mental ill health to control and manipulate. The mental health and wellbeing of women often persisted long after the abuse had ended.

12.6 Trauma and Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs)

All of the participants in the study had a number of adverse childhood experiences, and often had multiple abusive relationships across their life-course, and experienced different types of abuse. Those participants with higher numbers of ACEs had experienced a higher number of abusive relationships, types of abuse, and reported the most severe mental health disturbances, which is reflective of seminal and recent ACE research.

12.7 Structural and societal issues

Misogyny and gendered stereotypes heighten the risk of perpetrating domestic abuse, and findings from this study indicate that misogyny and patriarchal attitudes remained in abundance, and created environments and communities whereby domestic abuse was deemed to be acceptable. The consequences for women in this study was the creation of mother/woman-blaming culture that has contributed to stigma, feelings of shame and myths that has prevented disclosures of abuse. Although health professionals alone cannot address these structural attitudes, they are able to address stereotypes, and validate their experiences, to create a narrative whereby abuse is not acceptable. In turn, this is likely to form stronger relationships and promote earlier disclosures.

These conclusions will now lead to recommendations for policy and practice, which will be outlined in the following chapter.

13 Recommendations

This chapter will consider the disclosure model, Figure 16, in Section 9.2.4 which illustrated that the presence of positive relationships with professionals, increased awareness of non-physical abuse and effective routine enquiry are all required to facilitate positive domestic abuse disclosures. With the evidence from the study conclusions from Chapter 10, and this model in mind, the various recommendations for future practice, policy and research will also be discussed.

13.1 Recommendations for practice

A number of recommendations have been identified, some applicable to all healthcare professionals, and some that are specific to health visiting, midwifery and GP practice. These will be discussed below.

13.1.1 Routine enquiry

For routine enquiry to be successful, and delivered in alignment to CEL 41 (Scottish Government, 2008), health professionals are required to have a high level of knowledge and understanding of domestic abuse that will promote confidence in how they approach questioning, and how they respond to disclosures. Additionally, all women need to have a robust understanding of the types of abuse, and as the participants were not always aware, and particularly whilst experiencing the abuse, awareness raising is required to ensure that potential victims know about the nature of non-violent abuse in addition to physical abuse. Midwifery services are ideally placed to educate pregnant women and those in the peri-natal period, even including those in the pre-conception period where possible. It is common for mothers to be supported and in contact with Health Visitors who are also well placed to provide education and increase knowledge of domestic abuse through supportive conversations and educational materials that are provided following a baby's birth.

1. HVs, Midwives, GPs and GP Practice staff, e.g. Nurse Practitioners, Practice Nurses, often have contact with mothers in the post-natal period and should have a robust and comprehensive understanding of domestic abuse, and be confident in recognising indicators of abuse. Additionally, they should be confident in using domestic abuse assessment tools to support their

assessments in practice, escalate concerns appropriately, and make referrals to local MARACs and specialist services.

2. Raising awareness of domestic abuse is required in the following materials, to help women understand the non-physical types of abuse:
 - a) Child Health and Health Visitor resources such as Red Book/Health Promotion Apps, Ready Steady Baby, Ready Steady Toddler, Local Health Visitor Apps used by health professionals
 - b) Materials provided to women from Maternity Services
 - c) Posters and promotional materials available in GP practices and other health settings
 - d) All above materials to include myth busting and challenge gendered stereotypes
3. Routine enquiry should be incorporated into conversations throughout episodes of care to create multiple opportunities for disclosure. Health professionals working with women should be aware that they might need to have opportunities created for them when they see professionals on their own, in the absence of their partner.
4. All health and social care professionals should have an understanding of domestic abuse and be skilled in identifying indicators of abuse, and sensitively using routine enquiry.
5. Health Visitors should consistently enquire about domestic abuse in line with their respective service delivery models (for example, UHVP in Scotland), including at the antenatal contact. Where partners are present further opportunities should be created to ask about abuse.
6. Midwives and GPs should also enquire about abuse during periods of care, paying particular attention to triggers, for example pregnancy and at the end of a relationship.

7. HVs, Midwives and GPs should have a good knowledge and understanding of local resources and specialist services, and how to access them.
8. HVs, Midwives, and GPs should recognise the role of friends and families in the women's network, in helping her to access specialist services.
9. Promotional materials directed at informal networks are required to promote early help-seeking.

13.1.2 Education and training

Domestic abuse education is required across health services on an on-going basis, to ensure there is knowledge and understanding about:

1. Cyclical nature of abuse
2. Repeat victims in different relationships to prevent abuse
3. Non-violent forms of abuse, including coercive control and financial abuse
4. Women's knowledge of types of abuse and the potential impact of making assumptions that women know what perpetrator behaviours are abusive
5. Knowledge of the impact of living in rural communities, and how cultural considerations impact on domestic abuse disclosures
6. Gendered nature of abuse
7. Impact of poverty, ACEs, drugs and alcohol on domestic abuse experiences
8. Escalation points and identification of escalating behaviours

As well as education, all health professionals should also receive training in how to competently and confidently:

1. Instigate conversations with women about domestic abuse and provide reassurance to allay worries and fears

2. Identify indicators of abuse
3. Use routine enquiry instead of selective enquiry and direct questioning
4. Respond to disclosures
5. Work in line with local and national policy and guidance
6. Avoid language which infers blame/judgement/assumptions or gendered/patriarchal stereotypes

13.1.3 Relationships with professionals

Although positive relationships with women alone are not sufficient to promote disclosures, they are imperative, and can be successful when coupled with additional supportive influences:

1. Women in all health settings should be offered contact with a consistent health professional wherever possible in order to build relationships. This is especially important in Health Visiting and Midwifery services, and reflects the ambitions of the UHVP (Scottish Government, 2015) and Best Start (Scottish Government, 2017).
2. All health professionals should display non-judgemental, supportive behaviours that are conducive to building trust and empathy. This is particularly important for health and social care professionals within a multi-agency context, where concerns or risks exist in relation to domestic abuse.
3. Health professionals should ensure that practice is not influenced by their own judgements and perceptions of domestic abuse, and should avoid making assumptions about who may or may not be affected.
4. Health Visitors and Midwives should raise awareness of their roles and remit to those who are new to their service, paying particular attention to those entering the country.

5. Health Visitors and Midwives should inform and reassure service users regarding the confidential nature of service delivery, particularly in small communities.
6. An alternative health professional should be made available where personal or social connections or relationships exist with women to support open and honest discussions about abuse.

13.1.4 Nature and knowledge of abuse

The study findings have identified the following recommendations for practice relating to the nature and knowledge of abuse, are required:

1. Ongoing risk assessment by health and social care professionals is required in the post-separation period, where abuse is known to occur
2. Increased proactive screening of domestic abuse by Midwives, Health Visitors and GPs
3. Ongoing assessment, of the potential for child abuse occurring within child contact arrangements as a means of continuing to exert power over women
4. Increasing awareness of the cyclical nature of abuse and how it impacts of women's' willingness to disclose abuse and end abusive relationships

13.1.5 Mental Health

Mental health of abuse survivors is always impacted, therefore action is required to effectively screen, respond and manage mental ill health for women experiencing abuse. The following recommendations have been made relating to the mental health of domestic abuse survivors:

1. Exploration of domestic abuse is needed where PND is a concern in the perinatal period, by HV, GP & Midwives
2. Additional support offered to women with existing mental health conditions in the perinatal period, particularly where domestic abuse is known or suspected.

13.1.6 ACEs

The presence of ACEs has a significant bearing on how women experience abuse. The following recommendations relate to early identification and awareness of ACEs:

1. Consideration of screening and assessment of ACEs by Health Visitors, Midwives, and GPs, to increase insight and support individuals where this is required.

These recommendations relate to healthcare practice, however there is also relevance for policy makers, which will be considered next.

13.2 Recommendations for policy makers

The Universal Health Visitor Pathway in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2015) prescribes the use of routine enquiry for domestic abuse at each contact, reflecting the Chief Executive Letter (CEL 41: Scottish Government, 2008). Study findings suggest this remains the most appropriate method to support identification and response to domestic abuse by health professionals. Study findings suggest women accept routine enquiry, expect to be asked about abuse, and want to know whether health professionals are potentially someone who they can disclose to when the time is right for them. Without routine enquiry happening, this would not be possible.

Many barriers preventing disclosure are entrenched in gendered stereotypes and myths about domestic abuse. To rectify these misunderstandings, several actions are required:

13.3 Short term actions specific to health and social care settings

Materials to promote awareness of the types of abuse should be widely available across all health settings, including NHS Inform, and in Health Visitor, Midwife, and GP materials. Raising awareness of domestic abuse should continue to be integral to the public health role of Health Visitors.

13.4 Medium term actions

Continuing education for all health professionals is required to ensure confidence and competence to identify and respond effectively to domestic abuse. This includes education within higher education programmes, including Pre Registration Nursing, Medical and GP training, Midwifery and Specialist Community Public Health Nursing (SCPHN) programmes, to ensure students and newly qualified professionals have a good understanding of domestic abuse and the necessary skills to discuss with women, identify and respond to abuse disclosures.

Healthy relationship information should be consistently provided to all young people within education curriculum materials to increase awareness of all types of domestic abuse and the impact on psychological and physical health, including that of children.

Training and education is needed to address the gaps in knowledge, perceptions and attitudes, to facilitate improved multi-agency responses to domestic abuse

13.5 Long term actions

Addressing gender stereotypes is essential, at local, national and international structural levels, to influence messages portrayed through the media, which contribute to how abuse is perceived. Gendered and patriarchal language and messages require long term, consistent attention, lobbying and challenge.

13.6 Recommendations for future research

Domestic abuse is a broad topic that has already received much attention in literature. The study identified relationships between concepts, and has been able to confidently suggest recommendations for practice to support early help-seeking from those experiencing abuse. However, the study also highlighted areas for further study and exploration that could guide future practice and policy.

Existing research rarely studies the lived experiences of abuse survivors, possibly due to the anticipated ethical hurdles that exist for researchers. This study has, however, demonstrated that it is possible to overcome these challenges, and further research using interpretive methods would be beneficial to further hear the voices of those who have direct experience of abuse. Having a good understanding of lived experiences, will help researchers to further influence practice to continue to improve services for women, and all individuals who are marginalised.

For example, the following would benefit from further research:

1. The presence of sexual violence in intimate relationships, particularly where there is a large (ten years or over) age gap between partners
2. The influence of age and ethnicity on disclosing abuse and help-seeking
3. Disclosing abuse and help-seeking in the post-natal period and relationship with maternal age

4. The impact of perpetrator substance misuse, particularly cannabis use on non-violent abuse, including controlling and emotionally abusive behaviours
5. The connection between substance misuse, financial abuse and emotional abuse appears to be a new phenomenon, and requires further exploration
6. The impact of emotional and non-violent abuse on mental health conditions, and maternal mental health
7. The impact of domestic abuse on mental health conditions and related disorders e.g. bi-polar disorder, borderline personality disorder, and the impact of mental health stigma on disclosures
8. The relationship between domestic abuse and mental health in the peri-natal period; this includes presentations of postnatal depression diagnoses
9. If and why mothers are more likely to seek help for peri-natal mental health problems, than for domestic abuse
10. Help-seeking in rural communities; how the position of women in their communities might influence their willingness to disclose abuse and seek help
11. The relationship between ACEs and those perpetrating domestic abuse
12. The relationship between ACEs and those experiencing domestic abuse. This includes understanding more about repeat victims in different relationships and the possible association with victim ACEs
13. The use of routine enquiry in primary care settings and practice
14. The role of informal support networks for women experiencing domestic abuse; particularly their influence on help-seeking for specialist support, and promoting health and wellbeing

15. The relationships between women experiencing domestic abuse and health professionals when they are receiving multi-agency support
16. Preventing women becoming victims, and understand violence against women and girls out with a domestic abuse context within an intimate relationship
17. Associations between unemployment and non-violent abuse

14 Dissemination of study findings

Applying research to practice and policy requires dissemination at local and national level, using a variety of methods suitable to the target audience (Keen and Todres, 2007). This study has highlighted important findings and recommendations relevant for health visiting, midwifery and GP practice that can be applicable in Scotland and across the UK. Dissemination will require various strategies:

A summary of conclusions and recommendations will be shared with participants in the study.

Conclusions and recommendations will be shared with health visiting and midwifery managers, and Public Protection teams of participating Health Boards, and of other Boards in Scotland. National forums such as 'HV Leads' will be approached to share key messages.

Opportunities have been secured to present findings at national forums and conferences within Scotland and the UK, for example Institute of Health Visiting Conference, and Royal College of Nursing Conference.

Findings will be shared with GPs networks.

A summary of conclusions and recommendations will be shared with the participating Women's Aid organisation.

Publication in appropriate nursing journals will be sought to disseminate findings to reach a wider international audience.

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16 List of appendices

1	Search strings	
2	Prisma diagram	
3	Summary of literature review research studies	
3a	Updated Summary of literature review research studies	
3b	Patterning chart	
3c	PAGER framework	
4	Overview of interpretative research designs	
5	Feminist approaches	
6	Summary of main ethical principles	
7	National Research Ethics Committee application	
8	Participant Information Sheet	
9	Information for Health Visitors	
10	Information for Women's Aid Organisations	
11	Consent form	
12	Life History Calendar	
13	Interview schedule	
14	Participant safeguarding checklist	
15	Insurance certificate	
16	Organisation Information Document	
17	Research protocol	
18	MSc certificate	
19	University Ethical Guidelines	
20	Letter of favourable opinion	
21	Mind-map of codes and themes	
22	Women's Aid Model of Change	

16.1 Appendix 1 – Search strings

Database	Search terms/strings	Results
Cinahl	Domestic violence OR domestic abuse OR intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND therapeutic relationship AND disclosure	137
Cinahl	Domestic violence or domestic abuse or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND therapeutic relationship	421
Cinahl	Health visit* AND parent relationship	33
Cinahl	Strengths-based approach AND health visit* or specialist community public health nurs*	28
Cinahl	Domestic violence or domestic abuse or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND health visit* or specialist community public health nurs*	346
Cinahl	Mother or parent or woman or women AND helper relationship	50
Cinahl	Domestic violence or domestic abuse or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND health visit* or specialist community public health nurs* AND routine enquiry	26
EBSCOhost	Health visit* AND parent relationship	40
EBSCOhost	Strengths-based approach AND health visit* or specialist community public health nurs*	95
EBSCOhost	Domestic violence or domestic abuse or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND health visit* or specialist community public health nurs* AND routine enquiry	32
EBSCO host	Mother or parent AND parent helper AND relationship	304
EBSCO host	Mother or parent or woman or women AND helper relationship	378
EBSCO host	Health visit* or specialist community public health nurs* AND collaboration or partnership	1666
PsychArticles	Health visit* AND domestic violence or domestic abuse or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND disclosure	5
PsychArticles	“Help-seeking” AND domestic violence or domestic abuse or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND health professionals	168
PsychArticles	Routine inquiry AND domestic violence or domestic abuse or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND health professionals	13
PsychArticles	Disclos* AND domestic abuse or domestic violence or intimate partner violence or gender-based violence AND therapeutic relationship	162

16.2 Appendix 2 – Prisma Diagram

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

16.3 Appendix 3 - Summary of Literature Review Research Studies

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
1	Ahmad et al, 2009	Interpretivist, exploratory study	Why doesn't she seek help for partner abuse?	Barriers/delay help seeking from professionals: Social stigma, gender roles, marriage obligations, loss of supports, myths only seek help after sustaining severe injuries	South Asian female victims	Toronto
2	Ahmad et al 2016	Rapid Literature Review	IPV screening in Emergency Dept: rapid review of literature	Healthcare related factors - knowledge, awareness, attitudes to IPV not offered opportunities to disclose additional role for some staff, own attitudes to IPV Lack of attentiveness/empathy need training and support organisational factors - lack of privacy and time, lack of prompts/reminder to ask policies/protocols often lacking and referral pathways Patient related factors - lack of readiness, lack of confidence, embarrassment, fear, fear of abuser or losing children, language barriers, presence of others, environment - needing trust, respecting privacy	Health professionals	ED

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
3	Bacchus et al 2016	Nested, Interpretivist study	Opening the door	<p>Women happy to be asked about IPV, understand reasons why asked easier to talk to home visitor rather than family/friends</p> <p>Women often implicated themselves - feel to blame</p> <p>Concerns that disclosure will result in repercussions - more violence, taking children away, unwanted police involvement</p> <p>Trust needed to disclose - in staged manner - affected if past events had led to trust being abused</p> <p>Home visitor attributes - honesty, caring, friendly, knowledge, confidence, no discomfort</p> <p>Safety planning was welcomed, knowing about agencies to help, geographic isolation made it difficult - poor knowledge about hotlines etc., isolated.</p>	Female victims	Peri-natal home visiting, USA
4	Beynon et al 2012	Mixed methods study – survey & open ended questions	Why nurses and physicians ask (or don't) about partner violence	<p>Barriers - time, behaviours of women living with abuse, lack of training, partner presence, cultural practices, resources, space/privacy, personal discomfort, poor management support.</p> <p>Facilitators - training, community/professional resources to refer to, professionals tools and policies/guidance, routine enquiry, own IPV experience.</p>	Professionals - physicians and nurses	Canada, hospital setting
5	Bidmead, Cowley & Grocott 2016	Interpretivist study	The parental contribution to the parent-HV relationship	<p>Parent qualities - trust friendliness, trust in HV, openness, honesty, interest, respect</p> <p>parent skills - communication, information seeking, reciprocity</p>	HVs and parents	UK, HV setting

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
6	Bradbury Jones et al 2014	Interpretivist study	DA Awareness and recognition among primary healthcare professionals and abused women	<p>Many women don't identify as being abused</p> <p>Women want professional to see the abuse and be direct</p> <p>Women find it acceptable to be asked but resistance to do so from professionals</p> <p>women do conceal abuse - feelings of shame/stigma/removal of children - not always able to name abuse or see it as abuse</p> <p>Unrecognised bias and values - professionals did not always see abuse either - dual silence, no-one says anything</p>	Healthcare professionals, Midwives, HVs, GPs	UK
7	Brook & Salmon 2015	Interpretivist study	Qualitative study exploring parental perspectives and involvement in HV services during the HV implementation plan in South West England	<p>Valued personal contact with HV and welcome home visits rather than clinic setting</p> <p>Consistency of same HV</p> <p>use of EBP by HV rather than anecdotal but some flexibility and personal approach</p> <p>characteristics of relationship between parent and HV - effective communication, emphasis that relationship essential for parents to discuss concerns.</p> <p>Credibility and honesty, able to give time to parents, HVs that follow through and call back as promised</p>	Parents	UK HV setting

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
8	Clancy and Svensson 2010	Interpretivist study, ethnographic	Perceptions of public health nursing consultations	Development of relationship continuous contact - trust, respectful, dialogue and empowerment, openness, honesty Live up to PHN expectations - not always honest about problems - feel inferior power relationships importance of need to maintain professional relationship	Nurses, parents and young people attending clinic	Norway
9	Cross and Cheyne 2017	Interpretivist study Realist evaluation-informed case study	Strengths based approaches: a realist evaluation of implementation in maternity services in Scotland	Midwives found to be unfamiliar with strengths-based approaches - training needed Managers reports SBA being used in practice Time pressures in urban areas common language	Women and midwives case study	Maternity care Scotland
10	Damra et al 2015	Interpretivist study	Pregnant woman's experiences of IPV and seeking help from healthcare professionals	Barriers: lack of privacy/continuity of care/time - women not satisfied with process/responses/follow up. Lack of screening - lack of training for GPs - often women not asked Want to be screened and want information to be displayed in healthcare areas prefer women to ask - cultural considerations Need secure relationship, non-blaming feel DV is ignored Prefer women to ask, and home visits to increase privacy	Pregnant women	Jordan

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
11	Decker et al 2012	Mixed methods – Grounded theory	Violence related coping, help seeking and health care based intervention preferences, Mumbai, India	Only seek help when not able to hide injuries Fear of disclosing to family - social repercussions and economic dependence not always aware of formal supports acceptability of clinic based screening	Perinatal women	India
12	Dymytryshyn et al 2015	Interpretative descriptive study	Long term home visiting with vulnerable young mothers	Theme emerging from FGs - relationship and barriers to relationship building. Study qualitative study of secondary analysis of FGs and interpretative description of individual interviews	Young women	Jordan

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
13	Evans and Feder 2014	Interpretivist study	Help seeking among women survivors of DV	<p>Little known about part played by health pros in women's help seeking strategies</p> <p>motivations to seek help/disclose - protect children/family members/reduce own isolation/result of crisis e.g. rape/assault/homeless</p> <p>Barriers - psychological, social and emotional reasons - self-blame, socially isolated - loss of knowing what is normal. Depression/low self-esteem, burden to others, shame embarrassment, fear of judgement - family/cultural norms, fearful of change, experience of previous unhelpful disclosures - triggers of violence response</p> <p>Rarely disclosed to formal supports</p> <p>informal support - more likely to disclose to friends/family who facilitate involvement from DA agencies.</p> <p>Role of health pros - minimal GP support and low expectations from GP, lack of continuity of GP - disclosure to GP often patient led rather than response to enquiry - inadequate response by most GPs</p>	Women survivors of DV	UK
14	Feder et al 2009	Systematic review	How far does screening women for DV in different healthcare settings meet the criteria for a screening programme	<p>Screening for DV, high prevalence and high public health issue. Variety of screening tools available and relatively valid/reliable.</p> <p>Screening acceptable to most women</p> <p>insufficient evidence for screening programme in health services generally or in specific settings</p>		

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
15	Francis, Loxton & James 2016	Interpretivist study – narrative enquiry	The culture of pretence: a hidden barrier to recognising disclosing and ending domestic violence	Various barriers prevent disclosure: not all women recognise relationships were abusive/denied or minimised abuse to cope with IPV - normalising violence fear/shame/embarrassment/humiliation if shared relationship to others Also financial barriers and emotionally constrained, self-blame leading to feeling need to remedy relationships non-judgmental open supportive professionals who understood considered crucial Women found difficult to obtain flexible support from services	Female victims & professionals who had supported women	Australia
16	Hasselle et al 2019	Interpretivist study – exploratory, phenomenology	Barriers to intervention engagement among women experiencing IPV	Various barriers: mental health barriers - depression/anxiety/lack self-worth, ability to trust; pregnancy and health related barriers - health related barriers. Partner related barriers: fear of betraying, fear of repercussions/control over intervention programme/retaliation. Practical barriers: time/scheduling/duration/access to services/transport - limited access to transport, lack of clearly defined benefits/parental duties. Cultural barriers - social stigma, gender roles, normalisation of IPV/ambivalence/lack trust in institutions/services for IPV - perceptive lack of resources	Perinatal female victims	USA

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
17	Heron, Eisma and Brown, 202	Interpretivist study - ethnographic	Barriers and facilitators of disclosing domestic violence to the UK Health Service	Emotional, physical and organizational barriers, additional barriers for ethnic minority women. Facilitators also identified, both diverse, some specific to ethnic groups. Professionals need training and awareness	Women in UK, ethnically diverse sample	UK
18	Hultmann et al 2013	Interpretivist study; mixed methods, standardized survey	Asking routinely about IPV in child and adolescent psychiatric clinic	Attitudes of clinicians: Screening tool seen more as an obstacle than a resource - negative opinions and anxiety, concern about increased harm to patient - upset/distress/destroying therapeutic relationship More urgent matters/uncertainty and personal shortcomings - strong emotions of fear/anxiety also a barrier Written forms easier to ask about DV	Clinicians – MH setting	USA
19	Kirkpatrick et al 2007	Interpretivist study	Working in partnership: user perceptions of intensive home visiting	Positive relationship, non-judgmental	Service users	UK
20	Keeling & Fisher 2015	Interpretivist study, narrative interviews	Health professionals response to women's disclosure of domestic violence	Poor responses by health care professionals Dismissive - validating woman's concerns lack of enquiry by professionals	Female victims	UK

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
21	Lelaurain et al 2017	Systematic review	IPV and help seeking	Focus on severity/increasing violence and help seeking Environmental barriers/non accessible services Health services not concerned need first positive contact, empathy and non-judgmental approaches		
22	Lo Guidice 2015	Qualitative meta synthesis	Pre-natal screening for IPV	Gap between theory and practice.	Professionals	Sweden, USA, NZ
23	Lowoko et al 2011	Positivist study Cross sectional survey	Screening for IPV against women in healthcare Sweden	Only half asked about IPV - not routine or universal - training needed Women pros more likely to screen than males Doctors and nurses more likely to enquire than midwives Inequalities in readiness to screen - need to review protocols/clear guidelines those who screen have low fear of offending women professionals preparedness, available support networks	Screened healthcare staff in hospital	Sweden
24	Lundell et al 2017	Interpretivist study; descriptive methods	Women's experiences with healthcare professionals after suffering from GBV	Feelings of guilt - often reinforced by attitudes of healthcare pros - mainly through questioning their actions/non verbals etc. Lack of interest by healthcare pros - not having undivided attention/interruptions feel not taken seriously, feel less important feel guilty taking up time of healthcare pros - told how busy they are Feel as burden - can open up when given time Need to feel secure to disclose - first impressions important	Female victims	Mexico hospital setting

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
25	McFeely 2016	Mixed methods	Health Visitor response to domestic abuse	Mixed methods - interviews with women victims, FGs with HVs, secondary analysis of police reports. Highlights poor HV response, poor relationship and mistrust.	HVs & female victims	HV setting, UK
26	O'Doherty et al 2015	Systematic review	Screening for women for IPV in healthcare settings	Screening increases the identification of women experiencing IPV x 2 no evidence of cost effectiveness of if increases use of specialist services no method found to be better at disclosing e.g. computer based or face to face lack of evidence for adverse outcomes/health impacts insufficient evidence to ask all women about RE/IPV		
27	Odero et al, 2014	Interpretivist study, ethnographic	Responses to and resources for IPV	Cultural barriers to disclosure - Dependence on men for money/income, male dominant society, lack of services health services - first formal contact for help only if severe injuries Family support often sought first and avoid all support if feelings of shame financial pressures if women leave as dependent on men - if seek legal action, need ID, and most women don't have this.	Pregnant women and service providers	Kenya
28	Peckover 2003	Interpretivist study	I could have just done with a little more help	Qualitative interviews 16 women receiving HV services. Poor response from HVs, women often don't disclose. Especially difficult for BME women.	Female service users	UK

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
29	Prosman, Wong, 2013	Interpretivist study	Why abused women do not seek professional help	Various barriers to disclosure : unawareness of impact of abuse on themselves or children/denial of IPV unfamiliarity and negative experiences with professionals - long waiting lists/lack of info given by profs fear of partner need informal support to seek professional help	Female victims	Netherlands, GP setting
30	Roddy 2013	Interpretivist study Grounded theory and narrative	Client perspectives: the therapeutic challenge of DV counselling	Trust needed before disclose - importance of understanding, degree of empathy, non-judgemental genuine and consistency of counsellor.	DV Victims	UK
31	Rose et al 2010	Interpretivist study cross sectional interview	Barriers and facilitators of disclosures of DV by mental health service users	Service user barriers - fear - fear of SW involvement/not be believed/result in further violence/disruption to family life/consequences of immigration status professionals fear of RE: lack of knowledge/expertise, DA not a priority/limited opportunity/time/partner presence/fear of consequences/medical model/personal discomfort about topic/lack of confidence/complex issue/gender/culture/no indication of IPV. therapeutic engagement necessary	Professionals and patients	MH UK setting

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
32	Rossiter et al, 2012	Interpretivist study	Supporting depressed mothers at home: their views on an innovative relationship based intervention	Empathetic warm genuine personal characteristics predictability of programme and consistent practitioner/continuity increased confidence, reassurance, increased mother baby interactions strengths based/partnership working	Women receiving home visiting parenting service	Australia
33	Saias et al 2016	Mixed methods, Case note study	Parent-provider relationship in home visiting interventions	Home visitors success depends on quality of relationship so trust can be developed quality of relationship depends on relationship itself rather than individual attributes	Case records	French Home visiting
34	Salmon, Baird and White, 2015	Mixed methods Survey and interviews	Women's views and experiences of antenatal enquiry for DA during pregnancy	RE is acceptable to women and expect midwives to ask about DV and respond appropriately RE raises issue so women aware can be discussed at later date and be aware of supports available if decides to leave	Women in maternity services	UK
35	Schaefer 2016	Mixed methods	Personal characteristics of effective home visitors	Effective at forming relationships - empathetic therapeutic relationships self -awareness, lifelong learners, belief in change - using strengths based approaches, ecological approach (Holistic) genuineness, warmth and empathy	Home visitors	USA

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
36	Shanti 2017	Interpretivist study grounded theory	Engaging parents in early head start home based programmes	Forming relationships, building trust, using family strengths, following through: communicating respectfully, recognising cues, sharing common ground. Recognising own bias/self-reflective, bringing in other family members learning family culture. maintaining professionalism maintaining active working relationship	Home visitors	USA
37	Sinclair et al 2016	Systematic review	Scoping review of healthcare literature : compassion	Review of literature surrounding compassion in healthcare. Differences between compassion, empathy and sympathy. Conceptual factors, antecedents, cultivating, relational factors, barriers and enablers.		
38	Spangaro et al 2011	Interpretivist study	Persist persist: qualitative study of women's decision to disclose and perceptions of impact of routine screening for IPV	timing of disclosure important - trust and safety important to women need to be directly asked about IPV given choice whether to disclose disclosure needed trusted person, but will only disclose when deemed safe to do so. Naming abuse/developing connection through workers' caring/knowledge of potential support safety from perpetrator, and safety from being shamed and from others assuming control	Female victims	Australia, mental health, substance misuse, antenatal setting
39	Sundborg et al 2012	Positivist study	Nurses preparedness to care for women exposed to IPV	Poor knowledge of IPV, unsure how to ask, lack of mandate and lack of guidance and organisational support; prejudice, lack of written guidance, policies	Nurses	Primary care setting, Sweden

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
40	Suryavanshi et al 2018	Mixed methods	GBV screening methods preferred by women - Pune, India	Screening for IPV is acceptable to women, but rarely asked in healthcare settings face to face interview favoured by women doctors and nurses preferred people to ask rather than GPs	Women	India, tertiary healthcare setting
41	Svavarsdottir 2010	Interpretivist study – cross sectional	Detecting IPV in clinical settings	Self-reporting procedure on its own did not increase detection of IPV compared with interview - disclosure rate varied depending on methods used as well as type of abuse Women more often disclosed physical abuse in face to face interview. Self-reported instrument saw more disclosures of emotional or sexual abuse mixed methods favourable	Women	Iceland, A&E and antenatal care clinic
42	Tanninen et al 2014	Positivist /Quantitative survey	How resource enhancing family nursing is realized by Finnish parents	Co-operative relationships personal qualities of the family nurses that supported positive relationships	Parents	Finland, Home visiting

	Author	Study design	Title	Themes	Perspective	Setting
43	Taylor et al 2013	Interpretivist study – critical incident techniques (Interviews and FGs)	Health professionals beliefs about domestic abuse and the issue of disclosure	Women and profs do not always share same views Women's want to be asked about DA - some women easier to ask than others profs don't feel comfortable/confident asking about DA Women don't always realise they are being abused Escalation/crisis point resulted in disclosure - disclosure or process rather than singular event Continuity in relationship important for disclosure Opening up a can of worms - profs feel unprepared to deal with what is disclosed	Professionals	HVs, Midwives, GPs. UK
44	Visentin et al 2015	Interpretivist study – exploratory descriptive study	Women's primary care nursing in situations of gender violence	Need to create bond/relationship permeated by trust to break stigma and verbalise situation - need to use empathy and attentive listening, open dialogue and trust Unpreparedness of profs, lack of demand and lack of awareness/confidence in dealing with IPV - training needed	Nurses	Brazil Health Unit
45	Waller et al 2023	Interpretivist grounded theory study	I am the one that needs help.	Help seeking behaviours, theory of help seeking emerged from the study; sociocultural factors, beliefs and agency influence how women seek help.	Abuse survivors, African American	USA
46	Williams et al 2020	Interpretivist study	Disclosing GBV during health care visits.	Factors that facilitate or impede disclosures: Patient-provider connectedness, children, social support, ambiguity in role of provider in addressing GBV, consequences of disclosing	Abuse survivors	USA,

16.4 Appendix 3a - Summary of Literature Review Research Studies

Author and study details	Study design	Data collection methods	Participants	Setting	Language	Country	Sample size
Ahmad et al 2009	Interpretivist, exploratory study	Focus groups	Women victims of abuse	Community	Hindi	Toronto Canada	22
Ahmad et al 2016	Rapid literature review	N/A	N/A	Emergency Dept	English	Global	24 articles
Bacchus et al, 2016	Nested qualitative interpretive study	Semi structured interviews	Women victims of abuse	Home visiting setting	English and Spanish	USA	26
Beynon et al 2012	Mixed methods	Survey - open ended questions	Nurses and physicians 624 female 307 male	Various disciplines	English	Canada	931
Bidmead, Cowley & Grocott 2016	Interpretivist study	Focus Groups	Health Visitors and Parents	Health Visiting	English	UK	
Bradbury Jones et al 2014	Interpretivist study	Focus groups and interviews	Healthcare professionals Midwives, HVs, GPs and abused women	Community based health professionals in 2 health boards	English	UK Scotland	29 professionals 14 women
Brook & Salmon 2015	Interpretivist study	Semi structured interviews and focus groups	Parents	Parents receiving HV care/support	English	UK	22

Author and study details	Study design	Data collection methods	Participants	Setting	Language	Country	Sample size
Clancy and Svensson 2010	Interpretivist ethnographic	Participant observation and interviews	Nurses, parents & young people	Clinic setting	English	Norway	8 PHNs 15 service users
Cross & Cheyne 2017	Interpretivist study Realist evaluation-informed case study	Individual interviews & focus groups	Midwives and women	Clinic setting	English	Scotland, UK	15 women 31 health professionals
Damra et al 2015	Interpretivist study	Semi structured interviews	Abused women	Hospital settings	Arabic	Jordan	25 women
Decker et al 2013	Mixed methods, grounded theory	Interviews & survey	Abused women	Clinic based	Urdu/Hindi	India	32 interviewed women 1038 survey responses
Dymytryshyn et al 2015	Interpretative descriptive study	Focus Groups and interpretative description of individual interviews	Public Health Nurses	Community based	English	Canada	16 PHNs
Evans & Feder 2014	Interpretivist study	Individual interviews	Abused women	Community based	English	UK	31 women
Feder et al, 2009	Systematic review	N/A	N/A	N/A	English	Global	14 databases
Francis Loxton James 2016	Interpretivist study, using narrative inquiry	Individual interviews and focus groups	Abused women and professionals	Community based	English	Australia	12 abused women and 25 professionals
Hasselle et al, 2019	Interpretivist, exploratory phenomenology	Focus group feedback sessions	Perinatal abused women	Community based	English	USA	9 abused women

Author and study details	Study design	Data collection methods	Participants	Setting	Language	Country	Sample size
Heron, Eisma & Browne 2020	Interpretivist, ethnographic study	Semi structured interviews	Abused women	Community based	English	UK	29 women
Hultmann et al 2013	Interpretivist study; mixed methods, standardized survey	Semi structured interviews	Clinicians – child and adolescent clinics	Clinic based	English	Sweden	14 clinicians
Kirkpatrick et al 2007	Interpretivist study	Interviews	Women receiving home based intervention	Community based	English	UK	20 women
Keeling & Fisher 2014	Interpretivist study, narrative interviews	interviews	Women in health settings	Health settings	English	UK	15 women
Lelaurain et al 2017	Systematic review				English & French	France	90 studies
LoGuidice et al 2015	Qualitative meta synthesis		Healthcare providers		English	USA, Sweden and New Zealand	142 health care providers
Lawoko et al 2011	Positivist study Cross sectional survey	Survey	Healthcare providers	Clinic settings	English and Swedish	Sweden	217 providers
Lundell et al 2017	Interpretivist study; descriptive methods	Interviews	Abused women	Hospital setting	Spanish & English	Mexico	7 women
Mcfely 2016	Mixed methods	Interviews and focus groups	Health visitors and HV service users	Community setting	English	Scotland, UK	20 Health Visitors 17 HV service users

Author and study details	Study design	Data collection methods	Participants	Setting	Language	Country	Sample size
O'Doherty et al 2015	Systematic review				English	Global	
Odero et al, 2013	Interpretivist study, ethnographic	Focus groups and interviews	Pregnant women and service providers	Clinic setting	English/African	Kenya, East Africa	29 pregnant women and 32 partners/friend of pregnant women service providers
Peckover 20023	Interpretivist study	Semi structured interviews	Female service users	Community setting	English	UK	16 women receiving health visiting support
Prosman, Wong 2013	Interpretivist study	Interviews	Women receiving home visiting programme	Community setting	Dutch	The Netherlands	33 abused women
Roddy 2013	Interpretivist study Grounded theory and narrative	Interviews	Abused Women	Clinic setting	English	UK	4 Abused Women
Rose et al 2013	Interpretivist study cross sectional interview	Individual interviews	Service users and MH professionals	Mental Health setting	English	UK	18 services users 20 health professionals
Rossiter et al 2012	Interpretivist study	Qualitative survey	Mothers	Community setting	English	Australia	111 mothers
Saias et al 2016	Mixed methods, Case note study, RCT	Qualitative analysis of case notes	Home visiting service users	Community setting	French	France	1024 case notes 440 pregnant women
Salmon, Baird and White, 2015	Mixed methods	Survey and in depth interviews	Pregnant women	Clinic setting	English	UK	500 women

Author and study details	Study design	Data collection methods	Participants	Setting	Language	Country	Sample size
Schaefer 2016	Mixed methods	Interviews, vignettes and empathy scale	Home visitors	Community setting	English	USA	11 home visitors
Shanti 2017	Interpretivist study grounded theory	Interviews	Home visitors	Community setting	English	USA	38 Home visitors and supervisors
Sinclair et al 2016	Systematic review					Global	8 databases, 44 studies
Spangaro et al 2011	Interpretivist study	Interviews	Women service users	Mental health, substance misuse, antenatal setting	English	Australia	20 women
Sundborg et al 2012	Postivist study	survey	nurses	Primary care setting	Swedish	Sweden	40 nurses
Suryavanshi et al 2018	Mixed methods	Interviews & observational study	Women	Tertiary healthcare setting		India	300 women
Svavarsdottir 2010	Interpretivist study – cross sectional	Survey and interviews	Pregnant women and nurses	ED and perinatal clinic	Icelandic	Iceland	208 pregnant women and nurses
Tanninen et al 2014	Positivist study	Survey	Families	Home visiting	Finnish	Finland	26 families
Taylor et al 2013	Interpretivist study –	Critical incident techniques (Interviews and FGs)	HVs, Midwives, GPs and abused women	Community setting	English	UK	29 Health professionals and 14 abused women

Author and study details	Study design	Data collection methods	Participants	Setting	Language	Country	Sample size
Visentin et al 2015	Interpretivist study – exploratory descriptive study	Interviews	Nurses	Clinic setting	Spanish	Brazil	17 nurses
Waller et al (2023)	Interpretivist, Grounded theory study	Interviews	Abuse survivors	Clinic setting	English	USA	30 women
Williams et al (2020)	Interpretivist	Interviews	Abuse survivors	Family justice centre	English	USA	25 women

16.5 Appendix 3b - Patterning chart

Included studies

	Author and study details	Positivist study design	Interpretive study design	Participants are Service users	Participants are service providers	Setting	UK	Global	Feasibility of Screening for DA	Barriers or facilitators to disclosure or inquiry	Relationship based practice
1.	Ahmad et al 2009		x	X DA		Community		x		x	
2.	Ahmad et al 2016					Emergency Dept		x		x	
3.	Bacchus et al, 2016		x	X DA		Home visiting setting		x	x	x	x
4.	Beynon et al 2012	x	x		x	Various disciplines		x		x	
5.	Bidmead, Cowley & Grocott 2016		x	x	x	Health Visiting	x				x
6.	Bradbury Jones et al 2014		x	X DA	x	Community	x		x	x	
7.	Brook & Salmon 2015		x	x		Community	x				x
8.	Clancy and Svensson 2010		x	x	x	Clinic setting		x			x
9.	Cross & Cheyne 2017		x	x	x	Clinic setting	x				x
10.	Damra et al 2015		x	X DA		Hospital settings		x	x	x	
11.	Decker et al 2013	x	x	X DA		Clinic based		x	x	x	

	Author and study details	Positivist study design	Interpretive study design	Participants are Service users	Participants are service providers	Setting	UK	Global	Feasibility of Screening for DA	Barriers or facilitators to disclosure or inquiry	Relationship based practice
12.	Dymytryshyn et al 2015		x	x		Community based		x			x
13.	Evans & Feder 2014		x	X DA		Community based	x		x	x	
14.	Feder et al, 2009							x	x		
15.	Francis Loxton James 2016		x	xDA	x	Community based		x		x	
16.	Hasselle et al, 2019		x	X DA		Community based		x		x	
17.	Heron, Eisma & Browne 2020		x	X DA		Community based	x			x	
18.	Hultmann et al 2013	x	x		x	Clinic based		x	x		
19.	Kirkpatrick et al 2007		x	x		Community based	x				x
20.	Keeling & Fisher 2014		x	X DA		Health settings	x	x	x		
21.	Lelaurain et al 2017							x		x	
22.	LoGuidice et al 2015		x		x			x	x		
23.	Lowoko et al 2011	x			x	Clinic settings		x	x		
24.	Lundell et al 2017		x	X DA		Hospital setting		x	x	x	
25.	Mcfely 2016	x	x	X DA	x	Community setting	x	x			
26.	O'Doherty et al 2015							x	x		

	Author and study details	Positivist study design	Interpretive study design	Participants are Service users	Participants are service providers	Setting	UK	Global	Feasibility of Screening for DA	Barriers or facilitators to disclosure or inquiry	Relationship based practice
27.	Odero et al, 2013	x	x	X DA	x	Clinic setting		x		x	
28.	Peckover 20023	x	x	x		Community setting	x			x	
29.	Prosman, Wong 2013		x	X DA		Community setting		x		x	
30.	Roddy 2013		x	X DA		Clinic setting	x			x	x
31.	Rose et al 2013		x	X DA	x	Mental Health setting	x			x	x
32.	Rossiter et al 2012		x	x		Community setting		x			x
33.	Saias et al 2016	x	x	x		Community setting		x			x
34.	Salmon, Baird and White, 2015	x	x	X DA		Clinic setting	x		x		
35.	Schaefer 2016	x	x		x	Community setting		x			x
36.	Shanti 2017		x		x	Community setting		x			x
37.	Sinclair et al 2016							x			x
38.	Spangaro et al 2011		x	X DA		Mental health, substance misuse, antenatal setting		x	x	x	
39.	Sundborg et all 2012	x			x	Primary care setting		x	x		

	Author and study details	Positivist study design	Interpretive study design	Participants are Service users	Participants are service providers	Setting	UK	Global	Feasibility of Screening for DA	Barriers or facilitators to disclosure or inquiry	Relationship based practice
40.	Suryavanshi et al 2018	x	x	X DA		Tertiary healthcare setting		x	x		
41.	Svavarsdottir 2010		x	X DA	x	ED and perinatal clinic		x	x	x	
42.	Tanninen et al 2014	x		x		Home visiting		x			x
43.	Taylor et al 2013		x	x	x	Community setting	x		x	x	
44.	Visentin et al 2015		x		x	Clinic setting		x	x	x	x
45.	Waller et al (2023)		x	X DA		Clinic		x		x	
46.	Williams et al (2020)		x	X DA		Clinic		x		x	

16.6 Appendix 3c– PAGER Framework

Pattern	Advances	Gaps	Evidence for practice	Research recommendations
Theme 1 Feasibility of screening and routine enquiry				
<p>IPV is significant public health problem and appropriate for screening and intervention – a variety of interpretations and approaches exist</p> <p>Screening can be useful to women and support disclosures of abuse</p> <p>Relationship between screening and identification of IPV and early support</p> <p>The benefits of screening women for IPV are unclear</p>	<p>There is some evidence that providing appropriate training and facilities to health care professionals, building trust and rapport with victims, to overcome barriers to IPV screening and management in ED.</p> <p>Women find screening acceptable</p> <p>Evidence for acceptability of advocacy is growing</p> <p>Screening evidence is inconclusive, however can be beneficial to women.</p> <p>New outcomes measures should be considered and include views of women Training professionals to identify and respond to IPV would be more effective than applying</p>	<p>Evidence suggests variations of IPV screening tools/approaches across studies.</p> <p>RCTs unlikely to bring significant findings due to differing individual accounts and experiences</p> <p>Lack of consensus in literature about most effective methods/tools to detect IPV</p> <p>Insufficient evidence to implement screening for IPV for all women into healthcare settings.</p> <p>Benefits and harms of screening remain unclear.</p>	<p>Evidence suggests that staff training is needed to fully address IPV.</p> <p>Staffing levels also influence the ability and capacity of staff to meet victim needs.</p> <p>Healthcare professionals should offer multiple opportunities for disclosure without pressure.</p> <p>Healthcare professionals education should include differences in approach/type of abuse and method of inquiry</p>	<p>Further qualitative research is needed to explore the views of patients and healthcare professionals on IPV screening in the ED setting;</p> <p>Review of evidence is needed to understand strengths and limitations of approaches to IPV screening in ED.</p> <p>Trials of system-level and psychological and advocacy interventions; qualitative studies exploring what women want from interventions; cohort studies measuring risk factors, resilience factors and the lifetime trajectory of partner violence; and longitudinal studies measuring the-long-term prognosis for survivors of partner violence</p> <p>Trials using outcomes measures that are important to women themselves, eg. Naming abuse and reduced isolation</p>

	screening to every women in healthcare settings.			<p>Further studies needed to confirm effective tools and methods to identify IPV</p> <p>Further studies and trials are needed to include diverse populations,</p> <p>Studies are needed to confirm benefits and harm to women because of screening. IPV screening in pregnancy also needs further exploration.</p>
Theme 2 Acceptability of screening/routine enquiry				
<p>Routine enquiry for domestic abuse is acceptable to women if asked sensitively</p> <p>Screening women for IPV supports disclosure</p>	<p>Screening is not common and poorly undertaken</p> <p>Evidence that healthcare settings can support abused women.</p> <p>Evidence that it is acceptable to women to be asked about abuse; Women want professionals to help them see abuse.</p> <p>Various reasons why women conceal abuse. Frameworks can be useful to support discussions. Non judgemental approaches are needed.</p>	<p>Evidence suggests frameworks to support enquiry and disclosures require testing and evaluation, and there is a lack of feedback from practice to date.</p> <p>Evidence of increased vulnerability when women are not aware of abuse and professionals unable to enquire.</p> <p>Inconclusive evidence about use of routine screening in health settings. Domestic abuse in under-developed areas is not well studied.</p>	<p>Training is required for health professionals to undertake routine enquiry; educational materials are also required to support discussions.</p> <p>Staff need support to ask about domestic abuse in health settings</p>	<p>Further studies needed in resource-limited settings</p>

Theme 3 Barriers to disclosure				
There are many barriers to help-seeking: Social stigma; gender roles; marriage obligations; loss of supports, myths.	There is evidence that there are several barriers to seeking support, including lack of screening, direct questioning, a lack of privacy.	There is a need for further work exploring how health professionals consider cultural differences in their assessments and contact with women from various countries.	Evidence suggests cultural competence of professionals should be increased.	Further research and programme evaluation is required to understand the needs of ethnic women.
Often women disclose only in response to crises or in an unplanned manner	Cultural factors, immigration status, patriarchal attitudes influence how women seek help for abuse	Help seeking patterns and preferences are not well known, neither are experiences of formal supports.	Patriarchal attitudes are not sufficiently considered by services when asking about abuse; the level of professionals' knowledge and skill regarding barriers is unclear.	Further community-participatory research is needed to develop and test interventions to protect women's health and wellbeing
Low awareness of formal supports; formal help seeking is uncommon	Women only seek help when not able to hide injuries – usually from informal supports.	The thought processes of women contemplating disclosure and leaving an abusive situation are poorly understood.	Efforts needed to de-stigmatize abuse, and to raise awareness.	Further research is needed to clarify the role and formal and informal support services
Barriers preventing women disclosing abuse are complex and vary between women	Fear of disclosing to family - social repercussions and economic dependence	Little is known about the part played by health professionals in women's help seeking strategies.	Need to integrate screening and healthcare based interventions	Further research to understand women's experience of ending or leaving abuse and help seeking over several years. Longitudinal study is needed to increase knowledge about the best ways to support abused women
Women rarely disclose abuse or seek help	Women do not always recognise abuse in their relationships	Research and conceptual frameworks on IPV are underdeveloped in Europe	Professionals need training and skills to enhance knowledge.	Theoretical frameworks would be beneficial in helping to understand abuse. More European research needed.
Lack of universal IPV screening	Women often hold information about specialist services for long periods before acting.	Current understanding of responses to IPV and utilisation of existing resources is limited	Continuity of GP and tailored support needed.	Research is needed into addressing community norms and how this might influence abuse.
Women are dissatisfied with care providers	Only after connecting with specialist services do		Screening should be integrated into existing record keeping systems to improve compliance/ use by professionals	Studies are needed to understand access to and delivery of services to abuse victims.

<p>responses/follow up to IPV disclosures</p> <p>Poor understanding of domestic abuse in ethnic women</p> <p>Various barriers to accessing resources for IPV in African countries</p>	<p>women often disclose to others.</p> <p>Community level approaches are needed to support victims of abuse; lack of resources available; structural barriers exist in some cultures</p> <p>It is not necessary to wait until therapeutic relationship has been developed before screening</p> <p>Women more likely to ask about IPV, and doctors/nurses more likely to enquire than midwives.</p> <p>Women want to be asked, but need a secure relationship, non-blaming.</p> <p>Poor understanding of women's experiences of disclosing abuse in health settings.</p>	<p>Evidence is lacking to demonstrate effectiveness of routine screening, and perspectives of both providers and women. Inconclusiveness of whether to universally screen for IPV.</p> <p>Evidence suggests a lack of frameworks available to explore various issues associated with IPV enquiry and inter-sectoral approaches that are required.</p> <p>Lack of screening - lack of training for GPs - often women are not asked, but want to be screened and want home visits to increase privacy</p> <p>Limited focus on ethnic women, and only small evidence base currently exists in UK.</p>	<p>Consistency in approach to IPV across professions, and clear guidelines needed</p> <p>Consistent screening required in healthcare settings;</p> <p>Information should be displayed in clinical areas, and safe advertising of resources</p> <p>More train the trainer models should be used and development of training materials for professionals</p> <p>Health professionals should participate in reflection on personal attitudes to abuse.</p>	<p>More research is needed to explore victims' experiences of disclosures in health settings. Qualitative research using qualitative methods such as grounded theory/ethnography would be useful</p> <p>Further studies with large sample sizes and from wide geographical areas would be beneficial.</p>
<p>Theme 4 Facilitators to disclosure</p>				
<p>Various facilitators to asking about and disclosing IPV</p>	<p>Evidence suggests training, policies, professional tools,</p>	<p>Facilitators not widely studied, in comparison to barriers to abuse disclosures.</p>	<p>Training has been identified by both physicians and nurses;</p>	<p>There is a need for research that addressed needs of all women, and are sensitive to race, ethnicity, sexuality, socio</p>

	community supports were helpful facilitators.		especially regarding the complex nature of IPV. Approaches that are multifaceted are required.	economic status etc.; and identifies best practice from perspectives of abused women and professionals
Theme 5 Health professionals as barriers to disclosure				
<p>Health professionals' attitudes and beliefs influence their willingness to ask about abuse, and for women to disclose</p> <p>Women rarely receive appropriate response to IPV</p> <p>Health Visitors do not always identify domestic abuse</p> <p>Healthcare Professionals rarely identify abuse and women rarely accept help</p> <p>Preparedness is associated with improved responses to women experiencing IPV.</p> <p>Mental health and Domestic abuse closely linked</p>	<p>Health professionals and women do not always share same beliefs about abuse;</p> <p>Professionals rarely ask about abuse, resistance to ask</p> <p>Evidence of various multifaceted barriers prevent asking about IPV, including time, partner presence, language/cultural practices, lack of interest, trust and respect.</p> <p>Lack of trust between HV and service users</p> <p>Response to abuse is often inadequate. Health professionals not responding appropriately mirror abuser behaviours.</p> <p>Women find it difficult to seek help from HVs; did</p>	<p>Men as victims of abuse are not well represented in literature</p> <p>Little is known about health professionals beliefs about abuse and disclosure and how these compare to those of victims of abuse. Little evidence about women's experiences of health care settings and domestic abuse.</p> <p>Lack of understanding about HV attitudes to abuse; and the impact of HV own experiences of abuse on their willingness to enquire and respond.</p> <p>It is not well understood how health professionals respond to IPV</p> <p>Lack of clarity about why policy aspirations do not translate into practice</p>	<p>Training is needed for health professionals to understand dynamics and presentations of abuse to help them identify abuse and respond more effectively.</p> <p>Healthcare professionals need training to ask about and sensitively respond to domestic abuse</p> <p>Domestic abuse should be part of training programmes;</p> <p>HVs need to engage with specialist services for skills and training to better support women with DA experience.</p> <p>Health professionals should understand the complexity of violent relationships to avoid mirroring abuser behaviours.</p>	<p>Research involving men as victims is needed.</p> <p>Further study of the health professional – woman dyad is needed to avoid miscommunication.</p> <p>Research with greater sample sizes is required</p> <p>Further research is needed to understand HVs attitudes, and qualitative research is needed to understand why response to domestic abuse is different to other sensitive issues, e.g. child abuse</p> <p>Further research is needed to understand experiences of women from differing cultures and ethnic backgrounds. Research involving professionals from a range of health settings would also be valuable.</p> <p>Studies are needed to understand HV attitudes and whether increased knowledge and training</p>

	<p>not always receive adequate support</p> <p>Increasing skills of other professionals to help women access specialist services</p> <p>Nurses in primary health care less well prepared than in other disciplines, e.g. sexual health, emergency care. Lack of organisational support/protocols</p> <p>Health Professionals are not always adequately prepared.</p> <p>Empathy and attentive listening is needed</p> <p>Evidence suggests that despite training health professionals continue to feel uncomfortable asking about abuse.</p> <p>DA not often identified by MH professionals. Number of barriers for both professionals and service users.</p>	<p>Content of mental health programmes and institutions (frequent changes of healthcare providers, long waiting list) are not in line with the needs of abused women seeking help in an early stage of change.</p> <p>Association between child abuse and IPV seem lacking in nurses knowledge</p> <p>Causing harm to patients is often cited as reason for avoiding asking about abuse – and little research in this area.</p> <p>There is little research evidence supporting interventions to support mental health service users experiencing domestic violence</p>	<p>Nurses and GPs require adequate skills to recognise and support women experiencing IPV</p> <p>Active listening is needed by healthcare professionals to understand readiness for change.</p> <p>Nurses need training to ensure protocols are followed relating to child abuse and domestic abuse. More local guidelines are needed to support staff</p> <p>Reflective practice and clinical supervision should be available to professionals when identifying IPV</p> <p>Professionals need to demonstrate cultural sensitivity, non-judgmental approaches toward leaving the relationship. System-level changes are needed that improve intervention accessibility</p>	<p>helps women to share DA experiences.</p> <p>Further research is recommended to investigate the effectiveness of psychological treatment for post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) for abused women</p> <p>Primary care research would help understand needs of more diverse groups of women</p> <p>More research needed focusing on primary care professionals.</p> <p>Studies are needed to include women's voices.</p> <p>Research is needed to expand the current evidence base for interventions to support mental health service users experiencing domestic violence. The development and evaluation of clear care pathways, involving the domestic violence sector are needed</p>
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Theme 6 Relationships				
<p>Relationships between HV and parents can be hindered by HV capacity</p> <p>Relationships require trust and sincerity. Feedback and openness are needed to empower families.</p> <p>Links exist between relationships and outcomes for families in home visiting</p> <p>Relationships form basis for disclosures when screened for IPV</p> <p>Compassion is expected in healthcare</p> <p>Parental engagement is necessary for home visiting programmes to have positive outcomes. Inconsistent counselling provision for abuse survivors;</p>	<p>Evidence that parental participation is important when reviewing HV service.</p> <p>HV-Parent relationship most valued by parents.</p> <p>Relationships are important and consistency is also useful. Honesty, empathy, genuineness and directness are valued by mothers/women.</p> <p>Partnership working and co-operative relationships using strengths-based approaches are supportive to families</p> <p>Therapeutic relationship is central to improving maternal and child outcomes</p> <p>Disclosure of abuse is often staged process; communication skills of professional and trusting relationship are influencing factors</p>	<p>Previously omitted parental views when planning for HV services.</p> <p>Continuity is important to build relationships. Balancing agendas can be difficult but required to empower.</p> <p>Lack of research involving fathers, especially in service evaluations.</p> <p>Little evidence of the impact of working with vulnerable families on nurses; community of support is small</p> <p>Little evidence about what domestic abuse interventions within health visiting, women find helpful.</p> <p>Lack of evidence to support outcomes of home visiting interventions; particularly, needs of ethnic minority women not adequately represented in research</p>	<p>Efforts needed by HVs to be ambassadors for the service, and build on partnership working to address power imbalances.</p> <p>Training is needed for HVs to use strengths-based approaches in their work with families.</p> <p>Training required to gather feedback and increase opportunities for empowerment.</p> <p>Family nurses need ongoing support and training to address complex and sensitive issues</p> <p>Approaches to address compassion fatigue, vicarious trauma/secondary traumatic stress and burnout should be considered by managers and organisations</p>	<p>More realist evaluation would be beneficial across other health care sectors; and wider in scope.</p> <p>Future research should explore what programmes work for whom and under what circumstances.</p> <p>Further research needed to explore initial findings with larger sample; and to identify most appropriate approach for abuse survivors.</p>

<p>lack of specialist provision</p>	<p>Building relationships require trust friendliness, trust in HV, openness, honesty, interest, respect parent skills - communication, information seeking, reciprocity</p> <p>Home visiting preferable over clinic- based interventions; professionals' interest in women as person central to developing trusting relationship</p> <p>Empathetic relationships are required to affect change; non-judgemental attitudes and positive regard are required. Staged processes are used to engage parents, including: Forming relationships, building trust and communicating respectfully; learning family cultures, maintaining professionalism.</p> <p>Strengths based approaches increase self-efficacy in targeted</p>	<p>Limited understanding of compassion in healthcare; lack of empirical evidence to date, especially that which includes patients.</p> <p>No previous work identified that explores process of engaging families in home visiting programmes – and stages of relationship building</p> <p>Limited evidence of approaches that have been used to address gaps in skills and knowledge. Training alone not sufficient Time and resources commonly cited.</p> <p>It is unclear why certain home visiting programmes do not work, for who and under what circumstances.</p> <p>Reflection is needed on the risk of home visiting programs to increase social inequalities, when they are not flexible enough to meet families' needs</p>	<p>Staff require training to identify and respond to abuse; also additional training to understand the relationship between domestic abuse and child abuse, and impact on children</p> <p>Professionals have role to play in establishing trusting relationships to improve outcomes</p> <p>Relationship potential, and belief in ecological approaches and non-judgemental attitudes should be considered when recruiting home visitors.</p> <p>Qualities of clinicians to be examined and linked to quality outcomes</p> <p>Home visitors will need training on the prescribed steps to facilitate positive relationships and engagement</p> <p>Role of champions yet to be explored but could be a useful vehicle for</p>	
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	<p>programmes; can be used successfully to address complex health issues</p> <p>Important to have good knowledge of domestic abuse, and open discussions about endings.</p>	<p>Lack of evidence to suggest which is best approach for abuse survivors to avoid secondary trauma</p>	<p>improving skills and knowledge.</p> <p>Coaching and packages of training and support more likely to be successful.</p>	
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16.7 Appendix 4 – Overview of interpretative research designs

Design	Research focus	Strengths	Weaknesses, Challenges, and Limitations
Narrative	Narrative research explores and conceptualizes human experience. Narrative research aims to explore in-depth the life of an individual or small number of individuals, and the meanings people give to their experiences, through the stories that develop from interviews and answering questions.	Produces rich, in-depth data from individual stories; Collects data from various sources that would be difficult to observe from both participant and researcher perspectives.	Authenticity and validity of narratives can be questioned; stories can be embellished, or subject to poor recall; Potential ethical concerns as participants may be recalling traumatic events; Time and cost implications in the collection of extensive information about each participant; Requires researcher to be reflexive and aware of power imbalances.
Grounded Theory	This approach aims to construct new theory about a specific phenomenon from data, using systematic approaches to collect and analyse data.	Use of rigorous and systematic procedures to analyse and evaluate phenomenon and generate theory; Inductive theory development; Beneficial when no existing theory available to explain a process; Provides flexible method for addressing real world issues	Time consuming to collect data; Can be difficult to identify when data categories are saturated or when theory has enough detail.
Ethnography	Driven by the interest of 'being there', and observing events while they occur, usually over a period of time to gain a deep understanding of a group's shared culture and social dynamics	Explorative; Can produce rich/thick description about human behaviour	Time consuming, requires prolonged stay with the group under study; Researcher is required to have specific skills to engage with participants; Presence of researcher can influence results; Researcher is required to understanding of cultural anthropology; High risk of researcher being compromised in the study in unfamiliar culture group; Cultural sensitivity and competence of researcher is essential.

Design	Research focus	Strengths	Weaknesses, Challenges, and Limitations
Phenomenology	Phenomenological researchers are concerned with describing, interpreting and reflecting on everyday human lived experiences and believe individuals can be understood from within their subjective experiences.	Small samples, therefore fewer subjects required for collect data Selection of theoretical framework precedes data collection; Provides a deep understanding of a phenomenon as experienced by others	Requires a familiarity with phenomenology philosophy; Generating theory and generalising data can be challenging with this approach due to being dependent on specific context or viewpoint. Relatively small samples are used and limited data is available for analysis Presence of researcher can influence results; Identifying participants with required characteristics can be challenging depending on the research topic; Bracketing personal experiences can be challenging, and requires researchers to have reflective skills and insight
Case Study	Develops in-depth descriptions and analyses of one case or multiple cases. Developed from symbolic interactionism, and in contrast to Grounded Theory, researchers observe daily routines of others to explore how individuals make sense of their lives.	Produces in-depth findings from one or more viewpoints, using multiple sources of information; Challenges existing theory; High validity; Efficient approach, as theory can be disproved by one case study; Can be used to highlight a unique case, or understand a specific issue	Challenging to generalise; Small sample sizes; Presence of researcher can influence results; Difficult to duplicate; Time consuming, and low reliability; Subjective findings

Edmonds and Kennedy, 2017, pp. 141-168; Korstjens and Moser, 2017; Cresswell and Poth, 2018, pp67-111

16.8 Appendix 5 – Feminist theories

<p>Feminism Gender norms are socially constructed and not determined by biology Feminism is a political movement and exists to remove gender inequality Inequality between men and women is the most significant</p>	
<p>Radical Feminism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blames the exploitation of women on men • Men benefit from the subordination of women • Women are oppressed, in a patriarchal society where men dominate • Rape and violence secure power over women <p>Criticised for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patriarchy criticised for ignoring variations in expressions of oppression • Focuses on negative expressions of women, fails to acknowledge women can have happy marriages • Portrays women as universally good and men universally bad – man hating <p>Other forms of radical feminism: Radical Libertarian feminists: aim for a state of androgyny Radical Cultural feminism: believe in superiority of women</p>	<p>Marxist Feminism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source of oppression is capitalism instead of patriarchy • Women reproduce labour for free • Believe gender inequality will end • Women absorb the anger of men • Women's subordination benefits capitalism <p>Criticised for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radical feminists claim inequality is ignored, for example sexual violence • Patriarchal systems existed prior to capitalism • Women reported to not be happy under capitalism
<p>Liberal Feminism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both men and women harmed by gender inequalities • Liberal ideas had most impact on women's lives, e.g. mainstreaming • Culture and values explain gender inequalities • Socialisation is main source of gender inequality – produced inflexible expectations of women and men • Discrimination prevents women having equal opportunities • Want changes to take place within existing structures – do not want revolutionary changes • Main aim to create equal opportunities & eradicate sexism <p>Criticised for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on male assumptions and norms • Encourages women to be more like men • Fails to take account of structural inequalities 	<p>Post-modern feminism</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do not see women as a single homogenous group • Claims previous theory as 'false universality' for example western, white, middle class and essentialist • Concerned with balance of power and knowledge rather than politics and oppression • No one universal truth, no such thing as objectivity <p>Criticised for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women are still oppressed by objective social structures for example patriarchy • Dividing women's subgroups weakens movement for change

Feminist Empiricism	Feminist Standpoint
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges the way traditional methods are used, rather than methods themselves • Argues to value-freedom of traditional approaches • Early criticism of male dominated scientific epistemology • Uses scientific methods to tackle gender bias <p>Criticised for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being unable to affect change due to the inherent gender bias that all scientific inquiries face 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dismisses scientific theory as it excluded women's experiences • Similar to Marxist theory; women are oppressed class but can understand their own experiences and viewpoint of their oppressors • Provides more valid basis for knowledge through the insight into the oppressor, knowledge arises as fight oppression <p>Criticised for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focussing on only 1 group gives their perspective false superiority over others • Focussing on biology and traditional values- reinforces female stereotypes

(Haralambos and Holborn (2021, p15), McAfee and Howard, 2018)

16.9 Appendix 6 - Summary of main ethical principles

Ethical Principle	Summary
Autonomy	Individuals able to make own decisions & give informed consent without coercion Ability to withdraw at any time Awareness of risks and benefits of participation Wellbeing of participants is prioritised Those with diminished autonomy require additional protection
Beneficence	Participation can often be cathartic for participants Benefits of participating balanced against vulnerabilities Benefits to both individuals and wider society Support during & following participation
Non-maleficence	Seeking to do no harm Assessment or risk to participants and researchers Risk-Benefit analyses Identification of poor practice
Justice, confidentiality, privacy & anonymity	Treating people fairly and equitably Ensuring anonymity, privacy and confidentiality

(Fouka and Mantzourou, 2011)

16.10 Appendix 7 – NHS Research Ethics Committee Application

Full Set of Project Data

IRAS Version 6.2

Welcome to the Integrated Research Application System

IRAS Project Filter

The integrated dataset required for your project will be created from the answers you give to the following questions. The system will generate only those questions and sections which (a) apply to your study type and (b) are required by the bodies reviewing your study. Please ensure you answer all the questions before proceeding with your applications.

Please complete the questions in order. If you change the response to a question, please select 'Save' and review all the questions as your change may have affected subsequent questions.

Please enter a short title for this project (maximum 70 characters)
A meaningful insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse

1. Is your project research?

Yes No

2. Select one category from the list below:

- Clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product
- Combined trial of an investigational medicinal product and an investigational medical device
- Clinical investigation or other study of a medical device
- Other clinical trial to study a novel intervention or randomised clinical trial to compare interventions in clinical practice
- Basic science study involving procedures with human participants
- Study administering questionnaires/interviews for quantitative analysis, or using mixed quantitative/qualitative methodology
- Study involving qualitative methods only
- Study limited to working with human tissue samples (or other human biological samples) and data (specific project only)
- Study limited to working with data (specific project only)
- Research tissue bank
- Research database

If your work does not fit any of these categories, select the option below:

Other study

2a. Please answer the following question(s):

- a) Does the study involve the use of any ionising radiation? Yes No
- b) Will you be taking new human tissue samples (or other human biological samples)? Yes No
- c) Will you be using existing human tissue samples (or other human biological samples)? Yes No

3. In which countries of the UK will the research sites be located? (Tick all that apply)

England

- Scotland
 Wales
 Northern Ireland

3a. In which country of the UK will the lead NHS R&D office be located:

- England
 Scotland
 Wales
 Northern Ireland
 This study does not involve the NHS

4. Which applications do you require?

- IRAS Form
 Confidentiality Advisory Group (CAG)
 Her Majesty's Prison and Probation Service (HMPPS)

Most research projects require review by a REC within the UK Health Departments' Research Ethics Service. Is your study exempt from REC review?

- Yes No

5. Will any research sites in this study be NHS organisations?

- Yes No

6. Do you plan to include any participants who are children?

- Yes No

7. Do you plan at any stage of the project to undertake intrusive research involving adults lacking capacity to consent for themselves?

- Yes No

Answer Yes if you plan to recruit living participants aged 16 or over who lack capacity, or to retain them in the study following loss of capacity. Intrusive research means any research with the living requiring consent in law. This includes use of identifiable tissue samples or personal information, except where application is being made to the Confidentiality Advisory Group to set aside the common law duty of confidentiality in England and Wales. Please consult the guidance notes for further information on the legal frameworks for research involving adults lacking capacity in the UK.

8. Do you plan to include any participants who are prisoners or young offenders in the custody of HM Prison Service or who are offenders supervised by the probation service in England or Wales?

- Yes No

9. Is the study or any part of it being undertaken as an educational project?

Yes No

Please describe briefly the involvement of the student(s):

The student will be the researcher in the study, supported by Chief Investigators/supervisory Team, Professor Jean Rankine, and Ruth Astbury.

9a. Is the project being undertaken in part fulfilment of a PhD or other doctorate?

Yes No

10. Will this research be financially supported by the United States Department of Health and Human Services or any of its divisions, agencies or programs?

Yes No

Integrated Research Application System
Application Form for Research involving qualitative methods only

The Chief Investigator should complete this form. Guidance on the questions is available wherever you see this symbol displayed. We recommend reading the guidance first. The complete guidance and a glossary are available by selecting [Help](#).

Please define any terms or acronyms that might not be familiar to lay reviewers of the application.

Short title and version number: (maximum 70 characters - this will be inserted as header on all forms)
A meaningful insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse

PART A: Core study information

1. ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

A1. Full title of the research:

Developing a meaningful insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse.
Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during historic periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these might have prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.

A2-1. Educational projects

Name and contact details of student(s):

Student 1

Title Forename/Initials Surname

Address

Personal details withheld.

Post Code

E-mail

Telephone

Fax

Give details of the educational course or degree for which this research is being undertaken:

Name and level of course/ degree:

PhD

Name of educational establishment:

University of the West of Scotland

Name and contact details of academic supervisor(s):

Academic supervisor 1

Title Forename/Initials Surname
DR RUTH ASTBURY

Address	[REDACTED]						
Post Code	[REDACTED]						
E-mail	[REDACTED]						
Telephone	[REDACTED]						
Fax	[REDACTED]						
Academic supervisor 2							
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Title</th> <th>Forename/Initials</th> <th>Surname</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>PROFESSOR</td> <td>MARY</td> <td>LYNCH</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Title	Forename/Initials	Surname	PROFESSOR	MARY	LYNCH
Title	Forename/Initials	Surname					
PROFESSOR	MARY	LYNCH					
Address	[REDACTED]						
Post Code	[REDACTED]						
E-mail	[REDACTED]						
Telephone	[REDACTED]						
Fax	[REDACTED]						

Please state which academic supervisor(s) has responsibility for which student(s):
Please click "Save now" before completing this table. This will ensure that all of the student and academic supervisor details are shown correctly.

Student(s)	Academic supervisor(s)
Student 1 MRS KERRY ELLIS	<input type="checkbox"/> DR RUTH ASTBURY <input type="checkbox"/> PROFESSOR MARY LYNCH

A copy of a current CV for the student and the academic supervisor (maximum 2 pages of A4) must be submitted with the application.

A2-2. Who will act as Chief Investigator for this study?

- Student
- Academic supervisor
- Other

A3-1. Chief Investigator:

	Title	Forename/Initials	Surname
	MRS	KERRY	ELLIS
Post	PHD STUDENT		
Qualifications	MSc Vulnerability Specialist Community Public Health Nursing (Health Visiting) Dip (HE) Nursing (Adult) BA (Hons) Environmental Studies		
ORCID ID			
Employer	[REDACTED]		
Work Address	[REDACTED]		

Personal details withheld.

Post Code
Work E-mail
* Personal E-mail
Work Telephone
* Personal Telephone/Mobile
Fax

** This information is optional. It will not be placed in the public domain or disclosed to any other third party without prior consent.
A copy of a current CV (maximum 2 pages of A4) for the Chief Investigator must be submitted with the application.*

A4. Who is the contact on behalf of the sponsor for all correspondence relating to applications for this project?
This contact will receive copies of all correspondence from REC and HRA/R&D reviewers that is sent to the CI.

Title Forename/Initials Surname
DR RUTH ASTBURY
Address
Post Code
E-mail
Telephone
Fax

Personal details withheld.

A5-1. Research reference numbers. *Please give any relevant references for your study:*

Applicant's/organisation's own reference number, e.g. R & D (if available): Yet to be provided
Sponsor's/protocol number: N/A
Protocol Version: N/A
Protocol Date:
Funder's reference number (enter the reference number or state not applicable):
Project website:

Additional reference number(s):

Ref.Number	Description	Reference Number
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Registration of research studies is encouraged wherever possible. You may be able to register your study through your NHS organisation or a register run by a medical research charity, or publish your protocol through an open access publisher. If you have registered your study please give details in the "Additional reference number(s)" section.

A5-2. Is this application linked to a previous study or another current application?

Yes No

Please give brief details and reference numbers.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE RESEARCH

To provide all the information required by review bodies and research information systems, we ask a number of specific questions. This section invites you to give an overview using language comprehensible to lay reviewers and members of the public. Please read the guidance notes for advice on this section.

A6-1. Summary of the study. *Please provide a brief summary of the research (maximum 300 words) using language easily understood by lay reviewers and members of the public. Where the research is reviewed by a REC within the UK Health Departments' Research Ethics Service, this summary will be published on the Health Research Authority (HRA) website following the ethical review. Please refer to the question specific guidance for this question.*

This study addresses the retrospective experiences of mothers during periods of domestic abuse. Domestic abuse is a significant global public health issue, affecting 1 in 3 women (WHO, 2013); throughout the Coronavirus epidemic, this has gained further attention as the prevalence of domestic abuse has heightened (Scottish Government, 2021), and the impact on victims, children and families has become more apparent. Women who experience abuse suffer a plethora of psychological and physical health issues, as do their children (WHO, 2013), and consequently they present frequently to healthcare settings (Lundell et al, 2017).

Despite the known incidence and prevalence of domestic abuse in communities, it is also known to be widely under-reported (Decker et al, 2012), and women face many barriers to disclosing abuse, many of which relate to the healthcare setting (Decker et al, 2012). The pandemic lockdown restrictions have resulted in an increase in requests for help from victims, while also limiting women's contact with others, access to services, and opportunities to disclose (Social Care Institute for Excellence, 2020).

This Hermeneutic study aims to explore the relationships that women have had with health professionals during periods of abuse, and identify how these relationships with Health Visitors, midwives, GPs, might have promoted or prevented disclosure of abuse. Women who have experienced abuse while their children were aged 0-5 and within the last 5 years will be invited to participate. Data will be collected via semi-structured interviews, using the life history calendar framework to produce a visual timeline (Yoshihama et al, 2002; Nelson, 2010).

Women will be recruited from areas within Scotland that are accessible to the researcher, via Health Visiting caseloads, and also via Women's Aid organisations. It is anticipated that findings could influence policy and practice within Scotland.

A6-2. Summary of main issues. *Please summarise the main ethical, legal, or management issues arising from your study and say how you have addressed them.*

Not all studies raise significant issues. Some studies may have straightforward ethical or other issues that can be identified and managed routinely. Others may present significant issues requiring further consideration by a REC, R&D office or other review body (as appropriate to the issue). Studies that present a minimal risk to participants may raise complex organisational or legal issues. You should try to consider all the types of issues that the different reviewers may need to consider.

Purpose and design

Domestic abuse is a significant public health issue, affecting large numbers of women globally. It is also known that women often face several barriers to disclosing abuse to professionals, despite routine and sensitive enquiry efforts. Therefore, this study can be legitimised by acknowledging that improvements are required across health settings that support women to disclose abuse; additionally, there is a lack of contemporary research that confirms what conditions are required with relationships between women and health professionals to enable this to happen. Findings from the study can be used to inform practice and improve the service to survivors of abuse, with a view to early identification of abuse and timely support to women.

Recruitment & Sampling

The primary risk to prospective participants in domestic abuse research, is the potential for escalation of abuse by a perpetrator. Within this study, this potential risk has been minimised by the recruitment and sampling strategy chosen, which includes only women who are, at the time of the study, those who confirm they are safe from abuse and not in a relationship with a perpetrator of abuse. This is determined by several factors: their living arrangements - they will be either living in their own accommodation, or in safe accommodation provided by Women's Aid. Additionally, they will be asked to confirm that they are not in contact with any known or suspected perpetrator of abuse. These steps reduce the risk of escalation of any abuse, or any repercussions to women, as a direct result of participating in the study, and also protect the researcher from any similar threats from any perpetrator. Secondly, participants might risk experiencing some psychological impact or secondary trauma, from participating in domestic abuse research, as it is likely that they will be recalling traumatic events, which may be distressing and upsetting.

To remain inclusive, but to manage the risk associated with including women who have experienced significant trauma, women will also be asked to confirm that they believe they are emotionally able to participate, while also being made aware by the researcher of the possibility of becoming upset and distressed. Prospective participants will also be made aware of the supports that will be available to them following participation in the study. When seeking consent, the researcher will also identify each participant's network of support, and also continue to assess for risk throughout the duration of data collection, to ensure women remain comfortably within their 'window of tolerance' (Siegel, 2012), where they can access strategies to deal with the range of possible emotions that participation may incur, without risk of potential re-traumatisation.

It is anticipated that between 7-10 women will be recruited to the study.

Obtaining consent

A continuous process of consent will be used, to allow the researcher to confirm consent throughout the process. Information about the study will be provided in a way that is easy to understand, and women will be asked to express interest in the study prior to seeking consent.

Participant information (Appendix 1) will be provided which will describe the study, and illustrate the potential risks and benefits to women participants, and emphasises that participation is entirely voluntary, and information collected will remain confidential. Privacy is required for any data collection, more-so when discussing sensitive and personal information; therefore, when consent has been given, the need for privacy will be emphasised, and will go ahead with only the women and researcher present, however women can choose to have someone else with them if they wish, but who will not participate in the interview (WHO, 2016b).

Once women have expressed an interest in participating, the researcher will make contact with them individually, to discuss the study further, and provide an opportunity for them to ask questions; if they remain agreeable to participating in the study, consent will be sought. At the outset of the interview, participants will be asked to sign a consent form (Appendix 4), to confirm that they agree to take part in the study. Participants will be advised that they can stop the interview and withdraw their involvement at any time, without any repercussion or explanation; participants will be given the option to sign their consent using a pseudonym if they prefer or make some note other than their signature. During the interview the researcher will 'check-in' with participants to ensure the participants are agreeable to continue and not suffering any adverse effects.

Confidentiality

Various steps will be taken by the researcher to protect the confidentiality, and promote the safety and wellbeing of the women participating in the study. Although storage of participant demographic details is required, these will be limited to storage in one central place, on a secure, password protected Excel spreadsheet, which will record their first name (or their chosen name), and demographic details. The spreadsheet will be saved on an encrypted device, (NHS Computer, password protected) with only the researcher able to access this. Each participant will be assigned an ID code which will be used throughout the study.

This ID code will be on all documentation, interview recordings and transcripts to ensure participants remain anonymous. This also ensures any direct quotes remain anonymous, and are not identifiable, or traceable back to the participant by anyone other than the researcher. The researcher will undertake their own transcription of data, thus eliminating any additional concerns about confidentiality; during the transcription process, any identifiable information such as geographical location, and names of other parties, including children, will be omitted to ensure confidentiality is upheld and any risks to participants are reduced as much as possible. Only the researcher and her supervisors will have access to interview transcripts; once transcribed, interview data will be uploaded and held electronically; paper interview notes will also be uploaded electronically and both will be password protected and saved on a secure device, and destroyed as soon as is practicable to do so.

Women will be assured that health service professionals and other professionals that they may discuss during interviews will not be aware of their participation in the study. All responses and interview data will be kept confidential and will not be disclosed at any point during the study to the practitioners or services that the participants refer to. Women will be assured that their participation in the study will not impact on any current or future health services they may receive.

Managing risks and benefits

As steps have been taken to reduce the risk of repercussions from perpetrators, it is possible that participants might still experience upset or distress during interviews, as they are recalling events that have been traumatic over their life course. It may be that as they recall their experiences over their life course, events re-surface that had been repressed, and consequently cause distress and negative emotions as they re-live periods of abuse. Regular check-ins with participants during the interviews will be a method used to ensure they are able and agreeable to continuing with their stories, and this also provides the researcher with reassurance that participants are not experiencing any

undue distress, and are not feeling under pressure to continue. Participants displaying signs of upset/distress, will be given space and time as they feel required to recover, and be treated with comfort, empathy and respect at all times.

Additionally, at the outset of all interviews, the researcher will ask about their network of support, and will encourage participants to seek contact with them, if required following the interview. All participating women will be provided with a list of local agencies and helplines that they can access following participation if needed. Additionally, for those already in contact with Women's Aid, they will be advised that additional support will be available to them if required. For those not currently receiving support, women will be asked if they wish for the researcher to make referrals to agencies such as Women's Aid following the interviews. Women's Aid organisations are available in all the regions in Scotland where women will be recruited from.

Additionally, the researcher has several years experience working with children, families and women, many who face adversity and have been victims of domestic abuse; additionally, the researcher brings experience of managing difficult, sensitive topics, communicating and engaging individuals during times of difficulty. Although not specialist support, it is anticipated that the researcher is able to communicate empathetically with participants in a way that supports them to take the lead in interviews, allowing them to disclose what they feel able to, and gauging the impact this has on participants as interviews progress.

Although this describes the plan to minimise and manage any potential distress, it is possible that during the data collection process participants become so distressed that it would not be ethical to continue. The researcher's experience and previous training suggests that significant distress can be identified and responded to appropriately, ending interviews if needed (WHO, 2016b). In such circumstances, participants will be advised that interviews will be suspended, and support sought for them with their consent. They will be provided with contact details of the researcher should they wish to continue interviews at a later date. The participants will make the decision whether they wish to withdraw, and their decision respected. Where participants are visibly distressed, the researcher will end the interview and with consent, request additional support where supportive mechanisms are already in-situ, e.g. from their current Women's Aid worker.

Although participating in domestic abuse research has the potential to incur psychological costs for participants, such as feelings of guilt, shame, embarrassment, or further trauma, it is also argued that participating in well-designed domestic abuse research can be meaningful and bring certain benefits that out-weigh any costs, such as participants report feeling valued, listened to, respected, able to help others, and they have welcomed an opportunity to demonstrate that domestic abuse exists and has real impacts for victims (Cromer et al, 2006; DePrince and Chu, 2008). Similarly, although it may be initially distressing, women claim being interviewed about abuse is more beneficial than harmful, due to the cathartic nature of talking about the abuse (Synder, 2016). The researcher will make potential participants aware of the possible benefits, however this will not be used as leverage to entice them to be involved in the study.

To promote inclusion, women who may not have English as their first language will be able to participate, with the support of interpreters. Similarly, for women who may not be literate, or where literacy skills are poor, material will be provided in video format that can be listened to instead of read.

A risk assessment has been completed (Appendix 7).

3. PURPOSE AND DESIGN OF THE RESEARCH

A7. Select the appropriate methodology description for this research. Please tick all that apply:

- Case series/ case note review
- Case control
- Cohort observation
- Controlled trial without randomisation
- Cross-sectional study

- Database analysis
- Epidemiology
- Feasibility/ pilot study
- Laboratory study
- Metanalysis
- Qualitative research
- Questionnaire, interview or observation study
- Randomised controlled trial
- Other (please specify)

A10. What is the principal research question/objective? Please put this in language comprehensible to a lay person.

The aim of the study is to: 'develop a meaningful insight into mother's experiences of domestic abuse', and identify the relationships mothers have had with health professionals during historical periods of abuse, exploring how these have promoted or prevented disclosures of abuse.

A11. What are the secondary research questions/objectives if applicable? Please put this in language comprehensible to a lay person.

Objectives:

1. To collect and chronologically record, mothers' retrospective experiences of domestic abuse
2. To explore in depth the factors that influence mothers' decisions to disclose domestic abuse
3. To develop an understanding of the influencing factors that impact on mothers' experiences of domestic abuse
4. To develop an understanding of the role health care practitioners play in supporting mothers who are experiencing domestic abuse
5. To identify supportive mechanisms to mothers experiencing domestic abuse

A12. What is the scientific justification for the research? Please put this in language comprehensible to a lay person.

Domestic abuse is a subject widely studied, and continues to be a public health issue that is associated with high costs to society, communities and individuals (WHO, 2013). The impacts of domestic abuse on victims are vast, and therefore robust evidence is continually needed to respond to disclosures of abuse and provide early intervention and prevention strategies (WHO, 2013).

The issue of disclosure of abuse through sensitive or routine enquiry has been explored in previous studies (Feder et al, 2009); a variety of barriers often exist to prevent women disclosing abuse, however there is an absence of contemporary research that considers the nature of the relationship between women and health care professionals and how this relationship might impact on willingness to disclose abuse. Furthermore, this has rarely been explored in the context of mothers with young children, who will have had contact with midwifery, Health Visiting and GP professionals from primary care settings. Furthermore, there has been no identifiable studies that explore the relationships between women and their Health Visitor since the introduction of the Universal Health Visiting Pathway in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2015), which offers a programme of 11 home visits for each child.

Additionally, despite routine and sensitive enquiry being promoted in healthcare practice, evidence suggests there are a variety of barriers that exist to prevent this from occurring consistently and effectively (Lundell et al, 2017). This study aims to use a life history approach to determine if there are phenomenon within relationships that facilitate disclosure - an approach which has not been used to explore this issue in recent times.

Further justification for this research lies in response to the current global Coronavirus pandemic; domestic abuse prevalence has increased considerably during the pandemic, with Police across all 4 nations seeing an increase in domestic abuse related calls, and demand for victim services following lockdown measures (ONS, 2020). These increases have been evident internationally, as well as in the UK, as stay at home restrictions, furlough and the impact on family finances, has led to increased prevalence of abuse alongside a restriction in availability and accessibility to support services (United Nations, 2020). Data suggests that only 40% of domestic abuse is disclosed, and it can be presumed that as families adhere to the stay at home messages, and have limited access to supportive networks, these additional barriers will mean even fewer incidents of abuse will be disclosed (Scottish Government, 2020).

A13. Please summarise your design and methodology. *It should be clear exactly what will happen to the research participant, how many times and in what order. Please complete this section in language comprehensible to the lay person. Do not simply reproduce or refer to the protocol. Further guidance is available in the guidance notes.*

Research Design

To fully achieve the aims of the study, a Hermeneutic interpretive research design will be used, following Heideggerian philosophical principles which is unique, and dissimilar to other types of qualitative research.

The research design combines semi-structured interviews and narrative enquiry to support the collaboration between participant and researcher, by adding an interpretive dimension as stories are constructed and participant voices become heard.

The Participant

Involvement in the study will mean that the research participant will be interviewed once, and this interview will last approximately 90 minutes.

Recruitment & Sampling

This study requires the participation of women who have experienced domestic abuse in the past, and are now living in safety, whether that be in their own homes, or in safe accommodation.

To ensure accessibility for data gathering, women from 7 regions within Scotland will be invited to participate. Women will be recruited from Women's Aid organisations and from Health Visitors from within 7 geographical areas of Scotland. These professionals will act as gatekeepers who will facilitate contact between the researcher and potential participants. Women's Aid workers will be invited to identify eligible women who reside in their safe accommodation, or who are known to their organisation, and similarly, Health Visitors will be asked to identify eligible mothers from their caseloads. Gatekeepers will be asked to share details of the study with eligible women from the pre-defined criteria, and support women to make contact with the researcher to discuss the study further if they wish to do so. Information to gatekeepers will emphasise that participation is voluntary, and no coercion is to be used to pressure women into participating; equally, however, gatekeepers should provide women with all the information available, so she is able to make an informed decision about whether to participate.

As the study is concerned with women's relationships with health professionals, in particular Health Visitors, Midwives and GPs, the sample will include women who have experienced domestic abuse while their children were pre-school age (0-5), and within the last 5 years, to aid recall of historical events. It is anticipated that 7-10 women will be recruited to the study.

Information about the research study will be provided to Health Visitor Service Managers (Appendix 2) in these same 7 regions within Scotland deemed accessible to the researcher. They will be asked to disseminate information about the study to Health Visitors. Additionally, in order to support the process, the researcher will offer to attend team meetings to provide further information about the study. Information about the study will also be provided to Women's Aid organisations (Appendix 3) in the specific regions in Scotland, and the researcher will also attempt to make contact with these teams to provide more information about the study to promote and encourage identification of eligible women.

Where women express interest in participating, women will be contacted by telephone or virtual means such as MS Teams, Zoom etc, to discuss the study further, and will be provided with information about the study (Appendix 1). Where permitting, the researcher will make arrangements for interviews to take place and for consent to be formally sought. Women will be met face to face (either virtually or in person) on one occasion, for an interview; consent will be sought at the outset, where women will be asked to sign a consent form (Appendix 4) with their first name/name of their choice.

Women who would be eligible to participate will meet the following criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

Women who are mothers, and who:

- are over 18 years
- have experienced domestic abuse in the past while their children were pre-school (Aged 0-5) and within the last 5 years at the time of the research taking place
- have no current contact with any previously known, or suspected perpetrator
- feel they are able to discuss domestic abuse experiences without any significant distress or adverse impact on their general health or psychological wellbeing
- are living in their own accommodation, or Women's Aid accommodation within one of the 7 areas of Scotland

Women who do not have English as a first language, who may have poor literacy skills, can also be included in the study, and can also be employed in one of the gatekeeping roles/NHS or Women's Aid Organisations and meet other

inclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria:

Women who:

- are not mothers
- are under 18 years
- report to having contact with any known past or current perpetrator of abuse.
- are deemed by themselves, to be likely to suffer adversely in terms of their psychological health or wellbeing, as a result of participating in the study.
- have formally opted out of midwifery or health visiting services.
- do not live, at the time of data collection, within one of the 7 areas of Scotland.
- are known to the researcher, and where a current professional relationship exists
- are involved in ongoing criminal investigations or due to make court appearances at the time of the study.

Data Collection

Data collection methods will combine the use of life history calendar tools, story-telling narrative, with individual interviews. An interview schedule (Appendix 6) will be used to supplement and guide the interview narratives, by providing prompts only when required. During the interviews, the researcher, together with the woman, will develop a visual timeline and once completed, the woman will be asked to confirm that it accurately represents her experiences, and can be later be used to compare and draw themes and analyses. Where interviews are conducted remotely, timelines will be shared and discussed using virtual methods, e.g. whiteboards/jamboards. Interviews with all participants will be undertaken over a 3 month period, and will be audio recorded.

Safety of both the participant and researcher will be considered when arranging the interviews. Interviews will strive to take place using virtual technology, e.g. MS Teams, Zoom, WhatsApp etc, to reduce the risk to the researcher from a lone working perspective, and also to consider the ongoing risks related to the Coronavirus pandemic. However, if women do not have access to technology that would facilitate remote interviews, or if they choose, the researcher will aim to undertake interviews in either Women's Aid or Health Board premises.

It is also acceptable that a support worker, or another person of the participant's choosing, is present during the interviews, however their level of involvement will be discussed and agreed, and should be entirely to support women, and not to participate in the interviews. Additionally, where any face-to-face interviews take place, details will be made available to the researcher's supervisory team, to promote researcher safety, and the researcher will comply with the relevant Board's Lone Working policies. Furthermore, Government Guidance in relation to the Coronavirus pandemic will be adhered to. This provides further justification for the use of remote/virtual interviews, providing this is acceptable to the participants.

Data collection and analysis will be undertaken in parallel and therefore the researcher will be aware when data saturation has been achieved. The sample is expected to be between 7-10 participants, as this reflects sample sizes of similar studies, and is thought to be achievable across 7 regions within Scotland.

Data analysis

The life history calendar (LHC) matrix (Appendix 5) is used as a data collection tool, and will be populated with information from the interviews and will assist in identify the timing of significant events and support more accurate recall of retrospective events and experiences. The data recorded on the LHC, and the visual timelines, will also be subject to the analysis process as well as the qualitative written text arising from the interviews.

All interviews with women will be audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim by the researcher following each interview to allow immersion in the data, and to promote accurate recollections which may be compromised if transcriptions were to take place at a later time. Women will be informed that other non-verbal emotional expressions, e.g. crying, distress, silence, that arise alongside their narratives will also be recorded with the transcriptions, to allow their lived experiences to be interpreted (Heidegger, 1996). Transcribed interviews and analysis of the visual timeline will form the basis of data analysis. Women will be advised that audio-recordings will be destroyed once transcribed, and also coded, so not identifiable to anyone other than the researcher.

To analyse qualitative written text, Heidegger's (1962) circle method will be used to continually move back and forth to review parts of and whole parts of texts arising from interviews with participants. Transcripts will be read and re-read to allow the researcher to become immersed in the narratives. Individual words and phrases used by participants to describe their experiences of domestic abuse, and their relationships with others during periods of abuse will be

highlighted and interpreted as having additional value (Mackey, 2005). Thematic analysis will also be used to perform line by line coding to reduce data into concepts which are then grouped into themes (Christie et al, 2020). By collectively reviewing the words and phrases of each participant, the researcher will clarify and understand the lived experiences of women who have survived domestic abuse, and will be able to identify themes, similarities and differences between participants. Meditative thinking (Heidegger, 1966) will also be undertaken to allow the researcher to be open to thinking and be attuned to the ontological experiences of participants.

Dissemination of research findings

Reports will be compiled to summarise the aggregate findings of the research, and will be provided to participants, Health Visiting Teams and Women's Aid organisations from the 7 geographical areas that participated in the research, and to Senior Managers and Service Managers, responsible for Health Visiting and Midwifery services across Scotland, as well as GP Leads. The researcher will aim to publish findings and present at conference where opportunity allows.

Rigour

The researcher will conduct a pilot study to test the use of the data collection instruments and protocols: the Life History Calendar (LHC), use of prompting questions and development of a timeline. This will enable the researcher to overcome any difficulties associated with the data collection tools, and ensure the interviews are not prolonged for the participants, and undertaken confidently, and ensuring all interview data is used appropriately, any prompts are relevant and not superfluous to the study.

A14-1. In which aspects of the research process have you actively involved, or will you involve, patients, service users, and/or their carers, or members of the public?

- Design of the research
- Management of the research
- Undertaking the research
- Analysis of results
- Dissemination of findings
- None of the above

Give details of involvement, or if none please justify the absence of involvement.

The life history calendar tool will be tested prior to data collection by an individual known to the researcher who is agreeable to provide feedback. During individual interviews, the life history calendar tool will be used to develop timeline to illustrate participant experiences over the life course. This will be developed in collaboration with the participant, who will be present to confirm its accuracy.

On completion of the research study, a report will be compiled for participants which will summarise and explain the key findings from the study, and implications for future practice.

4. RISKS AND ETHICAL ISSUES

RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

A15. What is the sample group or cohort to be studied in this research?

Select all that apply:

- Blood
- Cancer
- Cardiovascular
- Congenital Disorders

- Dementias and Neurodegenerative Diseases
- Diabetes
- Ear
- Eye
- Generic Health Relevance
- Infection
- Inflammatory and Immune System
- Injuries and Accidents
- Mental Health
- Metabolic and Endocrine
- Musculoskeletal
- Neurological
- Oral and Gastrointestinal
- Paediatrics
- Renal and Urogenital
- Reproductive Health and Childbirth
- Respiratory
- Skin
- Stroke

Gender: Female participants only
 Lower age limit: 18 Years
 Upper age limit: No upper age limit

A17-1. Please list the principal inclusion criteria (list the most important, max 5000 characters).

Inclusion criteria for participating in this study include:

Women who are mothers, and who:

- are over 18 years
- have experienced domestic abuse in the past while their children were pre-school (Aged 0-5) and within the last 5 years at the time of the research taking place
- have no current contact with any previously known, or suspected perpetrator
- feel they are able to discuss domestic abuse experiences without any significant distress or adverse impact on their general health or psychological wellbeing
- are living in their own, or Women's Aid accommodation within one of the 7 areas of Scotland

All participants will be women and mothers, as it is women who are disproportionately affected by domestic abuse; additionally, it is women who have had children who are more likely than men to have consistent contact with health professionals - both during pregnancy, and post natal periods, but also for her own health as a direct result of experiencing domestic abuse. Participants should be 18 years of age, however there is no upper age limit, providing they have experienced abuse while their children were pre-school (Aged 0-5) and within the last 5 years at the time of the research taking place. This is to facilitate the recollection of contact with health professionals, particularly Health visitors, midwives and GPs.

Women working for domestic abuse organisations, or who are working as Health Visitors, who meet inclusion criteria can also be invited to participate, as it is recognised that they too are likely to be eligible to participate, and may have their own experiences of domestic abuse. Additionally, women who do not have English as a first language and women with pre-existing mental health issues will also be will also be eligible to participate.

A17-2. Please list the principal exclusion criteria (list the most important, max 5000 characters).

Exclusion criteria:

Women who:

- are not mothers
- are under 18 years
- report to having contact with any known past or current perpetrator of abuse.
- are deemed by themselves, to be likely to suffer adversely in terms of their psychological health or wellbeing, as a result of participating in the study.
- have formally opted out of midwifery or health visiting services.
- do not live, at the time of data collection, within one of the 7 areas of Scotland.
- have a current professional relationship with the researcher
- are involved in ongoing criminal investigations or due to make court appearances at the time of the study.

RESEARCH PROCEDURES, RISKS AND BENEFITS

A18. Give details of all non-clinical intervention(s) or procedure(s) that will be received by participants as part of the research protocol. These include seeking consent, interviews, non-clinical observations and use of questionnaires.

Please complete the columns for each intervention/procedure as follows:

1. Total number of interventions/procedures to be received by each participant as part of the research protocol.
2. If this intervention/procedure would be routinely given to participants as part of their care outside the research, how many of the total would be routine?
3. Average time taken per intervention/procedure (minutes, hours or days)
4. Details of who will conduct the intervention/procedure, and where it will take place.

Intervention or procedure	1	2	3	4
One semi-structured interview using the life history calendar data collection tool and timeline production.	1		90mins	The same researcher will interview every participant. Interviews will be conducted by the same researcher at a location agreed between participant and researcher.

A21. How long do you expect each participant to be in the study in total?

Participants will be in the study from the time when consent is given, and through the duration of the interview, where they will be able to confirm findings if they wish. The interview is expected to be approximately 90 minutes in duration.

A22. What are the potential risks and burdens for research participants and how will you minimise them?

For all studies, describe any potential adverse effects, pain, discomfort, distress, intrusion, inconvenience or changes to lifestyle. Only describe risks or burdens that could occur as a result of participation in the research. Say what steps would be taken to minimise risks and burdens as far as possible.

Participating in the study is likely to involve women sharing their experiences of abuse, which has the potential to cause them distress. To reduce the risks associated with this, the researcher will ensure participants firstly feel able to discuss their experiences without this being likely to have significant psychological impacts on their health and wellbeing. The researcher will assess risk for all women participating. Additionally, at the outset of the interviews, the researcher will discuss what support networks women have available to them following participation. Women participating in the study will also be given a detailed list of support available, e.g. helplines and organisations that provide support in their local area.

Women will be made aware that they can withdraw from the study, or stop interviews at any time, and without reason; consent will be reviewed throughout the interview, taking cues from women's presentation, verbal and non-verbal cues, to continually assess the impact of discussing their experiences of abuse.

For those already in receipt of Women's Aid support, they will also be informed that additional support can be arranged from their existing support worker. For those women not receiving Women's Aid support, the researcher will offer referral if required at the end of the interview. Furthermore, women will be encouraged to make contact with their support networks following participation in the study, as a means of reflection and support should the process

have brought past trauma to the forefront.

The researcher has worked previously with women who have experienced trauma and abuse, and therefore feels able to identify if women were suffering distress - or where it would be unethical to continue. Women would be offered an opportunity to continue with the interview at a later date, if requested by the woman. The interviews are semi-structured, with the researcher providing only prompts as needed, to ensure women only disclose what they are comfortable doing; the researcher is reliant on women using narrative to tell their stories, and will use an empathetic approach, and respond appropriately to the cues of women, to ensure they only continue where the women feel comfortable and able to do so.

The risk of compromising the women's relationship with health professionals will be managed by assuring women that their involvement in the study will have no bearing on the health services they receive either at the time of the study, or in the future. They will also be advised that the healthcare professionals they may be in contact with, eg. GP, Health visitors, Midwife, will not be informed of their participation in the study and women will be reassured that the content of their interviews will be kept confidential and will not be fed back to the specific professionals.

Various steps will be taken by the researcher to protect the confidentiality, and promote the safety and wellbeing of the women participating in the study.

Although storage of participant demographic details is required, these will be limited to storage in one central place, where only the researcher has access, and where identification of participants can occur safely. These details will be kept securely in one place, on a password protected Excel spreadsheet, which will record their first name (or their chosen name), and demographic details. This will be saved on an encrypted device (NHS computer), with only the researcher able to access this. Each participant will be assigned an ID code. This ID code which will be on all documentation, interview recordings and transcripts to ensure women remain anonymous. This also ensures any direct quotes remain anonymous, and are not identifiable, or traceable back to the participant by anyone other than the researcher (Allmark et al, 2009). The researcher will undertake their own transcription of data, thus eliminating any additional concerns about confidentiality; during the transcription process, any identifiable information such as geographical location, names of other parties, will be omitted to ensure confidentiality is upheld and any risk to women is reduced as much as possible.

Other measures to promote the confidentiality of participants include the transcription of interview data; only the researcher will have access to interview transcripts, and will transcribe these independently. The interview data will be transcribed and uploaded electronically and saved on an encrypted device. Paper interview notes will also be uploaded electronically and saved on a secure device, and destroyed as soon as is practicable to do so.

Additional risks pertain to the potential disclosure of information suggesting that a child may be at risk of harm; in which case, women will be made aware that if such concern arises, the researcher will discuss this with them, and support will be sought from relevant welfare agencies.

A23. Will interviews/ questionnaires or group discussions include topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting, or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

Yes No

If Yes, please give details of procedures in place to deal with these issues:

The interviews focus very directly on women who have experienced domestic abuse, and specifically focuses on periods of their lives where they were subject to abuse. It is therefore possible that women may become upset/distressed when recalling these events.

The researcher will use empathetic approaches to supporting women through this process with minimal prompts, and use narrative, semi-structured approaches, to allow women to converse at a pace they are comfortable with, and on subjects they are comfortable discussing. An interview schedule (Appendix 6) will support this by providing key prompts where necessary.

Disclosures of information that suggests children may be at risk of harm will result in child welfare agencies (Social services) being made aware - and this will be outlined in the Participant Information, so women are aware of the researcher's obligations, while empathising that this is a supportive mechanism as well as a Duty of Care by the researcher.

The researcher is familiar with supporting women who have experienced trauma and abuse, and also experience of alerting other agencies to concerns of abuse or neglect; therefore the researcher is confident this can be achieved while supporting the women and minimising distress.

Midwifery and Health Visiting practice is regulated by the Nursing And Midwifery Council; where the researcher identifies any professional's practice which is considered in breach of professional regulations, this will be

discussed with the study supervisory team. Where poor practice by Women's Aid workers is highlighted, this will also be discussed with the supervisory team to agree a course of action and escalation.

A24. What is the potential for benefit to research participants?

The benefits of participating in the research are considered to outweigh the risks, as many women who participate in domestic abuse research often report that it is cathartic and empowering. Although participation can be upsetting, women report they feel the benefits of being able to help others, by telling their stories, and highlighting the issue of domestic abuse. Participating in the study also means that women will have access to a number of domestic abuse agencies and services, that she may not have previously been aware of, or felt able to access.

Providing the participants with an opportunity to discuss their experiences in an unstructured manner complements the work of domestic abuse organisations, who support women who are surviving abuse. This study also supports Women's Aid's Research Integrity Framework, and contributes to wider research into Violence Against Women and Girls (VAWAG), to promote learning regarding the experiences of women who have been subject to abuse.

A26. What are the potential risks for the researchers themselves? (if any)

The study will require the researcher working closely and intimately with participants as they re-live their abusive experiences; it is likely that this will have an emotional impact on the researcher as they understand and interpret the participants' narratives.

The use of a reflective diary, practising reflexivity and regular supervision are methods that will be used to mitigate some of these impacts.

If any lone working is required, the researcher will adhere to Board policies and provide a schedule to the research team to promote safety.

Risks to participants and the researcher associated with Covid-19 will be mitigated by maintaining social distancing in face to face meetings, and ensuring participants are free of Covid symptoms prior to any face to face contact.

A risk assessment has been completed (Appendix 7), and insurance details can also be found in Appendix 8.

RECRUITMENT AND INFORMED CONSENT

In this section we ask you to describe the recruitment procedures for the study. Please give separate details for different study groups where appropriate.

A27-1. How will potential participants, records or samples be identified? Who will carry this out and what resources will be used? For example, identification may involve a disease register, computerised search of social care or GP records, or review of medical records. Indicate whether this will be done by the direct care team or by researchers acting under arrangements with the responsible care organisation(s).

Women will be recruited from Women's Aid organisations, and from Health Visiting caseloads within specified areas of Scotland. Information about the research study (Participant Information - Appendix 1) will be provided to Women's Aid organisations and to Health Visitor managers in a variety of regions within Scotland deemed accessible to the researcher. They will be asked to disseminate information about the study to their employees (Women's Aid Workers and Health Visitors). The researcher will also seek to attend Team Meetings in the specified areas, to provide further details about the study. Domestic abuse workers and Health Visitors will act as gatekeepers who will facilitate contact between the researcher and potential participants. Information for Health Visitors (Appendix 2), and Information for Women's Aid (Appendix 3) will be provided to inform both agencies about the study.

Gatekeepers will be asked to identify potential participants, from the pre-defined criteria, and share the information about the study, and support women to seek further information from the researcher if they wish to participate. Once the researcher has had contact with women who are interested in participating, arrangements will be made for the interview to take place, and consent will be discussed. It is at the outset of this interview that consent will be discussed further, and women will be asked to sign a consent form (Appendix 4). Due to the emotive nature of the study, women will be given the choice to not use their real names; participating women will be assigned an identification code to prevent detection, maintain anonymity, but where they can still be identifiable to the researcher throughout the study.

Information to gatekeepers will emphasise that participation is voluntary, and no coercion is to be used to pressure

women into participating; equally, however, gatekeepers should provide women with all the information available, so she is able to make an informed decision about whether to participate.

A27-2. Will the identification of potential participants involve reviewing or screening the identifiable personal information of patients, service users or any other person?

Yes No

Please give details below:

No.

A28. Will any participants be recruited by publicity through posters, leaflets, adverts or websites?

Yes No

A29. How and by whom will potential participants first be approached?

Potential participants will be approached by either Women's Aid workers, or Health Visitors initially, who will provide women who fulfil the inclusion criteria with details of the study (Appendix 1).

They will be equipped with the relevant information about the study, and will encourage women to contact the researcher for further details if they are considering participating. A video of the researcher discussing the study and what participants can expect will be available as well as written material, within the Participation Information Sheet (Appendix 1).

Where potential participants express an interest in participating, the researcher will make contact to discuss the study; equally, participants can contact the researcher to discuss the study. Where women continue to be keen to participate, and give their consent, arrangements for the interview will be made.

These arrangements are in place due to accessibility to potential participants, and the relationship that will already exist between these professionals and the women. Women and gatekeepers will be made aware that women should only consent to participate where they choose freely to do so, and without coercion, and will be made aware they can withdraw at any time.

Although gatekeepers have an important role in the study, their involvement in the study is likely to be beneficial to Health Visitors and Women's Aid Workers. It is possible that providing women with an opportunity to talk openly about their past experiences over their life course, can support their recovery, wellbeing and general health. Women's Aid workers are experienced in supporting victims of abuse and supporting women to rebuild their lives where they have escaped abusive situations. Involvement in the study provides women with an opportunity to discuss their experiences which can promote their healing and empower them to make positive changes. Similarly, Health Visitors are specialist public health nurses, who support women who have experienced domestic abuse as part of their core business, particularly as the impact on women, as well as their children is clearly evident, and contributes to wider health inequalities. There is the potential that following inclusion in this study might result in additional support being needed from Health Visiting Teams; however, supporting in an empowering, cathartic, and supported manner could prevent further risks associated with poor health and wellbeing.

A30-1. Will you obtain informed consent from or on behalf of research participants?

Yes No

If you will be obtaining consent from adult participants, please give details of who will take consent and how it will be done, with details of any steps to provide information (a written information sheet, videos, or interactive material). Arrangements for adults unable to consent for themselves should be described separately in Part B Section 6, and for children in Part B Section 7.

If you plan to seek informed consent from vulnerable groups, say how you will ensure that consent is voluntary and fully informed.

A written Participant Information sheet (Appendix 1) will be provided to any women identified as eligible to participate by Gatekeepers. To help women decide whether to consent, a short video message outlining the study in simple, non-jargonistic language will be made, which will be embedded within the Information Sheet. It is hoped this will answer questions, alleviate any anxieties, and also overcome any literacy difficulties.

Once women express an interest in participating with the Gatekeepers, contact will be made with the researcher, who will facilitate a telephone or video call to discuss the study in more detail and explain the consent process. Where women remain in agreement to participate, arrangements will be made to interview the women. Location of the interview will be determined by participant choice, and will be either in person, or via virtual means, which will be determined between the researcher and participant, and considering safety issues for both parties. At the outset of the interview, the researcher will gain written consent from the women, and consent form (Appendix 4) will be completed. This also allows the researcher to clarify that women are fully aware of the study and what it will involve.

Consent will be continually reviewed during the interviews to ensure women are not unduly distressed, and remain in agreement to give their consent.

If you are not obtaining consent, please explain why not.

Please enclose a copy of the information sheet(s) and consent form(s).

A30-2. Will you record informed consent (or advice from consultees) in writing?

Yes No

A31. How long will you allow potential participants to decide whether or not to take part?

Participants will have between 2-4 weeks to decide if they wish to take part.

A33-1. What arrangements have been made for persons who might not adequately understand verbal explanations or written information given in English, or who have special communication needs?(e.g. translation, use of interpreters)

Interpreters will be used where needed to support women to participate and provide their consent, where English is not the first language.

Additionally, a video will be created to explain the research to potential participants, which will overcome any literacy difficulties, and avoids any anxieties that may exist associated with reading large volumes of text in the Participant Information Sheets (Appendix 1).

A35. What steps would you take if a participant, who has given informed consent, loses capacity to consent during the study? Tick one option only.

- The participant and all identifiable data or tissue collected would be withdrawn from the study. Data or tissue which is not identifiable to the research team may be retained.
- The participant would be withdrawn from the study. Identifiable data or tissue already collected with consent would be retained and used in the study. No further data or tissue would be collected or any other research procedures carried out on or in relation to the participant.
- The participant would continue to be included in the study.
- Not applicable – informed consent will not be sought from any participants in this research.
- Not applicable – it is not practicable for the research team to monitor capacity and continued capacity will be assumed.

Further details:

Consent will be sought throughout the research process. If a participant loses capacity at any point of the research process, the participant and any data pertaining to them will be withdrawn from the study.

Data collected that relates to the participant will be held until the study is complete, and destroyed, but will not be included in any analysis.

CONFIDENTIALITY

In this section, personal data means any data relating to a participant who could potentially be identified. It includes pseudonymised data capable of being linked to a participant through a unique code number.

Storage and use of personal data during the study

A36. Will you be undertaking any of the following activities at any stage (including in the identification of potential participants)? (Tick as appropriate)

- Access to medical records by those outside the direct healthcare team
- Access to social care records by those outside the direct social care team
- Electronic transfer by magnetic or optical media, email or computer networks
- Sharing of personal data with other organisations
- Export of personal data outside the EEA
- Use of personal addresses, postcodes, faxes, emails or telephone numbers
- Publication of direct quotations from respondents
- Publication of data that might allow identification of individuals
- Use of audio/visual recording devices
- Storage of personal data on any of the following:
 - Manual files (includes paper or film)
 - NHS computers
 - Social Care Service computers
 - Home or other personal computers
 - University computers
 - Private company computers
 - Laptop computers

Further details:

Contact details - addresses and telephone numbers will be held in one central location so that interviews can be arranged, and consent reviewed and confirmed - these details will be held electronically and securely on an encrypted NHS device, by the researcher.

The spreadsheet with such details will be password protected to ensure data remains confidential, and will be held on a secure NHS computer/encrypted device, where only the researcher has access.

Only one copy of a spreadsheet will exist. Each participant will be allocated an identification ID, which will be used throughout the study. Only the researcher will have the necessary access to the database which cross references the IDs to the participant details. Only first names will be used, and women participating in the study can choose to use names that are not their own.

Any direct quotes, transcripts, visual data arising from the study will be anonymised through the use of the participant ID, which will ensure they are not identifiable throughout the study.

Interviews will be audio-recorded and transcribed by the researcher. Audio recordings will be deleted once transcription has taken place. Transcriptions will be undertaken electronically, and uploaded and stored securely on an encrypted device. Minimal paper records will be kept; any paper interview notes will be scanned/uploaded so they exist electronically.

Only the researcher will have access to audio devices and subsequent transcriptions. Audio recordings will be destroyed once transcribed and saved electronically. Any personal or identifiable information will be omitted from the transcriptions to ensure participants remain anonymous.

A37. Please describe the physical security arrangements for storage of personal data during the study?

Demographic data relating to participants will be held on an encrypted device, on the researcher's NHS personal computer - which is used solely by the researcher. Additional security measures, password protection to files with personal details, will be added. Paper consent forms that are returned by participants will be scanned and uploaded so they can be saved electronically on the same device. Paper copies will then be destroyed.

A38. How will you ensure the confidentiality of personal data? Please provide a general statement of the policy and procedures for ensuring confidentiality, e.g. anonymisation or pseudonymisation of data.

All participants involved in the study will be provided with a participant ID at the outset - which will be attributed to them for the entirety of the study. For consent purposes, participants will also be free to choose a pseudonym if they prefer, to ensure their names are not disclosed.

Only first names will be used, and recorded against their respective ID numbers on an encrypted NHS secure device. Any email contact with participants will be undertaken using NHS email addresses for security.

During interviews, to develop a trusting relationship with the participant, names will be used (whether real name or pseudonym), however these will be removed during transcription and replaced with the participant ID.

Additionally, any geographical location disclosed during the interviews will be removed from the transcripts/visual timelines, to ensure the women cannot be identifiable by their location.

A40. Who will have access to participants' personal data during the study? Where access is by individuals outside the direct care team, please justify and say whether consent will be sought.

No-one other than the researcher will have access to the personal data of the women participants.

Potential participants will already be known to the Gatekeepers (Women's Aid Workers and Health Visitors) in the study, and will already have access to their personal details, and are bound by their own respective professional and organisational codes of conduct and confidentiality measures.

Storage and use of data after the end of the study

A41. Where will the data generated by the study be analysed and by whom?

Data generated during the study will be analysed by the primary researcher only, who will discuss themes arising with the supervisory team.

Analysis will occur at the researcher's home - within their home office, whereby they only have access and use.

Analysis will happen independently, and will not involve anyone else - only the researcher and supervisory team will have sight of transcripts and access to audio-recordings, which will be listened to in private using headphones to ensure it remains confidential.

Any data in paper form will be kept to a minimum and scanned and uploaded where possible. Where paper data exists, (e.g. interviews waiting to be transcribed), when not in use by the researcher will be securely stored within one room, in a locked cupboard/drawer, with no-one else having access.

A42. Who will have control of and act as the custodian for the data generated by the study?

	Title	Forename/Initials	Surname
	MRS	KERRY	ELLIS
Post	PhD STUDENT		
	MSc Vulnerability		
Qualifications	Dip HE Nursing		
	Specialist Community Public Health Nursing (Health Visiting)		
	BA (Hones) Environmental Studies.		
Work Address			
Post Code			

Personal details withheld.

Work Email
Work Telephone
Fax

Personal details withheld.

A43. How long will personal data be stored or accessed after the study has ended?

- Less than 3 months
 3 – 6 months
 6 – 12 months
 12 months – 3 years
 Over 3 years

If longer than 12 months, please justify:

Personal data will be kept separately from other data.

Data will be kept for 3 years from the end of this study, in line with UWS regulations.

A44. For how long will you store research data generated by the study?

Years: 3

Months: 0

A45. Please give details of the long term arrangements for storage of research data after the study has ended. Say where data will be stored, who will have access and the arrangements to ensure security.

Personal data will be kept centrally on a password protected, encrypted spreadsheet, with only the researcher having access. All research data will be kept securely in this same way by the researcher for 3 years. After this time data will be destroyed in line with NHS and UWS protocols.

INCENTIVES AND PAYMENTS

A46. Will research participants receive any payments, reimbursement of expenses or any other benefits or incentives for taking part in this research?

- Yes No

A47. Will individual researchers receive any personal payment over and above normal salary, or any other benefits or incentives, for taking part in this research?

- Yes No

A48. Does the Chief Investigator or any other investigator/collaborator have any direct personal involvement (e.g. financial, share holding, personal relationship etc.) in the organisations sponsoring or funding the research that may give rise to a possible conflict of interest?

- Yes No

NOTIFICATION OF OTHER PROFESSIONALS

A49-1. Will you inform the participants' General Practitioners (and/or any other health or care professional responsible for their care) that they are taking part in the study?

Yes No

If Yes, please enclose a copy of the information sheet/letter for the GP/health professional with a version number and date.

PUBLICATION AND DISSEMINATION

A50-1. Will the research be registered on a public database?

Yes No

Please give details, or justify if not registering the research.

The study will be registered with the researcher's employing organisation, NHS Dumfries & Galloway once approval has been granted.

The study will be registered on the local public NHS site of where the researcher is employed, and also within areas of Scotland where participants reside.

Registration of research studies is encouraged wherever possible.

You may be able to register your study through your NHS organisation or a register run by a medical research charity, or publish your protocol through an open access publisher. If you are aware of a suitable register or other method of publication, please give details. If not, you may indicate that no suitable register exists. Please ensure that you have entered registry reference number(s) in question A5-1.

A51. How do you intend to report and disseminate the results of the study? Tick as appropriate:

- Peer reviewed scientific journals
- Internal report
- Conference presentation
- Publication on website
- Other publication
- Submission to regulatory authorities
- Access to raw data and right to publish freely by all investigators in study or by Independent Steering Committee on behalf of all investigators
- No plans to report or disseminate the results
- Other (please specify)

Study findings are likely to impact on primary care services, therefore it is anticipated that findings will be disseminated to Service Managers of health visiting and midwifery services, and GPs across Scotland. Service managers will be encouraged to share the findings with their teams.

Reports will be devised for participants to give details of the study findings. Similar reports will be provided to the Women's Aid organisations who participated, and also to the wider Women's Aid Organisation.

The researcher will also aim to publish the study, and present at conferences where opportunities arise.

A52. If you will be using identifiable personal data, how will you ensure that anonymity will be maintained when publishing the results?

Published results will not include any identifiable data.

All participants' direct quotes/personal details/geographical locations will be anonymised.

Only themes of data will be published, to avoid women's personal journey's or unique life stories leading to them being identifiable.

A53. How and when will you inform participants of the study results?

If there will be no arrangements in place to inform participants please justify this.

Findings from the study will also be produced in a written format that is understandable to the participants, avoiding any jargon or technical language.

Any participant will be made aware they can request verbal account of findings if necessary to overcome any literacy difficulties.

5. Scientific and Statistical Review

A54-1. How has the scientific quality of the research been assessed? *Tick as appropriate:*

- Independent external review
- Review within a company
- Review within a multi-centre research group
- Review within the Chief Investigator's institution or host organisation
- Review within the research team
- Review by educational supervisor
- Other

Justify and describe the review process and outcome. If the review has been undertaken but not seen by the researcher, give details of the body which has undertaken the review:

The study will be reviewed within the chief investigating institution (University of the West of Scotland), the University Ethics Committee and also reviewed by the supervisory team.

For all studies except non-doctoral student research, please enclose a copy of any available scientific critique reports, together with any related correspondence.

For non-doctoral student research, please enclose a copy of the assessment from your educational supervisor/ institution.

A59. What is the sample size for the research? *How many participants/samples/data records do you plan to study in total? If there is more than one group, please give further details below.*

Total UK sample size: 10
Total international sample size (including UK): 10
Total in European Economic Area: 10

Further details:

Purposive sampling will be used to identify potential participants from women residing either in their homes or in Women's Aid accommodation across a variety of geographical locations within Scotland and who meet the inclusion criteria - as they are most likely to be able to meet the aims and objectives of the study.

Participants will be invited to be part of the study from various locations across Scotland to improve the likelihood of reaching a sample large enough to obtain depth and understanding of the research topic. Areas that will be included in the sample will be: Southern Scotland (Dumfries And Galloway), Borders region, Ayrshire, Lanarkshire, Edinburgh, Glasgow and Forth Valley.

It is expected that sample sizes will be relatively small, approx between 7-10, which will ensure resources allocated to the study can adequately manage data collected. Data will be reviewed after each interview to identify if and when data saturation has been achieved, and no new themes or understandings have been reached.

A60. How was the sample size decided upon? *If a formal sample size calculation was used, indicate how this was done, giving sufficient information to justify and reproduce the calculation.*

The 7 areas within Scotland were decided due to the accessibility of the researcher to reach them to meet participants and collect data. Also, sampling from more than one area of Scotland provides a more diverse population than if women from only one area were invited to participate. Each of these areas also has a Women's Aid organisation, offering accommodation and services, thus increasing the likelihood of obtaining an adequate sample.

The sample size will be between 7-10, however, there is scope for this sample be larger than what is proposed, should the response be more positive than anticipated.
This sample size is also comparable to similar studies.

A62. Please describe the methods of analysis (statistical or other appropriate methods, e.g. for qualitative research) by which the data will be evaluated to meet the study objectives.

Data analysis will primarily take the form of analysing interview transcriptions through thematic analysis. However, in Hermeneutic research this requires the researcher to move move back and forth between new knowledge generated in the interviews, and what was already known about the subject. Heidegger's (1962) circle method will be used to continually review and question parts of and whole parts of texts arising from interviews with participants.

Data will be transcribed by the researcher to ensure full immersion with the data; transcripts will be read and re-read to allow the researcher to become immersed in the narratives and develop interpretive summaries and identify themes, illustrating similarities and differences between participants. Individual words and phrases used by participants to describe their experiences of domestic abuse, and their relationships with others during periods of abuse will be highlighted and interpreted as having additional value (Mackey, 2005). This will involve line by line coding to reduce data into concepts which are then grouped into themes (Christie et al, 2020). Meditative thinking is a strategy that will be used when data is interpreted as it allows researchers to be open to thinking and be attuned to the ontological experiences of participants (Heidegger, 1966).

Alongside analysis of transcriptions, the visual timelines will be compared and analysed to identify similarities and themes. Member checking by a supervisor will also be used as good practice, to ensure rigour, and to ensure all themes are appropriately identified and given necessary attention in the study.

6. MANAGEMENT OF THE RESEARCH

A63. Other key investigators/collaborators. Please include all grant co-applicants, protocol co-authors and other key members of the Chief Investigator's team, including non-doctoral student researchers.

Title Forename/Initials Surname
Post
Qualifications
Employer
Work Address
Post Code
Telephone
Fax
Mobile
Work Email

A64. Details of research sponsor(s)

A64-1. Sponsor

Lead Sponsor
Status: <input type="radio"/> NHS or HSC care organisation
Commercial status:

- Academic
- Pharmaceutical industry
- Medical device industry
- Local Authority
- Other social care provider (including voluntary sector or private organisation)
- Other

If Other, please specify:

Contact person

Name of organisation University of the West of Scotland
 Given name Dr William
 Family name Mackay
 Address
 Town/city
 Post code
 Country
 Telephone
 Fax
 E-mail

Personal details withheld.

Legal representative for clinical investigation of medical device (studies involving Northern Ireland only)
Clinical Investigations of Medical Devices that take place in Northern Ireland must have a legal representative of the sponsor that is based in Northern Ireland or the EU

Contact person

Name of organisation
 Given name
 Family name
 Address
 Town/city
 Post code
 Country
 Telephone
 Fax
 E-mail

A65. Has external funding for the research been secured?

Please tick at least one check box.

- Funding secured from one or more funders
- External funding application to one or more funders in progress

No application for external funding will be made

What type of research project is this?

- Standalone project
 Project that is part of a programme grant
 Project that is part of a Centre grant
 Project that is part of a fellowship/ personal award/ research training award
 Other

Other – please state:

Please give details of funding applications.

Organisation General Nursing Council - National Education for Scotland (NES)
Address Westport 102
West Port
Edinburgh
Post Code EH3 9DN
Telephone 01316563200
Fax 01316563201
Mobile
Email GNC@nes.scot.nhs.uk

Funding Application Status: Secured In progress

Amount: £2300

Duration

Years: 1

Months: 0

If applicable, please specify the programme/ funding stream:

What is the funding stream/ programme for this research project?

GNC for Scotland (Education) Fund 1983 and Margaret Callum Roger Midwifery Fund.

Organisation McQueen Bursary/Community Practitioner's Health Visiting Association (CPHVA)
Address 78 Chamber Street
London
Post Code E1 8BL
Telephone
Fax
Mobile
Email Personal details withheld.

Funding Application Status: Secured In progress

Amount: 2300

Duration

Years: 1

Months:

If applicable, please specify the programme/ funding stream:

What is the funding stream/ programme for this research project?

A66. Has responsibility for any specific research activities or procedures been delegated to a subcontractor (other than a co-sponsor listed in A64-1)? Please give details of subcontractors if applicable.

Yes No

A67. Has this or a similar application been previously rejected by a Research Ethics Committee in the UK or another country?

Yes No

Please provide a copy of the unfavourable opinion letter(s). You should explain in your answer to question A6-2 how the reasons for the unfavourable opinion have been addressed in this application.

A68-1. Give details of the lead NHS R&D contact for this research:

Title	Forename/Initials	Surname
	Janie	Candlish
Organisation	NHS Dumfries & Galloway	
Address	[Redacted]	
Post Code	[Redacted]	
Work Email	[Redacted]	
Telephone	[Redacted]	
Fax	[Redacted]	
Mobile	[Redacted]	

Personal details withheld.

Details can be obtained from the NHS R&D Forum website: <http://www.rdforum.nhs.uk>

A69-1. How long do you expect the study to last in the UK?

Planned start date: 05/08/2019

Planned end date: 30/11/2023

Total duration:

Years: 4 Months: 3 Days: 26

A71-1. Is this study?

Single centre

Multicentre

A71-2. Where will the research take place? (Tick as appropriate)

- England
- Scotland
- Wales
- Northern Ireland
- Other countries in European Economic Area

Total UK sites in study 7

Does this trial involve countries outside the EU?

- Yes No

A72. Which organisations in the UK will host the research? Please indicate the type of organisation by ticking the box and give approximate numbers if known:

- NHS organisations in England
- NHS organisations in Wales
- NHS organisations in Scotland 7
- HSC organisations in Northern Ireland
- GP practices in England
- GP practices in Wales
- GP practices in Scotland
- GP practices in Northern Ireland
- Joint health and social care agencies (eg community mental health teams)
- Local authorities
- Phase 1 trial units
- Prison establishments
- Probation areas
- Independent (private or voluntary sector) organisations
- Educational establishments
- Independent research units
- Other (give details)

Total UK sites in study: 7

A73-1. Will potential participants be identified through any organisations other than the research sites listed above?

- Yes No

A73-2. If yes, will any of these organisations be NHS organisations?

- Yes No

If yes, details should be given in Part C.

A74. What arrangements are in place for monitoring and auditing the conduct of the research?

Monthly supervision with UWS supervisors

A76. Insurance/ indemnity to meet potential legal liabilities

Note: in this question to NHS indemnity schemes include equivalent schemes provided by Health and Social Care (HSC) in Northern Ireland

A76-1. What arrangements will be made for insurance and/or indemnity to meet the potential legal liability of the sponsor(s) for harm to participants arising from the management of the research? Please tick box(es) as applicable.

Note: Where a NHS organisation has agreed to act as sponsor or co-sponsor, indemnity is provided through NHS schemes. Indicate if this applies (there is no need to provide documentary evidence). For all other sponsors, please describe the arrangements and provide evidence.

- NHS indemnity scheme will apply (NHS sponsors only)
 Other insurance or indemnity arrangements will apply (give details below)

Insurance will be provided by University of the West of Scotland (Appendix 8).

Please enclose a copy of relevant documents.

A76-2. What arrangements will be made for insurance and/ or indemnity to meet the potential legal liability of the sponsor(s) or employer(s) for harm to participants arising from the design of the research? Please tick box(es) as applicable.

Note: Where researchers with substantive NHS employment contracts have designed the research, indemnity is provided through NHS schemes. Indicate if this applies (there is no need to provide documentary evidence). For other protocol authors (e.g. company employees, university members), please describe the arrangements and provide evidence.

- NHS indemnity scheme will apply (protocol authors with NHS contracts only)
 Other insurance or indemnity arrangements will apply (give details below)

Insurance will be provided by University of the West of Scotland (Appendix 8).

Please enclose a copy of relevant documents.

A76-3. What arrangements will be made for insurance and/ or indemnity to meet the potential legal liability of investigators/collaborators arising from harm to participants in the conduct of the research?

Note: Where the participants are NHS patients, indemnity is provided through the NHS schemes or through professional indemnity. Indicate if this applies to the whole study (there is no need to provide documentary evidence). Where non-NHS sites are to be included in the research, including private practices, please describe the arrangements which will be made at these sites and provide evidence.

- NHS indemnity scheme or professional indemnity will apply (participants recruited at NHS sites only)
 Research includes non-NHS sites (give details of insurance/ indemnity arrangements for these sites below)

Please enclose a copy of relevant documents.

A78. Could the research lead to the development of a new product/process or the generation of intellectual property?

- Yes No Not sure

9. Has the study been the subject of a scientific review/opinion (Expert Panel)?

Yes No

If yes, please provide a copy of the review as part of your application.

PART C: Overview of research sites

Please enter details of the host organisations (Local Authority, NHS or other) in the UK that will be responsible for the research sites. For further information please refer to guidance.

Investigator identifier	Research site	Investigator Name
IN2	<input checked="" type="radio"/> NHS/HSC Site <input type="radio"/> Non-NHS/HSC Site Organisation name: NHS Ayrshire and Arran Address: PO Box 13, Boswell House 10 Arthur Street AYR Scotland Post Code: KA7 1QJ Country: SCOTLAND	Forename: KERRY Middle name: JOANNE Family name: ELLIS Email: [REDACTED] Qualification (MD...): Country: United Kingdom
IN3	<input checked="" type="radio"/> NHS/HSC Site <input type="radio"/> Non-NHS/HSC Site Organisation name: NHS Borders Address: NEWSTEAD MELROSE ROXBURGHSHIRE Post Code: TD6 9DB Country: SCOTLAND	Forename: KERRY Middle name: JOANNE Family name: ELLIS Email: [REDACTED] Qualification (MD...): Country: United Kingdom
IN4	<input checked="" type="radio"/> NHS/HSC Site <input type="radio"/> Non-NHS/HSC Site	Forename: KERRY Middle name: JOANNE

Organisation name	NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde	Family name	ELLIS
Address	J B Russell House Gartnavel Royal Hospital 1055 Great Western Road Glasgow Scotland	Email	[REDACTED]
Post Code	G12 0XH	Qualification (MD...)	
Country	SCOTLAND	Country	United Kingdom

IN5

- NHS/HSC Site
 Non-NHS/HSC Site

Organisation name	NHS Lanarkshire	Forename	KERRY
Address	14 Beckford Street HAMILTON Scotland	Middle name	JOANNE
Post Code	ML3 0TA	Family name	ELLIS
Country	SCOTLAND	Email	[REDACTED]
		Qualification (MD...)	
		Country	United Kingdom

IN6

- NHS/HSC Site
 Non-NHS/HSC Site

Organisation name	NHS Dumfries and Galloway	Forename	KERRY
Address	Grierson House The Crichton Bankend Road DUMFRIES Scotland	Middle name	JOANNE
Post Code	DG1 4ZG	Family name	ELLIS
Country	SCOTLAND	Email	[REDACTED]
		Qualification (MD...)	
		Country	United Kingdom

IN7

- NHS/HSC Site
 Non-NHS/HSC Site

Organisation name	NHS Forth Valley	Forename	KERRY
		Middle name	JOANNE
		Family name	ELLIS
		Email	[REDACTED]

Address 33 SPITTAL STREET
STIRLING

Qualification
(MD...)

Country United Kingdom

Post Code FK8 1DX
Country SCOTLAND

IN8

- NHS/HSC Site
 Non-NHS/HSC Site

Organisation name NHS Lothian
Address Waverley Gate
2-4 Waterloo Place
Edinburgh Scotland
Post Code EH1 3EG
Country SCOTLAND

Forename KERRY
Middle name JOANNE
Family name ELLIS
Email [REDACTED]
Qualification (MD...)
Country United Kingdom

IN9

- NHS/HSC Site
 Non-NHS/HSC Site

Institution name
Department name
Street address
Town/city
Post Code
Country

Forename KERRY
Middle name JOANNE
Family name ELLIS
Email [REDACTED]
Qualification (MD...)
Country United Kingdom

IN10

- NHS/HSC Site
 Non-NHS/HSC Site

Forename
Middle name
Family name
Email
Qualification (MD...)
Country

16.11 Appendix 8 - Participatant Information Sheet (PIS)

Study title: Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse: Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.

Introduction and summary of research

Thank you for taking the time to read this information. My name is Kerry Ellis, and I am a PhD (Doctoral degree) student at the University of the West of Scotland. The purpose of my study is to look back at mother's experiences of domestic abuse over her life, and her relationships with health professionals, including GPs, Midwives, Health Visitors, Hospital staff etc., to identify if, or how these relationships might have affected her decisions to tell others about the abuse. This can be any kind of abuse, for example, physical, emotional, financial, sexual, coercive control.

Who has reviewed this study?

The research has been reviewed and approved by the Heath Research Authority, University of West of Scotland Ethics Committee and NHS Dumfries and Galloway Research and Development Team.

What's involved?

The study will involve one face to face meeting, which will last between 60-90 minutes. We can discuss where this will take place, but can be undertaken at your home, a health centre, or even virtually, using Facetime, Teams, WhatsApp video call, or something similar. During this interview, I will ask you to talk about the periods in your life where you have experienced domestic abuse, so we can develop a timeline of events. To help, I might ask you about other significant events in your life, such as leaving school, employment, marriage, being pregnant, having children. You only have to talk about events you are comfortable with and can stop at any time if this is making you upset. If you choose to share your experiences of abuse with me, I might ask about any injuries that you sustained, medical attention you received, and any contact with health professionals, for example, Health Visitors, Midwives, GPs during these times, and whether you chose to tell them about the domestic abuse you were experiencing. I am asking women throughout Scotland to be involved and tell their stories.

Potential benefits of taking part in the study

Women who have been involved in domestic abuse research often report that having opportunities to talk about their experiences can be helpful and empowering to them. Some women report that it allows them to 'tell their story', which can then help other women who might be going through similar experiences. If you join the study, you will be helping to make health professionals think about how they respond to women

who are experiencing abuse so that they can receive appropriate help sooner and hopefully help to improve services to women in these situations.

Potential risks of taking part in the study

Involvement in the study will mean talking about your past experiences that may be painful and upsetting, and bring back bad memories; however, you don't have to talk about anything you don't want to, and you can decide how much to share. You can also decide not to continue, or to stop being part of the study at any time. Support following involvement can be found at: womensaid.org.uk, or through your local Women's Aid organisation.

Explanation, purpose, and background

Most women who have children will have had contact with a Health Visitor, GP, and Midwife; these health professionals are trained to ask about domestic abuse, however we know from previous research, that women don't often talk about domestic abuse to professionals, although it does help if they have a good relationship with that person.

It is hoped that by listening to women who are mothers, professionals will understand what helps a woman to disclose abuse, and the kind of professional relationship that is needed to for women to feel comfortable disclosing. It is also hoped that this study will help health professionals to identify, respond and support women who do tell them about abuse they are experiencing.

Further information

You can help in this study by agreeing to be involved in an interview and signing a consent form. The interview discussion will be recorded and you can choose to have your support worker, or another person of your choice present with you during the interview if you wish.

Joining in this study is completely your choice, and you can leave the study at any time, without giving any reason, during or following the interview. The recording will be deleted if consent is withdrawn. If you give consent to participate, I will check you are happy to continue at various times during the interview.

How will my data be used?

In the UK we follow General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) rules and the Data Protection Act, and any research has to protect the privacy of those who take part, and be approved by an Ethics Committee. In this study, your personal details will be kept confidential; only your first name will be used, and this doesn't have to be your real name. Your name will be replaced with an ID number and only I, as the researcher will have access to your details, which will ensure your contribution to the study remains anonymous. There will be no information that might identify you, where you live, or the health care teams you have had contact with. No-one else will know about you joining in the study, other than myself, unless you tell them.

The interview will be recorded and transcribed and your name will be removed; the recordings will be deleted once they have been transcribed, and transcription will be stored securely where only I have access. The content of the interview will remain confidential and only those present at the interview, and my University Supervisors, will know what is discussed. Any direct quotes will remove any information that could identify you.

If during the interview, I am concerned about your safety, we will discuss the supports available to you. If our discussions highlight current concerns about the safety or wellbeing of your children, it may be necessary to share information and request assistance from other agencies, but we will discuss this and work out a plan together.

Once the study is completed, you will receive a summary of the findings. These will also be shared with health professionals throughout Scotland, so health services can be improved to support women experiencing domestic abuse. If you think you might want to be involved in the study, or if you have any questions either you or your support worker can contact me, and I will be happy to discuss any queries.

Contact details for the study team

Kerry Ellis – Researcher – [REDACTED]
[REDACTED] [ac.uk](#)

Personal details withheld.

Kind regards

Kerry Ellis

Frequently asked Questions

Q: I see my Health Visitor regularly – will she know that I am participating in the study and be told what I say about her?

A: Your Health Visitor will only know you are participating, if they provided you information about the study, or if you choose to tell them. Your HV will not know what we discuss during the interview, and no details of the interview will be shared with them – unless there is ongoing risk of harm to you or your children.

Q: I experienced abuse for the first time when I was very young. I might not be able to remember everything accurately. Does this matter?

A: To help you recall abuse and timing of these events, I might ask about other significant events in your life, for example pregnancy, childbirth, marriage, jobs, to help identify the timing of abuse in your life, and develop the timeline.

Q: I am pregnant, will the information I provide in the interview affect the care I receive from the Midwives?

A: No. The midwifery team will not know about your participation in the study. Anything discussed in the interviews remains strictly confidential and will not be shared with the health care teams unless there is an ongoing risk of harm to you, your unborn child, or your children.

Q: I would like to have someone with me in the interview, can my friend be present?

A: Yes, you can have someone with you, this can be a support worker, a friend, or a family member. They will be there to support you, but not to take an active role in the interview.

16.12 Appendix 9 - Information for Health Visitors

Study title: Developing an insight into mother's experiences of domestic abuse: Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.

Introduction and summary of research

Thank you for taking the time to read this information.

My name is Kerry Ellis, and I am a PhD (Doctoral degree) student at the University of the West of Scotland. The purpose of my study is to explore mother's experiences of domestic abuse over their life-courses, and their relationships with health professionals (at the time?), including GPs, Midwives, Health Visitors, Hospital staff etc., to identify if, or how these relationships might have affected their decisions to disclose abuse to others.

What's involved?

Participants will be women who are mothers, who have experienced domestic abuse at some time in their past. They must not be currently experiencing abuse. The study will involve one face to face interview where they will be asked about periods in their lives where they have experienced domestic abuse, in order to develop a timeline of events. Interviews will be led by the mothers, but with prompts to explore any injuries that were sustained, medical attention that was required, and any contact with health professionals, for example Health Visitors, Midwives, GPs during these times. The participants will be invited to share whether they chose to tell these professionals about the domestic abuse they were experiencing, and the reasons behind their decision to disclose or not. I am offering the opportunity to mothers from various areas of Scotland to be involved and tell their stories; they will be recruited from Health visiting caseloads and from those with connections to Women's Aid. I am asking that Health Visitors from the specific areas within Scotland share details of the study with mothers on their caseloads who meet the inclusion criteria, and support them to request further information, or act as a facilitator between the researcher and the potential participants.

The research has been approved by the NHS Research Ethics Committee (NREC), University of West of Scotland Ethics Committee and NHS (Name) Research and Development Department.

Potential benefits of taking part in the study

Women who have been involved in domestic abuse research report that having opportunities to talk about their experiences can be helpful and empowering. Some women report that it allows them to 'tell their story' and have their voices heard. This

study provides an opportunity for you to be actively involved in contemporary research that relates directly to a public health issue which will affect women on your caseloads. Your involvement is pivotal in hearing the voices of abused women, to influence how practitioners identify and respond to women who experience abuse. Additionally, it is anticipated that the findings of the study will influence service delivery and improve the experiences of women through creating a better understanding of the conditions that are required for domestic abuse disclosure to take place.

Potential risks of taking part in the study

Although you will be asked to identify women on your caseloads who will be eligible to participate, there should be no pressure or coercion for them to do so. Also, any potential participants will be assured that their interview data will remain confidential, and this will not be shared with anyone else – including the health visiting team. Involvement in the study might be distressing for participants, as they are likely to be recalling traumatic and upsetting events from their past relating to the abuse they have experienced. It is possible that they will require additional support from you following participation, which could add to your workload.

Explanation, purpose and background

Most women who have children will have had contact with a Health Visitor, GP and Midwife, who often use sensitive and routine enquiry to ask about domestic abuse, however research tells us that women don't often disclose abuse to professionals, although it does help if they have a good relationship with that person (Prosman *et al*, 2013; Lundell *et al*, 2017). It is hoped that the study will identify the factors that influence mothers' decisions to disclose abuse to health professionals, and the role that the mother-professional relationship plays in her decision-making.

Further information

You can be involved in the study by helping to recruit mothers from your caseloads. Women who are eligible to participate must meet the following criteria:

- Have experienced abuse while their children were pre-school (Aged 0-5) and within the last 5 years at the time of the research taking place.
- Be no longer experiencing domestic abuse
- Be living in a safe environment – either in their own homes, or in Women's Aid accommodation
- Not have any contact with perpetrators of abuse
- Feel able to discuss their domestic abuse experiences without any anticipated significant emotional distress being likely to impact on their psychological health and wellbeing
- Be able to consent to participate in the study

Please note that women who meet this criteria but whose first language is not English, or who struggle with reading English will also be welcomed.

The following women will, however, not be suitable to be included:

- Those who report, or who are suspected to have contact with any known or suspected perpetrator of abuse
- Those who are known to be experiencing abuse at the time of the study.
- Those who have formally opted out of Midwifery or Health visiting services
- Those who report experiencing unresolved trauma
- Those involved in any legal proceedings or Police investigations at the time of the study

Once eligible mothers have been identified, you could help by discussing the study with them, and providing them with the Participant Information. Should these women want further information or be interested in participating, it would be appreciated if you could inform me, and provide them with my contact details for them to make contact and seek further information. This can be done by telephone, messaging, email or text. It is not your responsibility to seek consent that is my responsibility as the researcher.

Potential participants may require support in reading and understanding the Participation Information, and therefore, I would be grateful if you could help by providing clarity where this might be needed. You can also inform me where women are eligible to participate, and who might be interested in taking part, but where interpretation services are required to ensure that they can be included in the study.

If during the interviews, I am concerned about the safety of the women, I will discuss the supports available to them. If concerns arise during the interviews about the safety or wellbeing of their children, mothers will be made aware that it may be necessary to share information with and request assistance from other agencies. If referrals to Social Work are required due to child protection concerns, the Named Person/Health Visitor will be informed.

Once the study is completed, participants and professionals involved in recruitment will receive a copy of a summary report of the findings. A summary of the findings will also be shared with the relevant Service Managers throughout Scotland, so health services can be improved to support women experiencing domestic abuse.

If you have any questions about the study, I will be happy to answer these. I would be happy to attend team meetings to share information about the study and discuss the HV role in the study in more detail, if this is required. Alternatively, I can be contacted at any time using the details below.

Kind regards

Kerry Ellis

[Redacted signature block]

16.13 Appendix 10 - Information for Women's Aid Organisations

Study title: Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse: Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.

Introduction and summary of research

Thank you for taking the time to read this information.

My name is Kerry Ellis, and I am a PhD (Doctoral degree) student at the University of the West of Scotland. The purpose of my study is to explore mother's experiences of domestic abuse during their lives and the relationships they have had with health professionals (including GPs, Midwives, Health Visitors, and Hospital staff), to identify if, or how, these relationships might have affected their decisions to disclose abuse.

What's involved?

The study will involve one face to face interview with the women, where they will be asked about periods in their lives where they have experienced abuse, to develop a timeline of events. Interviews will be led by the women themselves, but with prompts to explore further details. Participants will be invited to share whether they chose to tell professionals about the abuse they were experiencing, and the reasons behind their decision to disclose or not. I am asking women from various areas of Scotland to be involved and tell their stories. Women will be recruited from Health visiting caseloads and from those who have connections with Women's Aid.

I would really appreciate your help, by asking your colleagues working for Women's Aid if they could please share details of the study with the women they might be supporting, who meet the inclusion criteria, and ask that they support women to contact me to ask for further information about the study.

The research has been approved by the NHS Research Ethics Committees (NREC), the University of West of Scotland Ethics Committee and the NHS (Name of Health Board) Research and Development Department.

Potential benefits of taking part in the study

Women who have been involved in domestic abuse research often report that having opportunities to talk about their experiences can be helpful and empowering. Some women report that it allows them to 'tell their story', and have their voices heard. This study provides an opportunity for local organisations to be actively involved in contemporary research that relates directly to a public health issue that affects large proportions of women across Scotland. Your involvement is pivotal in hearing the voices of abused women, with a view to influencing how healthcare services respond to women who experience abuse. Additionally, it is hoped that the

findings of the study will influence service delivery and improve the experiences of women; it will help us all to have a better understanding of the conditions that are required for domestic abuse disclosure to take place, with a view to earlier disclosures.

Potential risks of taking part in the study

Risks to your workers have been considered, and although they will be asked to identify women that would be eligible to participate, who are either living in Women's Aid accommodation or who they are supporting, they will not be directly involved in the study. Also, any women considering taking part will be assured that their data from the interview will remain confidential and will not be shared with anyone else – including their Women's Aid support workers.

It is likely that recalling events from the past will be upsetting for women and I do recognise that this may mean they may need additional support from yourselves and those around them; however, I am also aware that many women do find 'telling their story' therapeutic too.

Explanation, purpose and background

Most women who have children will have had contact with a Health Visitor, GP and Midwife; these health professionals often use sensitive and routine enquiry to ask about domestic abuse, however research tells us that women don't often disclose abuse to professionals, although it does help if they have a good relationship with that person. It is hoped that by listening to women who are mothers, professionals will understand the conditions that are required for a woman to disclose abuse, and also the kind of relationship that is needed to for women to feel comfortable disclosing. It is also hoped that this study will help health professionals to identify, respond and support women who do tell them about abuse they have experienced.

Further information

You can be involved by helping to recruit women to the study from your organisation.

Women who are eligible to participate must:

- Have experienced abuse while their children were pre-school (Aged 0-5) and within the last 5 years at the time of the research taking place.
- Be no longer experiencing domestic abuse
- Be living in a safe environment – either in their own homes, or in Women's Aid accommodation
- Not have any contact with perpetrators of abuse
- Feel able to discuss their domestic abuse experiences without any anticipated significant emotional distress being likely to impact on their psychological health and wellbeing
- Be able to consent to take part in the study

Please note that women who meet these criteria but whose first language is not English, or who struggle with reading English will also be welcomed.

The following women will, however, not be eligible to be included:

- Those who report, or who are suspected to have contact with any known or suspected perpetrator of abuse
- Those who are known to be experiencing abuse at the time of the study
- Those who have formally opted out of Midwifery or Health visiting services
- Those who report experiencing unresolved trauma, or who believe that participation in the study may have a negative emotional impact on their wellbeing
- Those involved in any legal proceedings or Police investigations at the time of the study

Once eligible women have been identified, your workers will be asked to discuss the study with them and provide them with Participant Information. Should women want further information or be interested in participating, your colleagues can provide the women with my contact details or your colleagues can make contact on their behalf. This can be done by telephone, messaging, email, or text. It is not the support worker's responsibility to seek consent, this is my responsibility as the researcher. It is also particularly important to me that there should be no pressure or coercion for any women to take part.

Potential participants may require support in reading and understanding the Participation Information, and it would be helpful if your workers could assist in providing clarity where this might be needed. They can also inform me where women are eligible to participate, and who might be interested in taking part, but where translation services are required to promote inclusion.

If during the interviews, I am concerned about the safety of any woman, I will discuss the supports available to them. If concerns arise during the interviews about the safety or wellbeing of a woman's children, they will be made aware that it is necessary to share information with, and request assistance from, other agencies.

Once the study is complete, the participants and you will receive a copy of a summary report of the findings. The findings will also be shared with the relevant Service Managers throughout Scotland, so health services can be improved to support women experiencing domestic abuse.

If you have any questions about the study, I will be happy to answer these. I would be happy to attend team meetings to share information about the study and discuss the study in more detail if this is required. Alternatively, I can be contacted at any time using the details below.

Kind regards

Kerry Ellis

Telephone: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

16.14 Appendix 11 – Consent form

IRAS ID: 292380

Study Number:

Participant Identification Number for this trial:

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: An insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse.

Name of Researcher: Kerry Ellis

Please
initial
box

1. I confirm that I have read the information sheet dated 19.5.22 (version 1.0) for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without my health/medical care or legal rights being affected.
3. I agree to my interview with the researcher being audio-recorded, for transcription and analysis purposes.
4. I understand that participation in the study will involve being asked to recall experiences which may be upsetting; and I understand that I can share only what I am comfortable with.
5. I confirm that I feel able to recall and share my experiences without any expected Significant adverse impacts on my mental or psychological health and wellbeing.
6. I agree to a timeline being produced based on the information provided in the interviews.
7. I confirm that at the time of participation I am not experiencing any kind of domestic abuse, including financial abuse, emotional abuse, coercive control, physical abuse, sexual abuse.
8. I confirm that at the time of participating I am not in any contact with any person who has perpetrated domestic abuse, or displaying any abusive behaviours.
9. I consent to the publication of any direct quotes which will be anonymised
10. I understand that some of my data collected during the study, may be looked at by individuals from the University of the West of Scotland, from regulatory authorities or from the NHS Health Board, where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records.

11. I consent to take part in the study

Name of Participant Date Signature
Name of Person Date Signature
taking consent

2 copies to be completed:

1 – Participant

1 – Researcher File

16.15 Appendix 12 – Life History Calendar

Age																																				
Year																																				
Month	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S			
Marriages	#												J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S			
Live with spouse																																				
Live with partner																																				
Children	#																																			
Pregnancies	#																																			
Lived with:																																				
Parents together																																				
M & D																																				
Mother																																				
Father																																				
Mother and partner																																				
Father and partner																																				
Self																																				
Carer																																				
Other																																				
Homeless																																				
School																																				
Full time																																				
Part time																																				
None																																				
Expulsions																																				
Further/Higher Education																																				
Employment																																				
Full time																																				
Part time																																				
None																																				
Health																																				
Hospital admissions																																				
Alcohol use																																				
Drug use																																				
Domestic Abuse																																				

16.16 Appendix 13 - Interview schedule

Focus area	Examples of questions/possible prompts
Personal Data	<p>Please confirm your age, DOB</p> <p>Where were you born?</p> <p>How many children do you have – ages?</p>
Early life	<p>Tell me about your early life, growing up – what was that like for you?</p> <p>What were your relationships like with your parents/carers/siblings?</p> <p>Tell me about school</p>
Personal relationships	<p>Can you tell me about your experiences of domestic abuse?</p> <p>What kind of abuse?</p> <p>How did this affect you?</p> <p>Have you had any relationships that were not abusive?</p> <p>Did you ever sustain injuries and present at a health setting, for example, GP, A&E etc.?</p> <p>When you did tell others abuse, who did you tell?</p> <p>Can you explain why you chose to tell this person?</p>
Relationship with health professionals	<p>Do you remember seeing the GP/Midwife/HV during pregnancy or when your children were small?</p> <p>Can you tell me about your relationship with each of them?</p> <p>What did you like/not like about this relationship?</p>

16.17 Appendix 14 - Participant Safeguarding Checklist

	*Yes	*No
1. The participant reports that they are not experiencing any kind of domestic abuse, at this time including financial abuse, emotional abuse, coercive control, physical abuse, sexual abuse		
2. The participant reports they are not, at the time of participating, in any contact with any person who has perpetrated domestic abuse, or displaying any abusive behaviours		
3. The participant reports that they feel able to recall and share experiences without any expected significant adverse impacts on their mental or psychological health and wellbeing.		
4. The participant can identify a network of support they are able to contact following participation in the study if needed		
5. Has the participant confirmed who else might be present with them (or in the vicinity) for the duration of the interview – and does this pose any risks?		
6. If the participant has someone to accompany them to the interview, is this person clear about their duty to keep information confidential, and does the participant understand that ensuring confidentiality from this third party is not the responsibility of the researcher?		
7. Does the participant already have support from Women’s Aid?		
8. Have details of support agencies been provided to the participant?		
9. Are any of your children still in contact with someone who may have abused you, does your participation in this research pose any risks to you or them?		

*Participant to initial each Yes/No box (as appropriate) where interviewed in person

*Where the interview takes place remotely, researcher to initial each Yes/No box (as appropriate) to confirm verbal response from participant

16.18 Appendix 15 – Insurance

Your Zurich Municipal Insurance

Our Reference BS/IND
Policy Number NHE-06CA03-0013
Customer Name University of the West of Scotland

To Whom It May Concern

This is to confirm that University of the West of Scotland have in force with this Company until the policy expiry on 31 July 2023 Insurance incorporating the following essential features:

Limit of Indemnity		
Public Liability	£50,000,000	any one event
Pollution/Products Liability	£50,000,000	for all claims in the aggregate during any one period of insurance any one event inclusive of costs
Employers' Liability	£50,000,000	any one event inclusive of costs
Excess		
Public Liability/Products Liability/ Pollution	£1,000	any one event
Employers' Liability	Nil	any one event
Indemnity to Principals	Covers include a standard Indemnity to Principals Clause in respect of contractual obligations.	
Full Policy	The policy documents should be referred to for details of full cover.	

Yours sincerely

Zurich Municipal

Contact Details

 Call us on
0800 232 1927

We may record or monitor calls to improve our service.

 Email us at
stephen.mcgeown@uk.zurich.com

 Visit us at
www.zurich.co.uk/municipal

 Write to us at
Zurich Insurance plc
Zurich House
1 Gladiator Way
Farnborough
GU14 6GB

16.19 Appendix 16 – Organisation Information Document

Organisation Information Document – Non-Commercially Sponsored Studies

(Template version: 1.6)

Study Information

1. * IRAS Project ID	292380
2. * Full Title of the Study	Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse. Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during historic periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these might have prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.
3. * Legal Name(s) of Sponsor/Co-Sponsors/Joint-Sponsors	W. Mackay, University of the West of Scotland
4. Contact details of person acting on behalf of Sponsor for questions relating to study set up. Please enter details of the person who is the Sponsor's main point of contact for all correspondence on setting up the study at this NHS / HSC organisation. This contact may be the Sponsor, a Study Manager, Clinical Research Scientist or Study Coordinator. Where a Contract Research Organisation (CRO) or Clinical Trials Unit (CTU) has been delegated to handle set up on behalf of the Sponsor, the contact at the CRO or CTU should be named here.	
Name	KERRY ELLIS
Telephone Number	[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]
5. * Are all participating NHS / HSC organisations undertaking the same protocol activities?	
Yes	
If 'No' give details of the activities taking place at NHS / HSC organisations that you will use this outline Organisation Information Document with. Additional outline Organisation Information Documents may be required for NHS / HSC organisations undertaking different activities.	
If no, give details	
Participating NHS / HSC Organisation Information	
6. Name of Participating NHS / HSC Organisation. If this Organisation Information Document is being used as an Agreement the name must be entered prior to agreement.	
NHS A&A	
7. Location/s: Please provide detail below where it is planned to undertake the research only at specified locations with the participating NHS / HSC organisation (i.e. hospital(s), GP Practice(s) and/or Research Unit(s)). It is not intended that the level of detail provided here captures individual departments within the participating NHS / HSC organisation.	
Location (enter text below)	Activity (enter text below)
All contact with study participants will take place by virtual means wherever possible.	1 x Interview with each participant lasting for approx 60-90 mins. Approx 7-10 participants expected to be included in the study overall

Location (enter text below)	Activity (enter text below)

8* . What is the role of the person responsible for research activities at the participating NHS / HSC organisation?

Principal Investigators are expected to be in place at participating NHS / HSC organisations where locally employed staff take responsibility for research procedures. In this scenario Principal Investigator should be selected even for single centre studies where the Chief Investigator will also be the Principal Investigator. Where this is not the case, local collaborators are expected to be in place where central study staff will be present at the participating organisation to undertake research procedures (the role of the Local Collaborator is to facilitate the presence of Sponsor / CRO research staff).

Where existing data is being provided for research purposes without additional research procedures and without the presence of central research team members at the participating NHS / HSC organisation, select Chief Investigator.

*Chief investigator/researcher will be responsible for all research activities, and will not require local staff to be directly involved with the research activities, other than supporting the researcher to identify potential participants.

Chief Investigator

9. Contact details of person responsible for research activities at this participating NHS / HSC organisation as indicated in question 8 (if known). If known, please enter the details of the person you have spoken to about their role in this study at this participating NHS / HSC organisation. If unknown, please leave blank and that person can be identified and listed here during the setup of the study.

Name	KERRY ELLIS
Post / Job Title	RESEARCHER/CHIEF INVESTIGATOR
Name of Employing Organisation	NHS DUMFRIES & GALLOWAY
Email Address	
Telephone number	

Timescales

10. Predicted Start and End Dates of the Study at this Participating NHS / HSC Organisation
The Sponsor or authorised delegate should propose a date on which it intends to start and complete research activity at this participating NHS / HSC organisation. Alternatively, this may be left blank when the Local Information Pack is shared, for agreement during study set up at the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation.

Predicted Start Date (activities at this organisation)	01/07/2022
Predicted End Date (activities at this organisation)	30/09/2022

For many types of study the following dates are not applicable and this may be stated in answer. Where they are applicable, they should be provided by the Sponsor or authorised delegate before sharing the Local Information Pack, as indicative targets for agreement, or they may be negotiated between Sponsor or authorised delegate and participating NHS / HSC organisation after sharing the pack.

Predicted Site Initiation Visit Date	Select predicted site initiation visit date
Predicted Start Date for participant recruitment	01/07/2022
Predicted End Date for participants recruitment (i.e. when the study moves into "follow up" activities.)	30/09/2022
Predicted End Date for all study activities (i.e. "last patient visit" completed and study is ready to be archived.)	31/12/2023

Participant Numbers

11. How many research participants are expected at this participating NHS / HSC organisation?

For studies not directly involving human participants, please indicate the number of samples or data-sets to be obtained.

Please state if number of participants is per month, per year, overall, etc.

[Approx 1-2 from NHS A&A, but 7-10 for the entire study/overall](#)

Study set up and delivery arrangements at Participating NHS / HSC Organisations

12 * . The following are needed at the participating NHS / HSC organisation to deliver the study: *for example specific equipment, patient/participant groups, service support, nursing time, etc. Please detail any specific requirements for participating NHS / HSC organisations to deliver this study, including by clarifying any requirements on participating NHS / HSC organisations relating to monitoring / self-monitoring, for example requirements for staff signature and delegation logs to be returned to the Sponsor and/or any particular access requirements that the Sponsor may have that it wishes to bring to the attention of the participating NHS / HSC organisation, likelihood of staff not employed at the participating NHS / HSC organisation coming on site, etc.*

[Health Visitors will be asked to identify potential participants to the study from their caseloads, and provide them with details of the study, including the researcher's contact details. Participating NHS Boards/HV teams will be asked to meet via MS Teams \(or in person if required\) with the Chief Investigator/Researcher to share information about the study. Health Board staff will not be required to obtain consent from potential participants.](#)

13 * . The following training will be provided by the Sponsor or authorised delegate for local research team members. Where only specific team members (for example the Principal Investigator) will receive this training, this should be specified.

[N/A Only the Chief Investigator/researcher will be undertaking the research.](#)

14 * . The Sponsor expects that local research team members will have the following skills and where they do not have those skills that they will undertake the relevant training before undertaking the relevant study activities. It would not be usual for the Sponsor to expect study specific training additional to that which it will provide. This section does however allow Sponsors to state, for example, that when they expect [training in Good Clinical Practice](#) for appropriate team members where the study is a Clinical Trial of an Investigational Medicinal Product, they will accept UK nationally recognised GCP training, training recognised on the [Transcelerate mutual recognition scheme](#), etc.

[Full details of the study will be provided to both NHS Board Health Visitor teams, and also to Women's Aid organisation staff in the same Board areas who will also be asked to identify potential participants from their caseloads.](#)

15 * . The following funding/resources/equipment, etc. is to be provided to this participating NHS / HSC organisation. The Sponsor should answer this question whether this Organisation Information Document is to be used as the Agreement with the participating NHS / HSC organisation or not. Where the document is intended as the Agreement, further detail should be provided in Appendix 2.

[None required.](#)

[Only where potential participants want to be involved in the study but are not able to connect via virtual means, would access to NHS premises be required to undertake face to face interviews. Due to small sample size expected, it is not anticipated that this will be required in many areas.](#)

16^ The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation confirms (by use of the drop-down box) that the Principal Investigator, where one is required, is aware of and has agreed to discharge their responsibilities in line with the [UK Policy Framework for Research and Social Care](#)..

[Not applicable](#)

17[^] The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation has considered and mitigated any conflict/s of interest declared by the principal investigator.	Not applicable
If yes, please detail conflict of interest	

Sponsor Authorisation

18 * Authorised on behalf of Sponsor by:	
Name	W. Mackay
Job Title	Reader – School of Health & Life Sciences
Organisation Name	University of the West of Scotland
Date	18 March 2022

Appendices

(Contents)

Appendix 1: General Provisions

Appendix 2: Finance Provisions

Appendix 3: Material Transfer Provisions

Appendix 4: Data Processing Agreement

Appendix 5: Data Sharing Agreement

Appendix 6: Intellectual Property Rights

The sponsor or authorised delegate should answer the question at the top of Appendix 1 and, if it intends that this Organisation Information Document will be incorporated into an exchange of correspondence to form the Agreement (“Agreement”) between itself and the participating NHS / HSC organisation, the questions that appear at the top of each subsequent appendix.

Appendix 1: General Provisions

<p>* Does the Sponsor intend that this Organisation Information Document forms the Agreement between itself and the participating NHS / HSC Organisation, or has a separate site agreement been provided?</p>	<p>Organisation Information Document</p>
<p>It is recommended that the Organisation Information Document is used as the Agreement between Sponsor and participating NHS / HSC organisation for studies that are not clinical trials or investigations. The model Non-Commercial Agreement (mNCA) should be used for clinical trials or investigations.</p> <p>Where the Organisation Information Document is to be used as the Agreement between the Sponsor and participating NHS organisation (hereafter singly “Party” or collectively the “Parties”), this document forms a formal legal contract between the Parties. In all cases where this document is the Agreement between the Parties, this Appendix 1 applies in full.</p> <p>Additionally, the Sponsor or authorised delegate should use the questions at the top of each subsequent appendix to indicate whether or not that appendix also forms part of the Agreement.</p> <p>Text highlighted in yellow is optional, including where alternative versions of the same clause may be used. The applicable option/s should be selected and text not to be used should be deleted prior to IRAS submission. No changes should be made to any text that does not appear in yellow highlight.</p>	

OBLIGATIONS OF THE PARTIES

The Parties agree to comply with all relevant laws, regulations and codes of practice applicable to this Agreement including to the performance of the study. The Parties agree to comply with the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki, titled “Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects” (where applicable) and the UK Policy Framework for Health and Social Care Research. The Parties shall conduct the study in accordance with:

- the Protocol, including appropriately made amendments thereto (which is/are hereby incorporated into this Agreement by reference);
- the terms of all relevant permissions and approvals. These may include, but are not limited to the terms and conditions of the favourable opinion given by the relevant NHS Research Ethics Committee, where applicable.

The Parties shall carry out their respective responsibilities in accordance with this Agreement. The Parties agree to comply with all applicable statutory requirements and mandatory codes of practice in respect of confidentiality (including medical confidentiality) in relation to participants and study personnel.

The Sponsor shall, on the giving of reasonable prior written notice to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation, have the right to audit the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation’s compliance with this Agreement. The Sponsor may appoint an auditor to carry out such an audit. Such right to audit shall include access, during normal working hours to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation's premises and to all relevant documents and other information relating to the study.

The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall;

- promptly notify the Sponsor should any responsible body conduct or give notice of intent to conduct any inspection at the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation in relation to the study;
- allow the Sponsor to support the preparations for such inspection; and
- following the inspection, provide the Sponsor with the results of the inspection relevant to the study. The Sponsor will be responsible for sharing such results with the funder if required.

In accordance with participant consent, the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall permit the Sponsor's appointed representatives and any appropriately appointed monitor access to all relevant data for monitoring and source data verification. The Parties agree that such access will be arranged at mutually convenient times and on reasonable notice. Such monitoring may take such form as the Sponsor reasonably thinks appropriate including the right to inspect any facility being used for the conduct of the study, reasonable access to relevant members of staff at the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation and the right to examine any procedures or records relating to the study, subject at all times to clause 6 of this appendix. The Sponsor will alert the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation promptly to significant issues (in the opinion of the Sponsor) relating to the conduct of the study.

LIABILITIES AND INDEMNITY

Nothing in this clause 2 shall operate so as to restrict or exclude the liability of a Party in relation to statutory or regulatory liability (including but not limited to breach of the data protection legislation), death or personal injury caused by the negligence or wilful misconduct of that Party or its agent(s), fraud or fraudulent misrepresentation or to restrict or exclude any other liability of a Party which cannot be so restricted or excluded in law.

Where a Party is a non-NHS/HSC organisation, or an NHS/HSC organisation that is not a member of an NHS indemnity scheme, then that Party shall maintain all proper insurance or equivalent indemnity arrangements to cover liabilities arising from its participation in the study, in respect of any claims brought by or on behalf of a participant. Where the Party is an NHS/HSC organisation and is a member of an NHS indemnity scheme, it shall maintain its membership therein or otherwise ensure it has appropriate cover against claims arising as a result of clinical negligence by the Party and/or its agents brought by or on behalf of the participants. Each Party shall provide to the other such evidence of their insurance or equivalent indemnity cover maintained pursuant to clause 2.2 as the other Party shall from time to time reasonably request, such evidence might comprise confirmation that an NHS/HSC organisation is a member of one of the NHS indemnity schemes.

2.3. **[SINGLE SPONSOR]** Subject to clauses 2.4, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7 and 2.8, the Sponsor shall indemnify the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation and its agents, against any reasonable claims, proceedings and related costs, expenses, losses, damages and demands ("Claims") to the extent they arise or result from the negligent acts or omissions of, or the wilful misconduct of the Sponsor, and/or contracted third party, in its performance of this Agreement or in connection with the study.

Subject to clauses 2.3, 2.5, 2.6 and 2.8, the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall indemnify the Sponsor and its agents, against any reasonable claims, proceedings and related costs, expenses, losses, damages and demands to the extent they arise or result from the negligent acts or omissions of, or the wilful misconduct of the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation, or its agents, in its performance of this Agreement or in connection with the study.

An indemnity under clauses 2.3 or 2.4 shall only apply if the indemnified Party:

informs the Party providing the indemnity in writing as soon as reasonably practicable following receipt of notice of the claim or proceedings;

upon the indemnifying Party's request and at the indemnifying Party's cost gives the indemnifying Party full control of the claim or proceedings and provides all reasonable assistance; and makes no admission in respect of such claim or proceedings other than with the prior written consent of the indemnifying Party.

Any indemnity under clauses 2.3 or 2.4 shall not apply to the extent any claims, proceedings and related costs, expenses, losses, damages or demands arise or result from the negligent acts or omissions or wilful misconduct or breach of statutory duty of the indemnified Party.

The indemnity under clause 2.3 shall not apply to the extent any claims, proceedings and related costs, expenses, losses, damages or demands arise or result from:

Participating NHS / HSC Organisation carrying out a treatment or procedure that would be routinely undertaken at or for that Participating NHS / HSC Organisation as part of National Health Service treatment; or

Participating NHS / HSC Organisation preparing, manufacturing or assembling any equipment which is not done in accordance with the protocol; or
with written instructions of the manufacturer; or
(where such instructions differ from the instructions of the manufacturer) other written instructions of the Sponsor.

No Party shall be liable to another in contract, tort/delict, breach of statutory duty or otherwise for any loss of profits, revenue, reputation, business opportunity, contracts, or any indirect, consequential or economic loss arising directly or indirectly out of or in connection with this Agreement.

If a Party incurs any loss or damage (including costs and expenses) ("Loss") arising or resulting from this Agreement and:

All Parties are NHS bodies as defined in Section 9(4) of the National Health Service Act 2006 or Section 17 of the National Health Service (Scotland) Act 1978 or Section 7 (4) of the NHS (Wales) Act 2006 or Articles 16 and 26 of the Health and Personal Social Services (Northern Ireland) Order 1972, which established the Boards and Central Services Agency respectively and Article 10 of the Health and Personal Social Services (Northern Ireland) Order 1991: which established Trusts in Northern Ireland as appropriate; or

One or more Party is a NHS body and the other Party (ies) is a NHS Foundation Trust; or

All Parties are NHS Foundation Trusts;

Then clauses 2.10, 2.11 and 2.12 shall apply.

If all Parties are NHS bodies / NHS Foundation Trusts in England, Wales or Northern Ireland and are indemnified by the same indemnity scheme (being one of the NHS Resolution's clinical negligence schemes or the Welsh Risk Pool or the Clinical Negligence Fund in Northern Ireland) and the Party incurring any loss can recover such loss under one of the indemnity schemes, then such Party shall rely on the cover provided by the indemnity scheme and not seek to recover the Loss from the other Party (ies). Where the other Party (ies) caused or contributed to the Loss, it undertakes to notify the relevant indemnity scheme(s) to take this into account in determining the future levies of all Parties in respect of the indemnity schemes.

If:

The Parties are members of the same indemnity scheme in England, Wales or Northern Ireland and the Party incurring the Loss is not indemnified for that Loss by its indemnity schemes; or

All Parties are NHS bodies in Scotland; or

The Parties are NHS bodies/Foundation Trusts established in different jurisdictions within the United Kingdom;

Then the Parties shall apportion such Loss between themselves according to their respective responsibility for such Loss.

If one or more Parties are NHS Foundation Trusts and the Party incurring the Loss is not responsible for all or part of the Loss and is not indemnified in respect of the Loss by one of the indemnity schemes then the Party incurring the Loss shall be entitled to recover the Loss from the other Party (ies) pursuant to the provisions of this Agreement.

2.13. **[SINGLE SPONSOR]** Subject to clause 2.1 and 2.7 the liability of the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation to the Sponsor and the liability of the Sponsor to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation arising out of or in connection with any breach of this Agreement or any act or omission of either Party in connection with the performance of the study should be the greater of the amount of fees payable by the Sponsor to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation under this Agreement or one hundred thousand (£100,000 GBP) pounds. For the avoidance of doubt, this cap applies also but not exclusively to the indemnities offered under clauses 2.3 and 2.4.

Notwithstanding clause 2.13, in the case of equipment loaned by or on behalf of the Sponsor to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation for the purposes of the study, the Participating NHS / HSC

Organisation's liability for damage to or loss of that equipment arising from its negligence shall exclude fair wear and tear and shall not exceed the replacement value of the equipment.

PUBLICITY

[Neither Party] shall use the name, logo or registered image of the other [Party] or the employees of such other Party in any publicity, advertising or press release without the prior written approval of an authorised representative of that Party.

The content and timing of any publicity, advertising or press release shall be agreed by [both] Parties, such agreement not to be unreasonably withheld.

PUBLICATION

In accordance with all relevant laws, regulations and codes of practice, it is agreed that the Sponsor has an obligation to and shall publish the results of the full study and that the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall not publish any study data, including through presentation or submission of an abstract, without the prior permission in writing from the Sponsor (which shall not be unreasonably withheld or delayed).

FREEDOM OF INFORMATION

Parties to this Agreement which are subject to the Environmental Information Regulations 2004 (EIR) and the Freedom of Information Act 2000 (FOIA) or the Freedom of Information (Scotland) Act 2002 (FOI(S)A) and which receive a request under EIR, FOIA or FOI(S)A to disclose any information that belongs to another Party shall notify and consult that Party, as soon as reasonably practicable, and in any event, not later than seven (7) working days after receiving the request.

The Parties acknowledge and agree that the decision on whether any exemption applies to a request for disclosure of recorded information under EIR, FOIA or FOI(S)A is a decision solely for the Party responding to the request.

Where the Party responding to an EIR, FOIA or FOI(S)A request determines that it will disclose information it will notify the other Party in writing, giving at least four (4) working days' notice of its intended disclosure.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Subject to clause 5 above, the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation agrees to treat the results, excluding any clinical data of the study, as confidential information of the Sponsor and the Sponsor agrees to treat personal data and confidential patient information as confidential information.

The receiving Party agrees:

To take all reasonable steps to protect the confidentiality of the confidential information and to prevent it from being disclosed otherwise than in accordance with this Agreement

To ensure that any of its employees, students, researchers, consultants or sub-contractors who participate in the operation of the Study are made aware of, and abide by, the requirement of this clause 6.2.

To use confidential information solely in connection with the operation of the Agreement and not otherwise, except in the case where the confidential information is personal data and/or confidential patient information, where it may be used solely on the basis of maintaining the common law duty of confidentiality and in accordance with the requirements of the data protection legislation, including but not limited to an appropriate legal basis/special category condition, appropriate transparency information and that the purpose is not incompatible with the original purpose.

Not to disclose confidential information in whole or in part to any person without the disclosing Party's prior written consent or, where the confidential information is personal data and/or confidential patient information, without maintaining the common law duty of confidentiality and in accordance with the requirements of the data protection legislation, including but not limited to an appropriate legal basis/special category condition, appropriate transparency information and that the purpose is not incompatible with the original purpose.

The provision of clause 6.2 shall not apply to the whole or any part of the confidential information that is:

lawfully obtained by the receiving Party free of any duty of confidentiality;
already in the possession of the receiving Party and which the receiving Party can show from written records was already in its possession (other than as a result of a breach of clause 6.2.1 or 6.2.2);

in the public domain (other than as a result of a breach of clause 6.2.1 or 6.2.2);

independently discovered by employees of the receiving Party without access to or use of confidential information;

necessarily disclosed by the receiving Party pursuant to a statutory obligation;

disclosed with prior written consent of the disclosing Party;

necessarily disclosed by the receiving Party by virtue of its status as a public authority in terms of the FOIA or the FOI(S)A;

published in accordance with the provisions of clause 4.

The restrictions contained in clause 6.2 shall remain in force without limit in time in respect of personal data and any other information which relates to a patient, his or her treatment and/or medical records. Save as aforesaid and unless otherwise expressly set out in this Agreement, these clauses shall remain in force for a period of 10 years after the termination or expiry of this Agreement.

Appendix 2: Finance Provisions

Where this Organisation Information Document is to be used as the Agreement between Sponsor and Participating NHS / HSC organisation, please select an option below.	
* Are there funds / resources / equipment, etc. being provided to this participating NHS / HSC organisation by the Sponsor? If no, this appendix should be left blank. If yes, this finance appendix forms part of the Agreement between the participating NHS / HSC organisation and the Sponsor.	No

A. Financial Arrangements

The overall, study-wide recruitment for this study is competitive with a maximum Figure of **1** Participants. Once this target has been reached, the Sponsor will notify the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation. No additional per participant payments will be made by the Sponsor to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation for participants consented after such notification becomes effective.

	* Area of Cost	* Payment (£ Sterling)
1 *	Click here to enter text	Click here to enter text
2 *	Click here to enter text	Click here to enter text
3 *	Click here to enter text	Click here to enter text
4 *	Click here to enter text	Click here to enter text
5 *	Click here to enter text	Click here to enter text

If VAT is payable, then the Sponsor shall pay the VAT in addition to the payment of the agreed costs on presentation of a VAT invoice in which the VAT is stated as a separate item. Such invoices should quote the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation's VAT registration number. If VAT is not payable, then the Sponsor shall issue a VAT exemption certificate.

Schedule of payments and details of payment arrangements

* Invoices to be submitted [Insert FREQUENCY OR INTERVAL for example quarterly] to:

[Insert JOB TITLE, NAME OF BODY & ADDRESS]

^ Payment to be made by cheque payable to:

[Insert NAME OF PARTICIPATING NHS / HSC ORGANISATION]

^ and remitted to:

[Insert JOB TITLE/POSITION]

[Insert ADDRESS]

^Or arrange BACS Transfer to: [Insert BANK NAME].

^Sort code: [Insert SORT CODE]

^Account: [Insert ACCOUNT NUMBER]

^And send the relevant paper work to [Insert ADDRESSEE FOR PAPERWORK] at the above address

Invoices must be paid promptly [within xx days of receipt]. No payment shall be made in the case where invoices are not presented in a complete, accurate and timely fashion and funding has been irrecoverably reclaimed by the funder as a result of such delay or inadequacy.

B. Supplies Arrangements

Any equipment, materials, consumables, software or other items being provided by the Sponsor or procured by the participating organisation for use in the study shall be specified below.

Note 1: Parties should complete the Table below. If the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation is to procure any items and is to be reimbursed by the Sponsor this should be specified in this appendix. Similarly if the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation is to pay the Sponsor for any items provided to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation by or on behalf of the Sponsor this should be specified in this appendix.

Note 2: Parties should specify in this appendix, as appropriate, arrangements for:

- Ownership of items
- Insurance
- Storage instructions
- Instructions for use, return and/or destruction
- Any training to be provided
- Maintenance of equipment

Item	Quantity	Frequency of supply	Responsibility to supply/procure (either Sponsor or Participating NHS / HSC Organisation only)
Click here to enter text			
Click here to enter text			
Click here to enter text			
Click here to enter text			
Click here to enter text			

Appendix 3: Material Transfer Provisions

Where this Organisation Information Document is to be used as the Agreement between Sponsor and Participating NHS / HSC organisation, please select an option below.	
* Does this study involve the transfer of human biological material from this participating NHS / HSC organisation to the Sponsor or its agents? If no, this appendix does not form part of this Agreement. If yes, these provisions form part of the Agreement between the Sponsor and this participating NHS / HSC organisation.	No

Material, as used in this appendix, means any clinical biological sample or portion thereof, derived from participants, including any information related to such Material, supplied by the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation to the Sponsor/Joint Sponsors/either of the Co-Sponsors or [its] / [their] nominee.

1. In accordance with the protocol, the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall send Material to the Sponsor/joint Sponsors/a co-Sponsor or, in accordance with provision 7 below, to a third party nominated by the Sponsor/joint Sponsor s/either of the co-Sponsors.
2. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation warrants that all Material has been collected with appropriate informed consent and has been collected and handled in accordance with applicable law (including, without limitation, the Human Tissue Act 2004 or the Human Tissue (Scotland) Act 2006 (as the case may be)) and as required by the protocol.
3. Subject to provision 2 above, the Materials are supplied without any warranty, expressed or implied, including as to their properties, merchantable quality, fitness for any particular purpose, or that the Materials are free of extraneous or biologically active contaminants which may be present in the Materials.
4. The Sponsor/joint Sponsors/one of the co-Sponsors shall ensure, or procure through an agreement with the Sponsor's/joint Sponsors'/co-Sponsor's nominee as stated in provision 1 above that:
 - 4.1. the Material is used in accordance with the protocol, the consent of the participant, and the ethics approval for the study;
 - 4.2. the Material is handled and stored in accordance with applicable law;
 - 4.3. the Material shall not be redistributed or released to any person other than in accordance with the protocol or for the purpose of undertaking other studies approved by an appropriate ethics committee and in accordance with the participant's consent.
5. The Parties shall comply with all relevant laws, regulations and codes of practice governing the research use of human biological material.
6. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation and the Sponsor/joint Sponsors/a co-Sponsor shall each be responsible for keeping a record of the Material that has been transferred according to this appendix.
7. To the extent permitted by law the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation and its staff shall not be liable for any consequences of the supply to or the use by the Sponsor/joint Sponsors/co-Sponsor of the Material or of the supply to or the use by any third party to whom the Sponsor/joint Sponsors/co-Sponsor subsequently provides the Material or the Sponsor's/joint Sponsors'/co-Sponsor's nominee as stated in provision 1 above, save to the extent that any liability which arises is a result of the negligence of the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation.

8. The Sponsor/joint Sponsors/co-Sponsor undertake(s) that, in the event that Material is provided to a third party in accordance with provision 2 above, [it] / [they] shall require that such third party shall undertake to handle any Material related to the study in accordance with all applicable statutory requirements and codes of practice and under terms no less onerous than those set out in this appendix.
9. Any surplus Material that is not returned to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation or retained for future research (in line with participant consent) shall be destroyed in accordance with applicable law (including, without limitation, the Human Tissue Act 2004 or the Human Tissue (Scotland) Act 2006 (as the case may be)).

**These provisions do not remove the need for the Sponsor to clearly lay out in their protocol (and to potential participants in the participant information) at a minimum the following information for all Material taken: 1) The nature of the Materials, 2) The reason that the Material is being taken, 3) where the Material is to be sent and, 4) what will happen to any remaining Material once it has been processed/analysed, etc. for the purposes of this study (for example return, retention or destruction). Detailed guidance on what information should be included in a protocol may be found on the HRA website: www.hra.nhs.uk*

Appendix 4: Data Processing Agreement

Where this Organisation Information Document is to be used as the Agreement between Sponsor and Participating NHS / HSC organisation, please select an option below.	
<p>* Does this study involve any processing of personal data by this participating NHS / HSC organisation on behalf of the Sponsor. If no, this appendix does not form part of this Agreement. If yes, these provisions form part of the Agreement between the Sponsor and this participating NHS / HSC organisation.</p> <p>For the avoidance of doubt, when used, these provisions are intended to form a legally binding contractual obligation for the purposes of compliance with the GDPR, specifically GDPR Article 28 (3).</p>	Yes

1. For the purposes of the data protection legislation, the Sponsor is the controller and the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation is the Sponsor's processor in relation to all processing of personal data that is processed for the purpose of this study and for any future research use under the controllership of the Sponsor, that would not have taken place but for this Agreement regardless where that processing takes place.
2. The Parties acknowledge that whereas the Sponsor is the controller in accordance with Clause 1 of this appendix, the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation is the controller of the personal data collected for the purpose of providing clinical care to the participants. This personal data may be the same personal data, collected transparently and processed for research and for care purposes under the separate controllerships of the Sponsor and Participating NHS / HSC Organisation.
3. Where the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation is the Sponsor's processor and thus where the processing is undertaken by the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation for the purposes of the study, Clauses 5.a. to 5.j below will apply. For the avoidance of doubt, such Clauses do not apply where the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation is processing the participant personal data as a controller.
4. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation agrees only to process personal data for and on behalf of the Sponsor in accordance with the instructions of the Sponsor and for the purpose of the study and to ensure the Sponsor's compliance with the data protection legislation;
5. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation agrees to comply with the obligations applicable to processors described by Article 28 GDPR including, but not limited to, the following:
 - a. to implement and maintain appropriate technical and organisational security measures sufficient to comply at least with the obligations imposed on the controller by Article 28(1);
 - b. to not engage another processor without the prior written authorisation of the Sponsor (Article 28(2) to process the personal data only on documented instructions from the Sponsor unless required to do otherwise by legislation, in which case the Participating NHS / HSC

Organisation shall notify the Sponsor before processing, or as soon as possible after processing if legislation requires that the processing occurs immediately, unless legislation prohibits such notification on important grounds of public interest (Article 28(3a)).;

- c. to ensure that personnel authorised to process personal data are under confidentiality obligations (Article 28(3b));
- d. to take all measures required by Article 32 GDPR in relation to the security of processing (Article 28(3c));
- e. to respect the conditions described in Article 28(2) and (4) for engaging another processor (Article 28(3d));
- f. to, taking into account the nature of the processing, assist the Sponsor, by appropriate technical and organisational measures, insofar as this is possible, to respond to requests for exercising data subjects' rights (Article 28(3e));
- g. to assist the controller, to ensure compliance with the obligations pursuant to Articles 32 to 36 GDPR taking into account the nature of the processing and the information available to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation (Article 28(3f));
- h. to, at the choice of the Sponsor, destroy or return all personal data to the Sponsor at the expiry or early termination of the Agreement, unless storage is legally required (Article 28(3g)) or where that personal data is held by the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation as controller for the purpose of clinical care or other legal purposes; and
- i. to maintain a record of processing activities as required by Article 30(2) GDPR.

6. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall ensure that:

- a. its agents do not process personal data except in accordance with this Agreement (and in particular the protocol);
- b. it takes all reasonable steps to ensure the reliability and integrity of any of its agents who have access to the personal data and ensure they:
 - i. are aware and comply with the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation 's duties under this clause;
 - ii. are subject to mandatory training in their information governance responsibilities and have appropriate contracts including sanctions, including for breach of confidence or misuse of data; and
 - iii. are informed of the confidential nature of the personal data and understand the responsibilities for information governance, including their obligation to process personal data securely and to only disseminate or disclose for lawful and appropriate purposes.

7. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation agrees to:

- a. allow the Sponsor(s) or another auditor appointed by the Sponsor(s) to audit the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation's compliance with the

obligations described by this Appendix, data protection legislation in general and Article 28 GDPR in particular, on reasonable notice subject to the Sponsor complying with all relevant health and safety and security policies of the participating site and/or to provide the Sponsor with evidence of its compliance with the obligations set out in this Agreement; and

- b. obtain prior agreement of the Sponsor to store or process personal data outside the European Economic Area.
8. Where the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation stores or otherwise processes personal data outside of the European Economic Area as the Sponsor's processor, it warrants that it does so in compliance with the Data Protection Legislation.

Appendix 5: Data Sharing Agreement

Where this Organisation Information Document is to be used as the Agreement between Sponsor and Participating NHS/HSC organisation, please select an option below.	
* Does this study involve the transfer of personal data from this participating NHS / HSC organisation to the Sponsor or its agents, or transfer of confidential information between the Parties? If no, this appendix does not form part of this Agreement. If yes, these provisions form part of the Agreement between the Sponsor and this participating NHS / HSC organisation.	Yes

1. Personal data shall not be disclosed to the Sponsor by the participating NHS / HSC organisation, save where this is required directly or indirectly to satisfy the requirements of the protocol, or for the purpose of monitoring or reporting adverse events, or in relation to a claim or proceeding brought by a participant in connection with the study.
2. The Sponsor agrees to use personal data solely in connection with the operation of the Agreement, or otherwise for purposes not incompatible with this original purpose (Article 5, 1 (b) GDPR), and not otherwise. In particular,
 - 2.1. Not to disclose personal data to any person except in accordance with applicable legal requirements and codes of practice.
3. The Sponsor agrees to comply with the obligations placed on a controller by the data protection legislation. This is not limited to, but includes, being responsible for and able to demonstrate compliance with the principles relating to processing of personal data (Article 5 GDPR)
4. The Sponsor agrees to ensure persons processing personal data under this Agreement are equipped to do so respectfully and safely. In particular:
 - 4.1. To ensure any persons (excluding employees, honorary employees, students, researchers, consultants and subcontractors of the participating NHS / HSC organisation) processing personal data understand the responsibilities for information governance, including their obligation to process personal data securely and to only disseminate or disclose for lawful and appropriate purposes.
 - 4.2. To ensure any persons (excluding employees, honorary employees, students, researchers, consultants and subcontractors of the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation) have appropriate contracts providing for personal accountability and sanctions for breach of confidence or misuse of data including deliberate or avoidable data breaches.
5. The Sponsor agrees to proactively prevent data security breaches and to respond appropriately to incidents or near misses. In particular,
 - 5.1. To ensure that personal data are only accessible to persons who need it for the purposes of the study and to remove access as soon as reasonably possible once it is no longer needed.
 - 5.2. To ensure all access to personal data on IT systems processed for study purposes can be attributed to individuals.
 - 5.3. To identify, review and improve processes which have caused breaches or near misses, or which force persons processing personal data to use workarounds which compromise data security.
 - 5.4. To adopt measures to identify and resist cyber-attacks against services and to respond to relevant external security advice.
 - 5.5. To take action immediately following a data breach or near miss.
6. The Sponsor agrees to ensure personal data are processed using secure and up to date technology. In particular,
 - 6.1. To ensure no unsupported operating systems, software or internet browsers are used to support the processing of personal data for the purposes of the study.
 - 6.2. To put in place a strategy for protecting relevant IT systems from cyber threats which is based on a proven cyber security framework such as Cyber Essentials.

6.3. To ensure IT suppliers are held accountable via contracts for protecting personal data they Process and for meetings all relevant information governance requirements.

Appendix 6: Intellectual Property Rights

Where this Organisation Information Document is to be used as the Agreement between Participating NHS / HSC organisation, please select an option below.	
* Does this study require the protection of background intellectual property rights, or is there potential for the generation of new intellectual property? If no, this appendix does not form part of this Agreement. If yes, these provisions form part of the Agreement between the Sponsor and this participating NHS / HSC organisation.	No

1. All background intellectual property rights (including licences) and know how and their improvements used in connection with the Study shall remain the property of the Party introducing the same and the exercise of such rights for purposes of the Study shall not knowingly infringe any third party's rights.
2. All intellectual property rights and know how in the Protocol, and in the study data, excluding clinical procedures developed or used by the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation independently of the Study, shall belong to the Sponsor. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation hereby assigns all such intellectual property rights, and undertakes to disclose all such know how, to the Sponsor.
3. Subject to clauses 1 and 2, all intellectual property rights deriving or arising from the Material or any derivations of the Material provided to the Sponsor by the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall belong to the Sponsor.
4. At any time within the duration of the Study, the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall at the request and expense of the Sponsor execute all such documents and do all acts necessary to fully vest the intellectual property rights in the Sponsor. To give effect to this clause 4, the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation shall ensure that its agents involved in the Study assign such intellectual property rights falling within clauses 2 and 3 and disclose such know how to the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation.
5. Subject to this Clause 5 and Clause 6, nothing in this Appendix shall be construed so as to prevent or hinder the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation from using its own know how or clinical data gained during the performance of the Study, at its own risk, in the furtherance of its normal activities of providing clinical care to the extent that such use does not result in the disclosure or misuse of confidential information or the infringement of an intellectual property right of the Sponsor, or their funder. This clause 5 does not permit the disclosure of any of the study data, all of which remain confidential until publication of the results. Any study data not so published remains the confidential information of the Sponsor, or their funder.
6. The Participating NHS / HSC Organisation may, with the prior written permission of the Sponsor (such permission not to be unreasonably withheld), use study data gained during the performance of the Study, at its own risk, in the furtherance of its normal activities of commissioning clinical services, teaching and research to the extent that such use does not result in the disclosure or misuse of confidential information or the infringement of an intellectual property right of the Sponsor or their funder. This clause 6 does not permit the disclosure of any of the study data, all of which remain confidential until publication of the results of the Study.

Authorisation When Using This Organisation Information Document as An Agreement

(when used as an Agreement, the Participating NHS Organisation is a “Party” to the Agreement and the Sponsor is a “Party” to the Agreement – collectively the “Parties”).

Authorisation on behalf of Participating NHS / HSC Organisation

It is not intended that this confirmation requires wet-ink signatures, or a passing of hard copies between the Sponsor and participating NHS / HSC organisation. Instead, Sponsors are expected to accept confirmation by email from an individual empowered by the Participating NHS / HSC Organisation to agree to the commencement of research (including any budgetary responsibility, where the study involves the transfer of funds).

^ Authorised on behalf of Participating NHS / HSC Organisation by:

Name	Enter name
Job Title	Enter job title
Organisation Name	Enter organisation name
Date	Select date of authorisation

16.20 Appendix 17 – Research protocol

STUDY PROTOCOL

Kerry Ellis

This protocol has regard for the HRA guidance.

FULL/LONG TITLE OF THE STUDY

Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse.
Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during historic periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these might have prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.

SHORT STUDY TITLE

Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse.

PROTOCOL VERSION NUMBER AND DATE

1.0

RESEARCH REFERENCE NUMBERS

IRAS Number: 292380

SPONSORS Number:

--

FUNDERS Number:

--

SIGNATURE PAGE

The undersigned confirm that the following protocol has been agreed and accepted and that the Chief Investigator agrees to conduct the study in compliance with the approved protocol and will adhere to the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki, the Sponsor's SOPs, and other regulatory requirement.

I agree to ensure that the confidential information contained in this document will not be used for any other purpose other than the evaluation or conduct of the investigation without the prior written consent of the Sponsor

I also confirm that I will make the findings of the study publicly available through publication or other dissemination tools without any unnecessary delay and that an honest accurate and

transparent account of the study will be given; and that any discrepancies from the study as planned in this protocol will be explained.

For and on behalf of the Study Sponsor:

Signature:

Date:

..18.../...3.../..22....

.....
 Name (please print):
 KERRY ELLIS

.....
 Position:
 RESEARCHER

Chief Investigator:

Signature:

Date:

...18.../...3.../22.

.....
 Name: (please print):
 KERRY ELLIS

LIST of CONTENTS

GENERAL INFORMATION	Page No.
HRA PROTOCOL COMPLIANCE DECLARATION	i
TITLE PAGE	ii
RESEARCH REFERENCE NUMBERS	ii
SIGNATURE PAGE	iii
LIST OF CONTENTS	iv
KEY STUDY CONTACTS	v
STUDY SUMMARY	v
FUNDING	vi
ROLE OF SPONSOR AND FUNDER	vi
ROLES & RESPONSIBILITIES OF STUDY STEERING GROUPS AND INDIVIDUALS	vi
STUDY FLOW CHART	vii
SECTION	
1. BACKGROUND	1
2. RATIONALE	1
3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK	2
4. RESEARCH QUESTION/AIM(S)	2
5. STUDY DESIGN/METHODS	2
6. STUDY SETTING	3
7. SAMPLE AND RECRUITMENT	4
8. ETHICAL AND REGULATORY COMPLIANCE	7
9. DISSEMINATION POLICY	10

10. REFERENCES	10
11. APPENDICES	12

KEY STUDY CONTACTS

Chief Investigator	KERRY ELLIS, [REDACTED]
Study Co-ordinator	As above
Sponsor	W Mackay [REDACTED]
Joint-sponsor(s)/co-sponsor(s)	
Funder(s)	Researcher self-funding General Nursing Council McQueen Bursary NHS Dumfries and Galloway Learning Fund NHS Dumfries & Galloway R&D Dept.
Key Protocol Contributors	KERRY ELLIS [REDACTED] RUTH ASTBURY SUPERVISOR [REDACTED]
Committees	

STUDY SUMMARY

Study Title	Developing an insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse.
Internal ref. no. (or short title)	
Study Design	Qualitative research/Hermeneutic phenomenological design
Study Participants	Mothers who have had children under 5 years old within the last 5 years.
Planned Size of Sample (if applicable)	7-10
Follow up duration (if applicable)	
Planned Study Period	Data collection period – 12 months Total study period 2 years.
Research Question/Aim(s)	'To develop an insight into mother's experiences of domestic abuse 'and identify the relationships mothers have had with health professionals during historical periods of abuse, exploring how these have promoted or prevented disclosures of abuse. Objectives: 1. To collect and chronologically record, mothers' retrospective experiences of domestic abuse 2. To explore in depth the factors that influence mothers' decisions to disclose domestic abuse

	<p>3. To develop an understanding of the influencing factors that impact on mothers' experiences of domestic abuse</p> <p>4. To develop an understanding of the role health care practitioners play in supporting mothers who are experiencing domestic abuse</p> <p>5. To identify supportive mechanisms to mothers experiencing domestic abuse</p>
--	--

FUNDING AND SUPPORT IN KIND

FUNDER(S) (Names and contact details of ALL organisations providing funding and/or support in kind for this study)	FINANCIAL AND NON FINANCIAL SUPPORT GIVEN
General Nursing Council	Contribution to course fees
McQueen Bursary	Contribution to course fees
NHS Dumfries and Galloway Learning Fund NHS Dumfries & Galloway R&D Dept.	Contribution to course fees

ROLE OF STUDY SPONSOR AND FUNDER

Funding sources listed have contributed to PhD course fees.

They have had no direct contribution or influence to the study, its design or conduct, data analysis and interpretation, manuscript writing, or dissemination of results.

W. Mackay from the University of the West of Scotland is the sponsor for the study, and has provided guidance in the process for ethical review.

PROTOCOL CONTRIBUTORS

As this study is for an academic award, contribution and support has been received from the supervisory team, Dr Ruth Astbury, Professor Jean Rankin, and Dr Mary Lynch.

Sponsors or funders have not made any contribution to any aspect of the research design, conduct, data analysis and interpretation, manuscript writing, and dissemination of results. However, views of women who have experienced domestic abuse have confirmed the research design is appropriate and acceptable to them as potential participants in a study of this kind.

The sponsor/funders will not be involved /control in any aspect of the study.

16.21 Appendix 18 – MSc Certificate

Kerry Joanne Ellis
having complied with all the conditions required by
the University, has been awarded the degree of

Master of Science
in
Vulnerability

Principal and Vice Ch

Secretary to Court

Date

16th November 2016

**School of Health and Life
Sciences**

Research and scholarship ethics guidelines

Introduction

The school of Health and Life Sciences Ethics committee is constituted under the university senate committees (<https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/3547/university-senate-committees-2017-18.pdf>). The current membership of the school ethics committee is listed on the ethics committee moodle site (<https://my.uws.ac.uk/course/view.php?id=2653>)(self enrolment code; HLSethics).

Consideration of the potential ethical implications/issues associated with research or scholarship is an essential first step in planning our activities in this area. The university ethics committee has established “Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship” (<https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-uws/uws-commitments/university-ethics/>).

All staff and students must consider the potential ethical implications of their research and scholarship activities. The criteria below and flowchart at the end of these guidelines will help you to decide if formal ethical approval is required for your research/scholarship.

The university guidelines state that research and scholarship involving animals, human participants, personal data or risk to the investigator not adequately controlled by proper application of school/university health and safety policies/procedures requires independent ethical scrutiny. The school of Health and Life Sciences requires that risk to the investigator is considered and eliminated, or at least minimised, during the health and safety risk-assessments for the proposed work.

Animals

Research or scholarship involving captive or temporarily captive living vertebrates or cephalopods requires ethical scrutiny. For work on such animals regulated under the terms of the Animals (Scientific procedures) Act, 1986 (ASPA)(<https://www.gov.uk/research-and-testing-using-animals>), this ethical approval should be obtained from the university Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Body (AWERB). For work on such animals not regulated under the terms of ASPA ethical approval should be obtained from the school of Health and Life Sciences ethics committee (see below for details).

Research involving animals which does not fall into the above categories, e.g., observational studies of wild animals should be assessed and any animal welfare considerations involved in this should be considered and eliminated or minimised during the fieldwork risk-assessment for the work (<http://intranet.uws.ac.uk/policy/Documents/Fieldwork%20Procedure.doc>).

Human participants

All research and scholarship involving human participants (other than the investigator(s)) or personal data¹ must have **prior** approval from the school ethics committee. The school ethics committee **will not** grant retrospective approval to any study.

Research or scholarship involving personal data may not always require ethical approval, e.g., where the data being used is already in the public domain. The school ethics committee is happy to provide

¹Applicants are reminded of the need to comply with the university’s GDPR regulations including the possible need for a privacy impact assessment (<https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-uws/compliance/information-records-management/data-protection/>).

advice on whether proposed research or scholarship requires a full application to the committee (healthandlifesciencesethics@uws.ac.uk).

Procedure for applying for ethical approval of research and scholarship

1. The investigator(s) should complete the online application form (<https://uws.forms.ethicalreviewmanager.com>). Training materials to help with completion of the form are available on the following moodle site (<https://moodle.uws.ac.uk/course/view.php?id=1610>) and in the application form itself. Where the investigator is a student, the application should be reviewed and approved by the student's supervisor/director of studies and signed by both parties to confirm that this process has taken place. Staff applicants should ask colleagues within their research institute to peer-review their application prior to submission.
2. The application and supporting documents (e.g., participant information sheet, copies of any questionnaires, letters of invitation, advertising etc., that the investigator is proposing to use) are submitted via the online system. Applicants should note that once an application is submitted it cannot be altered/amended or added to until after the review process, so please ensure that you have supplied the "final"/correct version of all documents before submitting. Where the investigator feels that the work or procedures to be used are complex or of a highly technical nature, they may suggest a reviewer to the committee (healthandlifesciencesethics@uws.ac.uk). This suggested reviewer must have no part in the proposed work nor can they have any formal relationship with any of the investigators (e.g., supervisor, line manager/line managed by the investigator(s)).
3. The ethics committee will send the application out for independent review. The number of reviewers (1 or 2) will depend on the likely risk associated with the proposal. "Higher-risk" or complex applications will be assessed by two independent school reviewers before being sent to the university ethics committee (UEC) for a further opinion. The UEC ethics guidelines (<https://www.uws.ac.uk/about-uws/uws-commitments/university-ethics/>) give information on what might constitute "higher risk" proposals. Applicants proposing to carry out such work can and should use their application to explain the measures they have put in place to mitigate the risk.
4. In the case of projects that involve the NHS (either, staff, patients, or facilities) then the ethics applicant must first visit the Healthcare Research Authority website "Is my project research?" (<http://www.hra-decisiontools.org.uk/research/>). The NHS has specific criteria for what they consider as being research. The online decision tool will result in either:
 - a. Your project being considered research as per the NHS definition – please submit an ethics application directly to the NHS via IRAS (<https://www.myresearchproject.org.uk/>). You DO NOT need to submit a separate ethics application to the school ethics committee.
 - b. Your project not being considered research as per the NHS definition – you MUST submit an application to the school ethics committee.

If you are a student applicant, then please work with your supervisory team to prepare the necessary documentation

Whether the route you take regarding ethics approval is a) or b) you may have additional documentation to complete. It is strongly recommended that you contact the NHS Research and Development Department(s) of the NHS boards where your research is to be undertaken to discuss any further regulatory/approval requirements.

5. The committee will endeavour to assess applications within 20 working days but complex applications may take longer (particularly where the opinion of the UAIEC or other external body is required). Applicants should factor these timelines into their research planning. Where the committee needs to send an application back to the author(s) for further work/information the 30 day timescale will apply from the date of resubmission by the applicant.

6. The reviewers will assess the application and will give a recommendation to the committee as follows;

Approved: the project can proceed

Approved with conditions: the project can proceed provided the compulsory changes are made or requirements met

Not approved: the project cannot proceed for the reasons clearly specified

No decision: the project requires further clarification or further review

7. The committee will communicate the outcome of the review to the applicant. Where "No decision" has been reached the applicant should address the comments/feedback provided and resubmit the proposal. Where the decision involves "conditions" the applicant or, in the case of a student, their supervisor/director of studies should inform the committee chair that the conditions have been met prior to the commencement of the work.

Once approval has been given for a study, applicants are reminded that it must be carried out in accordance with the application submitted and in compliance with any conditions of approval. Any modifications to the study must be notified to the school ethics committee immediately and before they are implemented. This can be done by submitting an amendment request to the approved study on the online system (<https://uws.forms.ethicalreviewmanager.com>).

8. The applicant may appeal the decision of the school ethics committee to the university academic integrity and ethics committee, if the applicant can demonstrate that the evidence was not fully and properly considered in relation to the 'risk' the project poses. If you wish to lodge an appeal you should complete an appeal form on the online system (<https://uws.forms.ethicalreviewmanager.com>).

Oversight of research

In addition to being charged with scrutinising and approving applications for research or scholarship the school ethics committee is also responsible for oversight of the research being carried out. To facilitate this role the school ethics committee requires applicants to report back to the committee at the conclusion of the research project or 1 year after approval (whichever is the sooner) on the outcome/progress of the work. In the case of UG and PG projects this is fulfilled by the submission of the student's dissertation/thesis. In the case of staff applications the committee requires a report describing the conduct of the research and reflecting on how it had been carried out and any issues which had arisen. A form for such reports is available on the ethics committee moodle site (<https://moodle.uws.ac.uk/course/view.php?id=1911>). If your project has been approved by an external ethics committee you may submit a copy of the reports to these committees to the SEC.

Is ethical approval required for my work? Where should I go to get it?

22/08/2022

16.23 Appendix 20 – Letter of favourable opinion

North of Scotland Research Ethics Committee
Summerfield House
2 Eday Road
Aberdeen
AB15 6RE

[REDACTED]

30 June 2022

Mrs Kerry Ellis
PhD Student
NHS Dumfries & Galloway

[REDACTED]

Dear Mrs Ellis

Study title:	Developing a meaningful insight into mothers' experiences of domestic abuse. Exploring the relationships between mothers and health professionals during historic periods of domestic abuse, to identify how these might have prevented or promoted disclosure of abuse.
REC reference:	22/NS/0078
Protocol number:	N/A
IRAS project ID:	292380

Thank you for your letter of 29 June 2022, responding to the Research Ethics Committee's (REC) request for further information on the above research and submitting revised documentation.

The further information has been considered on behalf of the Committee by the [Chair and a member of the Committee](#).

Confirmation of ethical opinion

On behalf of the Committee, I am pleased to confirm a favourable ethical opinion for the above research on the basis described in the application form, protocol and supporting documentation [as revised](#), subject to the conditions specified below.

Good practice principles and responsibilities

The [UK Policy Framework for Health and Social Care Research](#) sets out principles of good practice in the management and conduct of health and social care research. It also outlines the

responsibilities of individuals and organisations, including those related to the four elements of [research transparency](#):

1. [registering research studies](#)
2. [reporting results](#)
3. [informing participants](#)
4. [sharing study data and tissue](#)

Conditions of the favourable opinion

The REC favourable opinion is subject to the following conditions being met prior to the start of the study.

Confirmation of Capacity and Capability (in England, Northern Ireland and Wales) or NHS management permission (in Scotland) should be sought from all NHS organisations involved in the study in accordance with NHS research governance arrangements. Each NHS organisation must confirm through the signing of agreements and/or other documents that it has given permission for the research to proceed (except where explicitly specified otherwise).

Guidance on applying for HRA and HCRW Approval (England and Wales)/ NHS permission for research is available in the Integrated Research Application System.

For non-NHS sites, site management permission should be obtained in accordance with the procedures of the relevant host organisation.

Sponsors are not required to notify the Committee of management permissions from host organisations

Registration of Clinical Trials

All research should be registered in a publicly accessible database and we expect all researchers, research sponsors and others to meet this fundamental best practice standard.

It is a condition of the REC favourable opinion that **all clinical trials are registered** on a publicly accessible database within six weeks of recruiting the first research participant. For this purpose, 'clinical trials' are defined as:

- clinical trial of an investigational medicinal product
- clinical investigation or other study of a medical device
- combined trial of an investigational medicinal product and an investigational medical device
- other clinical trial to study a novel intervention or randomised clinical trial to compare interventions in clinical practice.

Failure to register a clinical trial is a breach of these approval conditions, unless a deferral has been agreed by the HRA (for more information on registration and requesting a deferral see: [Research registration and research project identifiers](#)).

If you have not already included registration details in your IRAS application form you should notify the REC of the registration details as soon as possible.

Publication of Your Research Summary

We will publish your research summary for the above study on the research summaries section of our website, together with your contact details, no earlier than three months from the date of this favourable opinion letter.

Should you wish to provide a substitute contact point, make a request to defer, or require further information, please visit: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/application-summaries/research-summaries/>

N.B. If your study is related to COVID-19 we will aim to publish your research summary within 3 days rather than three months.

During this public health emergency, it is vital that everyone can promptly identify all relevant research related to COVID-19 that is taking place globally. If you haven't already done so, please register your study on a public registry as soon as possible and provide the REC with the registration detail, which will be posted alongside other information relating to your project. We are also asking sponsors not to request deferral of publication of research summary for any projects relating to COVID-19. In addition, to facilitate finding and extracting studies related to COVID-19 from public databases, please enter the WHO official acronym for the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in the full title of your study. Approved COVID-19 studies can be found at: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/covid-19-research/approved-covid-19-research/>

It is the responsibility of the sponsor to ensure that all the conditions are complied with before the start of the study or its initiation at a particular site (as applicable).

After ethical review: Reporting requirements

The attached document "After ethical review – guidance for researchers" gives detailed guidance on reporting requirements for studies with a favourable opinion, including:

- Notifying substantial amendments
- Adding new sites and investigators
- Notification of serious breaches of the protocol
- Progress and safety reports
- Notifying the end of the study, including early termination of the study
- Final report
- Reporting results

The latest guidance on these topics can be found at <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/approvals-amendments/managing-your-approval/>.

Ethical review of research sites

NHS/HSC sites

The favourable opinion applies to all NHS/HSC sites taking part in the study, subject to confirmation of Capacity and Capability (in England, Northern Ireland and Wales) or management permission (in Scotland) being obtained from the NHS/HSC R&D office prior to the start of the study (see "Conditions of the favourable opinion" below).

Non-NHS/HSC sites

I am pleased to confirm that the favourable opinion applies to any non-NHS/HSC sites listed in the application, subject to site management permission being obtained prior to the start of the study at the site.

Approved documents

The final list of documents reviewed and approved by the Committee is as follows:

<i>Document</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>
Evidence of Sponsor insurance or indemnity (non NHS Sponsors only) [Insurance document]		30 June 2021
Interview schedules or topic guides for participants	1.0	18 May 2022
IRAS Application Form - IRAS Form received 17/05/2022	292380/1563379/37/911	17 May 2022
IRAS Checklist XML [Checklist_29062022]		29 June 2022
Information for HVs	1.0	18 May 2022
Information for Women's Aid Organisations	1.0	18 May 2022
Life History Calendar	1.0	18 May 2022
Risk Assessment	1.0	18 May 2022
Gantt Chart	1.0	18 May 2022
summary of revisions	1.0	28 June 2022
Safeguarding Checklist	1.1	29 June 2022
Participant consent form	1.0	19 May 2022
Participant information sheet	1.1	28 June 2022
Research protocol or project proposal	1.0	19 May 2022
Summary CV for Chief Investigator - Kerry Ellis		14 April 2022
Summary CV for supervisor (student research) - Mary Lynch		24 March 2022
Summary CV for supervisor (student research) - Ruth Astbury		21 March 2022

Statement of compliance

This Committee is recognised by the United Kingdom Ethics Committee Authority under the Medicines for Human Use (Clinical Trials) Regulations 2004, and is authorised to carry out the ethical review of clinical trials of investigational medicinal products.

The Committee is fully compliant with the Regulations as they relate to ethics committees and the conditions and principles of good clinical practice.

The Committee is constituted in accordance with the Governance Arrangements for Research Ethics Committees and complies fully with the Standard Operating Procedures for Research Ethics Committees in the UK.

User Feedback

The Health Research Authority is continually striving to provide a high quality service to all applicants and sponsors. You are invited to give your view of the service you have received and the application procedure. If you wish to make your views known please use the feedback form available on the HRA website: <http://www.hra.nhs.uk/about-the-hra/governance/quality-assurance/>

HRA Learning

We are pleased to welcome researchers and research staff to our HRA Learning Events and online learning opportunities– see details at: <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/learning/>

IRAS project ID: 292380 Please quote this number on all correspondence
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With the Committee's best wishes for the success of this project.

Yours sincerely

Dr Ruth Stephenson
Chair

Enclosures: "After ethical review – guidance for researchers" [\[SL-AR2\]](#)

Copy to: Dr William Mackay, University of the West of Scotland

16.24 Appendix 21 – Mind map

16.25 Appendix 22 - Women's Aid Model of Change

Women's Aid (2023b)

